

*Efficiency Improvements
and Mathematical
Modelling of Reverse
Osmosis Desalination Plant
A Thesis*

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By

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بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ
الَّذِي جَعَلَ لَكُمْ

الْأَرْضَ فِرَاشًا وَالسَّمَاءَ بِنَاءً

وَأَنْزَلَ مِنَ السَّمَاءِ مَاءً

فَأَخْرَجَ بِهِ مِنَ الثَّمَرَاتِ رِزْقًا لَكُمْ

فَلَا تَجْعَلُوا لِلَّهِ أَنْدَادًا وَأَنْتُمْ تَعْلَمُونَ

صَدَقَ اللَّهُ الْعَلِيِّ الْعَظِيمِ

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Abstract

Most previous studies related to the operation conditions and the performance of desalination plants that operate with a reverse osmosis system depend on short-term studies of the variables used in these studies, such as temperature, concentration, and the rate of flow of feed water. In this thesis, the limits of these variables were expanded to reach critical levels of concentrations and temperatures that can significantly affect the performance of the desalination plant. The number of experimental attempts reached more than 120 with a synthetic water concentration, temperature, and discharge limits ranging from 1063 to 9948 mg/l, 10 to 39°C, and 7.0 to 13.3 m³/h, respectively.

These variables were relied upon to determine the operation conditions of the Second Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant GARO2 in Garmatt-Ali, north of Basrah. On the other hand, long-term operation was relied upon for a period of six months starting from 1/1/2022 and ending on 30/6/2022, during which the station's performance was monitored using feed water from the Shatt Al-Arab River. The GARO2 plant showed consistent and adaptable performance under varying feed water conditions. Despite challenges from high salinity and turbidity, the system sustained effective salt rejection and stable recovery. Seasonal tuning of operating parameters was key to long-term stability.

A detailed plan outlined in Chapter 3. In this study, a simulation model was created for the GARO2 desalination plant using the Winflows 4.04 software, where the outputs from the software were used to compare with the experimental results and to simulate the same operational conditions in terms of concentration, temperature, and discharge of feed water. It was found that there was a high degree of agreement in the results, with a deviation rate that did not exceed 10%.

Three scenarios were applied to enhanced the performance of RO desalination plant. Connecting the two vessels in series within the GARO2 system resulted in a clear performance improvement across key parameters. Permeate water concentration decreased, and both recovery and salt rejection rates increased, with performance improvement percentages ranging from 0.7% to 40.8%. These enhancements indicate a strong positive effect from serial configuration, making it a valuable operational adjustment for boosting system efficiency.

Adding an Air Stripper unit showed targeted improvements, mainly in reducing permeate concentration and increasing salt rejection. However, the benefits were limited to these two areas, with no significant changes in other performance aspects. The Air Stripper proved most effective under high salinity and moderate-to-high flow rates, suggesting it could be a useful supplementary unit but not a comprehensive solution on its own.

The recycling and mixing strategy significantly improved recovery rates, with increases between 28% and 77%, and an additional gain over the baseline state of up to 34%. However, this approach also led to higher permeate concentrations, with values rising by 1.1% to 69.4%. While effective in maximizing water recovery, the method may require additional treatment steps to maintain desired water quality.

Four mathematical models representing different objective functions were developed with the help of Gene Expression Programming (GEP). In these functions, the variables that had the most influence on the performance of the desalination plant were used. This was done by extracting the correlations for the variables using the IBM SPSS Statistics Program, and the most valuable ones were chosen for which the correlation coefficient was close to 1. Through this objective

function, the optimal values of the variables that give the best broadcast to the station were determined using the Gene Expression Programming (GEP) as an optimization tool. The optimal values for the variables T, r%, Sc, and Kcp were 20.519°C, 45.01%, 572.6, and 2.456×10^{-5} , respectively, to obtain the best permeate flow rate as the objective function. This study provides key insights into optimizing RO desalination systems for highly saline water from the Shatt Al-Arab River. The developed models support cost-effective design and improved performance, offering sustainable solutions for water scarcity in southern Iraq. The findings also aid in shaping practical and economically viable local water management policies.

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Nomenclature

List of English Symbols

Symbol	Description	Units
A_m	Active area of membrane element	m^2
C	concentration of solutes	mol/l
C_c	Brine water concentration	mg/l
C_{C1}, C_{C2}	Brine water concentration of GARO1 and GARO2, respectively.	mg/l
C_f	Feed water concentration	mg/l
C_{f1}, C_{f2}	Feed water concentration of GARO1 and GARO2, respectively.	mg/l
$C_{fc, avg}$	average feed-concentrate	mg/l
C_m	Concentration Polarization	mg/l
C_p	Permeate water concentration	mg/l
C_{P1}, C_{P2}	Permeate water concentration of GARO1 and GARO2, respectively.	mg/l
dH	hydraulic diameter	m
DI	solute's diffusion coefficient in water	m^2/s
EC	Electrical Conductivity	$\mu S/cm$
FI	Fouling Index	
h	height of feed channel	m
J_s	Mass flux of solute	$mg/m^2 \cdot h$
J_{sm}	Measured solute flux	$mg/m^2 \cdot h$
J_w	Water flux	$m^3/m^2 \cdot h$
J_{wm}	Measured water flux	$m^3/m^2 \cdot h$
K_{cp}	mass transfer coefficient of concentration polarization	m/s
K_{cp}	Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient	m/s
$KPIs$	key performance indicators	
K_w	water flux coefficient of mass transfer	$m^3/m^2 \cdot h \cdot bar$
NDP	Net Driving Pressure	bar
N_m	Number of membranes involved in the work	
$P_{FC, avg}$	pressure's average value in channel of the feed-concentrate	bar
pH	The acidity	-
P_p	pressure's permeate water	bar
Q_{favg}	Average feed flow rate	m^3/h
Q_p	Permeate water flow rate	m^3/h

R	universal gas constant (0.083145)	l·bar/mol·K
r %	recovery	
R %	salt rejection	
Re	Reynold's number	
Sc	number of Schmidt	
Sc	Schmidt Number	-
SDI	Silt Density Index	
T	Temperature	°C
Ta	absolute temperature	K
TCF	Temperature Correction Factor	
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids	mg/l
TFC	Thin-Film Composite membrane	
t _f	time to collect first 500-mL sample	min
t _i	time to collect final 500-mL sample	min
T _m	Measured Temperature	°C
T _s	Standard Temperature, °C (equal to 25°C)	°C
T _{total}	Total Time (15 min.)	min
v	water velocity in channel of feed	m/s

List of Greek Symbols

Symbol	Description	Units
ϕ	Osmotic coefficient	
β	concentration polarization factor	
ΔP	Pressure difference	bar
$\Delta \pi$	Osmotic pressure difference	bar
λ	factor ranged between 0.40 to 0.54 (taken 0.50)	
μ	dynamic viscosity of feed water	kg/m·s
π	Osmotic Pressure	bar
π_f	Osmotic pressure of feed water	
$\pi_{FC,avg}$	Osmotic pressure's average value of the feed-concentrate	bar
π_P	Osmotic pressure of permeate water	bar
ρ	density of feed water	kg/m ³

List of Abbreviations

Symbol	Description
ACF	Active Carbon Filter
ANFIS	adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
AS & AI	Chemical additives
ASP	accelerated seeded precipitation
ATP	adenosine triphosphate analysis
BW	Back-Wash
BWP	Back-Wash Pump
BWRO	Brackish Water Reverse Osmosis
CA	cellulose acetate membrane
Ca ⁺²	Calcium ion
CaCO ₃	Calcium Carbonate
CEB	Chemical Enhanced Backwash
CF	Cotton Filter
CIP	Cleaning in Place
Cl ⁻	Ion of chloride
Cl ⁻	Chloride ion
CSO	The Central Statistical Organization
DAF	DISSOLVED AIR FLOTATION SYSTEM
DMF	Dual-Media Filter
DOE	Design of Experiments
DP	Differential Pressure
ED	electro-dialysis
ERD	Energy Recovery Device
FIS	fuzzy inference systems
FO-RO	Forward osmosis-reverse osmosis
FP	Feed Pump
G1	Garma-1 water treatment plant
GARO1	The first Garmatt-Ali desalination plant
GARO2	The second Garmatt-Ali desalination plant
GEP	Gene Expression Programming
HCO ₃ ⁻	Bicarbonate ion
HPP	high-pressure pump
HPP	High-Pressure pump
ICD	Intermediate concentrate demineralization techniques
IE	ion exchange
K ⁺	Potassium ion

MF	Micro Filtration
Mg ⁺²	Magnesium ion
Na ⁺	Ion of sodium
Na ⁺	Sodium ion
OTS	Operator Training Simulator
PA	Polyamide membranes
PRO	Pressure retarded osmosis
PSO-ANN	Particle Swarm Optimization assisted ANNs
PV/RO	reverse osmosis are powered by photovoltaic energy
PX	Pressure exchanger
PX2	The second pressure exchanger
QSPR	quantitative structure-property relationships
QUICK	Quadratic Upwind Interpolation Convective Kinematics
RO	Reverse osmosis
ROSA	Reverse Osmosis System Analysis
ROU	Reverse Osmosis Membrane Unit
SCMM	system conditions monitoring and maintenance
SCR	solids contact reactor
SF	Sand Filter
SO ₄ ⁻²	Sulfate ion
SRO	SPECTRUM RO systems
ST	Sedimentation basin
SVR	Support Vector Regression
SWRO	Seawater Reverse Osmosis System
T1	Feed water tank
T2	Permeate Water Tank
T3	Brine Water Tank
T4	Back-Wash Water Tank
TFN	thin-film nanocomposite
UF	Ultrafiltration
UF	Ultrafiltration
V	Valves

CHAPTER

1

Introduction

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 General

Although water is the most prevalent substance on earth, just a small percentage of it is actually usable or fit for human consumption [1]. Just 3% of the world's water capacity is made up of freshwater, which includes water that has been frozen in glaciers and polar ice caps. Approximately 97% of the water resource is saline water [2]. Although fresh water is a renewable resource, its supply is slowly running out on the planet. Less than 1% of freshwater (~0.007% of all water on Earth) is available for direct human use in rivers, lakes, reservoirs, and shallow subsurface sources. Freshwater is defined as water containing less than 1000 mg/l [3]. The Food and Agriculture Organization FAO uses similar TDS thresholds in its irrigation water quality guidelines.

Traditional water sources closely related to human life, such as lakes, rivers, and groundwater resources, are insufficient to meet the growing demand for high-quality drinking water due to population growth, rapid urbanization, and global climate change [4, 5, 6]. In many regions of the world, freshwater supply is currently insufficient to meet demand. Many parts of the world are predicted to experience worsening water shortages in the near future [1]. Many countries are currently facing a drinking water crisis due to various reasons. For this reason, desalination procedures must also be used to treat the oceans and seas and low quality rivers [7, 8]. Iraq is one of these countries, with a significant problem of surface water scarcity in many of its provinces. Consequently, a number of provinces have started experimenting with different sources, such as brackish water [9].

Water scarcity has resulted from constructing of multiple dams on the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, mostly in Turkey, as well as from Iraq's unrestrained water use. Because fresh and saline water were mixed, the Shatt Al-Arab River now has higher salinity content. The population needs water for household use (domestic), so a workable replacement that can provide both long-term supply and safe drinking water must be found right away. The reverse osmosis RO units are the most important of all these options. But this choice is constrained by a dearth of empirical studies and practical understanding of the high level salinities in the Shatt al-Arab River, especially when the water changes from brackish to seawater.

The main components of the Shatt Al-Arab River water are influenced by a variety of factors, the most significant of which is being affected by the salt tide (salinity intrusion) from the northwest of the Arabian Gulf, evidently during the tidal phenomenon. This is because the waters of the Shatt al-Arab River are connected to the marine waters through the Arabian Gulf. Salts enter through molecular diffusion when fresh water discharge drops to less than 20 m³/s (in some places along Shatt Al-Arab River); however, it takes three to four months for the salinity to reach Basrah [10, 11]. In addition to the weather patterns that started to shift as a result of climate change, such as increased evaporation, decreased rainfall, and increased released pollutants, another factor contributing to an increase in salt concentrations in the Shatt al-Arab River is the convert the path of the Karun River towards Bahmshir River in Iran. This river functioned as a barrier to stop the intrusion of seawater upward into the Shatt al-Arab River [12].

The high level of salinity levels of the Shatt Al-Arab River was not the sole factor driving the urgent demand for clean water in Basrah Governorate. A major contributing factor is the region's rapidly growing population, which presents a substantial challenge for local authorities in securing sufficient water resources

for domestic use. According to a 2021 report published online by the Central Statistical Organization (CSO) under the Iraqi Ministry of Planning, the population of Basrah Governorate has reached approximately 3,142,449 individuals, distributed across seven administrative districts [13]. Assuming an average domestic water consumption rate of 350 liters per person per day (especially in Iraq), the total daily residential water demand is estimated at nearly 1,100,000 tons.

The need for desalination technology has grown due to the lack of freshwater supplies and the expansion of industry, agriculture, and population. Certain nations, like those in the Gulf (Iraq included), exclusively use desalinated water [14]. RO and other seawater and brackish water desalination technologies are therefore receiving a lot of attention in an effort to boost the efficiency and dependability of freshwater production operations.

Two types of saline water were often distinguished. The first type is referred to as seawater (TDS greater than 10,000 mg/l), whereas the second type is brackish water (TDS less than 10,000 mg/l) [15]. Various technologies have been utilized for the desalination of saltwater. RO, electro-dialysis (ED), ion exchange (IE), and distillation are some of these technologies [16].

In this thesis, the most common, easiest, and most economical method will be studied, which is desalination by RO. In many areas with freshwater lakes, seawater desalination via RO has recently become the primary source of drinking water supply [17].

1.2 Material of Reverse Osmosis Membrane

Basically, membranes are classified into two types in terms of the materials that make up the membrane:

1- Cellulose Acetate membranes AC: Reid and Breton reported in the late 1950s that salt could be effectively retained by a hand-cast thin symmetrical CA membrane, attaining 98% rejection; nevertheless, the permeate flux was very disappointing, with an order of $<10 \text{ mL m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ [18]. Cellulose acetate CA was used to create the first membrane of RO produced in 1960 by Sourirajan and Loeb, and RO membranes made of this substance are currently sold commercially (See Figure 1.1). CA-based membranes usually have an asymmetrical structure. Because cellulose acetate is hydrophilic, fouling is reduced and high flow values are maintained [19]. A thick micro-porous body was covered in a dense 200 nm thin layer to generate an asymmetric CA membrane. Compared to the original symmetric membrane, this new shape generated a water flux that was at least an order of magnitude larger [20]. On the other hand, free chlorine at a concentration exceeding 1 mg/l, the pH value greater than 8 or less than 3, biological decomposition, and temperatures higher than 30°C are all conditions that negatively affect the performance of the CA. Furthermore, a decrease in flux occurs with time as a result of membrane compaction brought on by the high working pressure and asymmetric structure.

Fig. 1.1 Cellulose Acetate membranes AC

2- Polyamide membranes PA: Chemical and physical stability, resistance to higher pH ranges, lack of hydrolysis, and resistance to bacterial degradation, all of these properties of PA membranes are better than CA [19]. However, PA membranes cannot withstand any concentration of free chlorine and pollution, as the membrane will deteriorate in the presence of any oxidizing substance in the feed water (See Figure 1.2).

Fig. 1.2 Polyamide membranes PA

1.3 Configuration of Reverse Osmosis Membrane Element

There are two membrane configurations of osmosis desalination processes, the first one is Spiral-wound, and the other hollow-fine-fiber.

1- Modules of Spiral-wound: The most often utilized design in RO desalination is the spiral wound membrane module layout. This arrangement is the least cheapest module configuration to build from flat sheet of Thin-Film Composite membrane TFC, and it also offers high specific membrane surface area, easy scaling up operation, interoperability, low replacement costs, and, most importantly, low cost [21, 22]. The process of creating spiral wound membranes goes through several stages [19]. Active membrane layers, spacer material, collection tube, and mesh as feed-side spacers are the main parts of desalination membranes (See Figure 1.3).

Fig. 1.3 Construction of spiral-wound membrane element [19].

2- Modules of Hollow-Fine-Fibers: Richter and Hoehn created the first non-cellulosic asymmetric membrane that attracted notice; it was an aromatic polyamide (PA) asymmetric hollow-fiber membrane [23]. The highly efficient packing of the hollow fibers, which exceeded the CA spiral wrapped elements in terms of flux per unit module volume, is responsible for the product's commercial success despite the low flux. Readers are referred to [24] for a thorough description of the variation in reactants for PA asymmetric membranes. The membrane's active surface is situated on the exterior of the fiber and has a thickness ranging from 0.1 to 1 μm . DuPont HFFs are no longer commercially available, but they are still widely used. Toyobo in Japan is now the only producer of hollow-fiber RO membranes. The concentrated brine emerges from one end of an HFF module while the feed enters from the other. The fibers are coiled and hung longitudinally within the module, exposing a set of fibers' open ends at either end. Helically, the fiber bundles are coiled around a central tube [19]. A single module can have ten times the surface area of spiral wound parts

and several hundred thousand fibers. Thirty percent of the product water is recovered per element.

1.4 Principle of Reverse Osmosis Desalination

Membrane separation techniques are becoming more and more important in fields including gas separation, industrial and municipal waste treatment, and water desalination. Aside from these, the generation of ultrapure water, boiler feedwater, drinking water systems, and pharmaceutical applications are among the fields where membrane technologies are finding widespread popularity [25]. RO is one such method. Since its commercialization in the 1960s and introduction in the late 1950s, RO units have grown to be essential components of the aforementioned applications.

Before starting to define RO, it must be understood and known the meaning of osmosis. Water naturally moves from a solution with little salt to one that is more concentrated through a semi-permeable membrane called osmosis (Figure 1.4). This process continues until the two solutions establish an osmotic equilibrium [26]. The osmotic pressure, which is based on the variations in solute concentrations between the two solutions, is what causes this water flow.

Fig. 1.4 Representation of osmosis theory [26]

A membrane that lets some atoms or molecules through but not others is called semi-permeable [27].

Reverse osmosis, on the other hand, is a pressure-driven membrane filtration method that is employed to extract tiny organic molecules and inorganic ions from solvents that have low molecular weights. Solute molecules are contained within a semi-permeable membrane, whereas solvent molecules are free to flow through it. When two solutions with different concentrations are divided by a semi-permeable membrane, the solvent from the solution with the lower concentration passes through the membrane and into the concentrated solution, a process known as osmosis takes place. The tendency to equalize the concentrations on both sides is what causes the observable flow [28]. However, the concentrations on either side of the membrane can never be equal if the solution on that side is made entirely of a pure solvent. In this instance, osmotic flow continues until the concentrated solution's pressure against the membrane reaches a point where it stops the solvent from flowing through, thereby reaching equilibrium between the chemical potentials of both sides. At equilibrium, the difference in hydrostatic pressure between the two sides of the membrane is called the osmotic pressure. As seen in Figure 1.3, the process known as reverse osmosis involves applying pressure to the concentrated solution side in order to exceed the osmotic pressure and create a solvent flux through the membrane against the concentration gradient [29].

As illustrated schematically in Figure 1.5, with high pressure, water is pumped through the membrane's surface, allowing some water to pass through. Targeted dissolved solutes are comparatively absent from the water that passes through the membrane, known as permeate, while the residual water, known as

concentrate (also frequently referred to brine or reject water), flow through the other side of the vessel. [19].

Fig. 1.5 Schematic of separation process through RO membrane

1.5 Aims of the Thesis

The main of the thesis is to evaluate and enhance the performance of RO desalination plant through experimental investigations, optimization techniques, and simulation tools. This study seeks to understand how various operational parameters influence system performance, ensure sustained, and efficient operational under real environmental conditions, and explore methods for performance optimization using both practical and computational approaches.

To achieve the above aims, the following specific objectives are set:

- 1- To operate desalination plant using synthetic water with different water concentrations, variable feed water temperature, and controlled feed water discharge. These operation conditions used to know its effect on the permeate flow, water and solution flux, recovery, salt rejection, and polarization concentration and its factors and coefficients within the limits of specifications and characteristics of the quality of water and membranes

used and available in local markets. Through this section, the results are presented with charts and tables summarizing the various effects.

- 2- To evaluate the long-term performance using the main water source in the study area (Shatt al-Arab River) and within optimal operation conditions. This study is scheduled to extend from January 1, 2022 to June 30, 2022, for a period of six months. Through this operation, you will notice the changes that will occur to the permeate flow, permeate water concentration, water flux, etc. The results will also be presented in the form of illustrative charts and tables showing these changes.
- 3- To utilize a Gene Expression Programming (GEP) to optimize the outcomes of operating conditions in order to maximize the performance of the desalination plant and to look into ways to modify the RO process's operation in order to maintain a constant water flow during the operating season, summer or winter.
- 4- To simulate the desalination process using Winflows 4.04 software as a simulation tool for the desalination plant and comparing the simulation results with the practical results and the extent to which the program results match the practical reality.
- 5- To utilize various circumstances to enhance the manufacturing process (quantity and quality) and contrasting the outcomes with the plant's initial condition.

1.6 Description of the Study Area

This research focused on the RO desalination plant located at the University of Basrah (Garmatt-Ali Camp) in the Basrah region of southern Iraq. The plant's coordinates are (Zone: 38N, Easting: 763,309.48 m, Northing: 3,385,252.95 m). Figure 1.6 illustrates the geographical position of the University

of Basrah, situated to the north of Basrah city and on the western side of the Shatt Al-Arab River. The plant has a production capacity of 9 m³/h. The primary objective behind the construction of GARO was to provide Engineering College of University of Basrah with a reliable source of potable water.

Fig. 1.6. Location of the RO plant in Garmatt Ali- Basrah Province

1.8 Thesis Structure

The structure of this thesis is as follows:

- 1- Chapter One/Introduction: In this chapter, a general introduction to the topic and area of study was reviewed. The types of membranes that can be used in the study were also reviewed in terms of the material from which the membranes were made or in terms of appearance. In addition to mentioning the main principles of desalination using RO. The study objectives, expected challenges, and study methodology were also mentioned.
- 2- Chapter Two/ Literature Presentation: In this chapter, the parts of the station are described, the performance of the RO processes, methods for improving

performance, modeling and simulation, and optimizing technologies according to previous studies.

- 3- Chapter Three/Experimental Work: In this chapter, the practical side of the thesis was studied, which is divided into two main parts. The first concerns the operation conditions of the second desalination plant, while the second part concerns studying the performance of the plant for long term operation (six months). The general procedure of analysis and design, and guidelines were also reviewed. The stations GARO1 and GARO2 were described in detail, and the data obtained during the study period was analyzed and plotted.
- 4- Chapter Four/ Modeling and Optimization: In this chapter, the results obtained from experimental works were optimized to obtain the best operation conditions that can be relied upon to obtain the best performance. A simulation model of the desalination plant was also created using the Winflows 4.04 software, and the simulation results were obtained and compared with the realistic results obtained from operating the plant.
- 5- Chapter Five/ Enhancement Operation: In this chapter, several scenarios are presented for improving the operating results of the desalination plant to obtain a good quantity and quality of water produced.
- 6- Chapter Six/Conclusions and Recommendations: In this chapter, it lists a summary of the results and recommendations of the study.

CHAPTER

2

Literature Review

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2.1 General

To satisfy the increasing requirement of clean water worldwide, RO is a prominent technique for desalination and wastewater reuse adopted by hundreds of desalination plants so far. This section provides comprehensive review of the key operational parameters of the RO plant and explains effective strategies for enhancing its performance. Main influences on RO performance: properties semi permeable membrane, biofouling mitigation, energy consumption membrane modification emitting renewable energy sources etc. Capabilities for producing high-quality water through membrane properties like salt rejection and water flux. The efficiency of desalination have significantly improved with the advancements of thin polyamide layer technology giving a considerable increase in salt rejection, sensible heat transfer and sweep flow rates of water for bypassing biofouling and maintaining appropriate RO performance. Simultaneously biofouling need to be kept under control for the optimal performance of RO.

System performance optimization and reduction of energy consumption by making use of strategies like pressure exchangers, recovery device and membrane modification techniques. One of the critical yardstick of RO plant efficiency is power consumption, especially with the intent to be more environment friendly. Utilizing renewable energy sources (photovoltaic systems), in theory can further increase the efficiency and decrease carbon emission. Pre-treatment and modified operating conditions for lowering membrane fouling effects as well feed water salinity variations has been researched as well. Primary KPIs of RO (energy

consumption, permeation flow; recovery rate; salt rejection rate) on which the continuous development of this technology depends on.

This chapter offers insights into the difficulties, tactics, and developments in optimizing RO plant performance, supporting the long-term supply of clean water for a range of uses.

2.2 Reverse osmosis plant Process

An RO membrane process is a usual membrane technique for desalinating seawater and brackish water. According to Figure 2.1, an industrial RO water desalination system typically consists of four primary sub-systems: input, pretreatment, RO membrane units, and post-treatment [1].

Figure 2.1 RO process system [1]

In 2002, Hisham T. El-Dessouky Hisham M. Ettouney explained in more detail the processes of RO plants, which Figure 2.2 is only one illustration of how the quantity of feed pretreatment is highly influenced by the feed water quality as following [30]:

- 1- It is used movable displays or mesh strainers to filter large particles from the supply water. In well water delivery systems, mesh strainers are utilized to block and filter sand particles that may be pumped from the well.

Traveling screens are mostly employed in surface water sources with high quantities of biological material.

- 2- Disinfecting surface feed water to limit biological activity is routine practice. Well water has relatively little biological activity and, in most situations, does not need to be chlorinated. Chlorination is sometimes used to oxidize iron and manganese in well water before filtering. Hydrogen sulfide-containing well water should not be chlorinated or exposed to air. When an oxidant is present, the sulfide ion can oxidize to elemental sulfur, which can eventually clog membrane components.
- 3- Surface water settles in a detention tank, resulting in a decrease in suspended particles. The addition of flocculants, such as iron or aluminum salts, causes the creation of matching hydroxides; these hydroxides neutralize colloidal particle surface charges, agglomerate, and adhere to floating particles before settling at the clarifier's bottom section. To bind together the flock particles, it can be add an organic polymer; this case is increasing the robustness and the size of the flock. The use of lime causes a rise in pH, as well as the creation of calcium carbonate and magnesium hydroxide particles. Lime clarity reduces hardness and alkalinity while also clarifying treated water.
- 4- The last line of defense in RO systems against suspended solids is the cartridge filters, which are located before the high-pressure pump HPP. Cartridge filters measuring 5-15 microns are the most commonly use. The smaller the cartridge size, the higher the replacement rate.
- 5- There are many equipment that have entered the RO market that are considered primary treatment equipment, such as ultrafiltration and microfiltration membranes. This equipment is characterized by its low feed pressure (less energy), high recovery rates, and backwash capability.

However, this equipment is expensive when compared to the cost of RO units.

Fig. 2.2 Typical RO process with screening, chlorination, filtration, acidification and scale inhibition [30]

John C. Crittenden and others in 2012 [19] mentioned that almost all RO systems require feed water preparation. One objective of pretreatment when sparingly soluble salts are present is to avoid scaling. Without preliminary treatment of the water drawn from the inlet stream, the deposition of dissolved material ions on the surface of the membranes may cause blockages and damage that will be difficult to treat in the future. pH modification and/or antiscalant addition are used to control scale. It is necessary to adjust the pH in the desalination units because of its importance in preventing calcification on the surfaces of the membranes, and with the help of anti-scalants, the rate of sediment formation will decrease.

In other hand, they said post treatment of permeate is often required, which includes the removal of dissolved gases, alkalinity, and pH correction. Membranes are ineffective in removing small, uncharged molecules, particularly dissolved gases. If hydrogen sulfide is found in the source groundwater, it must be removed before it is distributed to customers. Sulphides must be cleaned from the gas

released during the stripping process to prevent corrosion and unwanted odor problems. The increase in pH is due to the elimination of carbon dioxide, and as a result, the amount of base required to stabilize the water decreases. There is normally that the permeate water has low alkalinity and hardness, so to reduce scaling, acid must be added. On the other hand, to avoid and inhibit corrosion in pipelines or equipment, adding a base that balances the pH is very necessary.

2.3 Modelling of Reverse Osmosis Membrane

The design and operation of the RO process are significantly influenced by several roles. One of these roles is the mathematical modeling of RO systems. It enables process variable optimization without requiring changes to be made to the actual plant by connecting RO performance indicators, such as permeate recovery and solute rejection, to operational and design variables, such as feed pressure and membrane module size.

2.3.1 Silt Density Index (SDI)

The Fouling Index (FI), commonly referred to as the Silt Density Index (SDI), is a useful formula for estimating the colloidal fouling potential of RO input water. There are many different sources of colloids in RO feed waters, and they frequently contain bacteria, clay, colloidal silica, and results of iron corrosion. If they are not eliminated in the clarifier or by appropriate medium filtration, pretreatment chemicals employed in a clarifier such as alum, ferric chloride, or cationic polyelectrolytes can also result in colloidal fouling [31].

Increasing turbidity does not give any indication of the reason for its increase, but measuring the SDI roughly gives the reason for the increase from examining the color or smell of the filter paper used.

SDI can be found by the equation 2.1 as following [19]:

$$SDI = \frac{1 - \frac{t_f}{t_i}}{T} \times 100 \quad (2.1)$$

Where;

t_f = time to collect first 500-mL sample, min

t_i = time to collect final 500-mL sample, min

T = 15 min.

If the SDI is less than 3 min^{-1} , the feed water quality is excellent and highly suitable for reverse osmosis systems. An SDI between 3 and 5 min^{-1} is considered acceptable but may require enhanced pretreatment. If the SDI exceeds 5 min^{-1} , the water quality is poor, indicating a high risk of membrane fouling.

2.3.2 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

To obtain the value of the TDS, it must be found the electrical conductivity EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and then converted to TDS (mg/l). Based on the documented linear connection between specific conductance and ionic strength for fluids with conductance ranging from 10 to 10,000 S/cm , electrical conductivity is used [32]. A typical equation is:

$$TDS = k_e \times EC \quad (2.2)$$

where k_e is a proportionality constant. The ionic makeup of the water and the amount of dissolved species have an impact on the TDS-EC connection. The k_e value for the majority of natural waters ranges from 0.55 to 0.85 [33].

The membrane's composition and fluid viscosity are both impacted by temperature. As the connection between membrane material, temperature, and flux varies depending on the product, TCF (Temperature Correction Factor) values should typically be obtained from membrane producers who conduct experiments to establish values. If manufacturer TCF values are not available, the

following equation, which may be suitable for membranes with holes, can be used to estimate the connection between flux and fluid viscosity:

$$TCF = (1.03)^{T_s - T_m} \quad (2.3)$$

Where;

T_s = Standard Temperature, °C (equal to 25°C)

T_m = Measured Temperature, °C

On K_w , temperature has an impact. The permeability will increase as the water temperature rises. Per °C, the permeability changes by around 3%. Water viscosity and K_w are related.

Variations in feed temperature modify the properties of the membrane. According to Sarkar et al. (2008), this impact is empirically taken into account when determining the link between feed water temperature and membrane permeability [34]. Keep in mind that temperature affects all physical characteristics including osmotic pressure.

2.3.3 Concentration Polarization C_m

A gas or liquid mixture meets the membrane's feed side during membrane separation procedures, and a permeate that is richer in one of the mixture's components is removed from the membrane's downstream side. Concentration gradients arise in the fluids on opposite sides of the membrane due to the varying rates at which the components of the feed mixture penetrate. We refer to these phenomena as concentration polarization [35]. Salts that are rejected by a membrane during water flow might collect near the membrane's surface, where their concentration will progressively rise as shown in Figure 2.3 [36].

Fig. 2.3 Concentration polarization schematic [36]

When compared to theoretical calculations, concentration polarization has the effect of reducing the rejection of the salt and the real permeate flow rate [13]. Therefore, it must be listed the concentration polarization effects as following:

- 1- Water flux J_w will be decrease.
- 2- Mass flux J_s will be increase.
- 3- A greater osmotic pressure will be created on the surface of the membranes compared to the pressure in the feed water transport channels. This leads to a decrease in Net Driving Pressure NDP through the desalination membrane.
- 4- Increase in membrane scaling due to particular potential for precipitation of salinity.

In order to know how concentration polarization occurs on membranes, the mathematical models that govern this process must be discussed. These models are divided into two parts:

2.3.3.1 Water Flux Model

The rate at which water passes through a semi-permeable membrane is defined by the following relation [19]:

$$J_w = K_w (\Delta P - \Delta \pi) \quad (2.4)$$

Where;

J_w = Volumetric water flux, $\text{m}^3/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h}$.

K_w = Water flux coefficient of mass transfer, $\text{m}^3/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h} \cdot \text{bar}$.

ΔP = Applied pressure differentials, bar.

$\Delta \pi$ = osmotic pressure differentials, bar.

The term of $(\Delta P - \Delta \pi)$ is called The Net driving Pressure NDP. It takes feed channel head loss, osmotic pressure, and variations in feed and permeate pressures into account. The dropping of applied pressure and the steadily rising will be occur during the permeate water reaching to the feed-concentrate channel. The net driving pressure must therefore account for average conditions. The following equation explains how to calculate NDP:

$$NDP = \Delta P - \Delta \pi = (P_{fc,avg} - P_p) - (\pi_{fc,avg} - \pi_p) \quad (2.5)$$

Where;

$P_{FC,avg}$ = Pressure's average value in channel of the feed–concentrate, (bar).

$$= \frac{(P_F + P_C)}{2} \quad (2.6)$$

P_p = Pressure's permeate water, (bar).

P_F = Feed water pressure, (bar).

P_C = Brine water pressure, (bar).

$\pi_{FC,avg}$ = Osmotic pressure's average value of the feed-concentrate, bar.

π_p = Osmotic pressure of permeate water, bar.

Quantifying the dissolved salts concentration in a solution allows for experimental determination of its osmotic pressure, or π . The following equation yields the osmotic pressure:

$$\pi = \phi \cdot C \cdot R \cdot T_a \quad (2.7)$$

Where;

π = Osmotic Pressure, bar

ϕ = Osmotic coefficient, unitless ($\phi = 1$)

C = Concentration of solutes, mol/l

R = Universal gas constant, 0.083145 l·bar/mol · K

T_a = Absolute temperature, K (273 + T° C)

To find $\pi_{fc,avg}$, it first must be find average feed-concentrate $C_{fc,avg}$ by applying the equation 2.8 as following:

$$C_{fc,avg} = \frac{(C_f + C_c)}{2} \quad (2.8)$$

Where:

C_f = Feed water concentration, mg/l.

C_c = Brine water concentration, mg/l.

The concentration units in Equation 2.7 are mol/l, so the concentration units extracted from Equation 2.8 must be converted from mg/l to mol/l by dividing the concentration value by the molecular weight. When one mol of NaCl is added to a solution, two mol of ions are produced, which doubles the osmotic

pressure. In an equal-mass addition of several solutes, when the solute has highest molecular weight, it generates the lowest osmotic pressure.

To compute permeate flow Q_p , recovery r %, and salt rejection R % it should be applying the following equations:

$$Q_p = J_w \times A_m \times N_m \quad (2.9)$$

$$r \% = \frac{Q_p}{Q_f} \times 100 \% \quad (2.10)$$

$$R \% = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_f}\right) \times 100 \% \quad (2.11)$$

Where:

A_m = Active area of membrane element, m^2 .

N_m = Number of membranes involved in the work.

C_p = Permeate water concentration, mg/l.

2.3.3.2 Mass Flux of Solute Model

In RO desalination plants, the mass flux of solutes can also be impacted by the feed water temperature. Elevated temperatures in the feed water can augment the mass flux of solutes, resulting in elevated rates of salt rejection and enhanced desalination efficacy. It's crucial to remember that raising the feed water temperature has some limitations. Mass flux of solute J_s can be found by using the following equation:

$$J_s = J_w * C_p \quad (2.12)$$

Where;

J_s = solute's mass flux, $(mg/m^2 \cdot h)$.

2.3.3.3 Concentration Polarization Factor and Mass Transfer Coefficient

The concentration polarization factor, or the ratio of the concentration of salt at the membrane surface to the concentration of feed water in the bulk, can rise with feed water temperatures higher. Lower water flow and total desalination efficiency can be the outcome of a greater concentration polarization factor. The concentration polarization factor can be found as the following equations [19]:

$$\beta = e^{J_w/K_{cp}} \quad \text{or} \quad \beta = \frac{C_m}{C_{fc,avg}} \quad (2.13)$$

Where;

β = concentration polarization factor, dimensionless.

K_{cp} = mass transfer coefficient of concentration polarization, m/s.

C_m = Polarization concentration, mg/l.

The impact of mass transfer because of the mesh spacer makes some additional correlations for concentration polarization important. By utilizing both the surface velocity and the channel height, Marinas₁ and Urama (1996) established a correlation [37]. They are correlated as follows:

$$K_{cp} = \lambda \frac{Dl}{dH} (Re)^{0.5} (Sc)^{0.333} \quad (2.14)$$

$$Re = \frac{\rho v dH}{\mu} \quad (2.15)$$

$$Sc = \frac{\mu}{\rho Dl} \quad (2.16)$$

$$dH = 2h \quad (2.17)$$

Where;

λ = factor ranged between 0.40 to 0.54 (taken 0.50).

Dl = solute's diffusion coefficient in water, m^2/s .

ρ = density of feed water, kg/m^3 .

Re = Reynolds' number, dimensionless.

μ = dynamic viscosity of feed water, $kg/m \cdot s$

Sc = number of Schmidt, dimensionless.

h = height of feed channel, m.

v = water velocity in channel of feed, m/s.

dH = hydraulic diameter, m.

Reynolds and Schmidt numbers are dependent on the fluid's viscosity and density, and these values may be obtained from Table (2.1).

Table 2.1 Effect of Temperature on the Density and Viscosity of Water

Temperature	ρ water (Kg/m ³) for each temperature	μ water (Kg/m.s) for each temperature	Temperature	ρ water (Kg/m ³) for each temperature	μ water (Kg/m.s) for each temperature
10	999.7	0.001308	25	997	0.00089
11	999.6	0.001272	26	996.74	0.000872
12	999.5	0.001236	27	996.48	0.000853
13	999.37	0.001204	28	996.22	0.000835
14	999.24	0.001171	29	995.96	0.000816
15	999.1	0.001139	30	995.7	0.000798
16	998.92	0.001112	31	995.35	0.000784
17	998.74	0.001084	32	995	0.000769
18	998.56	0.001057	33	994.65	0.000755
19	998.38	0.001029	34	994.3	0.00074
20	998.2	0.001002	35	993.95	0.000726
21	997.96	0.00098	36	993.6	0.000714
22	997.72	0.000957	37	993.25	0.000698
23	997.48	0.000935	38	992.9	0.000682
24	997.24	0.000912	39	992.55	0.000666

2.3.4 Salt Rejection %

The salt rejection can be found by the following equation [13]:

$$R\% = \frac{c_f - c_p}{c_f} \times 100 \quad (2.18)$$

2.4 Previous Studies

2.4.1 Performance of Reverse Osmosis Processes

When it comes to the removal of salt from salty water, RO is one of the most effective methods available. Due to its ability to generate water with an exceptionally high quality, RO has become the most widely used technology for desalination and wastewater recycling in the modern era [38]. Worldwide, the demand for RO technology is growing and it represents more than about half of world market.

Water permeance and salt rejection — the chief factors that contribute to RO (common process for desalination and water purification). Water permeability across an RO membrane is called the speed of water that are able to move through RO membrane. Polymeric RO membranes, with a notable selectivity polyamide thin film layer, are inherently very permeable to water and rejection salt [39]. But salt rejection, which reflects the efficiency of the membrane in removing impurities and dissolved salts. Advances in membrane technologies of RO plants have also led to improvement on salt rejection, permeate flux and water rejections.

In addition, development of high flux membranes with low operating pressures has massively enhanced the total energy efficiency of RO plants [40].

Monitoring the system conditions and maintenance (SCMM)—optimized system conditions for RO plants to operate at the best efficiency. This comprises checking certain variables like membrane age, temperature, pressure, recovery

and feed water concentrate. These parameters need to be controlled within their set-points in order to withdraw the needed clean water while at the same time not risking system failure. Additionally, fouling and scaling in the RO membrane have critical impacts on plant performance and life, hence fouling must be controlled as well.

A variety of technologies and techniques have been designed for the enhancement of operation and performance of RO plants. An example of such a device is one that uses pressure exchangers or turbochargers to transfer energy from saline concentration to incoming feed water. In turn, this leads the total energy efficiency of the system to increase. A third method works to recover energy, for example with pressure exchangers or isobaric chambers utilisation of energy. It helps in reducing the energy requirement of RO plants to a large extent by reusing the energy that is usually wasted in the process of desalination.

Continuous improvement in RO membrane technologies has elevated both the performance and efficacy of RO plants [41]. Thin polyamide films are frequently utilized in RO plants because of their amazing salt rejection and water permeability. These thin layers of polyamide serve as a channel through which water molecules are able to diffuse and where the salts ions as well as all other foulants remain blocked. So membrane technology has greatly improved the salt rejection and therefore has enabled a substantial increase in efficiency of desalination as well as a higher water flux rate.

In addition, research and development work has been carried out to improve the permeate of RO membrane under applied pressures. Concomitantly, low-energy membrane with high-flux have been synthesized which beneficially reduce energy requirement and enhance the performance of the RO plant [40]. The

planning and management of RO installations have also benefited from advancements in membrane technology.

Important for desalination, wastewater treatment and other solution concentration processes: operation of RO plants (Latest Updates at the bottom of post)

Several factors had reversed osmosis characterized by its performance, the following stats will say:

- RO membrane characteristics - Scott (1995) Full description of RO membrane including design and features critical to understanding RO performance [42].

Regulatory control of biofouling: Rahaman et al. (2014) outlines biofouling management to the RO membranes, though pointing out how important it is still its preservation for continuance of RO plants Works to optimize RO performance has to take the biofouling into consideration, which has a major effect on RO efficiency [43].

- Energy consumption: to bring some clarity over RO energy consumption McGovern and Lienhard (2014) compared the energies required for forward osmosis vs RO desalination.

The rationale to assess the full sustainability and performance of RO must first, quantify the energetic factors associated to it [44].

- Membrane modification: Liu et al. This work (2018) focuses on supporting materials modification to improve RO membranes performance Only, relevant aspect could reduce biofouling and enhance efficiency of RO System (45).

- Renewable energy integration Carvalho et al. (2004), shows that use of renewable energy sources for an RO system through the example of a photovoltaic-assisted RO plant in Brazil. Insight into the effects of integrating

renewable energy on performance of RO plants can be derived from this reference [46].

To summarize, there are various factors which are obviously, Membrane characteristics, bio-fouling control RO performance, membrane modifications,, hybrid PV system and the integration of renewable energy variables, affecting the performance.

Knowing those variables is important for improveon RO systems performance in different contexts when understanding these factors.

An RO facility performance is evaluated based on numerous performance indicators (KPIs) to ascertain how efficient an RO facility. Some of these parameters are permeate flux, salt rejection, energy utilization rate; recovery letdown. Permeate flux quantifies the rate at which water becomes permeated through the RO membrane and is basically a measure for how much more clean water plants can supply in an exact time. Salt rejection rate: this tells us how effective the RO membrane is at getting rid of the salt ions in the feed water (the more it rejects the salt, the purer your plant is capable of outputting). Energy consumption, which is a pivotal KPI that charts the energy required to run the plant — usually expressed as mean kWh/m of water produced. Lower the number, better is the plant operationally it is less impact on environment. The percentage of the feed water that is translated into permeate and what is then removed as brine is called recovery rate. The key improvements this will help with in RO technology isup expertly.

Various KPIs (key performance indicators) like pre-treatment technologies, fouling control measures, energy requirement, comparison of different desalination technologies, integration with renewable energy sources, and reduction of the carbon footprint are assessed to the performance of RO plants.

- RO pre-treatment: One of the best-suited analyses provided by Qasim and his colleagues highlighted the procedures for optimizing the RO plants performance in 2019. [47].

- Fouling control: Ability to predict and control fouling is one of the most significant KPIs to assess the efficiency and sustainability of the RO plants. Ruiz-García et al. [48], fouling prediction plays a significant role in evaluating long-term operating conditions and expenses (with data up to October 2023).

- Energy productivity: Energy consumption is probably one of the most commonly used Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring the performance of RO systems. Results of process modeling are shown by Shaffer et al. if a combined forward and RO process would yield better product water quality at lower total energy cost or not (2012) [49].

- Comparative effectiveness of different desalination systems: The forward osmosis approach might be more energy-efficient than RO desalination; however, it is essential to compare the effectiveness of different desalination systems [44].

- Integration of Renewables: Mito et al. (2019) focuses on the use of renewable energy resources to supply RO plants for carbon emissions reduction. This is a helpful KPI in understanding the impact that renewable energy integration has to RO system performance and sustainability [50].

- Lowering the carbon footprint: Leon et al. (2021) highlight the importance of using the carbon footprint as an indicator of RO plant performance and propose a methodology for evaluating membranes replacement in saline water RO desalination facilities [51].

Keen insights from here that reflect on the importance of infamous gaps in RO based desalination at the pre-treatment level of efficiency, fouling control,

energy consumption and comparative effectiveness of various desalination methods, integration of REs and a reduced carbon footprint will make very useful substantiation for the other performance metrics in any RO operation of course.

Several factors can affect the performance of RO plants, including changes in the input power and salinity of the feed water, membrane fouling and poor pre-treatment process or even at times the set-up of the entire plant. These causes can lead to reduced permeate flux, lower salt rejection, increased energy consumption, and overall reduced plant efficiency.

To improve the efficiency of these RO plants, researchers have focused either on the development of advanced membrane materials with increased salt rejection capabilities or regulation of operating parameters such as the feed water temperature, pressure, and pH. Additionally, some studies have been carried out to explore the developments in pre-treatment technology aimed at relieving the influence of variable salinity in feed water and minimizing the membranous fouling.

One of the promising approaches for improving the performance of RO plants is through the development of thin-film nanocomposite (TFN) membranes. In the case of TFN membranes, the selective layer is composed of polyamide, and nanomaterials are incorporated into it to enhance the permeate flux and salt rejection. It has been shown for example that TFN membranes containing carbon nanotubes could achieve permeate flux exceeding $100 \text{ L/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$ and salt rejection exceeding 99.9% under working pressures less than 20 bar.

Another strategy for improving RO plant performance is operational condition optimization. Some methods, e.g. increasing the operating temperature, can improve permeate flux but increase the energy consumption and membrane fouling as well. It becomes very important to find the right operating temperature

that balances these conflicting parameters. In addition to this, changing the pH level of the feed water could help in enhancing the salt rejection and reducing the membrane fouling.

It is also required for optimum operation of RO plants. Methods for the pre-treatment membranes with coagulation, flocculation and sedimentation can remove suspended particles and other potential-feed water contaminants, which can reduce membrane fouling and enhance membrane durability. Pre-treatment can also help reduce the variation in feed water salinity and thereby improve the efficacy and performance of RO plants.

Researchers have overall advanced RO plant performance through the research and advancement of more elaborate membrane materials, optimization of the operating settings, and industrialization of the pre-treatment technology. Scientists can improve both the efficiency and the energy intensity of this vital water desalination process by continuing to tailor the RO plant performance based on the factors affecting it through research.

The researchers studied a number of aspects that affect the performance of RO plants, providing considerable insight into the key factors governing their performance and longevity. For example, Scott (1995) provides a comprehensive review of industrial membranes, including those used in RO plants. For a better understanding of how RO systems function, knowledge of the structure and properties of the membranes used in them is important, which is also why this particular reference is relevant [42].

As highlighted by several researchers, predicting fouling in reverse osmosis (RO) systems is crucial for determining long-term operational conditions and associated costs. In this context, Ruiz-García et al. [52] addressed the challenges of fouling prediction within these systems. Additionally, Massoud et

al. (2017) described the engineering challenges associated with large-scale reverse osmosis desalination plants powered by solar and wind energy, particularly those relying on photovoltaic (PV) electricity.

As initially demonstrated by Srivastava et al. (2018), the importance of routine maintenance for the long-term operation of reverse osmosis (RO) plants is emphasized, while acknowledging the challenges associated with early fault detection and predictive maintenance in this context [58]. One of the key variables influencing the performance of RO facilities is the concentration of the feed solution [59]. The concentration level significantly affects the performance and efficiency of RO systems. Specifically, at higher concentrations, such as in seawater, greater pressure and energy are required to separate water from the salt. Recent advancements, as highlighted by Phuc et al. (2017), indicate that membrane technology has contributed to improving the efficiency of RO plants [40]. Innovations in this field include, but are not limited to, the development of low-operating pressure membranes that reduce energy consumption, as well as high-flux membranes that facilitate higher water flow rates. Additionally, these enhanced membranes are designed to withstand the extreme conditions of feed solutions, such as high salinity or the presence of organic contaminants. Furthermore, RO plants demonstrate significantly higher energy efficiency compared to alternative desalination technologies, such as multi-stage flash distillation systems.

The reverse osmosis (RO) process is influenced by several factors, including osmotic and operational pressures, salt rejection rates, and permeate recovery [30]. The properties of the membrane material play a crucial role in determining its performance, affecting both physical and chemical characteristics. An optimal membrane material should provide high flux rates without

experiencing clogging or fouling, while also being physically durable, biologically inert, chemically stable, cost-effective, and resistant to chemical degradation [19].

Vrouwenvelder et al. (1998) investigated biofouling in nanofiltration and reverse osmosis systems at three pilot plants in the Netherlands. Operational issues such as increased normalized pressure drop (NPD) and reduced normalized flux (MTC) were linked to biofilm formation, as confirmed by membrane autopsies and biomass analyses (TDC, ATP, HPC). Despite low AOC in feed water, biofouling was exacerbated by chemical dosing (e.g., acid for CaCO₃ control), which increased biofilm formation. Cleaning reduced metabolic activity (ATP), but failed to effectively remove biomass (TDC), highlighting the limited efficacy of conventional cleaning. The study concluded that preventive strategies—such as removal of growth-promoting compounds, chemical purity, and improved cleaning methods—are essential for managing biofouling in RO systems [62].

Al-Mutaz and Al-Ghunaimi (2001) investigated the effect of feed water temperature on the performance of reverse osmosis (RO) units, using theoretical analysis, simulation software, and data from Riyadh water treatment plants. The study highlighted that as temperature increases, the required feed pressure decreases, while permeate salinity increases. This results in lower energy consumption and potential membrane cost savings, since higher temperatures allow for greater permeate flow and fewer required membrane elements. The authors reported an approximate 3% increase in permeate flux per 1°C rise in feed temperature. These findings underscore the importance of temperature management for optimizing RO system efficiency and reducing operational costs.

In 2012, Alireza Zirakrad and colleagues conducted an investigation into the performance of the Bandar-Lengeh RO plant in Iran. As shown in Figure 2.4, while water treated by RO1 and RO2 displayed variations in quality, parameters

such as total dissolved solids (TDS), Na⁺, and Cl⁻ levels in both saltwater and groundwater exhibited minimal changes during the first half of 2012. The highest values for these parameters were recorded in June for RO1 desalted water, whereas the lowest values were observed in July for RO2 desalted water [35].

In 2016, N.K. Khanzada and colleagues conducted an experimental study using synthetic water at various concentrations, with changes in the recovery value within a specified range, to examine the rejection efficiency under these conditions. The study considered the impact of different membrane types, with two distinct types used in the experiments. Additionally, the researchers explored various pre-treatment methods to assess the performance of desalination membranes under different scenarios [61].

The results revealed that pre-treatment methods involving forward osmosis and ultrafiltration were more effective than the other methods tested. However, it is important to note that these methods entail higher operational costs.

Taha et al. (2021) conducted a techno-economic evaluation of small-scale reverse osmosis (RO) desalination systems operating in Safwan, Iraq, where brackish groundwater is used due to surface water scarcity. Data collected from eight RO plants revealed that the cost of producing potable water (\$2.4/m³) exceeds the selling price (\$1.3/m³), primarily due to high membrane replacement (30.98%) and energy costs (48.38%). The study identified elevated total dissolved solids (TDS) levels—up to 13,000 mg/L—as a major contributor to membrane degradation, far exceeding the recommended operating range for BWRO membranes (1,000–7,000 mg/L). Additionally, software-based analysis indicated a high risk of inorganic scaling, further increasing operational costs. The authors emphasized the importance of proper feedwater pre-treatment, conservative design, and skilled operation to extend membrane lifespan and improve cost

efficiency. They also recommended using anti-scaling strategies, optimizing the recovery ratio, and integrating renewable energy sources to reduce energy costs. Skill development for plant operators was highlighted as a critical factor for improving system performance and maintenance practices. [63].

2.4.2 Improvement of Reverse Osmosis Processes

Because of its low energy consumption, low investment costs, and enhanced membrane technologies with high fluxes and low operating pressures, RO desalination technology is becoming more and more common. Numerous publications emphasize how RO desalination can help with issues related to water scarcity.

A number of techniques and technologies, such as the following, can be used to enhance the performance of RO plants:

- Making use of cutting-edge membrane materials with optimal salt rejection qualities. Higher water quality and higher rates of salt rejection may result from this.
 - Enhancement of operational parameters such as pressure and temperature. Increasing permeate flux can result in more rapid water production and enhanced effectiveness.
 - Implementing successful pre-treatment methods such as sedimentation and coagulation, this will extend the membrane's life and improve overall plant performance by minimizing membrane fouling and filtering out suspended particles.
 - Systems for energy recovery among others, this helps in recovering and recycling energy from brine concentrate stream which aids in reduction of overall energy consumption in RO plant.

With these tactics and technology in place, RO plants can perform significantly better, generating more water at higher rates, better salt rejection, using less energy with a more sustainable overall plant design.

Nevertheless, due to the results of the innovative membrane technologies development, the last decade has seen high-flux membranes with low working pressure, the ability to withstand aggressive water-state feed plants, that makes them feel great.

These improved membranes use less energy, invest capital, occupy space and require maintenance compared to alternative techniques for desalination.

Ongoing research and development activities are focused on developing membrane technologies, optimizing operating conditions and new pre-treatment methods, to enhance the performance of RO plants.

RO desalination has proven to be a promising technology in many work streams seeking cheaper and environmentally friendly methodologies for water recovery. There are a range of tools and technologies that can be used to enhance the efficiency of RO plants, including:

- 1- Advanced membrane materials: Researchers are indeed developing new membrane materials with improved salt-tolerance capabilities. In the end, these advanced membranes can extract much more salt ions from the feed water, which results in higher water quality and salt rejection rates.
- 2- Optimization of operating conditions: It is incredible how much better RO plant performance can be achieved by determining the ideal operating parameters, such as pressure and temperature. It is possible to enhance permeate flux by modifying these parameters.

- 3- Remove those bothersome particles and enhance overall plant performance through a variety of techniques, including coagulation, flocculation, and sedimentation.
- 4- Energy recovery systems: These systems, which include pressure exchangers, turbine generators, and energy transfer pumps, can actually assist in recovering and recycling energy from the brine concentrate stream.

By enhancing RO plant performance and efficiency, these technologies can raise water production rates, boost salt rejection, lower energy use, and enhance plant sustainability overall. Research on innovative membrane designs, such as thin-film composite membranes and nanostructured materials, is still ongoing because it seems like there is always potential for improvement.

Carvalho et al. [46] (2004) investigated the implementation of a photovoltaic-powered reverse osmosis (PV-RO) system for potable water supply in a remote, semi-arid region of Brazil. The study evaluated two motor configurations: a DC motor and a three-phase induction motor, under high ambient temperature (28°C) and solar irradiance (~2000 kWh/m²/year) conditions. Data analysis showed that the three-phase induction motor was more suitable, delivering better performance with a specific energy consumption of 3.03 kWh/m³ and a recovery ratio of 27%. The cost of producing drinking water was estimated at US\$12.76/m³. The research also emphasized the critical role of community engagement in ensuring system sustainability and proposed the development of self-financing mechanisms to cover operation and maintenance costs, which accounted for approximately 6% of the total capital investment.

Gabelich et al. [69] (2007) evaluated a two-stage RO process with intermediate chemical demineralization (ICD) for achieving high water recovery (up to 95%) from Colorado River brackish water. The process integrated primary

RO (PRO), alkaline-induced precipitation in a solids contact reactor (SCR), and secondary RO (SRO). At an SCR effluent pH above 10, the system achieved removal efficiencies of 94–97% Ca^{2+} , 97–98% Ba^{2+} , 88–95% Sr^{2+} , and 67–85% SiO_2 , which significantly reduced the scaling potential in the SRO stage. Despite operational variations, the pilot system maintained stable performance over months, with <10% variation in permeate flux and normalized salt passage <3%. The study emphasized the need for robust pH control and appropriate antiscalant selection, particularly to mitigate silica and gypsum scaling. This integrated approach proved technically feasible for high-recovery desalination, particularly in water-scarce regions, though it demands precise operational control.

Sanciolo et al. [68] (2012) investigated the enhancement of water recovery in RO systems treating municipal wastewater by using Accelerated Seeded Precipitation (ASP), specifically with calcium phosphate to remove calcium from the concentrate stream. Laboratory results demonstrated effective calcium removal (from 250 mg/L to 10 mg/L) using phosphate dosing at pH 10. Pilot-scale testing on a 25 kL/day system confirmed the feasibility of the process, though challenges emerged with turbidity post-ceramic ultrafiltration (CUF), likely due to heating-induced precipitation. The ASP-RO system allowed for up to 90% water recovery, significantly reducing the volume of brine requiring disposal. However, chemical and energy costs were high—estimated at \$21/kL and \$3.8/kL respectively—though partially offset by reduced evaporation pond requirements and the potential reuse of recovered calcium phosphate as fertilizer. The study concludes that this approach is economically viable mainly in inland regions with stringent brine disposal constraints.

McGovern and Lienhard [44] (2014) conducted a comparative analysis of forward osmosis (FO) and RO in the context of seawater desalination, with a

particular focus on energy requirements. The study concludes that RO significantly outperforms FO in terms of energy efficiency. The primary limitation of FO lies in the energy-intensive draw dilution and regeneration step, which substantially increases its theoretical and practical energy demand. Even with optimized draw solutions and potential reductions in membrane fouling during regeneration, FO remains energetically inferior to RO for seawater applications. The authors suggest that future FO research should concentrate on niche applications—such as treatment of high-salinity brines or non-regenerative systems—where RO is less viable.

Omar [67] (2015) investigated the use of seeded precipitative softening (seeded crystallization) as a pretreatment for brackish water reverse osmosis (BWRO) concentrate streams, aiming to reduce scaling potential and enable their reuse in secondary RO systems. Under optimal conditions (pH 10.6, 3 g/L seed concentration, 100 μm seed size, 1 min residence time, 1 L/min flow rate), the process achieved a 96.76% reduction in calcium ion concentration and lowered the Langelier Saturation Index from 1.6 to 0.05. These improvements significantly reduce membrane scaling risks, supporting higher water recovery rates and smaller concentrate volumes. The study demonstrates the feasibility of continuous seeded crystallization as an effective method for enabling concentrate reuse in multi-stage RO desalination setups.

Ammous et al. [70] (2016) explored the integration of Photovoltaic Thermal (PV/T) technology with RO desalination and proposed a Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) to optimize system performance. The PV/T system provides both thermal and electrical energy, improving RO efficiency by increasing feed water temperature and reducing membrane stress. The fuzzy controller dynamically regulates the circulating fluid flow rate through the PV/T collectors

to maximize electrical output, protect membrane integrity, and reduce energy consumption per cubic meter of desalinated water. Simulations in LABVIEW showed enhanced PV/T efficiency, stabilized RO operation, and reduced salt rejection, leading to ecological and economic advantages. The economic analysis demonstrated that PV/T-RO systems have a lower initial cost and reduced water production cost compared to conventional PV-RO setups.

Chantharawong et al. [65] (2017) evaluated the effectiveness of pretreating groundwater with activated carbon and cationic exchange resin before RO for defluoridation. The study, conducted under controlled conditions (0.6 MPa, 25 °C), demonstrated that the RO system with pretreatment achieved slightly higher fluoride rejection (97%) compared to the system without pretreatment (95%), along with a higher permeate flux. During membrane fouling tests using kaolin, both systems showed reduced performance; however, the system with pretreatment achieved better flux recovery (92%) post-chemical cleaning, compared to 81% for the untreated system. The findings emphasize the importance of pretreatment in enhancing fluoride removal efficiency, improving flux, and sustaining long-term membrane performance.

Liu et al. [45] (2018) investigated the modification of polysulfone (PSf)/sulfonated polysulfone (SPSf) blended porous ultrafiltration (UF) supports to enhance the RO performance of aromatic polyamide thin-film composite (TFC) membranes. The study systematically explored the influence of solvent type, polymer concentration, and SPSf doping content on membrane structure and performance. Through surface and structural characterization (SEM, AFM, and contact angle analysis), the authors demonstrated that a support composition of 6 wt% SPSf, 14 wt% PSf, and DMF as the solvent yielded supports with higher porosity, larger pore size, and increased surface hydrophilicity. These

characteristics promoted the formation of polyamide TFC membranes with significantly improved water flux (approximately 1.2 times higher) and slightly enhanced salt rejection compared to membranes fabricated with unmodified PSf supports. The findings highlight a simple yet effective method for improving the separation efficiency of RO membranes by modifying the support layer composition and structure.

Qasim et al. [47] (2019) provided a comprehensive state-of-the-art review of RO desalination, highlighting it as the most mature and widely adopted membrane-based technology for addressing global water scarcity. The review covered fundamental theories and models related to concentration polarization and membrane transport, critically evaluating their accuracy in predicting polarization effects. Detailed analysis was presented on various RO membrane module configurations—plate-and-frame, tubular, spiral-wound, and hollow-fiber—as well as membrane characterization techniques. Significant focus was placed on membrane fouling, a major operational challenge in RO, which increases energy demand and maintenance costs due to reduced flux, declining permeate quality, and membrane degradation. The authors reviewed both conventional (e.g., coagulation-flocculation, media filtration, disinfection) and advanced (e.g., microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF)) pre-treatment strategies, identifying UF, MF, and coagulation-flocculation as the most prevalent in practice. Design principles, energy efficiency, and economic aspects of RO systems were also discussed, noting that technological advancements have significantly lowered the cost of desalinated water to competitive levels. Lastly, the review addressed emerging hybrid RO systems and outlined the ongoing challenges that hinder further optimization of RO desalination technologies.

Yerizam et al. [72] (2019) evaluated the performance of reverse osmosis membranes in producing ultrapure water (TDS ≈ 0 ppm) using two feed types: PDAM water and water pretreated by microfiltration (MF) and ultrafiltration (UF). The study compared single-pass and circulating feed configurations. In single-pass mode, increasing pressure (20–50 Psig) improved both product flux and TDS rejection (96.6–97.5%). Under circulation feed at constant pressure (50 Psig), the system achieved TDS rejection up to 97.3%, with gradual reductions in TDS and conductivity upon recirculation. The produced water exhibited ultrapure characteristics (TDS 0.16–0.48 ppm, conductivity 0.17–0.49 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, pH 6.99–7.2, resistivity 177–185 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$), compliant with ASTM D1193-99e1 and NCCLS standards. The study confirms the effectiveness of RO in achieving high-purity water, especially when combined with recirculation feeding.

Ruiz-García and Nuez [64] (2020) conducted a simulation-based performance assessment of seawater reverse osmosis (SWRO) spiral-wound membrane modules (SWMMs) focusing on the influence of different feed spacer geometries (FSGs). Using correlations derived from experimental data and computational fluid dynamics modeling, the study evaluated how variations in FSGs and membrane permeability coefficients affected system performance across pressure vessels containing six to eight membrane elements. Results indicated that the impact of FSGs was more pronounced in membranes with higher water permeability coefficients and increased further with the number of elements in series. Additionally, FSG geometry significantly influenced specific energy consumption (SEC) and permeate concentration (C_p), particularly at higher feed flow rates (Q_f). The study suggests that tailoring FSGs to specific membrane types and operational conditions could enhance SWRO system performance and energy efficiency. However, the analysis was limited to simulation data and did not account for the effects of membrane fouling, which may influence FSG

performance under real operating conditions. The authors recommend further consideration of FSG customization by membrane manufacturers despite potential cost implications.

Aumesquet-Carretero et al. [71] (2022) evaluated the integration of pressure retarded osmosis (PRO) into RO desalination systems to harness salinity gradient energy for reducing specific energy consumption (SEC). Three RO–PRO hybrid configurations from Sarp et al.'s 2016 patent were analyzed using ROSA software, alongside a comparative conventional SWRO-BWRO scheme. Results showed that the optimal SEC depended on the type of low-salinity water source used in the PRO stage. For industrial wastewater, the best-performing configuration achieved 1.54 kWh/m³, though regulations limited its practical application. Replacing a pressure exchanger with a turbocharger offered regulatory compliance with slightly reduced efficiency. For urban treated wastewater, the conventional SWRO with two-pass BWRO delivered the lowest SEC of 1.47 kWh/m³. The study demonstrates that RO–PRO hybridization can significantly enhance desalination energy efficiency when appropriately matched with low-salinity feed sources and regulatory constraints.

2.4.3 Reverse Osmosis Processes Modelling and Simulation

The mathematical modeling of RO systems is critical in the design and operation of the RO process. Actually, the linking RO performance to operational factors and design variables, allowing you to optimize process variables without affecting the real plant. [1].

Abdel-Rahman [83] (2006) conducted a numerical modeling study on RO desalination systems with a focus on concentration polarization and system performance. The model solves momentum, energy, and mass conservation equations using the SIMPLE pressure-correction scheme and QUICK high-order

discretization, implemented on a staggered grid. Simulations were validated against experimental data, confirming the model's accuracy. The study analyzed the effects of varying operational parameters such as feed temperature and recovery rate, and emphasized the model's utility in simulating real-world scenarios. The simulation tool developed was shown to be versatile and applicable to a range of industrial RO systems, allowing for the integration of customized flux and rejection models.

Pascual Caro [28] (2014) developed several data-driven modeling and control approaches for RO desalination systems using experimental data from the Mini-Mobile-Modular (M3) pilot plant at UCLA. Using Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), both steady-state and dynamic models were built to accurately predict plant outputs, including freshwater conductivity, using only feed conditions. The composite SVR model showed high accuracy, outperforming traditional first-principles methods. Additionally, fault detection and data correction tools based on SOM and SVR were created, with SVR demonstrating superior fault isolation and sensor data correction capabilities. The study concluded that data-based models offer significant advantages in prediction accuracy, control, fault detection, and process optimization compared to conventional techniques.

Abdel-Fatah et al. [77] (2016) conducted a case study on the design and performance evaluation of a RO desalination plant aimed at producing 3,600 m³/day of permeate water with a quality of ~100 ppm TDS from a well water feed of 10,000 ppm TDS. The plant was designed with a 50% recovery rate, 132 membrane elements arranged in 22 pressure vessels (6 elements each), and incorporated an energy recovery device, saving approximately \$30,556/year. A degasifier was also included to reduce CO₂ levels and minimize NaOH

consumption in post-treatment. The design process involved multi-variable optimization using ROSA software, and emphasized operational safety, automatic control, and shutdown/startup protocols. The study highlights the cost and performance benefits of optimized design and advanced equipment in RO desalination..

Kazemian et al. [78] (2018) applied the Design of Experiments (DOE) methodology to evaluate the impact of system design (number of membranes, recovery rate) and operating conditions (feed flow rate, salinity, temperature, alkalinity) on energy consumption and permeate water quality in an industrial-scale RO plant. The study found that increasing feed water temperature and the number of membranes improves energy efficiency, while higher feed flow rate and alkalinity enhance permeate quality. Conversely, elevated feed salinity, temperature, and system recovery rate increased permeate salinity. The findings underscore the importance of optimizing these parameters to achieve cost-effective, high-performance, and environmentally friendly RO desalination.

Kok Pol Chee et al. [79] (2018) evaluated the performance of three desalination pilot plants (RO1, RO2, and NF3) in Mallard Slough using ROSA simulation software. The study compared simulated results with experimental data across key performance indicators: feed pressure, flux, recovery ratio, and TDS removal. The results revealed minimal deviations between simulated and actual values—less than 2% for flux and 8% for recovery in RO1 and NF3—demonstrating the reliability and accuracy of ROSA in modeling real plant performance. Notably, the RO1 double-pass system achieved the highest permeate volume and recovery rate (82%), while RO2 showed greater discrepancies, likely due to unmodeled factors like antiscalant omission and feed salinity variability.

The findings confirm ROSA's utility as a valid tool for pilot-scale RO system evaluation and optimization.

Lee et al. [74] (2019) conducted a dynamic process modeling and simulation study for the Gijang SWRO desalination plant in Korea, aiming to support the development of a high-fidelity Operator Training Simulator (OTS). The process models—covering DAF, DMF, UF, and RO with energy recovery devices (ERD)—were developed using real plant design parameters and validated against actual performance data. The simulator effectively replicated system behaviors, including pressure differentials, membrane fouling, and performance recovery following cleaning procedures (e.g., BW, CEB, CIP). It also demonstrated the capacity to predict seasonal performance variation due to changes in seawater temperature. This simulation framework provides a basis for integrated digital twin platforms and future OTS integration with real-time distributed control systems (DCS).

Mahadeva et al. [75] (2021) applied soft computing techniques—specifically ANN, PSO-ANN, FIS, and ANFIS—to model and optimize membrane performance in SWRO desalination plants. Using four key input parameters (feed temperature, pressure, flow rate, and TDS) and two outputs (permeate flow and TDS), the models were trained on experimental data. The PSO-ANN model outperformed others, achieving R^2 values of 0.998 (flow rate) and 0.997 (TDS) and the lowest mean squared errors, demonstrating high accuracy and minimal residuals. The study confirms the potential of hybrid neural-fuzzy models as reliable tools for real-time diagnostics and process optimization, contributing to reduced Capex, Opex, and energy usage in desalination operations.

Saeed and Alhawaj [27] (2024) developed a computational model to predict the performance of RO systems under different membrane configurations

and feed water salinities. The model simulated a single pressure vessel with seven membrane elements and evaluated system behavior for feed concentrations of 32,000 mg/L and 40,000 mg/L. Performance indicators such as recovery rate, feed pressure, salt rejection, and permeate concentration were analyzed and compared against results obtained using WAVE software. The simulation outcomes closely matched the WAVE predictions, indicating the model's high accuracy. The study concluded that the developed model can reliably forecast RO performance across various membrane types and manufacturers, making it a useful tool for system design and optimization.

2.4.4 Emerging Technologies for Optimizing Reverse Osmosis Performance

The performance of RO can be enhanced by a number of cutting-edge techniques and methods, such as membrane modification, pre-treatment technologies, integration of renewable energy sources, and sophisticated control schemes. New studies have shed light on the most recent developments and possible approaches to improve the sustainability and efficiency of RO systems. Membrane modification strategy is a key to maximizing RO performance as they describe how the porous support material can be modified in order to improve RO membrane performance [42].

Cohen-Tanugi and Grossman [81] (2012) used molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to explore the desalination potential of nanoporous graphene membranes. Their findings show that carefully controlled pore sizes and chemical functionalization (e.g., hydroxyl groups) enable effective salt rejection and ultrahigh water permeability—several orders of magnitude greater than conventional RO membranes. While hydroxylation enhances water flux due to hydrophilicity, it slightly compromises ion rejection by interfering with the

hydration shell of salts. The study underscores the potential of atomically thin nanostructures like graphene for next-generation high-efficiency membranes.

Safarpour et al. [80] (2014) developed a novel PVDF ultrafiltration membrane enhanced with reduced graphene oxide/titanium dioxide (rGO/TiO₂) nanocomposite, using the phase inversion method. The incorporation of 0.05 wt% rGO/TiO₂ significantly improved hydrophilicity, pure water flux (by 54.9%), and antifouling resistance, compared to unmodified PVDF membranes. Characterization techniques confirmed enhanced surface morphology (finger-like structure), reduced water contact angle, and increased flux recovery ratio. The study demonstrates that rGO/TiO₂ nanocomposites are promising antifouling additives, offering potential for improved membrane performance in RO pretreatment or hybrid systems.

2.4.5 Concluding Remarks

This research has presented a comprehensive study on enhancing the efficiency of RO desalination systems through mathematical modeling and system optimization. The developed models provided valuable insights into the operational behavior of RO processes, allowing for more precise performance predictions and efficiency improvements. By identifying key energy-consuming components and proposing targeted solutions, this work contributes to the ongoing efforts toward sustainable and cost-effective desalination technologies.

This study has highlighted the delicate balance between theoretical modeling and practical applicability. It has also underscored the critical role of interdisciplinary approaches—merging thermodynamics, fluid mechanics, and control systems—to address the complex challenges in water treatment. While the proposed methods show promising outcomes, further validation through large-scale pilot testing would strengthen the real-world applicability of the findings.

Ultimately, this thesis aspires to support future research and industrial implementation by offering a framework that not only improves performance but also aligns with **global sustainability goals in water resource management**.

CHAPTER

3

*Experimental
Works*

Chapter Three

Experimental Works

3.1 General

Numerous aspects that have a major impact on the operation of desalination plants are described in the sources; however, the presentation and quantity of these factors varied among the sources. For optimal performance and good membrane health, a facility has to detect and monitor variables such as pressure, flow, temperature, pH, and feed water concentration. It is also necessary to quantify and monitor the oxidation-reduction potential (ORP) in historical systems [83]. These measurement types have a direct bearing on the system's success and efficacy. As a result, the three categories of influences on the treatment plant's performance that were the subject of this study were as follows:

- 1- Influences of feed water concentration.
- 2- Influences of feed water temperature.
- 3- Influences of feed water flow rate.

The process of studying operating conditions also requires a complete description of the desalination plant and all its accessories.

3.2 General Analysis and Design Procedure

Feed water does not enter the desalination unit for RO until it is pre-treated. An effective RO system should aim to minimize feed pressure and membrane costs (number of elements) for a given needed permeate flow, while maximizing recovery and salt rejection. The relative relevance of these operational parameter-related factors (recovery vs. membrane expenses, for example) affects the best

design. The recovery as measured by a permeate flow is influenced by numerous parameters, although the desired salt rejection is typically accomplished.

Before beginning the experimental work as a research and analysis, the system design guidelines in the desalination plant in Garmatt-Ali were confirmed. The plant's operation and the analysis of field test results gathered by keeping a focus on production quality and performance both took these principles into consideration. The rules are displayed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 System Design Guidelines

Feed Source	Surface Water
Feed Water SDI	3 - 5
Max, % Recovery per Element	15
Max, Permeate Flow Rate per 8" Diameter Element (m ³ /h)	0.92
Max, Feed Flow Rate per 8" Diameter Element (m ³ /h)	12.6

Prioritizing the link between the desired permeate flow and operational parameters is the first step in designing a RO system. This is followed by optimizing the parameters within the physical constraints imposed by the RO membrane elements as well as the feed water, which may scale and foul. For instance, the solubility of salts that are sparingly soluble and the feed water's colloidal fouling potential of up to 87.5% (which can only be reached with a multi-array system) limit the recovery of brackish water systems. The scaling and fouling propensity of the feed water with an SDI of 3 to 5 limits the recovery by a single brackish water element to 15%.

In contrast, brackish water systems need more complex designs because of the different scaling and fouling potentials of the feed waters as well as the need for multi-array systems when recovery rates exceed 50%. Higher fouling rates and

more frequent chemical cleaning are expected to occur in a system designed with high permeate flux rates. There is a strong correlation between the amount of fouling particles present and the pretreatment feed water's silt density index (SDI) value. The limits on permeate flux and element recovery for various types of fluids can be established by experience with the association between the membrane fouling trend and the SDI value.

As part of the desalination plant's design and analytical testing, the GARO2 desalination plant's operating system was put through unusual applications like pumping water at maximum flow rate, raising the feed water temperature to the maximum extent, and increasing feed water concentrations.

3.3 General Description of the Plant

The RO desalination plant for Garmatt-Ali (GARO1) is a plant of the College of Engineering at Basrah University, which is managed by the Department of Chemical Engineering. This station is the main source of fresh drinking water at the university's site, in addition to marketing water by selling it general uses in the same region. So its financial revenues are very limited. This plant was established in 1995, and it was rehabilitated after 2003.

A small, secondary laboratory plant GARO2 (the case study) was added to the main station in 2016, and it is completely separated from the main station in terms of water source, water drainage, and operating hours. All details of GARO1 and GARO2 plants are shown in Figure 3.1 and 3.2 respectively.

GARO mainly is composed of two stages with three vessels (5-module with 8"-dia and 5 m length each) for first stage (GARO1) and two vessels (3-module with 8"-dia and 3 m length each) for second stage (GARO2).

Fig 3.1 GARO1 desalination plant diagram

3.3.1 First stage GARO1

The main source of feeding water is the water of the Shatt al-Arab river in the Garmatt Ali area, but it is not drawn directly through the GARO1, but rather through a conventional plant belonging to the General Directorate of Basrah Water, which is name Garma-1 (G1). This plant carries out the process of sedimentation, filtration, flocculation and coagulation, and then the GARO1 withdraws water from it, where all suspended solids and colors are removed during this stage. After that, the water delivered to the GARO1. The GARO1 consists, according to Figure 3.1 of the following parts and devices:

- 1- Sedimentation Tank (ST): for removal of suspended particles by gravity.

- 2- Feed Pump (FP): It is used to give the water the appropriate pressure to pass through the pretreatment processes ($Q= 18-45 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $H= 29.5\text{m}$).
- 3- Sand filter (SF): The process of reducing water turbidity by removing impurities, dirt and other materials (before it enters the desalination treatment plant) requires the presence of a filter or a group of sand filters, because the presence of turbidity leads to rapid damage to the membranes of the RO unit (i.e. protecting them from clogging). The carbon that forms after the sand filter, and the sand filter is backwashed after a certain period of operation, to remove the dirt collected on the layers of the sand filter.
- 4- Activated Carbon Filter (ACF): The presence of free chlorine in the water entering the desalination plant leads to damage to the membranes by oxidizing them and then destroying them. Therefore, it is necessary to place filters containing activated carbon before pumping to the desalination membranes, which absorb the free chlorine and reduce its concentration to nearly zero. There are other functions of the carbon filter, which is to retain any organic pollutants, as well as removing the smell and taste from the water. Of course, the carbon filter is backwashed to remove any impurities that accumulate in it after a period of operation.
- 5- Cotton Filter (CF): provides an extra measure of defense against any pollutants or turbidity, to collect any contaminants that escape from the sand filter.
- 6- Softening Filter (Sof. F): In RO plant system, a softening filter (typically an ion-exchange water softener) is used to remove hardness ions, primarily calcium (Ca^{+2}) and magnesium (Mg^{+2}) from the feed water before it reaches the RO membranes.
- 7- Feed water tank (T1): used to store water before pumping it to the RO filters.

- 8- Antiscalant and Acid Injection (AS & AI): The design of the RO pretreatment process is significantly simplified by using antiscalants as threshold inhibitors [84]. In the average range of 75–85% RO water recovery, scaling, dissolved iron, aluminum, and manganese, as well as silica polymerization chemistry, are virtually always managed. Antiscalants are crucial for brackish water recoveries that are 90–98% extreme. ROs are being tested to the limiting opposed osmotic pressure of 1000 psi (68 atmospheres) to lower the volume of RO concentrate that is needed for disposal in inland locations where disposing of RO concentrates is expensive or impracticable [85].
- 9- High-Pressure pump (HPP): used to provide necessary pressures.
- 10- The water enters the reverse osmosis units (ROU) (3 parallel vessels each one consists of 5 seawater spiral-wound membranes (Film Tec Corporation SW30ULE-400). There would reduce the percentage of salts in the feed water by pumping water with high-pressure pumps to membranes that have a reverse osmosis feature that divides the water into two parts, the first with low salinity or what is called permeate water, and the second with a high salt concentration and called brine water. The RO unit contains membranes containing polycarbonate membranes. Layers of rolled membranes that separate the water into two parts, the product and the reject. Multiple measuring devices can be added to the RO unit, including a measurement of the output flow, the reject flow, an inlet pressure gauge, an operating pressure gauge, and a measure of the percentage of water salts resulting from the RO unit.
- 11- Permeate Water Tank (T2): used to store the permeate water.
- 12- Back-Wash Water Tank (T4): This tank is used to hold some of the produced water for "back-washing," or cleaning the station with water.

- 13- Valves (V): To regulate the direction of the flow via the pipes.
- 14- Back-Wash Pump (BWP): It is used to provide the appropriate pressure to wash filters and membranes ($Q= 18-45 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $H= 29.5\text{m}$).

3.3.2 Second stage GARO2

Previously, the GARO2 laboratory plant took feed water directly from raw water, but due to the development of water networks in the region, the transmission line to this plant was cut in 2015. In this study, the path of the feed water was changed and the main source of feeding the plant became brine water for the GARO1 plant, as shown in Figures 3.1 and 3.2 (note the connection between the two plants). The description of GARO2 can be noted as the following:

- 1- Feed water tank (T1).
- 2- Feed Pump (FP).
- 3- Antiscalant and Acid Injection (AS & AI).
- 4- Sand filter (SF)
- 5- Activated Carbon Filter (ACF)
- 6- Cotton Filter (CF).
- 7- High-Pressure pump (HPP).
- 8- The RO units (ROU) (two parallel vessels each one consists of three brackish water spiral-wound membranes (Film Tec Corporation BW30-400/34).
- 9- Permeate Water Tank (T2).
- 10- Backwash Water Tank (T4).
- 11- Valves (V).
- 12- Back-Wash Pump (BWP).
- 13- Brine Water Tank (T3): used to collect the brine water, which is released, from the plant.

Fig 3.2 GARO2 desalination plant diagram

In order to guarantee the production of clean, transportable water and prevent system damage, the operation of a RO desalination plant, like the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant, requires regular monitoring and maintenance of system conditions [86]. Input and pretreatment problems surface of water have become prominent operational obstacles for saltwater desalination plants [20]. These problems may have an impact on the reverse osmosis process' overall effectiveness and performance, which may have an effect on the produced water's quality and raise operating expenses. Therefore, it is imperative for the operators of the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant to address these challenges and maintain optimal operating conditions to ensure the efficient and reliable operation of the plant. The increasing need for water and developments in

low-energy desalination technologies have led to a sharp rise in desalination plant capacity in recent years [87].

3.4 System Analysis and Design's Important Parameters

3.4.1 Silt Density Index (SDI)

3.4.1.1 Sampling points for SDI testing

Certain outlet points in the desalination plant are supposed to be installed at least five points. It can be summarized as follows:

- 1- Water intake point: The SDI value at this point determines the form of pretreatment, whether physical or chemical treatments. For example, a sedimentation tank is proposed, the diameter of the sand filter is determined, and the height of the media inside the sand filter. The value of the SDI affects the filtration rate, because there is an inverse relationship between the SDI and the filtration rate.
- 2- Before and after the sand filter: This determines the efficiency of the sand filter.
- 3- Before and after the cotton filter (cartridge filter): to know the efficiency of the cotton filter.
- 4- Before the high pressure pump: The SDI value at this point determines the details and shape of the RO membrane. For example, if the SDI value is high, it is preferable to use a membrane filter with a large thickness of feed spacers to prevent fouling of the membranes, which leads to increased concentration polarization. It is preferable to reduce the flux value to extend the life of the membranes. It is also possible to predict what will happen with the membrane model. The type of chemical washing of the filters (acid

or alkaline) can also be determined from the color of the filter paper for the SDI test.

3.4.1.2 Procedures to obtain SDI

- 1- Before measuring, rinse the pipe system for at least 10 minutes. Make sure all connections are tight and sealed. Use Teflon tape if necessary.
- 2- Close the inlet valve.
- 3- Connect the device to the sample point, attach the filter fixture, and open the external valve.
- 4- Open the inlet valve and remove the filter fixture by pushing the connector upwards.
- 5- Remove the base of filter fixture.
- 6- Place the filter paper and O-ring on the fixture base. Assemble the fixture and reattach it to the connector.
- 7- Open the inlet valve. Pull to unlock the pressure adjustment valve and set the pressure to 2.1 bar.
- 8- Close the inlet valve again and replace the filter.
- 9- Open the inlet valve completely and immediately measure how long it takes to drain 500 ml. This is initial time t_i .
- 10- Let the water flow for exactly 15 minutes and repeat the measurement (the measure time may differ considerably). This time is the final time t_f .
- 11- Calculate SDI by using equation 2.1

SDI can take the values shown in the Figure 3.3.

Fig 3.3 Desalination Plant Status Chart for Important SDI values

3.4.2 Turbidity

Erosion of riverbanks and soil is the main cause of turbidity. Turbidity is also increased by logging, dredging, extractive industries (like mining), and sewage flow. In metropolitan locations, where there are limited places for runoff after a rainstorm, turbidity also rises because of how rapidly a lot of fast-moving water may be produced there. Turbidity is further impacted by areas with subpar agricultural practices, extensive farm animal grazing, unfettered access by livestock to streams, and destruction of vegetation that preserves bank stability and filters runoff. Turbidity is more of an issue in clay soils than other types of soil.

The value of the SDI for water outside the filters along the study period is within the recommended limits in the desalination process ($SDI \leq 5 \text{ min}^{-1}$), so a decision was taken to monitor the SDI once every week and rely on the turbidity values for the following reasons:

- 1- The SDI measured during the first two weeks did not change significantly.
- 2- The period of operation of the GARO2 laboratory station is not continuing throughout the day (24 hours or a little less), which means the risk of

clogging of the membranes and the combination of the Fouling is relatively small.

- 3- Dependence on the value of the turbidity as a daily indicator to preserve the membranes.
- 4- The presence of sand and cotton filters is a safety factor that prevents the height of the SDI higher than the required limits.

3.5 Details of Some Equipment Used in GARO

3.5.1 Feed, Permeate, and Brine Water Tanks of GARO2

These tanks are made of polyethylene, which are 230 cm in diameter and 270 cm in height, are exposed to the outside air. The volume of each one is 10000 liters. These tanks were constructed at the GARO2 laboratory plant during the study period because of its importance in collecting water before and after the desalination process. They were placed on a horizontal Concrete base adjacent to the GARO2. Feed water tank full of brine water, which is disposed from GARO1.

3.5.2 The RO Membrane units

Specifications of the membranes used in the first stage GARO1 and the second stage GARO2 (membrane characteristics, the feed and inlet conditions, and detailed drawing of the membranes) are shown in Table 3.2.

3.5.3 High Pressure Pumps (HPP) of GARO2

A high-pressure pump of the type (Lowara SV-F 5SV12F022M Multistage Pump) was used, which has the specifications shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.2 Specifications and operating conditions of the Plants Membrane Elements.

		Product Name	
		SW30ULE-400i	BW30-400/34
Product Specifications			
Active Area (m ²)		37	37
Permeate flow rate (m ³ /d) [m ³ /hr]		41.6 [1.733]	40 [1.667]
Stabilized Salt Rej. (%)		99.7	99.5
Operating Limits			
Membrane Type		Polyamide Thin-Film Composite	
Max. Operating Temp. (°C)		45	45
Max. Operating Press. (bar)		83	41
Maximum Pressure Drop (bar)		0.9	1.0
pH Range, Continuous Operation		2-11	2-11
pH Range, Short-Term Cleaning (mg/l)		1-13	1-13
Maximum Feed Silt Density Index		5	5
Free Chlorine Tolerance (ppm)		<0.1	<0.1
Dimensions of Membrane Unit Inchs (mm)	A	40 (1,016)	40.0 (1,016)
	B	40.5 (1,029)	1.125 (29.0)
	C	7.9 (201)	7.9 (201)
	D	1.125 (29)	-
		SW30ULE-400i	BW30-400/34

Table 3.3 Characteristics of GARO2 High Pressure Pump HPP.

Adjective	Specification
Brand	Lowara SV-F
Type	10SV02F0156/M
Pressure bar	25
Flow l/min	40 - 143
Flow m3/h	6 - 17
Number of Impellers	2
Motor	1x 230V
Power kW	1,5
Temp max °C	40

3.6 The Sampling

The Sampling process in desalination plants requires several work steps to be followed as follows:

- 1- The Samples are taken after an operating period for the two stations of not less than half an hour.
- 2- For the purpose of physical examinations, a sample of water is taken using plastic bottles. As for the samples that are chemically examined (to be on the safe side), they are taken using bottles that are well insulated from sunlight until they are delivered to the laboratories of the Marine Science Center of the University of Basrah.
- 3- Rinse the sampling bottles with distilled water (if available) or using the same water as the samples.
- 4- Each sample consists of 3 mini samples, where the three samples are examined and the average results obtained for each sample are taken.
- 5- Physical tests include EC (TDS), pH, temperature, turbidity, and SDI. All the parameters that were calculated are included in the desalination plant design process (in the event that a new plant design is proposed), such as determining the form of physical and chemical treatment (pretreatment) or analyzing the results and evaluating the performance of the existing plant as a case study.

Five-point sampling was carried out as shown in Figures 3.1 and 3.2:

- 1- Prior to the high-pressure pump, also known as feed water, for the GARO1 desalination plant.
- 2- The produced water transportation line at GARO1 (Permeate Water).
- 3- The pipeline that carries effluent water from the first plant, known as brine water, which serves as the GARO2 plant's feed water.

- 4- The pipe that carries the water that the GARO2 desalination plant produces.
- 5- Brine Water for the GARO2 water transport pipeline.

3.7 Data Collection for Operation Conditions

Three locations provided water samples in GARO2, which were analyzed using equipment to determine TDS, EC, pH, and temperature. These places were:

- 1- Feed water tank after preparing synthetic water.
- 2- A washing tank or permeate water tank.
- 3- Brine water disposal pipeline.

3.8 Components of Assessing the Plants' Operating Conditions

A number of important factors must be taken into account when assessing the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant's operating conditions at the University of Basrah:

- 1- Feed concentration: The performance of RO plants is directly impacted by the feed concentration of the saline water. Elevated amounts of feedstock may result in decreased permeate flow rates and heightened membrane fouling, hence affecting the overall desalination process efficiency.
- 2- System maintenance and monitoring: It's critical to keep an eye on and maintain the RO desalination unit's system conditions at the proper set points [86]. This avoids system damage and guarantees the generation of the necessary volume of portable, clean water.
- 3- Operating pressure: Achieving the best possible results from the RO desalination process depends heavily on the operating pressure. It is possible to maximize the effectiveness of permeate production and salt removal by keeping the operating pressure within the acceptable range.

- 4- Pretreatment and membrane cleaning: In order to keep the RO membrane free of impurities such as dissolved organic matter and suspended particles, the supply water must be pretreated. Furthermore, in order to eliminate accumulated fouling and preserve system function, routine membrane cleaning is required. RO desalination plant performance can also be affected by variables like temperature.

pH values, salinity, and quality of feed water. These aspects need to be taken into account during the monitoring and maintenance procedures in order to provide the best possible operating conditions for the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant [91]. To maximize effectiveness and guarantee the production of clean, transportable water, the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant at the University of Basrah should have its operating conditions routinely evaluated and modified.

3.9 Results and Discussion of Operation Conditions

Due to fouling and membrane aging, performance of membrane reduces (solute flux increases, water flux decreases). However, variations in the temperature, pressure, and concentration of the feed water also affect the water and solute fluxes. Salt passage and permeate flow rate must be examined under controlled settings in order to assess the genuine reduction in system performance caused by fouling and aging [19].

According to the type of water, brackish or seawater membranes, there are two categories of membranes. As a result of the high salinity, saltwater membrane operating pressures are higher than those for brackish water membranes.

Since salinity or osmotic pressure have an adverse effect on applied feed pressure and its function, raising feed pressure is necessary to maintain a

consistent recovery percent. The osmotic pressure increases as feed salinity rises. Also, it is evident that the feed pressure and permeate salinity both rise in a similar fashion as feed salinity. If a concentrated solution were to flow, there would be a greater chance of scaling forming inside the membrane pores. This fouling may be caused by the entire or partial obstruction of several pores [97].

The feed-concentrate solution's high salt content raises osmotic pressure, which lowers the net driving pressure (NDP). As a result, the permeate salinity (C_p) rises while the product water flow rate decreases [36].

There is a distinction between raising the recovery percentage ($r\%$) and the feed flow rate (Q_f), since raising the recovery implies raising production as long as the feed flow rate (Q_f) stays constant. This is accomplished either as previously mentioned in the preceding paragraphs, or by enhancing the station's performance through pretreatment. However, increasing the feed flow Q_f by opening the valves more may result in increased pressure on the membranes and desalination pump, which raises the energy required to finish the desalination process. On the other hand, increasing the Q_f does not always increase recovery. It could have a negative impact on the station's overall performance.

3.9.1 Effect of Temperature on Permeate Concentration and Salt rejection

Reverse osmosis desalination plant performance can be noted the impact by the temperature of the feed water. Higher temperatures have been linked to decreased salt rejection and increased permeate concentration, according to research. The observed increase in salt passage in RO system at high temperature is due to changes in membrane properties (increased permeability and reduced selectivity) and decrease the water viscosity. For this reason, it's critical to keep the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant's temperature within a reasonable range in order to maximize salt rejection and reduce permeate

concentration. Temperature, pressure, pretreatment, and membrane cleaning are examples of operation parameters that are critical to the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant's best performance. Pressure is another essential component that must be closely regulated in addition to temperature for the reverse osmosis desalination plant to operate at its best.

The direct temperature variation of the permeate concentration and salt rejection are depicted in Figures (3.4 a-e) and (3.5 a-e), respectively. Consequently, a declining percentage of rejected salts is observed as following:

A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ$ C:

A.1- the permeate water concentration C_p rose from 27.8 mg/l to 62.1 mg/l.

A.2- The salt rejection $R\%$ decreased from 97.3% to 94.1%.

B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, $T = (12-38)^\circ$ C:

B.1- Permeate water concentration C_p rose from 483.0 mg/l to 937.8 mg/l.

B.2- The salt rejection $R\%$ decreased from 95.1% to 90.5%.

C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.1-13.3) m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ$ C:

C.1- Permeate water concentration C_p rose from 16.4 mg/l to 43.2 mg/l.

C.2- The salt rejection $R\%$ decreased from 98.4% to 95.9%.

D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.0-13.1) m³/h, $T = (12-38)^\circ$ C:

D.1- Permeate water concentration C_p rose from 410.9 mg/l to 638.3 mg/l.

D.2- The salt rejection $R\%$ decreased from 95.8% to 93.5%.

Fig 3.4 Effect of Temperature on Permeate Concentration Cp

Fig 3.5 Effect of Temperature on Salt rejection R%

3.9.2 Effect of Temperature on Concentration Polarization Factor and Concentration Polarization Mass Transfer Coefficient

In reverse osmosis, desalination plants, the feed water temperature had also effect the concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient and concentration polarization factor.

The concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} can also rise with temperature. To optimize the operating conditions of the Garmat-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant, it is imperative to comprehend the impact of temperature on these elements. Elevated temperatures may also affect the reverse osmosis unit's membrane permeability [92]. The effect of feed water temperature on the values of concentration polarization factor and concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient results can be discussed as follows (Figures 3.6 and 3.7):

A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about $(7.0-7.2)$ m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ$ C:

A.1- the Concentration polarization factor β increased from 1.125 to 1.227.

A.2- Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} rose from 2.31×10^{-5} m/s to 2.37×10^{-5} m/s.

B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about $(7.0-7.2)$ m³/h, $T = (12-38)^\circ$ C:

B.1- the Concentration polarization factor β increased from 1.111 to 1.179.

B.2- Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} rose from 2.36×10^{-5} m/s to 2.46×10^{-5} m/s.

C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about $(13.1-13.3)$ m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ$ C:

C.1- the Concentration polarization factor β increased from 1.116 to 1.177.

C.2- Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} rose from 3.22×10^{-5} m/s to 3.44×10^{-5} m/s.

D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.0-13.1) m^3/h , $T = (12-38)^\circ C$:

D.1- the Concentration polarization factor β increased from 1.108 to 1.149.

D.2- Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} rose from 3.25×10^{-5} m/s to 3.47×10^{-5} m/s.

The rise of β indicates that higher temperatures lead to more solute accumulation at the membrane surface relative to the bulk solution. Elevated temperatures enhance membrane permeability and solvent flux, which can increase the concentration of solutes near the membrane surface, intensifying the concentration polarization effect.

In other hand, increase K_{cp} is attributed to the reduction in water viscosity and the enhancement of molecular diffusion with temperature. As the temperature rises, the diffusivity of solutes in water increases, leading to improved mass transfer away from the membrane surface and hence a higher K_{cp} .

Fig. 3.6. Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} m/s

Fig. 3.7 Concentration polarization factor β

3.9.3 Effect of Temperature on mass flux of solute J_s

Figure (3.8 a-e) illustrates the effect of temperature of the feed water on the mass flow of the solute J_s . Because the solute permeability increases with the change in fluid characteristics brought on by an increase in temperature, as was previously indicated, the quantity of dissolved salts that may flow through desalination membranes increases as the temperature of the input water rises.

Depending on the input water concentration (C_f) and recovery percentage ($r\%$), the rate of mass flow solute rise versus temperature changes.

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ$ C: the mass flux of solute J_s increased from 273.0 mg/m².h to 1087.6 mg/m².h.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, $T = (12-38)^\circ$ C: the mass flux of solute J_s increased from 4317.9 mg/m².h to 13766.0 mg/m².h.
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.1-13.3) m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ$ C: the mass flux of solute J_s increased from 209.1 mg/m².h to 1075.4 mg/m².h.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.0-13.1) m³/h, $T = (12-38)^\circ$ C: the mass flux of solute J_s increased from 4942.8 mg/m².h to 11092.7 mg/m².h.

While elevated temperature may improve water flux, it can also reduce salt rejection efficiency, which may impact overall product water quality. Therefore, thermal effects must be carefully managed when optimizing RO operating conditions.

The experimental results indicate a direct correlation between temperature and solute mass flux (J_s) under varying feed concentrations (C_f) and flow rates (Q_f). Key findings can be summarized as follows:

- An increase in temperature within the range of approximately 11–38°C led to a significant rise in the solute mass flux. This trend was consistent across both low and high feed concentrations, suggesting that temperature positively influences membrane permeability and mass transfer kinetics in the reverse osmosis (RO) process.
- Higher feed concentrations (e.g., 9948 mg/L) resulted in substantially greater solute flux values compared to lower concentrations (e.g., 1063 mg/L) at comparable temperatures and flow conditions. This highlights the greater osmotic driving force and solute loading associated with more concentrated feeds.
- The relative increase with temperature remained pronounced, indicating that flow rate interacts with temperature effects, possibly by enhancing turbulence and reducing concentration polarization.
- While elevated temperatures enhance water and solute fluxes, they may adversely affect salt rejection efficiency. This trade-off underscores the importance of carefully balancing thermal input in RO operations to optimize productivity while maintaining desired product water quality.

Figure 3.8 Effect of Temperature on mass flux of solute J_s

3.9.4 Effect of Temperature on Feed Pressure P_f and Net Driving Pressure NDP

The temperature effect of feed water on feed pressure P_f and the NDP net driving pressure can be explained as follows (Figure 3.9 a-e and 3.10 a-e)):

A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, T= (11-38)° C:

A.1- feed water pressure P_f decreased from 15.9 bar to 13.0 bar.

A.2- Net driving Pressure NDP decreased from 14.8 bar to 11.9 bar.

B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, T= (12-38)° C:

B.1- feed water pressure P_f decreased from 22.5 bar to 19.8 bar.

B.2- Net driving Pressure NDP decreased from 13.1 bar to 10.0 bar.

C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.1-13.3) m³/h, T= (11-38)° C:

C.1- feed water pressure P_f decreased from 20.6 bar to 15.0 bar.

C.2- Net driving Pressure NDP decreased from 19.2 bar to 13.7 bar.

D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.0-13.1) m³/h, T= (12-38)° C:

D.1- feed water pressure P_f decreased from 27.3 bar to 22.0 bar.

D.2- Net driving Pressure NDP decreased from 17.6 bar to 11.8 bar.

As the temperature of the feed water increases, several physical changes occur:

- 1- Water viscosity decreases, which reduces resistance to flow through both the system and the membrane.
- 2- Membrane permeability increases, meaning less pressure is needed to achieve the same permeate flow.

3- Osmotic pressure may increase slightly due to higher solute diffusivity, but the net effect is typically a reduction in required operational pressure.

These effects lead to a decrease in both P_f and NDP as temperature rises.

Fig. (3.9 a-e) Effect of Temperature on Feed Pressure P_f

Fig. (3.10 a-e) Effect of Temperature on Net Driving Pressure NDP bar

3.9.5 Effect of Temperature on Feed and Permeate water Osmotic Pressure

π_f, π_p

Temperature is one of the main operational factors that impacts the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant's efficiency. The salinity of the feed water and the RO system's operating recovery rate determine the osmotic pressure in RO systems. Diffusion is usually driven by a concentration gradient, however a gradient in Gibbs energy provides a more robust thermodynamic explanation [93]. The osmotic pressure is the amount of pressure that must be added to a solution in order to stop water from passing through a semipermeable membrane [94]. The lowest pressure required to prevent osmosis is another definition of osmotic pressure.

The osmotic pressure π of permeate water and the feed water are directly impacted by temperature. According to earlier research, in RO processes, the temperature T of feed water greatly affects flow rate of generated fresh water and salt rejection. The RO unit's membrane permeability improves with rising feed water temperature [92, 95].

It is crucial to remember that there is a temperature range within which the RO process operates most efficiently. The Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant will function at its best and use the least amount of energy per cubic meter of water generated if it is operated within this ideal temperature range. The overall salinity of the starting water and the salt content of the desalinated water are crucial factors to take into account when operating the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant.

The amount of salt in the water immediately affects the relationship between water temperature and osmotic pressure, regardless is feed water or permeate water. The osmotic pressure π on feed waterside fluctuates from the

moment of water entering the model until it exits it because the osmotic pressure π is determined by concentration of water on both sides of membrane. This discrepancy results from the feed side's water concentration progressively rising to the maximum value, which denotes the concentration of brine water. As a result, the concentration is calculated as the average of the brine water and feed concentration. Thus, even though the concentration of the feed water remains constant during every realistic operational cycle, the osmotic pressure will fluctuate anytime the temperature of the feed water changes or the value of the feed water flow rate changes.

Although the feed water for each operational cycle is constant, in addition to the stability of the feed water discharge, the value of $C_{fc, Avg}$ changes with the change in the temperature of the feed water. The reason is that the value of the permeate water concentration increases with increasing temperature (as explained in paragraph (3.9.1)), and consequently a decrease in the value of the brine water concentration, which leads to a decrease in the concentration rate in the water channels adjacent to the membrane. Although the osmotic pressure is proportional directly proportional to the water concentration (osmotic pressure decreases with a decrease in concentration), but we notice an increase in the value of the osmotic pressure. Osmotic pressure is directly proportional to water concentration, as described by equation 2.7. While a decrease in concentration would typically lead to reduction in osmotic pressure, an overall increase is observed. This is attributed to the effect of elevated temperature which out weight the decline in concentration with in the membrane's feed channel (See Table 3.3 and Figure 3.11).

Table 3.3 Average of the osmotic pressure for all feed flow

Temperature (°C)	Average of the osmotic pressure in feed channel for all feed flow, bar					
	Cf= 1063 mg/l	Cf= 2105 mg/l	Cf= 4171 mg/l	Cf= 5979 mg/l	Cf= 8217 mg/l	Cf= 9948 mg/l
10-13	1.038	2.063	4.057	5.834	8.070	9.736
17-19	1.063	2.097	4.153	5.973	8.232	9.899
23-27	1.085	2.147	4.238	6.073	8.416	10.222
31-33	1.109	2.208	4.331	6.244	8.605	10.417
38-39	1.134	2.249	4.439	6.359	8.766	10.579

Fig. 3.11. Effect of Temperature on Feed-Concentrate water Osmotic Pressure π_{fc} bar

As the feed flow rate Q_f increase, the concentration polarization near the membrane surface is reduced due to enhanced mixing and decrease residence time. This lead to a lower salute concentration at the membrane interface, which in turn moderate the increase in osmotic pressure, as following (Figure 3.12).

A- Feed concentration $C_f=1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about $(7.0-7.2)$ m³/h, T= $(11-38)$ ° C:

Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.022 bar to 0.054 bar.

B- Feed concentration $C_f=9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about $(7.0-7.2)$ m³/h, T= $(12-38)$ ° C:

Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.391 bar to 0.830 bar.

C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.1-13.3) m³/h,
T= (11-38)° C:

Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.013 bar to 0.047 bar.

D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.0-13.1) m³/h,
T= (12-38)° C:

Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.333 bar to 0.565 bar.

In all cases, an increase in temperature led to a rise in the permeate water's osmotic pressure. This is attributed to enhanced solute transport through the membrane at higher temperatures, which results from increased diffusion coefficients and membrane permeability.

Higher feed flow rates significantly mitigated the increase in osmotic pressure with temperature when compared to lower flow rates. This is due to the reduced residence time and enhanced turbulence near the membrane surface, which minimize concentration polarization and result in a lower solute concentration at the membrane interface.

Systems operating at higher feed concentrations consistently exhibited greater osmotic pressures in the permeate compared to systems with lower concentrations, irrespective of the feed flow rate. This confirms the direct dependence of osmotic pressure on solute content.

The combination of higher temperatures and lower flow rates leads to more pronounced osmotic pressure buildup in the permeate, especially in high-salinity feeds. Therefore, to maintain membrane performance and delay fouling or scaling, it is advantageous to operate at higher feed flow rates where feasible, particularly in warm operating environments.

Fig. (3.12 a-e) Effect of Temperature on Permeate water Osmotic Pressure π_p

3.9.6 Effect of Temperature on Water Flux J_w , Permeate Flow Rate Q_p , and Recovery $r\%$

The recovery is measured in terms of permeate flow and permeate flow is measured in terms of flux. Since they are completely proportional to one another, the pattern of change in values is therefore precisely the same pattern. The

governing value that manages the remaining variables is the flux value. Since raising the temperature causes the flux to grow, it is crucial to understand how temperature affects the flux value in the desalination plant in Garmatt-Ali.

It is reasonable to maintain the amount of permeate flow constant, the number of desalination units operating when the temperature rises must be reduced, thus the energy consumptions are reduced, and thus the cost of producing one cubic meter is reduced [60]. The reason for the increase in flux is due to the increase in pore size of polymeric membranes, or perhaps due to the increased diffusion of water, which is due to a decrease in its viscosity, allowing larger quantities to pass through. All of these properties are physical properties that are directly affected by temperature [96].

The following can be used to describe how feed water temperature affects water flux, permeate flow rate, and recovery (Figures 3.13, 3.14, and 3.15, respectively):

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, T= (11-38)° C:
 - A.1- water flux increased from 0.009 m/h to 0.017 m/h.
 - A.2- permeate flow rate increased from 2.180 m³/h to 3.888 m³/h.
 - A.3- recovery r% increased from 30.7% to 54.7%.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (7.0-7.2) m³/h, T= (12-38)° C:

Fig. (3.13 a-e) Effect of Temperature on Flux of Water J_w

Fig. (3.14 a-e) Effect of Temperature on Permeate Water Flow Q_p

Fig. (3.15 a-e) Effect of Temperature on Recovery $r\%$

- B.1- water flux increased from 0.008 m/h to 0.014 m/h.
- B.2- permeate flow rate increased from 1.984 m³/h to 3.258 m³/h.
- B.3- recovery r% increased from 27.5% to 45.2%.
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.1-13.3) m³/h, $T = (11-38)^\circ \text{C}$:
- C.1- water flux increased from 0.012 m/h to 0.020 m/h.
- C.2- permeate flow rate increased from 2.831 m³/h to 4.487 m³/h.
- C.3- recovery r% increased from 21.6% to 34.2%.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, Feed flow Q_f is about (13.0-13.1) m³/h, $T = (12-38)^\circ \text{C}$:
- D.1- water flux increased from 0.012 m/h to 0.017 m/h.
- D.2- permeate flow rate increased from 2.670 m³/h to 3.857 m³/h.
- D.3- recovery r% increased from 20.3% to 29.6%.

The experimental findings from cases A through D demonstrate the significant influence of feed water temperature on key RO performance as following:

- In all tested configurations, water flux increased markedly with rising temperature. This is attributed to reduced water viscosity and enhanced diffusivity at elevated temperatures, which facilitate more efficient transport through the membrane matrix.
- The increase in water flux directly translated into higher permeate flow rates across all scenarios. For instance, at a low feed concentration, the permeate flow rose by nearly 78% (Case A), while at high concentration, the increase was around 64% (Case B) at similar flow rates. These results underscore temperature's strong effect on

volumetric water production, though the magnitude of increase diminishes slightly with higher salinity.

- Recovery percentages also improved with temperature, reflecting greater system productivity. However, the extent of improvement was influenced by both feed concentration and flow rate. At lower feed flow rates, recovery rose more significantly than at higher feed flow rates, indicating a trade-off between operating conditions and recovery optimization.
- Systems operating at lower feed concentrations and flow rates (Case A) experienced the highest relative gains in all three performance metrics. In contrast, high-concentration, high-flow conditions (Case D) exhibited more modest improvements, likely due to stronger osmotic effects and shorter membrane residence time.

3.9.7 Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on feed-concentrate and permeate water osmotic pressure

The impact of feed water concentration on the feed and permeate water osmotic pressure with constant feed flow rate Q_f is shown in Figures (3.16) and (3.17 a-e) for temperatures between 10°C and 39°C.

The performance of the desalination plant can be summarized in terms of permeate water osmotic pressure when changing the concentration value of dissolved materials from 1063 mg/l to 9948 mg/l, as follows (Figures 3.19 and 3.20):

A- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$:

A.1- feed-concentrate osmotic pressure π_{fc} increased from 1.037 bar to 9.720 bar.

- A.2- Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.022 bar to 0.391 bar.
- B- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$:
- B.1 feed-concentrate osmotic pressure π_{fc} increased from 1.130 bar to 10.548 bar.
- B.2- Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.054 bar to 0.830 bar.
- C- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$:
- C.1- feed-concentrate osmotic pressure π_{fc} increased from 1.038 bar to 9.746 bar.
- C.2- Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.013 bar to 0.333 bar.
- D- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$:
- D.1- feed-concentrate osmotic pressure π_{fc} increased from 1.134 bar to 10.597 bar.
- D.2- Permeate water Osmotic pressure π_p increased from 0.038 bar to 0.565 bar.

A consistent and significant increase in both feed-concentrate osmotic pressure and permeate osmotic pressure was observed as the concentration of dissolved salts increased. This is in accordance with the fundamental colligative property behavior, where osmotic pressure rises proportionally with solute concentration.

Elevated temperatures led to slightly higher osmotic pressures in both feed-concentrate and permeate streams compared to cooler conditions. This is likely due to the increased dissociation and mobility of ions at higher temperatures, contributing to a marginal rise in effective osmotic pressure.

Changes in feed flow rate had a negligible effect on feed-concentrate osmotic pressure but did appear to moderate the rise in permeate osmotic pressure. Higher flow rates (Cases C and D) were associated with slightly lower permeate osmotic pressures at equivalent concentrations and temperatures, indicating better mitigation of concentration polarization due to enhanced mixing and reduced solute accumulation at the membrane surface.

Among all scenarios, the highest osmotic pressures were recorded at high concentrations, high temperatures, and low flow rates—specifically, Case B. This highlights the importance of operating conditions in determining osmotic stress on the membrane. Increased osmotic pressure not only requires higher operating pressure to maintain flux but also may increase the risk of membrane fouling and reduce overall energy efficiency.

When scaling RO systems or adjusting operational parameters, careful consideration must be given to the solute concentration and temperature effects on osmotic pressure. Operating at higher feed flow rates and avoiding high salinity under elevated temperatures can help moderate osmotic pressure buildup and improve membrane performance and longevity.

3.9.8 Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Concentration Polarization C_m

The concentration of salt and other contaminants in the saltwater delivered into RO system is referred to as feed concentration. When the solute concentrations in feed water and membrane surface differ, the concentration

polarization phenomena takes place. Concentration polarization causes non-permeating materials to accumulate close to the membrane's surface, which decreases the membrane's ability to reject salt and flow [98].

Fig. (3.16 a-e) Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on permeate water osmotic pressure

Fig. (3.17) Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on feed-concentrate water osmotic pressure

The concentration polarization effect develops with increasing feed concentration and can have a detrimental influence on the process's efficiency. In the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant, it's critical to maintain a balanced feed concentration to lessen the impacts of concentration polarization. This can be accomplished by properly treating the feed water to remove big particles and contaminants using techniques like filtering and sedimentation. At the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant, operational pressure and flow rate have a major impact on the efficacy of the RO process in addition to feed concentration. Water permeability and salt rejection effectiveness of membrane are both impacted by the RO system's operating pressure. The performance of RO systems is negatively impacted by concentration polarization in a number of ways. The following describes these results [99].

- 1- Decrease Net Driving Pressure as a result of higher osmotic pressure at the membrane surface compared to bulk feed water. Hence, in order to retain the same flow, a greater feed pressure is needed (capacity).

- 2- Greater salt content at the membrane surface increases salt transport. Hence, there is less salt rejection (higher salt passage) greater C_p .
- 3- The probability of precipitation (scaling) will rise due to greater concentrations of salts with limited solubility (such as calcium carbonate and calcium sulphate) near the membrane surface.
- 4- A decrease in the membrane's ability to transfer water.
- 5- A higher rate of fouling because to the deposition of organic polymers at the membrane surface and suspended and colloidal particles.

Figure 3.18 shows the effect of increasing feed water concentration on the amount of the average concentration polarization C_{mavg} that has accumulated on membrane surfaces (it was taken Average Feed Flow $Q_{favg} = 10.15 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, Average Feed Water Temperature $T_{avg} = 24^\circ \text{ C}$). The C_{mavg} value rise from 1464.4 mg/l to 13494.24 mg/l when feed water concentration rise from 1063 mg/l to 9948 mg/l.

It was taken into consideration that the change in the values of polarization concentration C_m is very slight and is hardly noticeable when the values of feed water concentration C_f are constant despite the change in the temperature of the feed water and the feed flow rate.

Fig. 3.18 Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Average Concentration polarization C_m mg/l (Average Feed Flow $Q_f \text{ avg} = 10.15 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, Average Feed Water Temperature $T_{avg} = 24^\circ \text{ C}$)

3.9.9 Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Salt rejection R% & Feed Pressure

The requisite feed pressure and salt rejection percentage (R%) for the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant's effective operation are directly influenced by the feed concentration of the brackish water. Salt rejection rates are often lower at higher feed concentrations. This is because a greater concentration of feed causes a concentration polarization effect that lowers the membrane's ability to reject salt. The feed concentration needs to be properly managed and optimized in order to get around this problem. The Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant can guarantee the effectiveness of the reverse osmosis process and get a greater salt rejection percentage by keeping the feed concentration at a suitable level.

The feed water concentration effect on salt rejection R% and feed pressure P_f is clearly shown in Figure (3.19 a-e) and (3.20 a-e) respectively. Two types of risk can be distinguished, the first is related to the effect of increasing the feed concentration, which adversely affects the salt rejection values and directly on the feed pressure that must be applied to overcome the osmotic pressure π of feed water resulting from high concentration of that water. The second effect is related to the increase in the recovery of the system, where it is noted that the values of the two variables (salt rejection and feed pressure) increase from those of recovery less until they reach the maximum value at the recovery r of 60%.

The effect of feed water concentration on salt rejection can be summarized as follows:

A- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: Salt rejection R% decreased from 97.3% to 95.1%.

B- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: Salt rejection R% decreased from 94.1% to 90.5%.

C- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13)^\circ \text{C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: Salt rejection $R\%$ decreased from 98.4% to 95.8%.

D- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39)^\circ \text{C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: Salt rejection $R\%$ decreased from 95.9% to 93.5%.

Fig. (3.19 a-e) Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Salt rejection $R\%$

Fig. (3.20 a-e) Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Feed Pressure P_f

Salt rejection efficiency in RO membranes declines with increasing feed water concentration, and this effect is amplified at higher temperatures. Although increasing the feed flow rate can help mitigate concentration polarization to some

extent, it cannot fully counteract the decline in membrane performance caused by high salinity and thermal effects. These findings emphasize the need to carefully manage feed water quality and operational conditions to sustain high rejection rates and ensure product water quality.

On the other hand, the feed water pressure P_f increases as follows:

A- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: feed pressure P_f increased from 15.9 bar to 22.5 bar.

B- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: feed pressure P_f increased from 13.0 bar to 19.8 bar.

C- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: feed pressure P_f increased from 20.6 bar to 27.3 bar.

D- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39)^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: feed pressure P_f increased from 15.0 bar to 22.0 bar.

The feed pressure (P_f) required in an RO system increases significantly with rising feed water salinity, primarily due to the elevated osmotic pressure. This effect is more pronounced at lower temperatures and higher flow rates, where additional hydraulic resistance further raises pressure requirements. Therefore, system design and operation must account for salinity-dependent pressure adjustments, especially in applications dealing with high total dissolved solids (TDS) and variable temperature conditions.

3.9.10 Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Mass Flux of Solute J_s , $\text{mg}/\text{m}^2.\text{h}$

In the Garmatt-Ali Reverse Osmosis Desalination Plant, the mass flux of solute J_s is directly impacted by the feed concentration of the feed water C_f . Since there are more solute particles in the feed water at greater feed concentrations, the mass flux of the solute increases as well. As a result, the freshwater generated may

be of lower quality and the brine may be less concentrated. Carefully monitoring and controlling the feed concentration is necessary to assure the production of high-quality freshwater and optimize the desalination process.

As stated before in the Equation (2.11), it is known that the mass flow of the solute J_s is in terms of the permeate concentration C_p , with the value of the J_w confirmed. It is clear that a change in the value of C_f causes a direct change in the value of C_p . Thus, the C_f will have a direct impact on the J_s . J_s is therefore exactly proportional to C_f . The amount of salts that penetrate the membranes as mass flux of solute can be observed in Figure 3.21 as follows:

A- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: mass flux of solute J_s increased from $273.0 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$ to $4317.9 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$.

B- Feed flow $Q_f = (7.0-7.2) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: mass flux of solute J_s increased from $1087.6 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$ to $13766.0 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$.

C- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (10-13) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: mass flux of solute J_s increased from $209.1 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$ to $4942.8 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$.

D- Feed flow $Q_f = (13.0-13.3) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $T = (38-39) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Feed concentration $C_f = (1063-9948) \text{ mg/l}$: mass flux of solute J_s increased from $873.9 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$ to $11092.7 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$.

These findings suggest that in high-salinity or high-temperature feed conditions, membrane selectivity may be compromised, leading to increased salt passage and potential degradation of permeate quality. Therefore, operational adjustments and careful monitoring are essential in maintaining effective separation performance.

Fig. (3.21 a-e) Effect of Feed Concentration C_f on Mass Flux of Solute J_s $\text{mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{h}$

3.9.11 Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Recovery $r\%$

As shown in figure (3.22 a-e), when:

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 11^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Recovery $r\%$ decreased from 30.7% to 21.6%.

- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 12^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Recovery $r\%$ decreased from 27.5% to 20.3%.
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 38^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Recovery $r\%$ decreased from 54.7% to 34.2%.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 38^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.0) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Recovery $r\%$ decreased from 45.2% to 29.6%.

Increasing the feed flow rate (Q_f) in an RO system reduces the recovery percentage ($r\%$) across different salinity and temperature conditions. Although higher flow may help reduce concentration polarization and membrane fouling, the net effect is reduced permeate production due to insufficient water–membrane contact time. This emphasizes the importance of balancing flow rate with operational targets for recovery and membrane performance. System designers must carefully optimize flow rates based on feed characteristics and desired recovery levels to ensure energy-efficient and cost-effective operation.

3.9.12 Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Water Flux J_w

As shown in figure (3.23 a-e), when:

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 11^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Water flux J_w increased from 0.0098 m/h to 0.0127 m/h.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 12^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Water flux J_w increased from 0.0089 m/h to 0.0120 m/h.
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 38^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Water flux J_w increased from 0.0175 m/h to 0.0202 m/h.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 38^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.0) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Water flux J_w increased from 0.0146 m/h to 0.0173 m/h.

The results confirm that increasing feed flow rate (Q_f) leads to a measurable increase in water flux (J_w) across a range of salinities and temperatures. This improvement is attributed to better hydrodynamic conditions that reduce concentration polarization and enhance mass transfer near the membrane surface. The effect is especially pronounced at elevated temperatures, where membrane permeability and water mobility are higher. However, this must be balanced against potential energy costs and decreased recovery, as observed in prior analyses.

Fig. (3.22 a-e) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Recovery $r\%$

Fig. (3.23 a-e) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Water Flux J_w m/h

3.9.13 Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Mass Flux of Solute J_s

As shown in figure (3.24 a-e), when:

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 11^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h: Mass flux of solute J_s decreased from 150.0 mg/m².h to 116.4 mg/m².h.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 12^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.1)$ m³/h: Mass flux of solute J_s decreased from 1883.7 mg/m².h to 1481.4 mg/m².h.
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 38^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h: Mass flux of solute J_s decreased from 879.0 mg/m².h to 584.7 mg/m².h.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 38^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.0)$ m³/h: Mass flux of solute J_s decreased from 10445.0 mg/m².h to 7023.1 mg/m².h.

This improvement is due to enhanced hydrodynamic conditions, which reduce the concentration polarization effect and lower the solute concentration at the membrane surface. Consequently, higher Q_f not only improves water purity but also helps control solute leakage, especially in high-salinity and high-temperature conditions.

3.9.14 Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Feed Water Pressure P_f

As shown in figure (3.25 a-e), when:

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 11^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h: Feed water pressure P_f increased from 15.9 bar to 20.6 bar.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 12^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.1)$ m³/h: Feed water pressure P_f increased from 22.5 bar to 27.3 bar.

C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 38^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Feed water pressure P_f increased from 13.0 bar to 15.0 bar.

D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948 \text{ mg/l}$, $T = 38^\circ \text{ C}$, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.0) \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$: Feed water pressure P_f increased from 19.8 bar to 22.0 bar.

Fig. (3.24 a-f) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on mass flux of solute J_s mg/m².h

Fig. (3.25 a-e) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Feed Pressure P_f bar

Increasing the feed flow rate (Q_f) results in higher feed water pressure (P_f) due to elevated hydraulic resistance, increased turbulence, and the need to overcome both system and membrane-related pressure losses. This trend is more significant at lower temperatures and higher salinities, where water requires more force to pass through the membrane due to higher viscosity and osmotic pressure. Understanding this relationship is crucial for optimizing energy efficiency and membrane performance in RO desalination systems.

3.9.15 Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Permeate Concentration C_p and Salt Rejection $R\%$

As shown in figures (3.26 a-e) and (3.27 a-e), when:

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 11^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h:
 - A.1- Permeate concentration C_p decreased from 27.8 mg/l to 16.4 mg/l.
 - A.2- Salt rejection $R\%$ increased from 97.3% to 98.4%.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 12^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.1)$ m³/h:
 - B.1- Permeate concentration C_p decreased from 483.0 mg/l to 410.9 mg/l.
 - B.2- Salt rejection $R\%$ increased from 95.1% to 95.8%.
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 38^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h:
 - C.1- Permeate concentration C_p decreased from 62.1 mg/l to 73.2 mg/l.
 - C.2- Salt rejection $R\%$ increased from 94.1% to 95.9%.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 38^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.0)$ m³/h:
 - D.1- Permeate concentration C_p decreased from 937.8 mg/l to 638.3 mg/l.
 - D.2- Salt rejection $R\%$ increased from 90.5% to 93.5%.

Fig. (3.26 a-e) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Permeate Concentration mg/l

Fig. (3.27 a-f) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Salt Rejection R%

An increase in feed flow rate leads to lower permeate salinity (C_p) and higher salt rejection ($R\%$), due to reduced concentration polarization and enhanced mass transfer at the membrane surface. This effect holds across different feed concentrations and temperatures, although the magnitude of improvement may vary depending on fluid properties and membrane characteristics. These findings highlight the importance of optimizing Q_f to improve RO system performance.

3.9.16 Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Concentration Polarization Factor β

As shown in Figure (3.28 a-e), when:

- A- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 11^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h: Concentration polarization β decreased from 1.125 to 1.116.
- B- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 12^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.1)$ m³/h: Concentration polarization β decreased from 1.111 to 1.108
- C- Feed concentration $C_f = 1063$ mg/l, $T = 38^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.1-13.1)$ m³/h: Concentration polarization β decreased from 1.227 to 1.177.
- D- Feed concentration $C_f = 9948$ mg/l, $T = 38^\circ$ C, Feed flow $Q_f = (7.2-13.0)$ m³/h: Concentration polarization β decreased from 1.179 to 1.149.

The concentration polarization factor β decreases with increasing feed flow rate, regardless of feed concentration or temperature. This is due to the improved hydrodynamic conditions and enhanced back-diffusion of solutes from the membrane surface. Reducing β is critical for maintaining membrane performance, preventing fouling, and achieving higher salt rejection.

3.10 Results and Discussion of Long-Term Operation of GARO1 and GARO2

Regarding the long-term operation of the desalination plants in Garmatt-Ali, the main focus is on monitoring the GARO1 and GARO2 plants' performance during the six-month study period, which runs from January 1 to June 30, 2022. Semi-daily checks are carried out at a minimum of five days a week.

The Sampling process was conducted from 5 different points from the two plants, as mentioned previously. Tests include TDS, temperature, pH, feed pressure, turbidity, and SDI.

The results mentioned in the tables (Appendix) can be divided into two parts. The first one is the results of a field operation that was measured at the moment where the samples were taken using the devices mentioned previously.

In order to finish tests, samples are occasionally brought in from the field to the sanitary engineering lab. The computational findings of the mathematical and physical relationships between the variables (parameters) were the second set of results.

3.10.1 Turbidity

As mentioned in the previous paragraph 3.4.2, water turbidity is considered one of the most important elements that must be taken into consideration when designing and operating desalination plants. Water with a turbidity of more than 1 NTU leads to the consumption of RO membranes in a short period of time, as it causes fouling and clogging of the membranes. Therefore, it is necessary to apply a sand filter and cotton filter as a preliminary treatment for the feed water before it reaches the membranes.

Fig. (3.28 a-e) Effect of Feed Flow Rate Q_f on Recovery $r\%$

The highest value was registered for the pre -sand and carbon filters at 18.82 NTU on April 19. The lowest value for Turbidity was on January 24, at a value of 3.98 NTU. From the Figure 3.29, it was noticed that the value of the recess that decreases and rises randomly, there is no direct relationship between it and the temperature of the nutrition water.

Fig. 3.29 Comparison between Turbidity of Water before and after Filters

3.10.2 Feed Water Concentration C_f

- a- From Figure 3.30 it was noted that the value of the C_{f1} for GARO1 starts from 3222 mg/l as the highest value at the beginning of the study period. Then the slope gradually foretold until it reaches 922 mg/l at the end of March. The beginning of the search period is considered the most focused and the value of the concentrations begins to decrease significantly due to the high levels of seasonal rain and water breakthroughs for the dams of neighboring countries (Turkey and Iran). This effect reaches at the beginning of February, which plays a major role in reducing salt concentrations in the Shatt Al-Arab River and pushing the salt wedge border toward Gulf. The concentration of feed water decreases below 1200 mg/l over several different periods, starting from the last third of January to mid-February. After that, the value of the C_{f1} stabilizes between the 1200-1650 mg/l until the middle of March, which the nutrition water concentrations decrease to the minimum limits of 922 mg/l. Then it begins to decrease until the beginning of June, where the salt concentrations begin to rise, announcing the beginning of the dry season.

- b- Since the brine water for the first stage is delivered via pipes to the GARO2, the value of the C_{f2} for GARO2 is the same as the cerebral water concentration C_{c1} of GARO1, as was mentioned in the station description in paragraph 3.3. Given that their values are directly correlated with C_{f1} , the pattern of high C_{f2} concentrations is undoubtedly comparable to that of C_{f1} . The highest value for C_{f2} (C_{c1}) is 6287.51 mg/l and the lowest value is 1799.11 mg/l.

3.10.3 Permeate Water Concentration C_p

- a- For the same reasons in the previous paragraph, the value of the permeate water concentration C_{p1} of GARO1 ranges between 10.86-73.89 mg/l.
- b- As for the value of the permeate water concentration C_{p2} of GARO2, it starts from 33.08 mg/l to 177.34 mg/l (see figure 3.31).

Fig. 3.30 Comparison between Feed Water Concentration C_f of 1st and 2nd Stage

Fig. 3.31 Comparison between Permeate Water Concentration C_p of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.4 Brine Water Concentration C_c

- a- The GARO1 brine concentration C_{C1} values are the same as the Feed Water Concentration C_{F2} for GARO2 and mentioned in paragraph (3.10.2 b).
- b- From the Figure 3.32, the highest value of brine water concentration C_{c2} reaches 9137.0 mg/l. The lowest value was recorded on February 9 and amounted to 2510.46 mg/l.

Fig. 3.32 Comparison between Brine Water Concentration C_c of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.5 Water Temperature T

The water temperature T has a definite relationship with the atmosphere, so it has its lowest value in the winter and its highest value in the summer. However, the water temperature in general is lower than the atmosphere due to the physical properties of water. The water temperature in GARO1 is not significantly different from that in GARO2 ($\pm 1^\circ \text{C}$). The lowest water temperature was recorded at January 15 in GARO1 and GARO2, which were 11°C and 12°C , respectively.

The highest temperature recorded for both stages was the same value, which was 34°C at the end of the study period as shown in Figure 3.33.

Fig. 3.33 Comparison between Water Temperature T of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.6 Feed-Concentrate Water Osmotic pressure $\pi_{fc, avg}$

The average feed-concentrate water osmosis pressure $\pi_{fc, avg}$ (Figure 3.34) appeared as following:

- It is known that the value of osmotic pressure is directly proportional to the concentration of dissolved salts, whether C_f or C_c , so the pattern of rise and fall of the value of $\pi_{fc, avg}$ is completely similar to the concentration values that were previously stated in paragraphs 3.10.2 and 3.10.3. The highest and lowest values of $\pi_{fc, avg1}$ were 3.84 bar and 1.16 bar, respectively.
- In the same way, the highest and lowest values of $\pi_{fc, avg2}$ were 6.25 bar and 1.83 bar, respectively.

Fig. 3.34 Comparison between Average Feed-Concentrate Osmotic Pressure $\pi_{fc, avg}$ of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.7 Net Driving Pressure NDP and Feed Pressure Pf

Changes in permeate and feed pressures, feed channel head losses, and osmotic pressure are all taken into consideration by the net driving pressure. As permeate passes through the membrane in spiral wound membrane elements, the applied pressure drops and the osmotic pressure steadily rises throughout the feed-concentrate channel's length. Consequently average conditions must be considered by the net driving pressure as shown in equation 2.5.

- a- The values of Pf and NDP in GARO1 ranged between 36.78-52.57 bar and 34.00-48.45 bar, respectively.
- b- As for GARO2, the lowest value of Pf was 14.31 bars on June 26. That is, almost at the end of the practical study period. The highest value was obtained on January 2, which amounted to 20.45 bars. It is clear that temperature affects feed water pressure inversely. During the winter, when water temperatures were at their lowest levels, the pressure increased significantly in order to overcome viscosity of water, which rises with decreasing temperature. The opposite is true when the temperature rises. The NDP values ranged between 9.99-16.03 bar, with the same pattern and timing as the Pf. (See Figures 3.35 and 3.36).

Fig. 3.35 Comparison between Feed Pressure Pf of 1st and 2nd Stage

Fig. 3.36 Comparison between Net Driving Pressure NDP of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.8 Concentration Polarization Mass Transfer Coefficient K_{cp} and Schmidt Number Sc

Two factors primarily determine the values of the Concentration Polarization Mass Transfer Coefficient K_{cp} and Schmidt Number Sc , whose equations were discussed in the chapter two (Equation 2.13 and 2.15, respectively). The initial segment consists of the flowing fluid's characteristics, including its density, viscosity, and flow rate. Regarding the latter, it is contingent upon the dimensions, composition, and mode of transportation of the fluid (i.e., the kind of membrane employed in the desalination procedure). It is certain that the change in the values of the variables K_{cp} and Sc is caused by a change in the fluid's characteristics because the kind of membrane remained constant over the course of the investigation.

- a- Because the water temperature rarely varies by more than one degree Celsius, the Sc values for the two stations are nearly comparable. For GAR01 and GAR02, the Sc values varied from 551.29 to 942.59 and from 551.29 to 916.01, respectively (Figure 3.37).

Fig. 3.37 Comparison between Schmidt Number Sc of 1st and 2nd Stage

b- Despite the fact that the two stations' Kcp values differ, the Reynolds numbers in each case vary because of variations in the feed channel's flow velocity. In GARO1, their value varies from 3.71×10^{-5} to 3.88×10^{-5} m/s. In GARO2, 2.47×10^{-5} m/s is the lowest value while 2.63×10^{-5} m/s is the highest (Figure 3.38).

Fig. 3.38 Comparison between Concentration Polarization Transition Coefficient Kcp of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.9 Water Flux J_w, Solute Flux J_s, and Recovery r%

Fouling and membrane aging cause a deterioration in membrane performance (water flux drops, solute flux increases). On the other hand, variations in input water temperature, pressure, velocity, and concentration also affect the fluxes of solute and water [19]. Permeate water flow rate and salt

passage p% must be evaluated under regular operating circumstances in order to assess the actual loss in system performance brought on by fouling and aging. Plant performance was measured and assessed during the practical study period using equations 2.3 and 2.11.

As a result, it is evident that temperature has an impact on J_{wm} , J_{sm} , and $r\%$. This impact can be summed up as follows (Figures 3.39, 3.40, and 3.41):

1- GARO1

- a- On January 22, when the feed water is 13°C , J_{sm} has the lowest value of $0.336 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$, and on June 25, when the temperature is 32°C , it has the maximum value of $2.549 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$.
- b- On January 15, when the temperature was 11°C , the lowest values of J_{wm} and $r\%$ were $0.0286 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{h}$ and 33.45% , respectively. On June 30, at 34°C , the highest J_{wm} and $r\%$ recorded were $0.0472 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{h}$ and 55.20% , respectively.

2- GARO2

- a- The feed water temperature reached its highest recorded value of 33°C on June 25, corresponding to the maximum measured solute mass flux (J_{sm}) of $2.494 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$. In contrast, the lowest J_{sm} value of $0.364 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$ was observed at a temperature of 13°C on January 22.
- b- On June 2, at a feed water temperature of 30°C , the highest recorded water flux (J_{wm}) and recovery rate ($r\%$) were $0.0160 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$ and 44.54% , respectively. Conversely, the lowest values of J_{wm} and $r\%$ $0.0096 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$ and 26.74% , respectively—were observed on January 2 at a temperature of 12°C .

Because of the rise in production, the recovery and flux increases in both stations are seen favorably. This indicates that both stations' performances have

improved. However, this enhancement is accompanied with a rise in the solute flow that passes through the membranes of the station, increasing the proportion of salts in the permeate water. This indicates that, as will be discussed in the paragraphs that follow, the two stations' efficiency declines in this regard.

Fig. 3.39 Comparison between Mass Flux of Solute J_s mg/m².h of 1st and 2nd Stage

Fig. 3.40 Comparison between Recovery r% of 1st and 2nd Stage

Fig. 3.41 Comparison between Water Flux J_w m of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.10 Concentration Polarization Factor β

The concentration polarization factor is the ratio of the concentration of dissolved materials close to the membrane walls (the concentration polarization C_m) to the rate of water concentration in the feed channel in the desalination membrane units (the concentration of feed-concentrate water $C_{fc, avg}$). β is bigger than one since the value of C_m is always greater than the value of $C_{fc, avg}$. The concentration polarization transition coefficient K_{cp} and the water flux $J_w m$ can be used to derive the value of C_m from the exponential relationship represented in the equation (2.12) from chapter two. As mentioned in paragraphs 3.10.8 and 3.10.9, the increase in feed water temperature rates during the research period led to an increase in both the $J_w m$ and K_{cp} values. As a result, depending on the value of the exponential, the value of β generally increases with increasing temperature; so, there is fluctuation in the values of β during the research period.

As seen in the Figure 3.42, the values of β typically rise as the temperature of feed water rises from the beginning of January to the end of June. Thus, the following will be the values of β :

- a- In GARO1, the highest value of β was calculated as 1.41 on June 30 and its lowest value 1.23 was calculated on January 15.

- b- Conversely, on June 2, the highest value of β was reported at 1.19, while on January 2, the lowest value was 1.11.

Fig. 3.42 Comparison between Concentration Polarization β Factor of 1st and 2nd Stage

3.10.11 Concentration Polarization C_m

Equation 2.12 shows that, with $C_{fc, avg}$ constant, C_m is linearly proportional to β . It follows that the C_m values should logically follow the same pattern as the β values; but, in practice, this is not the case because the feed water concentrations cause the $C_{fc, avg}$ value to fluctuate continuously. For GARO1 and GARO2, the difference between the greatest and lowest value did not exceed 0.18 and 0.08 units, respectively. Therefore, the value of C_m is controlled by the variable $C_{fc, avg}$ (see Figure 3.43 A and B, which show the patterns of $C_{fc, avg}$, C_m , and β combined).

- a- In GARO1, C_m 's maximum value was determined to be 6059.87 mg/l, while its lowest value was determined to be 1762.67 mg/l.
- b- On the other hand, C_m was found to have a maximum value of 8587.05 mg/l and a minimum value of 2509.96 mg/l.

Fig. 3.43 The patterns of C_{fc} , avg, C_m , and β of A) GARO,1 and B) GARO2

3.10.12 Salt Rejection R%

The proportion of salts removed from the feed water is one of the major determinants of the overall efficiency of the desalination plant and the performance of the membranes in particular. Under typical settings, new membranes must have a salt rejection R% of at least 99%. However, as a result of shifting operational parameters like pH, feed water temperature, and station operating pressure, etc. The basic equation that was used to determine the value of R% was mentioned in this chapter under paragraph 3.10.5 as well as in all sources that were specifically focused on this field of research. The two

desalination plants' performance can be tracked using the salt rejection percentage (R%) shown in Figure 3.44 as the following:

- 1- In GARO1 and GARO2, the greatest R% values were 98.9% and 98.3%, respectively. The feed water in the two desalination facilities was measured to be 13°C on the same day, January 22.
- 2- When the feed water temperature was 30°C on June 12, the lowest R% value of 96.8% was recorded for GARO1. On June 30, the water temperature was recorded at 34°C, and the lowest reading in GARO2 was 95.5%.

Fig. 3.44 Comparison between the Effect of Temperature on Salt Rejection R% of 1st and 2nd Stage

The GARO2 plant demonstrated robust and adaptable performance over time, with effective handling of variable feed water conditions. While high salinity and turbidity periods required increased operating pressures, the membrane system maintained strong rejection efficiency and reasonable recovery rates. Seasonal adjustments to operating parameters—particularly in response to feed water quality and temperature—proved essential to sustaining long-term operational stability.

3.11 Summary

3.11.1 Operation Conditions

1- Effect of temperature: Temperature is considered one of the most influential operating conditions on the desalination system, as it directly and indirectly affects all other variables because it affects the properties of the fluid (density and viscosity) and the fluid's surroundings. These two reasons are sufficient to change the results of other variables. For example, but not limited to, increasing the temperature from (11-38) °C, fixing the feed water concentration (1063 mg/l), and fixing the discharge between (7.0-7.2) m³/h leads to following:

- a- Increase the permeate concentration from 27.8 mg/l to 62.1 mg/l.
- b- Decrease in salt rejection from 97.3% to 94.1%.
- c- Increase the concentration polarization factor from 1.125 to 1.227.
- d- Increased concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient from $2.31 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m/s to $2.37 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m/s.
- e- Increased mass flux of solute from (273.0-1087.6) mg/m².h.
- f- Decrease in feed pressure from 15.9 bar to 13.0 bar.
- g- Decrease in net driving pressure from 14.8 bar to 11.9 bar.
- h- Increase the permeate water osmotic pressure π from (0.022 - 0.054) bar.
- i- Increase water flux from (0.009 - 0.017) m/h.
- j- Increase permeate flow rate from 2.180 m³/h to 3.888 m³/h.
- k- Increase the recovery from 30.7% to 54.7%.

2- Feed water concentration effect: Increasing concentration of dissolved materials in the water source is considered one of the factors that negatively affect to desalination plants in general. It is possible for the water in the water source to turn from brackish water to seawater once the concentration increases and breaks the barrier of 10,000 mg/l as a TDS. This condition occurs almost annually in the

water of the Shatt Al-Arab River, especially in the dry season (summer season). The rivers suffer from a significant decrease in the water level due to the absence or scarcity of rain and a decrease in the level of water releases by the upstream countries (Turkey and Iran), which leads to the extension of the salt wedge to the areas of central and northern Basrah. Increasing the feed water concentration from 1063 mg/l to 9948 mg/l leads to:

- a- Increase in feed-concentrate water osmotic pressure from 1,037 bar to 9,720 bar.
- b- Increase in permeate water osmotic pressure from 0.022 bar to 0.391 bar.
- c- An increase in concentration polarization from 1443.3 mg/l to 13308.7 mg/l.
- d- Decrease in salt rejection from 97.3% to 95.1%.
- e- Increase in feed water pressure from 15.9 bar to 22.5 bar.
- f- An increase in mass flux of solute from 273.0 mg/m².h to 4317.9 mg/m².h.

3- Feed flow rate effect:

The amount of feed flow rate can be controlled through valves connected to the piping system of the treatment plant. The amount of increase in the discharge value of the feed flow rate is determined by several factors and determinants, the most prominent of which is the type of pump and membranes used. The type of membrane determines the minimum amount of drainage that can pass through it without problems in production and the force of pushing water through the membrane. The pump determines the largest amount of discharge that can be pumped as feed flow, according to the characteristics of that pump. Therefore, increasing the pumping amount from 7.1 m³/h to 13.1 m³/h and keeping the feed water concentration at 1063 mg/l and temperature 11 C leads to:

- a- Decrease in recovery from 30.7% to 21.6%

- b- Increase the water flux from (0.0098 - 0.0127) m/h.
- c- Decrease in mass flux of solute from (150.0 - 116.4) mg/m².h.
- d- Increase feed water pressure from 15.9 bar to 20.6 bar.
- e- A decrease in permeate concentration from 27.8 mg/l to 16.4 mg/l.
- f- Increase in salt rejection from 97.3% to 98.4%.
- g- Decrease in concentration polarization factor from 1.125 to 1.116.

3.11.2 Long-Term Operation of Desalination Plant

The study period extended from 1 January 2022 to the end of June of the same year (6 months). During this period, the station's performance was monitored, and its results were as shown in Table 3.7 (the feed flow rate is fixed for each operation throughout the study period, which is 8 m³/h).

Table 3.4. Summary of long-term operating results of GARO2 plant.

Details	Minimum Results		Maximum Results	
	Amount	Date	Amount	Date
Turbidity (NTU)	3.98	24-Jan	18.82	19-Apr
Cf (mg/l)	1799.1	25-May	6287.5	2-Jan
Cp (mg/l)	33.08	22-Jan	177.34	25-Jun
Cc (mg/l)	2510.4	9-Feb	9137.0	2-Jan
T (°C)	12	15-Jan	34	30-Jun
π_{f-c} avg (bar)	1.83	9-Feb	6.25	2-Jan
Pf (bar)	14.31	26-Jun	20.45	2-Jan
NDP (bar)	9.99	26-Jun	16.03	3-Feb
Kcp (m/s)	2.47*10 ⁻⁵	22-Jan	2.63*10 ⁻⁵	26-Jun
Sc	551.29	30-Jun	916.01	2-Jan
Js m (mg/m ² .h)	0.364	22-Jan	2.494	25-Jun
Jw m (m/s)	0.0096	2-Jan	0.0160	2-Jun
r%	26.7	2-Jan	44.5	2-Jun
β	1.11	2-Jan	1.23	2-Jun
Cm (mg/l)	2509.96	9-Feb	8587.06	2-Jan
R%	95.5	12-Jun	98.3	22-Jan

CHAPTER

4

Modeling and Optimization

Chapter Four

Modeling and Optimization

4.1 General

To develop sustainable and effective RO desalination plants, research is being conducted on the modeling and optimization of RO desalination systems. Various tools and techniques including MATLAB, Gene Expression Programming (GEP), and Winflows programming techniques, have been used to develop mathematical models of mass and heat transmission, salt rejection, and membrane solute permeability.

In this chapter, two methodologies were taken to develop and analyze mathematical models for desalination processes as an objective function to reach the best operation conditions that provide optimal processes for producing water in greater quantity and better quality.

4.2 First Methodology: Modeling and Simulation

4.2.1 Winflows 4.04 software

The Winflows 4.04 programming software and its use for RO desalination are introduced in this chapter. It gives the reader an overview of fundamental modeling ideas and demonstrates how easy it is to simulate specific process units using a graphical interface close to a flow sheet. For the purpose of the simulation process, the mathematical models that were previously mentioned in Chapter 2 (paragraph 2.3) can be used.

Utilizing Winflows version 4.04, a water technologies and solutions tool produced by the SUEZ group, was the primary instrument for analyzing and

modeling the RO plant's performance. Furthermore, the primary functions of the Microsoft Excel Worksheet were graph analysis and generation.

A quick and efficient way to create designs for desalination systems is with Winflows 4.04. It is expected that the user is familiar with the fundamentals of RO system design and is aware of the system under consideration's necessary performance [100, 101].

For the purpose of knowing more details about Winflows 4.04 programming tools and details, they will be mentioned in Appendix II.

Establishing an integrated water desalination system in this software is possible by utilizing the following additional qualities and capabilities:

- Chemical dosing – feed and product.
- Tool for antiscalant used to choose an argon analyzer.
- Product and feed Gas stripping.
- Filters of cartridge.
- Electro-deionization for permeate flow (EDI).
- Pelton wheels, turbochargers, and work and pressure exchangers are examples of energy recovery devices.
- Split permeate option ;Mixing different feed water compositions; Feed bypass and concentrate recycling options.

The work methodology in this program requires entering all data related to the desalination plant, including the type of membranes used, the type and specifications of pumps, feed flow rate, temperature, feed water concentration, and other input data to obtain results of the quantity and quality of water produced (permeate flow rate and permeate water concentration, respectively) as output

data. The simulation results for the Long-Term Operation of the GARO2 desalination plant can be found in Table AI.6.

In this paragraph, the difference in the results obtained from Winflows 4.04 programming will be explained and compared with the experimental one, under the name *Deviation Percentage %* (% Dev.) as shown in Table AI.7.

4.2.1.1 Permeate Flow Rate Q_p

As shown in Figure 4.1, the permeate flow rate Q_p were as follows (after applying Winflows 4.04 programming on GARO2):

- a- The maximum value was $3.350 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ in 2-June-2022, while its lowest value was determined $2.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ in 2-Jan-2022.
- b- On the other hand, the maximum absolute deviation percentage was 8.13 % in 18-June-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 3.23 % in 3-Jan-2022.

In Table AI.6, it is noted that the value of some deviation percentage been negative, which would mean that the values of Winflows programming results larger than of that of experimental values, therefore it was taken the absolute values to find maximum and minimum of deviation.

4.2.1.2 Water Flux J_w m

In Figure 4.2, the water flux J_w m was as follows (after applying Winflows 4.04 programming on GARO2):

- a- The maximum value was $0.0151 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2.\text{h}$ in 2-June-2022, while its lowest value was determined $0.0092 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2.\text{h}$ in 2-Jan-2022.

- b- On the other hand, the maximum absolute deviation percentage was 8.13 % in 18-June-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 3.23 % in 3-Jan-2022.

Fig. 4.1 Comparison the permeate flow rate between Experimental and Winflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

In Figure 4.1, the experimental data consistently exceeds the simulation values, especially in the later stages (> day 100). The average deviation remains mostly between 4% and 7%, indicating a systematic bias or unaccounted physical factors (e.g., membrane fouling, operating pressure fluctuations, not typical hydrodynamics). The closer trend line slopes between theory and experiment (0.0046 vs. 0.005) suggest that Winflows captures the general growth trend well, but not all variability. The higher R^2 in experimental data (0.7546) compared to Winflows (0.7392) indicates a better linear trend in actual measurements, likely due to controlled conditions or sensor calibration.

The systematic under prediction by Winflows in both J_w and Q_p (Figure 4.2) suggests potential causes such as:

- Model limitations in representing real operational variabilities (pressure, temperature, fouling dynamics).
- Experimental calibration drift or data smoothing that may slightly increase output readings.
- Unaccounted phenomena in simulations (e.g., variable recovery rate, chemical dosing effects, or operational overrides).

Fig. 4.2 Comparison the water flux between the experimental and Winflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

4.2.1.3 Mass Flux of Solute J_s

In Figure 4.3, the mass flux of solute J_s was as follows (after applying Winflows 4.04 programming on GARO2):

- The maximum value was 2.333 mg/m².h in 25-June-2022, while its lowest value was determined 0.367 mg/m².h in 22-Jan-2022.
- On the other hand, the maximum absolute deviation percentage was 27.33 % in 17-March-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 0.08 % in 7-Feb-2022.

Fig. 4.3 Comparison the mass flux of solute between the experimental and Wnflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

4.2.1.4 Feed Pressure P_f and Net Driving Pressure NDP

In Figures 4.4 and 4.5, the feed pressure P_f and net driving pressure NDP respectively were as follows (after applying Winflows 4.04 programming on GARO2):

- a- The maximum value of P_f was 19.69 bar in 2-Jan-2022, while its lowest value was 13.55 bar in 26-June-2022.
- b- On the other hand, the maximum absolute deviation percentage of P_f was 5.31 % in 26-June-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 3.7 % in 2-Jan-2022.
- c- For NDP, the largest value was 15.34 bar in 3-Feb-2022, while it's the smallest value found was 9.45 bar in 26-June-2022.
- d- In 18-June-2022, 8.13 % the maximum absolute deviation percentage was spotted. Its absolute minimum value was determined 3.23 % in 3-Jan-2022.

Fig. 4.4 Comparison the Feed Pressure P_f between the experimental and Winflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

In Figure 4.4, the fact that both simulated and experimental results decline at the same rate over time is notable, and supports the validity of Winflows in trend projection.

Fig. 4.5 Comparison the Net Driving Pressure NDP between the experimental and Winflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

4.2.1.5 Permeate C_p and Brine C_c Water Concentration

Figures 4.6 and 4.7 show the difference in the results values for C_p and C_c in the desalination plant GARO2 between experimental work and the simulation output by winflows 4.04 programming, as shown as follows:

- a- The maximum value of C_p was 179.67 mg/l in 25-June-2022, while its lowest value was 35.17 mg/l in 22-Jan-2022.
- b- The maximum absolute deviation percentage of C_p was 23.3 % in 17-March-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 3.7 % in 29-Jan-2022.
- c- For C_c , the largest value was 8867.0 mg/l in 2-Jan-2022, while it's the smallest value found was 2549.7 mg/l in 25-May-2022.
- d- In 4-June-2022, 20.28 % the maximum absolute deviation percentage of C_c was spotted. Its absolute minimum value was determined 0.36 % in 30-Jan-2022.

Fig. 4.6 Comparison the Permeate Water Concentration C_p between the experimental and Wnflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

Fig. 4.7 Comparison the Brine Water Concentration C_c between the experimental and Wnflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

4.2.1.6 Concentration Polarization Mass Transfer Coefficient K_{cp}

The difference in the results values for K_{cp} in the desalination plant GARO2 between experimental work and the simulation output by winflows 4.04 programming were showed in Figure 4.8:

- The maximum value of K_{cp} was 2.65×10^{-5} in 26-June-2022, while its lowest value was 2.48×10^{-5} in 23-Jan-2022.
- The maximum absolute deviation percentage of K_{cp} was 1.0 % in 4-June-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 0.26 % in 3-Jan-2022.

4.2.1.7 Concentration Polarization Factor β

In Figure 4.9, the Concentration Polarization Factor β was as follows (after applying Winflows 4.04 programming on GARO2):

- The maximum value was 1.177 in 2-June-2022, while its lowest value was determined 1.107 in 2-Jan-2022.
- On the other hand, the maximum absolute deviation percentage was 1.38 % in 4-June-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 0.39 % in 3-Jan-2022.

Fig. 4.8 Comparison the Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} between the experimental and Wnflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

Fig. 4.9 Comparison the Concentration polarization Factor β between the experimental and Winflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them

4.2.1.8 Concentration Polarization C_m

In Figure 4.10, the Concentration Polarization C_m was as follows (after applying Winflows 4.04 programming on GARO2):

- a- The maximum value was 8391.9 mg/l in 2-Jan-2022, while its lowest value was determined 2521.4 mg/l in 17-March-2022.
- b- So it was found that the maximum absolute deviation percentage was 9.43 % in 4-June-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 0.19 % in 1-Feb-2022.

Fig. 4.10 Comparison the Concentration polarization C_m between the experimental and Winflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them

4.2.1.9 Salt Rejection R%

The difference in the results values for R% in the desalination plant GARO2 between experimental work and the simulation output by winflows 4.04 programming were showed in Figure 4.11:

- a- The maximum value of salt rejection R% was 98.3 % in 22-Jan-2022, while its lowest value was 95.8 % in 30-Jun-2022.
- b- The maximum absolute deviation percentage of R% was 0.79 % in 17-March-2022, while its absolute minimum value was determined 0.01 % in 29-Jan-2022.

Fig. 4.11 Comparison the Salt Rejection R% between the experimental and Wnflows 4.04 programming results, and the deviation percentage of them.

4.2.2 MATLAB Coding

For a number of reasons, MATLAB was used to build RO model and conduct a numerical analysis for the production of brackish water desalination. These parameters match the practical data with a rather high degree of accuracy, according to the comparison between the model and the practical results. It was discovered that the RO system operated steadily in the temperature range of roughly 10° C to 40° C. Acceptable agreement was seen between the values and

findings taken from the practical portion of the investigation and the results derived from the mathematical model.

The flow chart for the mathematical modeling procedure is given in Figure 4.12. A mathematical model was created using the MATLAB/code script software version R2010a in order to study the RO system's performance and design. Given that the designed model affects the feed temperature, feed concentration, feed pressure, and feed flow rate. Table 4.1 shows the codes used in programming MATLAB and the corresponding variables and constants that were defined and mentioned previously in Chapter Two, as follows:

Additionally, to forecast how the quality of the feed water and different operating parameters, like operating pressure and recovery percentage, will affect the quantity and quality of the permeate water. Below is a summary of this program's primary steps:

- 1- Input the constant data including:
 - a- The characteristics of membrane element (effective area (A_{eff}), the coefficient λ (L_{amp}) which depends on the type of the elements' material).
 - b- Properties of feed water (mass transfer coefficient for water flux K_w , power of hydrogen pH, standard temperature T_s).
 - c- Properties of solute in water (diffusion coefficient for solute in water D_l).
- 2- Create a rotator to enter and calculate the variables that change in each practical experiment. The rotor consists of 150 trials ($i = 1$ to 150).
- 3- Recall variables data from an Excel Sheet which includes the following information:

Fig. 4.12. Algorithm of the mathematical modeling procedure

Table 4.1 Codes used in programming using MATLAB and the corresponding variables and constants

Variables		Description
Usual format	MATLAB Coding	
A_{eff}	Aeff	Effective area, (m ²)
pH	pH	Power of Hydrogen
K_w	Kw	Mass transfer coefficient for water flux, (L/m ² .h.bar)
T_s	Ts	Standard temperature (25° C)
DI	DI	diffusion coefficient for solute in water, m ² /s
λ	Lamp	Coefficient depends on filter elements material ranged from 0.40 to 0.54 (dimensionless)
C_f	Cf	Feed water concentration (mg/l or ppm)
ρ	Roh	Feed water density (Kg/m ³)
μ	Meo	feed water dynamic viscosity (kg/m.s)
T	T	Feed water temperature (° C)
Q_f	Qf	Feed water flow rate (m ³ /h)
P_f	Pf	Feed water pressure (bar)
P_p	Pp	Permeate water pressure (bar)
C_p	Cp	Permeate water concentration (mg/l or ppm)
NDPs	NDPs	Standard Net Driving Pressure (bar)
J_{ws}	Jws	Standard volumetric flux of water, L/m ² .h
C_c	Cc	Brine water concentration (mg/l or ppm)
C_{fc}	Cfc	Concentration of water in feed-concentrate channel (mg/l or ppm)
π_{fc}	PIfc	Feed-concentrate water Osmotic Pressure (bar)
π_p	PIp	Permeate water osmotic pressure (bar)
NDP	NDP	Net Driving Pressure (bar)
J_w	Jw	volumetric flux of water (L/m ² .h)
Q_p	Qp	Permeate water flow rate (m ³ /h)

r%	Recovery	Recovery (%)
Q_{avg}	Q_{avg}	Water flow rate in feed-concentrate channel (m^3/h)
V_{avg}	V_{avg}	Water flow velocity in feed-concentrate channel (m/h)
Re	Re	Reynolds number (dimensionless)
Sc	Sc	Schmidt number (dimensionless)
Kcp	Kcp	Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient (m/s)
β	Beta	concentration polarization factor (dimensionless)
C_m	C_m	Concentration polarization (mg/l or ppm)
R%	Rejection	Salt rejection (%)
J_s	J_s	Mass Flux of Solute ($mg/m^2.h$)

- a- Properties of feed water (concentration C_f , discharge Q_f , pressure P_f , temperature T , density ρ_{oh} , and viscosity Meo).
 - b- Properties of permeate water (concentration C_p , pressure P_p)
 - c- Standard Net Drive Pressure NDPs and standard water flux J_{ws} (which were determined by applying the equations 2.5 and 2.4 respectively).
 - d- Properties of brine water (concentration C_c).
- 4- Compute the concentration of feed-concentrate channel C_{fc} and its osmotic pressure P_{ifc} by applying the equations 2.8 and 2.7, respectively.
 - 5- Determine the Net Drive Pressure and water flux by using equations 2.5 and 2.4 respectively.
 - 6- Find out the Temperature Correction Factor TCF by applying the equation 2.3.
 - 7- By using the variables and factors which were found in the previous steps to determine measured water flux J_{wm} , permeate water flow rate Q_p (Equation 2.9), and Recovery (Equation 2.10). Measured water flux J_{wm} can be found as following [19]:

$$J_{wm} = \frac{J_{ws}}{TCF} \frac{NDP}{NDP_s} \quad (4.1)$$

8- Determine the water characteristics (average flow rate Q_{avg} and average velocity V_{avg}) as following:

$$Q_{avg} = \frac{Q_f + Q_c}{2} \quad (4.2)$$

$$V_{avg} = \frac{Q_{avg}}{A^i} \quad (4.3)$$

9- Reynolds's Number Re , Schmidt Number Sc which were found out by applying the equations 2.15 and 2.16 respectively.

10- Compute concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient K_{cp} (Equation 2.14), and concentration polarization factor Beta (Equation 2.13).

11- Calculate the concentration polarization C_m , Rejection, and the mass flux of solute J_s , by using the Equations 2.13, 2.11, and 2.12 respectively.

12- Display all results.

The last form in MATLAB programming can be shown in the following figure:

```

clc; clear all;
close all;
pH=7; Ts = 25; Kw = 1; Aeff = 37; D1 = 0.00000000135; Lamp = 0.5;
Cf = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','b1:b150');
Roh = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','i1:i150');
Meo = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','j1:j150');
T = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','c1:c150');
Qf = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','d1:d150');
Pf = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','g1:g150');
Pp = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','h1:h150');
Cp = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','e1:e150');
NDPs = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','k1:k150');
Jws = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','l1:l150');
Cc = xlsread('all_results.xls','1','f1:f150');
for i = 1:150
    Cfc(i) = (Cf(i)+Cc(i))/58400;
    PIfc(i) = Cfc(i)*0.083145*(273+T(i));
    PIp(i) = (Cp(i)*2*0.083145*(273+T(i)))/58400;

```

```

NDP(i) = (Pf(i)-Pp(i))-(PIfc(i)-PIp(i));
Jw(i) = Kw*NDP(i)/1000;
TCF(i) = 1.03^(Ts-T(i));
Jwm(i) = Jws(i)*NDP(i)/(TCF(i)*NDPs(i));
Qp(i) = Jwm(i)*Aeff*6;
Recovery(i) = Qp(i)*100/Qf(i);
Qavg(i) = (2*Qf(i)-Qp(i))/4;
Vavg(i) = Qavg(i)/112.72536;
Re(i) = Roh(i)*Vavg(i)*0.00172/Meo(i);
Sc(i) = Meo(i)/(Roh(i)*0.00000000135);
Kcp(i) = 0.0000003924418*(Re(i)^0.5)*(Sc(i)^0.33333);
Beta(i) = exp(Jwm(i)/(Kcp(i)*3600));
Cm(i) = Beta(i)*((Cf(i)+Cc(i))/2);
Rejection(i)=(Cf(i)-Cp(i))*100/Cf(i);
Js(i)=Jwm(i)*Cp(i);
end
disp('      Jwm      Qp      r%      R%');
disp('-----');
for i=1:150
A(i,1:4)=[Jwm(i) Qp(i) Recovery(i) Rejection(i)];
end
disp(A);

```

The results obtained from applying the MATLAB program can be observed in Figure 4.13, which represents part of the practical results.

4.3 Second Methodology: Optimization by Gene Expression Programming (GEP)

In the industrial sector, RO has been widely used as a highly effective method of separation. Most of the time, choosing the ideal set of operational parameters is necessary to maximize system performance. When compared to traditional gradient-based optimization methods, the GEPs are quicker and more effective [102].

Command Window				Command Window			
Jwm	Qp	r%	R%				
0.0098	2.1804	30.7099	97.3848	0.0124	2.7481	38.7054	95.4669
0.0103	2.2968	28.0097	97.7611	0.0128	2.8461	35.1365	95.7733
0.0112	2.4910	24.9099	98.1468	0.0137	3.0424	30.1223	96.4538
0.0123	2.7208	22.4861	98.2596	0.0146	3.2418	26.7917	96.5991
0.0128	2.8312	21.6125	98.4572	0.0151	3.3412	25.5057	96.7696
0.0112	2.4834	34.4919	96.7357	0.0152	3.3748	47.5331	94.6421
0.0116	2.5738	31.7754	97.2719	0.0156	3.4626	43.2827	95.1419
0.0126	2.7881	27.3341	97.4882	0.0166	3.6829	36.1067	95.8651
0.0134	2.9835	24.6574	97.9680	0.0175	3.8810	31.8116	96.3183
0.0139	3.0957	23.4520	98.0715	0.0179	3.9703	30.3074	96.5315
0.0125	2.7823	39.7475	96.2559	0.0175	3.8951	55.6450	93.0477
0.0130	2.8892	35.6695	96.6322	0.0180	4.0057	49.4535	93.9887
0.0139	3.0949	30.3426	96.8956	0.0190	4.2080	41.6634	95.0058
0.0148	3.2919	26.9832	97.3659	0.0199	4.4089	36.4370	95.5976
0.0152	3.3805	25.8053	97.6858	0.0204	4.5203	34.2447	95.6633
0.0147	3.2708	46.7253	95.0103	0.0092	2.0528	29.3264	96.7945
0.0153	3.3882	41.3196	95.2117	0.0098	2.1780	26.8890	96.8542
0.0161	3.5729	35.3748	96.2305	0.0108	2.4024	23.7862	97.0093
0.0170	3.7691	31.1499	96.6002	0.0119	2.6403	21.6418	97.3032
0.0175	3.8861	29.2184	97.0273	0.0124	2.7432	20.9403	97.4591
0.0175	3.8882	54.7640	94.1580	0.0104	2.3164	32.6259	96.0556
0.0180	3.9882	49.2369	94.3838	0.0110	2.4341	29.6840	96.3059
0.0189	4.1960	41.1373	95.3104	0.0119	2.6483	25.9638	96.5953
0.0197	4.3747	36.4562	95.9003	0.0128	2.8507	23.5598	96.7207
0.0202	4.4848	34.2350	95.9304	0.0133	2.9577	22.5780	96.8118
0.0099	2.1994	30.5479	97.0926	0.0117	2.5868	36.9542	94.9630
0.0103	2.2852	28.5645	97.1518	0.0122	2.6975	33.3027	95.3399
0.0113	2.5121	24.8724	97.3132	0.0131	2.9113	28.5419	96.0822
0.0124	2.7525	22.3784	97.6070	0.0140	3.1155	25.5369	96.2481
0.0127	2.8297	21.7669	97.7197	0.0144	3.2013	24.6254	96.3419
0.0108	2.3924	33.6951	96.3658	0.0136	3.0140	43.0572	94.1026
0.0112	2.4953	30.8061	96.5308	0.0141	3.1317	38.1910	94.7811
0.0122	2.7120	26.5881	97.0599	0.0149	3.3122	33.1224	95.4212
0.0131	2.9106	24.0547	97.2114	0.0159	3.5353	28.9778	95.6826
0.0135	3.0052	23.1172	97.3159	0.0164	3.6392	27.5700	95.9751
				0.0165	3.6526	51.4448	92.5316
				0.0169	3.7596	45.8489	93.5097

Fig. 4.13. Part of the MATLAB programming results

Natural behavior can be directly compared to the principles of GEP, which are search strategies founded on the ideas of natural evolution [103]. The general idea behind GEP is to first choose a population of initial solution points that are randomly distributed throughout the optimized space. Next, iteratively apply the processes of crossover, mutation, and reproduction/selection to improve the solutions until the desired stopping criteria is met [104].

4.3.1 Objective Functions Using Gene Expression Programming (GEP)

GEP was used to derive and analyze the objective functions, as shown in Figure 4.14 and Table 4.2, which are related to the most influential variables,

which were determined by extracting the correlation for all variables using the IBM SPSS statistical program, which will be explained in the next paragraph.

4.3.2 Procedures of work using GEP in this thesis

To extract the optimal values for the variables associated with the objective functions, the following procedures and steps were taken:

- 1- Determine the variables that have the most influence on the operation conditions by extracting the correlation coefficients for all variables in the desalination plant and using the statistical program SPSS, where variables with a correlation greater than 0.5 were identified (see Table 4.2).

Fig. 4.14 The objective functions and them variables with a higher correlation coefficient

Table 4.2 Correlation coefficient of the variables which were obtained by statistics program SPSS

	Qf	T	Cf	pH	Cp	Cc	Pf	Pp	NDP	Jwm	Qp	R%	Sc	Kcp	β	Cm	R%	P%	Js
Qf	1	-.001	.000	-.014	-.158	.004	.404	.962	.565	.419	.419	-.654	.001	.986	-.317	-.008	.411	-.411	-.060
T	-.001	1	.042	-.126	.277	.038	-.409	-.252	-.729	.851	.851	.683	-.986	.140	.843	.069	-.658	.658	.448
Cf	.000	.042	1	.307	.929	1.000	.787	-.029	-.342	-.223	-.223	-.180	-.043	.041	-.281	.999	-.605	.605	.855
pH	-.014	-.126	.307	1	.241	.308	.308	.014	.004	-.180	-.180	-.136	.135	-.021	-.186	.304	-.121	.121	.200
Cp	-.158	.277	.929	.241	1	.927	.570	-.230	-.566	-.077	-.077	.103	-.088	-.012	.939	-.806	.806	.965	
Cc	.004	.038	1.000	.308	.927	1	.790	-.025	-.337	-.225	-.225	-.185	-.039	.044	.939	-.601	.601	.852	
Pf	.404	-.409	.787	.308	.570	.790	1	.488	.309	-.370	-.370	.681	.419	.360	.772	-.052	.052	.482	
Pp	.962	-.252	-.029	.014	-.230	-.025	.488	1	.751	.200	.200	-.774	.253	.906	-.488	-.043	.552	-.552	
NDP	.565	-.729	-.342	.004	-.566	-.337	.309	.751	1	-.275	-.275	.745	.745	.428	-.634	-.364	.857	-.857	
Jwm	.419	.851	-.223	-.180	-.077	-.225	-.370	.200	-.275	1	1.000	.389	-.815	.517	.710	-.203	-.248	.248	
Qp	.419	.851	-.223	-.180	-.077	-.225	-.370	.200	-.275	1.000	1	.389	-.815	.517	.710	-.203	-.248	.248	
r%	-.654	.683	-.180	-.136	.103	-.185	-.681	-.774	-.753	.389	.389	1	-.654	-.574	.920	-.155	-.638	.638	
Sc	.001	-.986	-.043	.135	-.270	-.039	.419	.253	.745	-.815	-.815	-.654	1	-.145	-.800	-.068	.641	-.641	
Kcp	.986	.140	.041	-.021	-.088	.044	.360	.906	.428	.517	.517	-.574	-.145	1	-.224	.036	.305	-.305	
β	-.317	.843	-.281	-.186	-.012	-.286	-.690	-.488	-.634	.920	1	.920	-.800	-.224	1	-.255	-.543	.543	
Cm	-.008	.069	.999	.304	.939	.999	.772	-.043	-.364	-.203	-.203	-.155	-.068	.036	1	-.628	.628	.871	
R%	.411	-.658	-.605	-.121	-.806	-.601	-.052	.552	.857	-.248	-.248	-.638	.641	.305	-.543	1	-1.000	1.000	
P%	-.411	.658	.605	.121	.806	.601	.052	-.552	-.857	.248	.248	.638	-.641	-.305	.543	-1.000	1.000	.838	
Js	-.060	.448	.855	.200	.965	.852	.482	-.175	-.602	.133	.133	.177	-.427	.029	.871	-.838	.838	1	

Bad	0-0.5	±
Weak	0.5-0.6	±
Moderate	0.6-0.7	±
Good	0.7-0.8	±
Very Good	0.8-0.9	±
Excellent	0.9-1.0	±

- 2- Determine the variables that are considered as target elements, for each of which a function will be derived that is considered a target function. These variables are permeate water flow rate Q_p , water flux J_w , permeate water concentration C_p , and salt rejection $R\%$. The rest of the variables are considered independent variables.
- 3- Deriving an appropriate objective function for each of the four variables using GEP, taking into account the lowest expected error rate, as shown in Table 4.3.
- 4- Using the Excel sheet program, appropriate tables are organized that include all the results of the operation conditions obtained, grouped under the objective function and the most influential independent variables. In addition to the largest and smallest recorded value and the boundary conditions for all variables (note Tables 4.4 and AI.1).

It is most be known that the constraints that were chosen are among the specifications and requirements of membranes, pumps, and the limits of the specifications of the feed water used in the work, which in general do not exceed the max. and min. limits that were monitored from the operation of the desalination plant for the purpose of inferring the operation conditions.

- 5- To derive the optimal values, open the MATLAB, R2010a, V:7.10.0.499 using GEP technology.
- 6- Create a new script by [File → New → Script] to run Algorithm.
- 7- Start to write the commands by using the objective fitness function. This part will be saved and used later.
- 8- Write the fitness function by using independent variable (x) to predict or estimate the dependent variable like (y), but it depends on how many x 's

that will be used (one or more depending on the number of independent variables that effect on the objective function).

- 9- Translate the objective function that were written in Excel file to the programming code. Make sure to write carefully and correctly according to the language of the program. For example, but not limited to, change the writing of the formula (x1) to the formula x(1), meaning that the variable number is in parentheses, leaving a space between the variables and constants inside the objective function equation, and so on.
- 10- Conclude by writing the phrase (end) as its final step.
- 11- To check if it was correct steps, go to command window and write like this `[myfitness ([0 0 0 0])]`, by changing (x) with zeros equal to the number of independent variables which was found in the objective function. It must be noted that the first zero refers to x1 (first independent variable), second zero refers to x2, and so on.
- 12- Press (Enter) to run the program. The result represents the initial value for the objective function with independent variables equal to zero.
- 13- Check the results, which was obtained from GEP by doing a companion contrast between them and those from the experimental results after writing the objective formula. If the results are not close, either that mean the objective function, which was used in GEP programming had incorrect representation, or the origin of the function is not correct, so it is replaced by another equation.
- 14- After using zeros value of independent as initial values, then take randomly choose for x1, x2... Etc. from the table in Excel sheet and applying those by GEP after replacing the zeros values by real values of the independent variables as shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.3 Utilizing Gene Expression Programming (GEP) to generate objective functions.

y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13	E%	R ²	The objective function with form of y=f(x1,x2, ..., xn)
Qp	T	r %	Sc	Kcp	β	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0248799	> 0.99	$y = 1.813036329971869 + ((47578.2934943513 + 16.21153382880898 * x3) * (0.08028264034726941 * (x2 - (-19.16154602498517 + x1)) * (-1279.693756072737 * x4 + 0.02333570867961245))) + 0.9906347086696391 * (-4.856065462730521e-06 + x4))$
J _{w m}	Qf	T	Qp	Sc	Kcp	β	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.72*10 ⁻¹⁰	≈ 1	$y = 0.004504504512569102 * (x3 + 3.242133179450495e-09 * \tan(x2 + 0.1006565899122639))$
C _p	Cf	Cc	Pf	NDP	Cm	R%	P%	Js	-	-	-	-	-	0.0019854	≈ 1	$y = x7 * x1 / ((-6.72815519141161e-05) * (\tan(\tan(7.869586061344686e-05 + x8)) - (\cos(0.6456209325671695 * 8.000016884820001 * x3) / 0.2604299833471725)) + 6.40449299089886e-05 + x6 + x7)$
R%	Qf	T	Cf	Cp	Cc	Pf	NDP	r %	Sc	Kcp	Cm	P%	Js	2.51*10 ⁻⁹	≈ 1	$y = 100.000472805538 - (7.58462361781271e-05 / ((-57.40186283750788 - \tan(x5) + \tan(0.3331186021954319 * x2)) * (\tan(x9) - x9))) - (0.0004728037103777207 + x12)$

Table 4.4 Boundary Conditions and recorded value (max. and min. limits) of variables which were used in optimization by GEP

Variables in MATLAB and GEP format		y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13
GEP1 → Q_p	Variables in regular form	Q_p	T	r %	Sc	Kcp	β	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Boundary	4.5	30	55	969.2	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	1.2298	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Conditions	2	20	45	497.0	2.29*10 ⁻⁵	1.108	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Recorded Value	4.52	39	55.645	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	1.2298	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Variables in MATLAB and GEP format		y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13
GEP2 → J_{w m}	Variables in regular form	J_{w m}	Qf	T	Qp	Sc	Kcp	β	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Boundary	0.02	10	30	4.5	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	1.2298	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Conditions	0.01	8	20	2	497.04	2.29*10 ⁻⁵	1.108	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Recorded Value	0.0204	13.3	39	4.5203	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	1.2298	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Variables in MATLAB and GEP format		y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13
GEP3 → C_p	Variables in regular form	C_p	Cf	Cc	Pf	NDP	Cm	R%	P%	J_s	-	-	-	-	-
	Boundary	500	5000	14072.9	23	18	14055	99.5	3	13766	-	-	-	-	-
	Conditions	0	0	1491	20	16	1434.1	97	0.5	209.15	-	-	-	-	-
	Recorded Value	937.87	9948	14072.9	27.383	19.291	14055	98.457	9.4277	13766	-	-	-	-	-
Variables in MATLAB and GEP format		y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13
GEP4 → R%	Variables in regular form	R%	Qf	T	Cf	Cp	Cc	Pf	NDP	r %	Sc	Kcp	Cm	P%	J_s
	Boundary	99.5	10	30	5000	500	14072.9	23	18	55	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	14055	3	13766
	Conditions	97	8	20	0	0	0	1491	20	45	497.04	2.29*10 ⁻⁵	1434.1	0.5	209.15
	Recorded Value	98.5	13.3	39	9948	937.87	14072.9	27.383	19.291	55.645	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	14055	9.4277	13766
Variables in MATLAB and GEP format		y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13
Variables in regular form		R%	Qf	T	Cf	Cp	Cc	Pf	NDP	r %	Sc	Kcp	Cm	P%	J_s
Boundary		99.5	10	30	5000	500	14072.9	23	18	55	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	14055	3	13766
Conditions		97	8	20	0	0	1491	20	45	497.04	2.29*10 ⁻⁵	1434.1	0.5	209.15	
Recorded Value		98.5	13.3	39	9948	937.87	14072.9	27.383	19.291	55.645	969.18	3.49*10 ⁻⁵	14055	9.4277	13766
Variables in MATLAB and GEP format		y	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9	x10	x11	x12	x13
Boundary		90.6	7	10	1063	16.4	1491	13.094	9.995	20.383	497.04	2.29*10 ⁻⁵	1434.1	1.5428	209.15

Table 4.5 Comparing a sample of the results obtained from the application of GEP Programming with the results of experimental work of operation conditions

T	r %	Sc	Kcp	Qp	Qp
x1	x2	x3	x4	y by experimental work	y Applying GEP Programming
31	31.1499	583.0817	3.2622E-05	3.769137852	3.7434

15- Now, it must be to go for coding by try again emphasizing that it did not have any constraints other than the boundaries.

16- Directly proceed with main function. Main function is a code for minimizing or maximizing the fitness function by using GEP programming. Several codes can be summarized and defined in Table 4.6. After finishing writing the last sentence, these commands will be saved under another name, such as (main.m).

Table 4.6 Cods and commands used in GEP of MATLAB, R2010a, V: 7.10.0.499

Code	Description
objFcn	used to call the objective function in the command list
nvars	Number of independent variables in objective function
LB	Lower Boundary conditions
UB	Upper Boundary conditions
[x, fval]	Referring to the syntax used to implement an algebraic statement
ga	To direct the system to capture the GEP automatically
(.....)	Open the bracket will be open a window put back every think it has.

17- For purpose of finding other optimal values for the rest of the objective functions, the previous steps must be repeated, changing what is necessary to harmonize each individual equation with its variables. Table 4.7 shows the optimization results for all selected objective functions.

4.4 Summary

4.4.1 Simulation of Long-Term Operation by Using Winflows 4.04 Programming

The simulation was done using Winflows 4.04, and the results were as shown in Tables AI.6 and AI.7. Through analyzing and studying the data, it was found that the deviation between the real and simulated results does not exceed 10% in all the results obtained except for the mass flux of solute, where the deviation results exceeded 10% and was 50 out of 123 results. Only two results out of the 50 results had a deviation rate exceeding 15%. Therefore, it can be considered the results of the program to be largely acceptable, and this means that the simulation using Winflows 4.04 program gives a very good representation of the practical reality.

4.4.2 Optimization by Using Gene Expression Programming (GEP)

To obtain the most effective optimal values in the desalination system, four objective functions were derived using genetic algorithms. It was found that the optimal values for the variables became as follows:

- 1- The optimal values for the variables T , $r\%$, Sc , and K_{cp} were 20.519°C , 45.01% , 572.6 , and 2.456×10^{-5} , respectively, to obtain the best permeate flow rate as the objective function.
- 2- The optimal values of the variables Q_f , T , and Q_p were $8.0562 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, 20.31°C , and $2.398 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, respectively, to obtain the best water flux as the objective function.
- 3- The optimal values of C_f , J_s , P_f , $R\%$, and $P\%$ were 1063 mg/l , $1315.3 \text{ mg/m}^2.\text{h}$, 21.938 bar , 99.4% , and 0.5% , respectively, to obtain the best C_p as an objective function.

CHAPTER

5

Improving Performance

Chapter Five

Improving Performance

5.1 General

Researchers and workers in the field of water desalination using RO2 face many challenges directly related to the quantity and quality of the water produced as a major goal for desalination plants and scientific research alike. Therefore, several scientific methods are proposed to improve the performance of desalination plants (increasing the amount of water produced, improving the quality of the water produced, reducing the energy used in operating the desalination plant, etc.). Many methods for improving performance were mentioned in the Chapter Two. In this thesis, three scenarios are proposed. The first scenario involves modifying GARO2 from parallel splicing of vessels to sequential splicing. This scenario was applied practically and gave good results, as will be explained in the following paragraphs. The second scenario is adding a feed stripper to the plant. The quality of the produced water only improved without being affected by the quantities of production or the energy consumed represented by feed pressure. The third scenario is mixing portion of brine water of GARO2 with its feed water. This scenario used in case of long-term operation.

5.2 First Scenario – Connect Vessels in Series

All parts of the desalination plant in this scenario remain the same, except that the connection of the Vessels changes from parallel connection to series connection, as shown in the diagram and picture of Figure 5.1.

After modifying the desalination plant appropriately, it became possible to operate it in parallel or series mode by controlling the on/off the valves, as shown in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1. Getting parallel or series mode in GARO2 plant.

Connection Mode	Valves Case		
	Valve 1	Valve 2	Valve 3
Parallel	On	Off	On
Series	Off	On	Off

For comparing the performance of the desalination plant before and after the conversion process, to determine the extent to which the efficiency of the plant has improved, whether in terms of quantity or quality of production, it was operated under the same operating conditions used to determine the performance of the desalination plant.

Fig. 5.1. The vessel connection of GARO2 after modification

It must be noted that the following:

1. Every operational cycle in the normal state (Parallel Connection) is corresponding to an operational cycle in the state of (Series Connection).
2. The operational cycle means setting the water concentration to a specific value (6 different values have been identified, ranging from 1063-9948 mg/l) and the feed water temperature is specified, and then starting with a feed flow rate ranging from (7.0-7.2 m³/h), (8.0-8.3 m³/h), (10.0-10.3 m³/h), (12.0-12.3 m³/h), and (13.0-13.3 m³/h) respectively.
3. The subsequent operational cycle begins after changing the temperature of the feed water, as 5 temperature ranges were used.
4. The number of operational cycles is equal to 5 readings of the feed flow rate multiplied by 5 ranges of the temperature of the feed water multiplied by 6 states of the concentration of feed water. In other words, 150 examination forms for 30 operational cycles, with 5 examination forms per operational cycle.
5. The 150 examination forms in the case of a parallel connection are compared to 150 examination forms in the case of a series connection.

In this section, we present the outcomes achieved through the application of the first scenario as a tool to enhance the performance of the desalination plant. The term Percentage of Performance Improvement (PPI) is used to indicate the improvement in the plant's performance, and it can be calculated using the following equation:

$$PPI = \frac{k_i - k_f}{k_i} \times 100\% \quad (5.1)$$

Where;

PPI = Percentage of Performance Improvement.

k_i = Variable value before performance improvement.

k_f = Variable value after performance improvement.

Improvements in permeate concentration, permeate flux, recovery ratio, and salt rejection can be observed in Table 5.2. Additionally, increases in feed pressure and brine concentration are also noted in the same table, which represent the negative aspects associated with this scenario.

5.2.1 Permeate Water Concentration Improvement

In general, the permeate water concentration values will improve well. The lowest value of the Percentage of Performance Improvement PPI was 5.4% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 2105 mg/l and 12 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h. The highest value of the PPI was 40.8% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 4171 mg/l and 10°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h. The best PPI average rate was 32.4% occurred at a water temperature of 11°C, Cf 5979 mg/l and feed flow rate Qf between 7.1-13.0 m³/h as shown in Figure 5.2.

The results demonstrate that PPI is strongly influenced by feed water concentration, temperature, and flow rate. High PPI values indicate that substantial improvements can be achieved when operating under certain challenging conditions, particularly with high salinity and moderate temperature. These findings can guide the optimization of operating parameters to maximize the plant's performance efficiency.

5.2.2 Water Flow Rate and Recovery % Improvement

The effect of the parallel case system on the recovery and permeate flow rate is identical, due to the linear relationship between r% and Qp, which can be summarized as follows (Figures 5.3 and 5.4):

- a- The lowest value of the PPI was 0.7% at the feed water concentration and temperature were 9948 mg/l and 38 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate was 7.2 m³/h.
- b- The highest value were the PPI was 40.5% at the feed water concentration and temperature were 1063 mg/l and 11°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate was 13.1 m³/h.

These results reaffirm that feed water concentration and flow rate are critical factors influencing the effectiveness of performance improvements. While high temperatures and salinity negatively affect the outcome, low salinity and optimized flow significantly enhance performance. These findings provide valuable insights for selecting operational parameters that maximize the plant's performance improvement potential.

5.2.3 Salt Rejection Improvement

The effect of the parallel case system can be summarized as follows:

- a- The lowest value of the PPI was 0.16% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 2105 mg/l and 12 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h.
- b- The highest value of the PPI was 2.47% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 9948 mg/l and 38°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h.

The parallel case system exhibits significantly lower PPI values, suggesting that it is less sensitive to performance enhancement efforts compared to other configurations. The limited variation in PPI across different conditions implies that either the system has structural limitations to improvement or the applied modifications are not well-suited for this setup. This insight can help in deciding

whether alternative configurations (e.g., series systems) may be more effective for performance optimization.

Table 5.2. Rates of improvement and deterioration in the performance of the GARO2 desalination plant.

Cf mg/l	T (°C)	Qf = (7.0-7.2) m ³ /h					Qf = (8.0-8.3) m ³ /h					Qf = (10.0-10.3) m ³ /h					Qf = (12.0-12.3) m ³ /h					Qf = (13.0-13.3) m ³ /h				
		Cp	Cc	Pf	Qp or r%	R%	Cp	Cc	Pf	Qp or r%	R%	Cp	Cc	Pf	Qp or r%	R%	Cp	Cc	Pf	Qp or r%	R%	Cp	Cc	Pf	Qp or r%	R%
1063	11	31.7	43.6	-26.0	25.9	0.85	22.7	45.2	-29.5	29.6	0.52	12.7	46.5	-33.0	33.3	0.24	24.9	48.2	-36.5	36.9	0.44	12.8	51.1	-40.0	40.5	0.20
	18	22.7	42.8	-22.0	21.7	0.84	17.9	44.5	-25.3	25.1	0.50	16.5	45.6	-28.5	28.6	0.42	10.2	46.9	-31.8	32.0	0.21	24.9	49.0	-35.0	35.3	0.49
	24	12.7	42.4	-19.0	18.4	0.96	28.5	44.1	-21.8	21.3	0.99	24.5	44.6	-24.5	24.3	0.79	24.5	45.8	-27.3	27.2	0.66	18.3	47.5	-30.0	30.1	0.43
	31	24.9	42.6	-16.0	15.1	1.14	22.2	43.7	-18.8	18.0	1.12	17.9	44.5	-21.5	21.0	0.70	24.7	45.3	-24.3	24.0	0.87	17.4	46.5	-27.0	26.9	0.53
2105	38	12.8	41.0	-14.0	12.9	0.64	18.4	41.3	-16.5	15.6	1.10	19.6	42.3	-19.0	18.4	0.96	19.5	42.8	-21.5	21.1	0.83	28.1	43.1	-24.0	23.8	1.19
	12	5.4	42.8	-25.0	24.9	0.16	17.4	43.2	-28.3	28.5	0.51	24.5	43.8	-31.5	32.1	0.68	24.6	44.5	-34.8	35.6	0.60	28.8	45.0	-38.0	39.1	0.67
	17	21.2	42.5	-21.0	20.2	0.80	28.2	42.8	-23.8	23.3	1.02	24.5	43.0	-26.5	26.5	0.74	25.6	43.4	-29.3	29.6	0.73	26.7	44.0	-32.0	32.6	0.74
	24	15.0	42.2	-18.0	16.7	0.71	12.8	42.8	-20.8	19.9	0.56	29.3	42.9	-23.5	23.0	1.08	31.4	43.3	-26.3	26.1	1.11	31.5	43.6	-29.0	29.3	1.05
4171	33	24.5	42.6	-15.0	12.9	1.39	21.3	43.0	-17.5	15.9	1.09	24.5	43.1	-20.0	18.9	1.06	21.3	43.2	-22.5	21.8	0.81	24.5	43.5	-25.0	24.7	0.88
	39	16.2	42.2	-15.0	12.8	1.21	24.5	42.2	-17.3	15.5	1.57	17.0	42.7	-19.5	18.2	0.89	25.5	42.8	-21.8	20.9	1.18	30.9	42.8	-24.0	23.5	1.40
	10	16.3	42.7	-24.0	23.4	0.54	24.5	43.1	-27.3	27.4	0.80	27.3	43.0	-30.5	31.4	0.84	24.5	43.1	-33.8	35.3	0.68	40.8	43.3	-37.0	39.1	1.06
	17	17.6	42.9	-20.0	18.0	0.72	18.6	42.8	-22.8	21.7	0.71	16.5	42.8	-25.5	25.3	0.58	24.6	42.7	-28.3	28.7	0.83	36.6	42.8	-31.0	32.0	1.21
5979	23	24.5	42.2	-17.0	13.8	1.30	24.5	42.7	-19.8	17.5	1.20	20.9	42.8	-22.5	21.3	0.85	24.5	42.8	-25.3	24.9	0.96	24.6	42.8	-28.0	28.4	0.93
	30	18.4	42.7	-15.0	10.7	1.15	11.9	42.8	-17.5	14.4	0.65	22.0	42.8	-20.0	17.8	1.05	24.5	42.6	-22.5	21.2	1.11	23.3	42.8	-25.0	24.5	0.98
	38	12.8	42.4	-15.0	10.5	1.03	21.1	42.7	-17.3	13.5	1.47	13.0	42.8	-19.5	16.9	0.75	15.1	42.8	-21.8	20.1	0.77	18.2	42.8	-24.0	23.1	0.90
	11	31.9	43.2	-23.0	21.3	1.31	35.2	43.2	-26.3	25.8	1.43	33.3	43.2	-29.5	30.3	1.27	29.8	43.3	-32.8	34.6	1.04	31.7	43.5	-36.0	38.7	1.09
8217	18	32.1	42.8	-19.0	15.3	1.59	33.6	42.8	-21.8	19.3	1.61	28.5	42.9	-24.5	23.5	1.23	31.7	42.8	-27.3	27.3	1.33	32.4	43.0	-30.0	31.0	1.29
	23	31.3	42.4	-16.0	10.5	1.77	34.7	42.5	-18.5	14.3	1.96	24.6	42.5	-21.0	18.5	1.16	24.5	42.8	-23.5	22.1	1.13	24.5	43.0	-26.0	25.6	1.10
	32	24.5	42.8	-14.0	6.7	1.77	26.6	42.8	-16.5	10.8	1.69	24.3	42.9	-19.0	15.0	1.35	24.4	42.8	-21.5	18.9	1.23	22.6	42.8	-24.0	22.7	1.07
	38	21.5	42.5	-14.0	6.2	1.95	20.0	42.7	-16.3	10.0	1.60	27.9	42.4	-18.5	13.8	1.86	22.0	42.8	-20.8	17.6	1.28	26.0	42.8	-23.0	20.9	1.50
9948	13	20.8	42.8	-22.0	19.2	0.93	24.5	42.8	-25.3	24.4	1.07	24.5	42.8	-28.5	29.4	1.01	25.4	42.8	-31.8	34.2	0.96	31.3	42.8	-35.0	38.6	1.18
	19	24.5	42.8	-18.0	12.0	1.32	24.5	42.8	-20.8	16.8	1.29	18.4	42.6	-23.5	21.7	0.84	21.7	42.8	-26.3	26.0	0.97	26.6	42.9	-29.0	30.0	1.16
	26	27.3	42.8	-15.0	5.9	1.76	29.4	42.9	-17.5	10.4	1.87	22.6	42.8	-20.0	15.5	1.16	22.0	42.8	-22.5	19.8	1.08	26.1	43.1	-25.0	23.7	1.27
	33	24.6	41.8	-13.0	2.0	1.90	20.2	42.7	-15.5	6.6	1.41	25.0	43.0	-18.0	11.3	1.50	24.3	42.8	-20.5	16.1	1.29	25.8	43.1	-23.0	20.2	1.29
	39	23.0	40.5	-12.0	1.4	2.23	19.3	42.9	-14.3	3.4	1.67	17.6	42.8	-16.5	8.4	1.24	20.2	42.8	-18.8	12.7	1.26	25.5	42.8	-21.0	16.5	1.57
	12	22.3	42.7	-21.0	16.8	1.14	23.9	42.5	-24.3	22.5	1.19	28.9	42.9	-27.5	27.7	1.38	25.5	42.8	-30.8	32.9	1.11	30.0	42.3	-34.0	37.9	1.29
	17	20.6	42.6	-17.0	9.2	1.21	24.4	42.4	-19.8	14.3	1.39	28.6	42.8	-22.5	19.2	1.47	29.0	42.5	-25.3	24.1	1.47	30.4	41.3	-28.0	29.0	1.50
	27	26.9	42.8	-14.0	1.4	2.04	20.8	42.8	-16.5	7.0	1.42	22.2	42.8	-19.0	12.3	1.33	24.5	42.6	-21.5	17.3	1.34	29.9	41.2	-24.0	22.2	1.62
	33	24.5	42.8	-12.0	1.0	2.12	24.5	42.6	-14.5	2.0	1.94	24.0	42.6	-17.0	7.9	1.63	20.8	42.5	-19.5	13.3	1.23	26.6	40.9	-22.0	18.5	1.55
	38	23.7	42.2	-11.0	0.7	2.47	18.4	42.8	-13.3	1.6	1.72	27.4	42.4	-15.5	4.1	2.11	24.4	42.8	-17.8	9.0	1.69	29.4	40.8	-20.0	14.2	2.02

Fig. 5.2. The normal Cp and the improvement Cp comparison (Series case system)

Fig. 5.3. The normal Qp and the improvement Qp comparison (Series case system)

Fig. 5.4. The normal $r\%$ and the improvement $r\%$ comparison (Series case system)

5.2.4 Brine Water Concentration

Increasing the value of brine water concentration does not mean that there is no improvement in the performance of the desalination plant, on the contrary, as this increase is natural because the value of C_p has become lower, and therefore the values of C_c increase. However, increasing the concentration of brine water negatively affects the environment, especially if the brine water is discharged into the Shatt al-Arab riverbed or sewage sewers. The effect of the parallel case system can be summarized as follows (Figure 5.6):

- a- The lowest value of the PPI was 40.5% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 8217 mg/l and 39 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h.
- b- The highest value of the PPI was 51.1% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 1063 mg/l and 11°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h.

The parallel case system demonstrates strong and consistent performance improvements, with PPI values ranging from 40.5% to 51.1%, and an average of 47.4% under optimal conditions. This shows that when operating within appropriate feed concentration and flow rate ranges, the system can deliver efficient desalination. However, the environmental implications of increased brine salinity must be addressed, particularly regarding safe disposal practices to minimize ecological damage. Strategic planning and environmental management should accompany operational optimization to ensure sustainable performance.

Fig. 5.5. The normal R% and the improvement R% comparison (Series case system)

Fig. 5.6. Comparison between the normal Cc and the improvement Cc (Series case system)

5.2.5 Feed Water Pressure Increasing (Negative Effect NE)

Changing the plant system from parallel case to series case increases the pressure necessary to overcome the long path that the feed water needs to exit the two series vessels. Increasing the feed water pressure means increasing the energy required to operate the desalination plant and this is a negative matter that leads to an increase in the cost of producing one cubic meter of desalinated water. Figure 5.7 shows an increase in the feed pressure ratio (negative effect) as following:

- a- The lowest value of the NE was -11.0% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 8217 mg/l and 38 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h.
- b- The highest value of the NE was -40.0% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 1063 mg/l and 11°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h.

5.3 Second Scenario – Air Stripper

Air stripping (Figure 5.8) is a procedure used in water treatment units to achieve particular water treatment goals by applying the concepts of mass transfer [19]. This type of device is used to remove volatile substances from water to air and vice versa, such as carbon dioxide, volatile organic compounds, and hydrogen sulfide. Desorption is the term for the mass transfer process that involves removing volatile compounds from water and releasing them into the atmosphere. One of the most popular desorption techniques used in water treatment is air stripping. The stripper can also be used along with activated carbon to rid the water of bad odor and taste, so they can be used as post-treatment in desalination plants [36]. Sometimes stripper is used as part of additional wastewater treatment processes when it contains a high percentage of organic matter [105].

Fig. 5.7. Comparison between the normal Pf and the improvement Pf (Series case system)

Fig. 5.8. Air stripper sketch

In this thesis, it was proposed to add a feed stripper as a pretreatment to get rid of carbon dioxide, as this scenario will be done using the Winflows 4.04 software. The program outputs showed an improvement only in the permeate concentration, and thus an improvement in the salt rejection rate. As for the rest of the variables, such as brine concentration, feed pressure, and recovery, there is no improvement, or the improvement is very slight and intangible. The effect of adding stripper on Cp and R% will be reviewed in the next two paragraphs:

5.3.1 Permeate Water Concentration Improvement (by feed stripper)

The effect of adding the feed stripper on the system can be summarized as follows (Figure 5.9):

- a- The lowest value of the PPI was 24.3% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 2105 mg/l and 33 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.1 m³/h.
- b- The highest value of the PPI was 68.0% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 9948 mg/l and 12°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h.

5.3.2 Salt Rejection Improvement (by feed stripper)

The effect of the adding the feed stripper on salt rejection can be summarized as follows (Figure 5.10):

- a- The lowest value of the PPI was 0.65% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 1063 mg/l and 11 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h.
- b- The highest value of the PPI was 3.25% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 9948 mg/l and 38°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h.

Fig. 5.9. Comparison between the normal Cp and the improvement Cp (adding feed stripper- use Winflows 4.04)

Fig. 5.10. Comparison between the normal R% and the improvement R% (adding feed stripper- use Winflows 4.04)

5.4 Third Scenario – Recycling of brine water

Reusing a portion of the brine water and re-mixing it with the feed water is one technique that has been used for improving the GARO2 desalination plant's performance, as Figure 5.11.

Fig. 5.11. Recycling of brine water (third scenario)

5.4.1 Recycling goals

The main objective of this scenario is to improve the performance of the desalination plant according to the following axes:

- 1- Increasing the amount of produced water (permeate water) by recycling brine water.
- 2- Reducing the environmental impact caused by the release of large quantities of salt water.
- 3- Obtaining stable conditions to operate the station for a longer period of time.

During the extended study period of six months, it was noted that the concentration of feed water for the GARO2 desalination plant was relatively low

compared to the operational conditions to which the plant was exposed when analyzing and studying the operation conditions, as explained in Chapter 3. In addition, the quantities of water produced and produced can be easily controlled and managed by storing that water in tanks for a certain period until the appropriate quantity for mixing is obtained, and then connecting the tanks together. The mixing ratios of feed and brine water are not fixed because they depend on the concentration of each one, and the concentrations are constantly changing. Using the volumetric balance method, mixing ratios of water with different concentrations can be obtained to obtain specific and stable concentrations of new feed water (3000, 4000, 6000, and 7000 mg/l).

When the concentration of feed and brine water is less than 3000 mg/l, mixing is done in equal proportions, regardless of their concentration. It was noted that approximately half of the study period was stabilized at 3000 mg/l as the mixing concentration, while the rest of the time period can be observed in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3. Percentage of the time period of the mixture concentration

Mixture Concentration	Time Period Percentage %
3000	48.0
4000	30.0
6000	1.6
7000	1.6
others	18.8

5.4.2 Effect of Recycling on Recovery

The recycling process significantly increases recovery, as shown in Figure 5.12. The blue and red dots represent the amount of recovery after and before the cycling process, respectively. The resulting increase does not take a specific pattern because the amount of water taken from the brine water is not equal every

time, so a fluctuation occurs in the recovery after recycling and mixing compared to that without recycling. The highest recovery value was recorded on June 8, at 77%, with an increase rate of 34%. On the other hand, the lowest value was recorded at 28%, with a relative increase not exceeding 0.7% on January 8.

Fig. 5.12. Comparison between the recovery before and after recycle (mixing).

5.4.3 Effect of Recycling on Permeate Water Concentration

The concentration of the new feed water after mixing is greater than its counterpart before mixing, so it is natural that the concentration of permeate water after mixing is greater than before (negative effect). Despite this, the new permeate water conforms to international standards for drinking water, as the concentration ranges from 45.19 mg/l to 201.3 mg/l, with an increase rate ranging from 1.1% to 69.4%, respectively (See Figure 5.13).

Fig. 5.13. Comparison between the permeate water concentration before and after recycle (mixing).

5.5 Summary

The two vessels of GARO2 were connected in series to improve the system's performance. The results resulted in improved performance for some variables, while the rest of the variables changed negatively. It can be seen in [Table 5.4](#), which represents the percentage of change in performance, positive and negative, for the variables affected. As for the rest that did not suffer the change, they were not mentioned.

After adding the Air Stripper as a performance improvement unit in the system for the GARO2 treatment plant, it was found that the improvement occurred only in permeate concentration and salt rejection. It was found that the lowest value of the PPI was 24.3% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 2105 mg/l and 33 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.1 m³/h. In other side, the highest value of the PPI was 68.0% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 9948 mg/l and 12°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h. For salt rejection the highest value of the PPI was 3.25% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 9948 mg/l and 38°C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 7.2 m³/h. The lowest value of the PPI was 0.65% at the feed water concentration and temperature of 1063 mg/l and 11 °C, respectively, and the feed flow rate is 13.1 m³/h.

Recycling and mixing led to an increase in recovery by a rate ranging from 28% to 77%, with an increase rate compared to the natural state estimated at 0.7% to 34%, respectively.

In other hand, the concentration of permeate water increased by a rate ranged from 45.19 mg/l to 201.3 mg/l, with an increase rate ranging from 1.1% to 69.4%, respectively.

Table 5.4. Summary of Percentage of Performance Improvement PPI Results by Connect the Vessels Serially.

Details		PPI%	Performance Symbol*	Operation Conditions		
				T (°C)	C _f (mg/l)	Q _f (m ³ /h)
C _p	Max.	40.8		10	4171	13.1
	Min.	5.4		12	2105	7.2
Q _p & r%	Max.	40.5		11	1063	13.1
	Min.	0.7		38	9948	7.2
R%	Max.	2.4		38	9948	7.2
	Min.	0.16		12	2105	7.2
C _c	Max.	51.1		11	1063	13.1
	Min.	4.5		39	8217	7.2
P _f	Max.	11.0		38	8217	7.2
	Min.	40.0		11	1063	13.1

Performance Symbol*

Positively decrease

Positively increase

Negatively decrease

Negatively increase

CHAPTER

6

Conclusions and Recommendations

Chapter Six

Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

The conclusions can be divided into several axes covering the work in this thesis:

6.1.1 Effect of Temperature Rising

The effect of temperature rising can be listed as the following:

- 1- The observed increase in salt passage in RO system at high temperature is due to changes in membrane properties (increased permeability and reduced selectivity) and decrease the water viscosity.
- 2- The rise of β indicates that higher temperatures lead to more solute accumulation at the membrane surface relative to the bulk solution. Elevated temperatures enhance membrane permeability and solvent flux, which can increase the concentration of solutes near the membrane surface, intensifying the concentration polarization effect.
- 3- In other hand, increase K_{cp} is attributed to the reduction in water viscosity and the enhancement of molecular diffusion with temperature. As the temperature rises, the diffusivity of solutes in water increases, leading to improved mass transfer away from the membrane surface and hence a higher K_{cp} .
- 4- An increase in temperature within the range of approximately 11–38°C led to a significant rise in the solute mass flux. This trend was consistent across both low and high feed concentrations, suggesting that temperature

positively influences membrane permeability and mass transfer kinetics in the reverse osmosis (RO) process.

- 5- Higher feed concentrations (e.g., 9948 mg/l) resulted in substantially greater solute flux values compared to lower concentrations (e.g., 1063 mg/l) at comparable temperatures and flow conditions. This highlights the greater osmotic driving force and solute loading associated with more concentrated feeds.
- 6- The relative increase with temperature remained pronounced, indicating that flow rate interacts with temperature effects, possibly by enhancing turbulence and reducing concentration polarization.
- 7- While elevated temperatures enhance water and solute fluxes, they may adversely affect salt rejection efficiency. This trade-off underscores the importance of carefully balancing thermal input in RO operations to optimize productivity while maintaining desired product water quality.
- 8- In all cases, an increase in temperature led to a rise in the permeate water's osmotic pressure. This is attributed to enhanced solute transport through the membrane at higher temperatures, which results from increased diffusion coefficients and membrane permeability.
- 9- Higher feed flow rates significantly mitigated the increase in osmotic pressure with temperature when compared to lower flow rates. This is due to the reduced residence time and enhanced turbulence near the membrane surface, which minimize concentration polarization and result in a lower solute concentration at the membrane interface.
- 10- Systems operating at higher feed concentrations consistently exhibited greater osmotic pressures in the permeate compared to systems with lower concentrations, irrespective of the feed flow rate. This confirms the direct dependence of osmotic pressure on solute content.

- 11- The combination of higher temperatures and lower flow rates leads to more pronounced osmotic pressure buildup in the permeate, especially in high-salinity feeds. Therefore, to maintain membrane performance and delay fouling or scaling, it is advantageous to operate at higher feed flow rates where feasible, particularly in warm operating environments.
- 12- Water flux increased markedly with rising temperature. This is attributed to reduced water viscosity and enhanced diffusivity at elevated temperatures, which facilitate more efficient transport through the membrane matrix.
- 13- The increase in water flux directly translated into higher permeate flow rates across all scenarios. For instance, at a low feed concentration, the permeate flow rose by nearly 78%, while at high concentration, the increase was around 64% at similar flow rates. These results underscore temperature's strong effect on volumetric water production, though the magnitude of increase diminishes slightly with higher salinity.
- 14- Recovery percentages also improved with temperature, reflecting greater system productivity. However, the extent of improvement was influenced by both feed concentration and flow rate. At lower feed flow rates, recovery rose more significantly than at higher feed flow rates, indicating a trade-off between operating conditions and recovery optimization.

6.1.2 Effect Feed Concentration Rising

- 1- Elevated temperatures led to slightly higher osmotic pressures in both feed-concentrate and permeate streams compared to cooler conditions. This is likely due to the increased dissociation and mobility of ions at higher temperatures, contributing to a marginal rise in effective osmotic pressure.
- 2- Changes in feed flow rate had a negligible effect on feed-concentrate osmotic pressure but did appear to moderate the rise in permeate osmotic

pressure. Higher flow rates were associated with slightly lower permeate osmotic pressures at equivalent concentrations and temperatures, indicating better mitigation of concentration polarization due to enhanced mixing and reduced solute accumulation at the membrane surface.

- 3- Among all scenarios, the highest osmotic pressures were recorded at high concentrations, high temperatures, and low flow rates. This highlights the importance of operating conditions in determining osmotic stress on the membrane. Increased osmotic pressure not only requires higher operating pressure to maintain flux but also may increase the risk of membrane fouling and reduce overall energy efficiency.
- 4- When scaling RO systems or adjusting operational parameters, careful consideration must be given to the solute concentration and temperature effects on osmotic pressure. Operating at higher feed flow rates and avoiding high salinity under elevated temperatures can help moderate osmotic pressure buildup and improve membrane performance and longevity.
- 5- It was taken into consideration that the change in the values of polarization concentration C_m is very slight and is hardly noticeable when the values of feed water concentration C_f are constant despite the change in the temperature of the feed water and the feed flow rate.
- 6- Salt rejection efficiency in RO membranes declines with increasing feed water concentration, and this effect is amplified at higher temperatures. Although increasing the feed flow rate can help mitigate concentration polarization to some extent, it cannot fully counteract the decline in membrane performance caused by high salinity and thermal effects. These findings emphasize the need to carefully manage feed water quality and

operational conditions to sustain high rejection rates and ensure product water quality.

- 7- The feed pressure (P_f) required in an RO system increases significantly with rising feed water salinity, primarily due to the elevated osmotic pressure. This effect is more pronounced at lower temperatures and higher flow rates, where additional hydraulic resistance further raises pressure requirements. Therefore, system design and operation must account for salinity-dependent pressure adjustments, especially in applications dealing with high total dissolved solids (TDS) and variable temperature conditions.

6.1.3 Effect Feed Flow Rate Rising

- 1- Increasing the feed flow rate (Q_f) in an RO system reduces the recovery percentage ($r\%$) across different salinity and temperature conditions. Although higher flow may help reduce concentration polarization and membrane fouling, the net effect is reduced permeate production due to insufficient water–membrane contact time. This emphasizes the importance of balancing flow rate with operational targets for recovery and membrane performance. System designers must carefully optimize flow rates based on feed characteristics and desired recovery levels to ensure energy-efficient and cost-effective operation.
- 2- An increase in feed flow rate leads to lower permeate salinity (C_p) and higher salt rejection ($R\%$), due to reduced concentration polarization and enhanced mass transfer at the membrane surface. This effect holds across different feed concentrations and temperatures, although the magnitude of improvement may vary depending on fluid properties and membrane characteristics. These findings highlight the importance of optimizing Q_f to improve RO system performance.

- 3- The concentration polarization factor β decreases with increasing feed flow rate, regardless of feed concentration or temperature. This is due to the improved hydrodynamic conditions and enhanced back-diffusion of solutes from the membrane surface. Reducing β is critical for maintaining membrane performance, preventing fouling, and achieving higher salt rejection.

6.1.4 Long-Term Operation

The GARO2 plant demonstrated robust and adaptable performance over time, with effective handling of variable feed water conditions. While high salinity and turbidity periods required increased operating pressures, the membrane system maintained strong rejection efficiency and reasonable recovery rates. Seasonal adjustments to operating parameters (particularly in response to feed water quality and temperature) proved essential to sustaining long-term operational stability.

6.1.5 The Optimization by Using Gene Expression Programming (GEP)

The initial process involved building and simulating using Winflows 4.04 software. The simulated results were compared with the experimental data obtained from the GARO2 desalination plant to analyze the percentage deviation of various performance parameters. These parameters include the permeate flow rate, water flux, solute mass flux, feed pressure, net driving pressure, permeate water concentration, permeate mass concentration, brine water concentration, brine mass concentration, concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient (C_p), concentration polarization factor (γ), and salt rejection (R). The accuracy of the simulation results was verified by comparing them with the experimental data, with a maximum deviation of $\pm 10\%$.

It was using GEP techniques to optimize RO systems. Variables that exerted the greatest influence on the objective functions, such as the permeate flow rate (Q_p), water flux (J_w), permeate water concentration (C_p), and salt rejection ($R\%$), were identified using IBM SPSS software. Using Genetic Programming, objective functions were developed for key performance indicators. Subsequently, GA was used to determine the optimal values of the independent variables for each objective function.

For the Q_p objective function, the optimal values of T (Temperature), $r\%$ (Recovery rate), Sc (Schmidt number), and K_{cp} (Concentration polarization mass transfer coefficient) were determined to be 20.519°C , 45.01% , $572.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, and $2.456 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}$, respectively. Similarly, for C_p as the objective function, the optimal values of feed concentration (C_f), brine concentration (C_c), feed pressure (P_f), and net driving pressure (NDP) were 1063 mg/l , 1491 mg/l , 21.938 bar , and 16.197 bar , respectively. In contrast, C_m (Concentration polarization), $R\%$ (Salt rejection), $P\%$ (Permeate percentage), and J_s (Mass flux of solute) were determined to be 1436.16 mg/l , 99.4% , 0.5% , and $1315.3 \text{ mg/m}^2\cdot\text{h}$, respectively.

The results of this study yield important conclusions concerning the modeling and optimization of reverse osmosis (RO) desalination systems for the treatment of highly saline water sourced from the Shatt Al-Arab River in southern Iraq. The mathematical models and optimization frameworks developed herein offer a robust foundation for designing cost-effective and technically efficient water treatment strategies tailored to the region's specific environmental conditions. These findings contribute critical insights into the performance enhancement and operational planning of RO desalination plants, highlighting their potential as a sustainable solution for addressing water scarcity and salinity challenges in southern Iraq. Moreover, the outcomes of this research support the

formulation of integrated and economically viable water management policies at the district level.

6.1.6 Improvement the Performance by Connect the Vessels Serially (First Scenario)

The GARO2 system's two vessels were linked in series to increase system performance. As mentioned previously in Table 5.3, which illustrated the percentage change in performance. The results were as follows:

- 1- The concentration of permeate water decreased with a percentage of performance improvement (PPI) rate ranging from 5.4% to 40.8% (Positive effect).
- 2- The permeate water flow rate and recovery increased with a percentage of performance improvement (PPI) rate ranging from 0.7% to 40.5% (Positive effect).
- 3- The salt rejection increased with a slight percentage of performance improvement (PPI) rate ranging from 0.7% to 40.5% (Positive effect).

6.1.7 Improvement the Performance by Adding Air Stripper (Second Scenario)

The integration of an Air Stripper unit into the GARO2 reverse osmosis treatment system demonstrated a measurable performance enhancement, specifically in terms of permeate concentration and salt rejection efficiency. However, the improvement was limited to these parameters, with no significant gains observed in other performance indicators.

These findings suggest that the Air Stripper is most effective under high salinity and moderate-to-high flow conditions, particularly in enhancing permeate quality and overall salt rejection. However, its limited impact on other system

parameters highlights the need for complementary optimization strategies when targeting comprehensive performance improvements.

6.1.8 Improvement the Performance by Recycling and Mixing (Third Scenario)

Recycling and mixing led to an increase in recovery by a rate ranging from 28% to 77%, with an increase rate compared to the natural state estimated at 0.7% to 34%, respectively.

In other hand, the concentration of permeate water increased by a rate ranged from 45.19 mg/l to 201.3 mg/l, with an increase rate ranging from 1.1% to 69.4%, respectively.

6.2 Recommendations

The recommendation of this thesis are as following:

- 1- Using energy recovery devices to recover the wasted energy in the concentrate stream, because of more than 90% of the energy used to pressurize the concentrate stream and the capital expenses may be recovered. In addition to exerting pressure on the feed stream.
- 2- A feasibility study can be conducted on the possibility of developing the GARO2 treatment plant using Artificial Intelligence AI or the Supervisory Control and Data SCADA system to view and diagnose the problems that occur in the treatment plant and change its operating strategy online and without human intervention.
- 3- Study the performance of the GARO2 treatment plant using marine water or groundwater because of their components that greatly affect the performance of the plant. It is even possible to change parts of the plant to suit the new conditions for the purpose of effective treatment.

- 4- Although several scenarios have been used to reduce the environmental impact of the treatment plant, it is necessary to study the environmental impact completely or to use the brine water for agricultural purposes.
- 5- Study the possibility of providing energy to the station by adding turbines or energy savers.
- 6- Add Chillers to optimize temperatures.
- 7- Adding a SCADA program to achieve water mixing to improve the station's performance for the third scenario.

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APPENDIX

AI

*Results of
Experimental Works*

Appendix I

Results of Experimental Works (Operation Conditions in Normal State and Improved State of Plant), Long-Term Operation, and Application of Winflows 4.04

A.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Plant

A.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State of Desalination Plant

A.2.1 Improved State by Connection in Series A.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2

A.2.2 Improved State by using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)

A.3 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO1

A.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2

A.5 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing

A.6 Deviation Percentage %

A.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Plant

Table AI.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Desalination Plant GARO2

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 1063 mg/l																	
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r° %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R° %	Js mg/m ² .h	
					πfc	πp												
11	7.1	27.8	1502.0	15.99	1.0371	0.0225	14.86	1.513	0.0098	2.18	30.7	942.6	2.31E-05	1.125	1443.3	97.4	273.0	
	8.2	23.8	1504.0	16.82	1.0379	0.0192	15.65	1.513	0.0103	2.30	28.0	942.6	2.5E-05	1.122	1439.7	97.8	246.2	
	10.0	19.7	1505.3	18.20	1.0385	0.0159	16.97	1.513	0.0112	2.49	24.9	942.6	2.79E-05	1.118	1436.1	98.1	221.0	
	12.1	18.5	1506.2	19.84	1.0388	0.0150	18.54	1.513	0.0123	2.72	22.5	942.6	3.09E-05	1.117	1434.3	98.3	226.7	
	13.1	16.4	1506.5	20.63	1.0389	0.0133	19.29	1.513	0.0128	2.83	21.6	942.6	3.22E-05	1.116	1434.1	98.5	209.2	
18	7.2	34.7	1500.1	14.90	1.0619	0.0288	13.76	1.230	0.0112	2.48	34.5	783.9	2.37E-05	1.140	1461.0	96.7	388.2	
	8.1	29.0	1502.2	15.43	1.0628	0.0240	14.26	1.230	0.0116	2.57	31.8	783.9	2.54E-05	1.135	1456.3	97.3	336.2	
	10.2	26.7	1503.9	16.68	1.0635	0.0221	15.45	1.230	0.0126	2.79	27.3	783.9	2.88E-05	1.129	1448.5	97.5	335.3	
	12.1	21.6	1505.1	17.83	1.0640	0.0179	16.53	1.230	0.0134	2.98	24.7	783.9	3.16E-05	1.125	1444.8	98.0	290.3	
	13.2	20.5	1505.5	18.49	1.0641	0.0170	17.15	1.230	0.0139	3.10	23.5	783.9	3.32E-05	1.124	1443.4	98.1	285.9	
24	7.0	39.8	1499.0	14.06	1.0833	0.0337	12.91	1.030	0.0125	2.78	39.7	677.7	2.36E-05	1.159	1484.9	96.3	498.8	
	8.1	35.8	1501.2	14.59	1.0843	0.0303	13.40	1.030	0.0130	2.89	35.7	677.7	2.57E-05	1.151	1475.9	96.6	465.9	
	10.2	33.0	1503.0	15.60	1.0850	0.0279	14.36	1.030	0.0139	3.09	30.3	677.7	2.93E-05	1.141	1464.4	96.9	460.1	
	12.2	28.0	1504.0	16.58	1.0854	0.0237	15.27	1.030	0.0148	3.29	27.0	677.7	3.23E-05	1.136	1457.9	97.4	415.2	
	13.1	24.6	1505.0	17.02	1.0859	0.0208	15.68	1.030	0.0152	3.38	25.8	677.7	3.36E-05	1.134	1456.1	97.7	374.6	
31	7.0	53.0	1494.0	13.49	1.1067	0.0459	12.34	0.837	0.0147	3.27	46.7	583.1	2.36E-05	1.189	1520.1	95.0	781.4	
	8.2	50.9	1497.5	13.97	1.1082	0.0441	12.78	0.837	0.0153	3.39	41.3	583.1	2.6E-05	1.177	1506.7	95.2	776.8	
	10.1	40.1	1499.0	14.72	1.1089	0.0347	13.48	0.837	0.0161	3.57	35.4	583.1	2.94E-05	1.164	1491.2	96.2	644.9	
	12.1	36.1	1501.5	15.52	1.1099	0.0313	14.22	0.837	0.0170	3.77	31.1	583.1	3.26E-05	1.156	1481.7	96.6	613.6	
	13.3	31.6	1502.0	16.00	1.1102	0.0274	14.66	0.837	0.0175	3.89	29.2	583.1	3.44E-05	1.152	1477.2	97.0	553.1	
38	7.1	62.1	1491.0	13.09	1.1308	0.0550	11.93	0.681	0.0175	3.89	54.8	508.8	2.37E-05	1.228	1567.9	94.2	1087.7	
	8.1	59.7	1494.0	13.42	1.1322	0.0529	12.23	0.681	0.0180	3.99	49.2	508.8	2.58E-05	1.213	1551.3	94.4	1072.5	
	10.2	49.9	1497.0	14.12	1.1335	0.0441	12.87	0.681	0.0189	4.20	41.1	508.8	2.97E-05	1.193	1527.3	95.3	942.2	
	12.0	43.6	1498.0	14.72	1.1339	0.0386	13.42	0.681	0.0197	4.37	36.5	508.8	3.27E-05	1.182	1513.8	95.9	858.8	
	13.1	43.3	1500.1	15.09	1.1349	0.0383	13.76	0.681	0.0202	4.48	34.2	508.8	3.44E-05	1.177	1508.6	95.9	873.9	

Table AI.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 2105 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
12	7.2	61.2	2971.7	16.68	2.0599	0.0497	14.55	1.469	0.0099	2.20	30.5	916.0	2.34E-05	1.125	2855.4	97.1	606.3
	8.0	60.0	2975.1	17.27	2.0613	0.0487	15.12	1.469	0.0103	2.29	28.6	916.0	2.48E-05	1.122	2850.6	97.2	617.1
	10.1	56.6	2978.3	18.84	2.0626	0.0459	16.62	1.469	0.0113	2.51	24.9	916.0	2.82E-05	1.118	2841.9	97.3	640.0
	12.3	50.4	2980.3	20.51	2.0634	0.0409	18.21	1.469	0.0124	2.75	22.4	916.0	3.13E-05	1.116	2838.5	97.6	624.6
	13.0	48.0	2980.8	21.05	2.0636	0.0390	18.72	1.469	0.0127	2.83	21.8	916.0	3.22E-05	1.116	2838.2	97.7	611.8
17	7.1	76.5	2966.7	15.79	2.0940	0.0632	13.65	1.267	0.0108	2.39	33.7	804.1	2.35E-05	1.136	2880.2	96.4	824.4
	8.1	73.0	2971.9	16.41	2.0961	0.0603	14.24	1.267	0.0112	2.50	30.8	804.1	2.53E-05	1.131	2871.5	96.5	820.8
	10.2	61.9	2975.1	17.72	2.0975	0.0511	15.48	1.267	0.0122	2.71	26.6	804.1	2.88E-05	1.125	2858.0	97.1	756.0
	12.1	58.7	2977.3	18.92	2.0984	0.0485	16.61	1.267	0.0131	2.91	24.1	804.1	3.16E-05	1.122	2851.9	97.2	769.6
	13.0	56.5	2977.7	19.49	2.0985	0.0467	17.15	1.267	0.0135	3.01	23.1	804.1	3.28E-05	1.121	2850.0	97.3	764.8
24	7.1	95.4	2964.0	14.92	2.1434	0.0807	12.75	1.030	0.0124	2.75	38.7	677.7	2.38E-05	1.155	2928.1	95.5	1181.2
	8.1	89.0	2968.4	15.40	2.1452	0.0752	13.20	1.030	0.0128	2.85	35.1	677.7	2.57E-05	1.148	2913.4	95.8	1140.6
	10.1	74.6	2972.2	16.38	2.1469	0.0631	14.12	1.030	0.0137	3.04	30.1	677.7	2.92E-05	1.139	2892.7	96.5	1023.0
	12.1	71.6	2974.8	17.37	2.1479	0.0605	15.04	1.030	0.0146	3.24	26.8	677.7	3.22E-05	1.134	2880.6	96.6	1045.4
	13.1	68.0	2977.0	17.86	2.1489	0.0575	15.50	1.030	0.0151	3.34	25.5	677.7	3.37E-05	1.132	2877.1	96.8	1023.4
33	7.1	112.8	2949.7	14.20	2.2021	0.0983	12.00	0.789	0.0152	3.37	47.5	561.9	2.39E-05	1.193	3016.0	94.6	1714.6
	8.0	102.3	2957.3	14.54	2.2054	0.0891	12.31	0.789	0.0156	3.46	43.3	561.9	2.57E-05	1.184	2995.7	95.1	1595.0
	10.2	87.0	2962.5	15.40	2.2077	0.0758	13.10	0.789	0.0166	3.68	36.1	561.9	2.97E-05	1.168	2959.2	95.9	1444.0
	12.2	77.5	2968.1	16.17	2.2101	0.0675	13.80	0.789	0.0175	3.88	31.8	561.9	3.29E-05	1.159	2940.1	96.3	1354.9
	13.1	73.0	2969.8	16.51	2.2109	0.0636	14.12	0.789	0.0179	3.97	30.3	561.9	3.42E-05	1.156	2933.6	96.5	1305.8
39	7.0	146.3	2945.1	13.80	2.2433	0.1300	11.60	0.661	0.0175	3.90	55.6	497.0	2.36E-05	1.230	3105.3	93.0	2567.7
	8.1	126.5	2951.7	14.17	2.2462	0.1124	11.93	0.661	0.0180	4.01	49.5	497.0	2.59E-05	1.214	3068.6	94.0	2283.2
	10.1	105.1	2957.4	14.84	2.2487	0.0934	12.53	0.661	0.0190	4.21	41.7	497.0	2.96E-05	1.194	3023.2	95.0	1992.7
	12.1	92.7	2961.5	15.51	2.2505	0.0823	13.13	0.661	0.0199	4.41	36.4	497.0	3.30E-05	1.182	2994.6	95.6	1840.4
	13.2	91.3	2966.0	15.87	2.2525	0.0811	13.46	0.661	0.0204	4.52	34.2	497.0	3.47E-05	1.177	2984.8	95.7	1858.8

Table AI.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T) °C	Feed Concentration Cf = 4171 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R %	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _{fp}											
10	7.0	133.7	5881.5	18.47	4.0503	0.1077	14.41	1.558	0.0092	2.05	29.3	969.2	2.29E-05	1.119	5622.3	96.8	1236.3
	8.1	131.2	5890.0	19.38	4.0537	0.1057	15.28	1.558	0.0098	2.18	26.9	969.2	2.48E-05	1.116	5614.1	96.9	1287.3
	10.1	124.7	5898.5	21.03	4.0571	0.1005	16.86	1.558	0.0108	2.40	23.8	969.2	2.80E-05	1.113	5605.9	97.0	1349.9
	12.2	112.5	5902.5	22.78	4.0587	0.0906	18.53	1.558	0.0119	2.64	21.6	969.2	3.09E-05	1.113	5604.5	97.3	1337.8
	13.1	106.0	5903.8	23.54	4.0592	0.0854	19.25	1.558	0.0124	2.74	20.9	969.2	3.21E-05	1.113	5605.6	97.5	1309.6
17	7.1	164.5	5872.4	17.34	4.1467	0.1359	13.22	1.267	0.0104	2.32	32.6	804.1	2.36E-05	1.131	5678.4	96.1	1716.7
	8.2	154.1	5882.5	18.05	4.1509	0.1272	13.89	1.267	0.0110	2.43	29.7	804.1	2.56E-05	1.127	5662.7	96.3	1689.4
	10.2	142.0	5887.3	19.34	4.1529	0.1173	15.11	1.267	0.0119	2.65	26.0	804.1	2.88E-05	1.122	5641.9	96.6	1694.1
	12.1	136.8	5894.7	20.57	4.1559	0.1129	16.27	1.267	0.0128	2.85	23.6	804.1	3.16E-05	1.119	5634.1	96.7	1756.4
	13.1	133.0	5895.9	21.22	4.1564	0.1098	16.88	1.267	0.0133	2.96	22.6	804.1	3.30E-05	1.119	5631.2	96.8	1771.7
23	7.0	210.1	5868.1	16.52	4.2307	0.1771	12.36	1.061	0.0117	2.59	37.0	694.2	2.37E-05	1.146	5754.6	95.0	2448.1
	8.1	194.4	5877.3	17.09	4.2345	0.1638	12.89	1.061	0.0122	2.70	33.3	694.2	2.58E-05	1.140	5727.5	95.3	2361.8
	10.2	163.4	5885.9	18.20	4.2382	0.1377	13.91	1.061	0.0131	2.91	28.5	694.2	2.93E-05	1.132	5693.7	96.1	2143.0
	12.2	156.5	5888.0	19.24	4.2391	0.1319	14.89	1.061	0.0140	3.12	25.5	694.2	3.23E-05	1.128	5673.8	96.2	2196.2
	13.0	152.6	5892.2	19.68	4.2408	0.1286	15.30	1.061	0.0144	3.20	24.6	694.2	3.35E-05	1.127	5671.2	96.3	2200.2
30	7.0	246.0	5843.2	15.91	4.3200	0.2122	11.71	0.863	0.0136	3.01	43.1	593.7	2.38E-05	1.171	5864.9	94.1	3339.6
	8.2	217.7	5858.7	16.43	4.3267	0.1878	12.17	0.863	0.0141	3.13	38.2	593.7	2.62E-05	1.161	5823.5	94.8	3070.7
	10.0	191.0	5868.5	17.20	4.3309	0.1648	12.87	0.863	0.0149	3.31	33.1	593.7	2.94E-05	1.151	5779.8	95.4	2849.4
	12.2	180.1	5880.6	18.15	4.3361	0.1554	13.74	0.863	0.0159	3.54	29.0	593.7	3.29E-05	1.144	5749.8	95.7	2867.7
	13.2	167.9	5884.2	18.59	4.3377	0.1448	14.14	0.863	0.0164	3.64	27.6	593.7	3.43E-05	1.142	5740.7	96.0	2752.0
38	7.1	311.5	5827.1	15.44	4.4269	0.2759	11.20	0.681	0.0165	3.65	51.4	508.8	2.40E-05	1.210	6048.8	92.5	5125.3
	8.2	270.7	5840.9	15.84	4.4330	0.2397	11.53	0.681	0.0169	3.76	45.8	508.8	2.62E-05	1.196	5988.5	93.5	4584.5
	10.1	227.4	5855.0	16.51	4.4393	0.2014	12.12	0.681	0.0178	3.95	39.1	508.8	2.98E-05	1.181	5918.6	94.5	4046.5
	12.0	201.8	5863.5	17.18	4.4430	0.1787	12.71	0.681	0.0187	4.14	34.5	508.8	3.29E-05	1.171	5873.8	95.2	3766.9
	13.3	196.2	5873.5	17.64	4.4475	0.1737	13.12	0.681	0.0193	4.28	32.2	508.8	3.49E-05	1.166	5855.3	95.3	3780.5

Table AI.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 5979 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r°%	Sc m ² /s	Kep	β	Cm mg/l	R°%	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
11	7.1	234.9	8429.7	19.70	5.8259	0.1900	13.95	1.513	0.0092	2.05	28.8	942.6	2.32E-05	1.117	8044.4	96.1	2166.1
	8.0	232.6	8440.0	20.42	5.8301	0.1881	14.64	1.513	0.0097	2.15	26.9	942.6	2.48E-05	1.115	8035.1	96.1	2251.0
	10.2	219.1	8450.3	22.22	5.8343	0.1772	16.35	1.513	0.0108	2.40	23.5	942.6	2.83E-05	1.112	8023.5	96.3	2368.9
	12.1	201.4	8455.4	23.77	5.8363	0.1629	17.82	1.513	0.0118	2.62	21.6	942.6	3.10E-05	1.112	8022.3	96.6	2373.5
	13.0	198.3	8456.2	24.54	5.8366	0.1604	18.56	1.513	0.0123	2.72	21.0	942.6	3.21E-05	1.112	8025.0	96.7	2433.3
18	7.2	281.9	8410.3	18.61	5.9615	0.2336	12.78	1.230	0.0104	2.31	32.0	783.9	2.39E-05	1.128	8118.2	95.3	2928.1
	8.2	273.3	8422.4	19.24	5.9665	0.2265	13.36	1.230	0.0109	2.41	29.4	783.9	2.57E-05	1.125	8098.3	95.4	2969.7
	10.2	246.7	8437.2	20.50	5.9726	0.2044	14.54	1.230	0.0118	2.62	25.7	783.9	2.90E-05	1.120	8073.5	95.9	2917.0
	12.2	240.4	8445.6	21.77	5.9761	0.1992	15.74	1.230	0.0128	2.84	23.3	783.9	3.19E-05	1.118	8062.4	96.0	3075.9
	13.1	229.1	8447.1	22.37	5.9768	0.1898	16.29	1.230	0.0132	2.94	22.4	783.9	3.31E-05	1.117	8060.3	96.2	3034.9
23	7.1	321.1	8401.4	17.92	6.0602	0.2706	12.03	1.061	0.0113	2.52	35.5	694.2	2.40E-05	1.141	8200.5	94.6	3641.3
	8.1	320.4	8414.2	18.46	6.0656	0.2701	12.54	1.061	0.0118	2.62	32.4	694.2	2.58E-05	1.135	8171.6	94.6	3786.1
	10.1	268.5	8432.1	19.52	6.0731	0.2263	13.50	1.061	0.0127	2.82	28.0	694.2	2.92E-05	1.129	8131.8	95.5	3415.1
	12.1	263.2	8438.6	20.59	6.0759	0.2218	14.50	1.061	0.0137	3.03	25.1	694.2	3.23E-05	1.125	8109.3	95.6	3597.0
	13.0	256.3	8444.1	21.08	6.0782	0.2160	14.94	1.061	0.0141	3.13	24.1	694.2	3.35E-05	1.124	8104.3	95.7	3610.6
32	7.0	403.0	8361.9	17.13	6.2273	0.3500	11.16	0.813	0.0137	3.05	43.5	572.5	2.40E-05	1.173	8407.4	93.3	5531.5
	8.3	356.8	8385.0	17.68	6.2373	0.3099	11.63	0.813	0.0143	3.18	38.3	572.5	2.65E-05	1.162	8343.0	94.0	5105.4
	10.2	315.0	8399.8	18.48	6.2437	0.2736	12.34	0.813	0.0152	3.37	33.0	572.5	2.99E-05	1.152	8279.1	94.7	4781.6
	12.1	287.5	8416.2	19.27	6.2509	0.2497	13.05	0.813	0.0161	3.56	29.5	572.5	3.29E-05	1.145	8242.8	95.2	4615.2
	13.0	270.4	8420.8	19.65	6.2529	0.2348	13.38	0.813	0.0165	3.65	28.1	572.5	3.42E-05	1.143	8229.1	95.5	4450.4
38	7.1	497.6	8344.2	16.80	6.3420	0.4407	10.81	0.681	0.0159	3.52	49.6	508.8	2.41E-05	1.201	8598.0	91.7	7899.9
	8.0	443.8	8359.9	17.14	6.3489	0.3930	11.07	0.681	0.0163	3.61	45.1	508.8	2.60E-05	1.190	8530.4	92.6	7216.1
	10.0	373.7	8383.2	17.87	6.3592	0.3309	11.69	0.681	0.0172	3.81	38.1	508.8	2.97E-05	1.174	8431.6	93.8	6415.1
	12.2	328.9	8397.6	18.67	6.3656	0.2913	12.38	0.681	0.0182	4.04	33.1	508.8	3.33E-05	1.164	8365.3	94.5	5982.1
	13.1	325.7	8408.3	18.99	6.3704	0.2884	12.68	0.681	0.0186	4.13	31.5	508.8	3.47E-05	1.161	8350.4	94.6	6063.6

Table AI.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 8217 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	J _{wm} m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
13	7.2	351.2	11571.0	21.09	8.0573	0.2860	13.20	1.426	0.0093	2.06	28.5	892.0	2.36E-05	1.115	11032.0	95.7	3251.8
	8.2	343.7	11588.4	21.85	8.0644	0.2799	13.93	1.426	0.0098	2.17	26.4	892.0	2.54E-05	1.113	11020.6	95.8	3356.8
	10.1	325.6	11602.9	23.31	8.0703	0.2652	15.30	1.426	0.0107	2.38	23.6	892.0	2.84E-05	1.111	11007.7	96.0	3495.1
	12.0	298.0	11616.9	24.79	8.0760	0.2427	16.69	1.426	0.0117	2.60	21.7	892.0	3.11E-05	1.110	11009.9	96.4	3488.5
	13.3	297.7	11621.4	25.80	8.0779	0.2425	17.66	1.426	0.0124	2.75	20.7	892.0	3.28E-05	1.110	11014.9	96.4	3687.3
19	7.0	420.6	11545.8	20.04	8.2159	0.3497	12.06	1.194	0.0101	2.24	32.0	763.8	2.37E-05	1.126	11126.0	94.9	4249.8
	8.2	412.2	11568.0	20.78	8.2251	0.3427	12.76	1.194	0.0107	2.37	28.9	763.8	2.58E-05	1.122	11097.0	95.0	4405.8
	10.1	360.7	11584.5	21.96	8.2320	0.2999	13.84	1.194	0.0116	2.57	25.5	763.8	2.90E-05	1.118	11065.0	95.6	4181.7
	12.2	352.8	11597.3	23.28	8.2373	0.2933	15.08	1.194	0.0126	2.80	23.0	763.8	3.21E-05	1.116	11052.5	95.7	4455.3
	13.2	342.3	11605.8	23.91	8.2408	0.2846	15.67	1.194	0.0131	2.91	22.1	763.8	3.34E-05	1.115	11052.9	95.8	4491.2
26	7.1	498.3	11508.9	19.31	8.3971	0.4243	11.23	0.971	0.0116	2.57	36.2	647.7	2.42E-05	1.142	11264.6	93.9	5765.7
	8.0	491.4	11528.4	19.76	8.4054	0.4183	11.66	0.971	0.0120	2.67	33.3	647.7	2.59E-05	1.137	11229.5	94.0	5899.1
	10.2	400.3	11554.1	20.86	8.4164	0.3408	12.61	0.971	0.0130	2.88	28.3	647.7	2.97E-05	1.129	11163.4	95.1	5200.3
	12.0	384.6	11569.0	21.76	8.4227	0.3274	13.44	0.971	0.0138	3.07	25.6	647.7	3.24E-05	1.126	11137.8	95.3	5322.8
	13.1	381.2	11588.2	22.31	8.4309	0.3245	13.94	0.971	0.0144	3.19	24.3	647.7	3.40E-05	1.124	11134.6	95.4	5474.6
33	7.1	589.3	11478.7	18.78	8.5805	0.5134	10.62	0.789	0.0135	2.99	42.1	561.9	2.43E-05	1.166	11483.9	92.8	7928.5
	8.1	534.4	11511.3	19.22	8.5948	0.4656	10.98	0.789	0.0139	3.09	38.1	561.9	2.63E-05	1.158	11424.7	93.5	7430.5
	10.1	465.5	11534.9	20.07	8.6050	0.4056	11.71	0.789	0.0148	3.29	32.6	561.9	2.99E-05	1.148	11337.6	94.3	6906.3
	12.2	414.1	11560.6	20.95	8.6163	0.3608	12.48	0.789	0.0158	3.51	28.8	561.9	3.32E-05	1.141	11287.4	95.0	6546.0
	13.2	392.1	11569.6	21.37	8.6202	0.3417	12.84	0.789	0.0163	3.61	27.4	561.9	3.47E-05	1.139	11271.1	95.2	6380.5
39	7.2	725.3	11458.8	18.46	8.7400	0.6443	10.27	0.661	0.0155	3.45	47.9	497.0	2.45E-05	1.192	11730.1	91.2	11265.8
	8.0	653.4	11479.5	18.76	8.7492	0.5804	10.49	0.661	0.0159	3.52	44.0	497.0	2.62E-05	1.183	11653.4	92.0	10364.5
	10.2	542.5	11516.4	19.60	8.7655	0.4819	11.16	0.661	0.0169	3.75	36.7	497.0	3.02E-05	1.168	11520.8	93.4	9155.3
	12.1	482.3	11533.8	20.33	8.7733	0.4284	11.78	0.661	0.0178	3.96	32.7	497.0	3.33E-05	1.160	11455.8	94.1	8594.8
	13.1	476.0	11551.8	20.66	8.7813	0.4229	12.07	0.661	0.0183	4.05	30.9	497.0	3.49E-05	1.157	11431.6	94.2	8692.2

Table AI.1 Results of Operation Conditions in Normal State of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)°C	Feed Concentration Cf = 9948 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	J _{wm} m/s	Op m ³ /h	r% r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _{fp}											
12	7.2	483.0	14009.5	22.58	9.7210	0.3920	13.13	1.469	0.0089	1.98	27.6	916.0	2.36E-05	1.111	13308.7	95.1	4317.9
	8.3	471.6	14030.9	23.46	9.7297	0.3827	13.97	1.469	0.0095	2.11	25.4	916.0	2.55E-05	1.109	13299.3	95.3	4485.3
	10.0	453.9	14047.6	24.84	9.7364	0.3683	15.27	1.469	0.0104	2.31	23.1	916.0	2.82E-05	1.108	13293.9	95.4	4719.0
	12.3	415.5	14068.6	26.72	9.7449	0.3372	17.03	1.469	0.0116	2.57	20.9	916.0	3.14E-05	1.108	13305.2	95.8	4819.3
	13.1	411.0	14072.9	27.38	9.7467	0.3335	17.66	1.469	0.0120	2.67	20.4	916.0	3.25E-05	1.108	13312.1	95.9	4942.8
17	7.1	550.2	13985.8	21.68	9.8817	0.4543	12.14	1.267	0.0096	2.13	30.0	804.1	2.38E-05	1.119	13385.3	94.5	5273.2
	8.0	534.1	14010.2	22.29	9.8918	0.4410	12.71	1.267	0.0100	2.23	27.8	804.1	2.54E-05	1.116	13368.8	94.6	5357.5
	10.1	485.3	14028.8	23.71	9.8995	0.4007	14.02	1.267	0.0111	2.46	24.3	804.1	2.88E-05	1.113	13338.2	95.1	5370.9
	12.1	478.6	14044.1	25.07	9.9058	0.3952	15.31	1.267	0.0121	2.68	22.2	804.1	3.17E-05	1.112	13334.6	95.2	5783.6
	13.1	466.3	14048.3	25.76	9.9075	0.3850	15.95	1.267	0.0126	2.79	21.3	804.1	3.31E-05	1.111	13335.4	95.3	5870.1
27	7.0	700.5	13919.2	20.47	10.1940	0.5984	10.78	0.943	0.0114	2.54	36.3	634.2	2.41E-05	1.141	13614.7	93.0	8008.6
	8.1	635.3	13948.6	21.03	10.2066	0.5427	11.25	0.943	0.0119	2.65	32.7	634.2	2.62E-05	1.135	13559.7	93.6	7580.4
	10.3	564.5	13983.8	22.14	10.2216	0.4822	12.22	0.943	0.0130	2.88	27.9	634.2	3.00E-05	1.128	13494.2	94.3	7317.8
	12.1	514.4	14000.0	23.03	10.2286	0.4394	13.01	0.943	0.0138	3.06	25.3	634.2	3.27E-05	1.124	13462.4	94.8	7099.5
	13.1	511.5	14023.1	23.52	10.2384	0.4370	13.46	0.943	0.0143	3.17	24.2	634.2	3.42E-05	1.123	13461.8	94.9	7305.1
33	7.1	792.2	13890.8	20.08	10.3856	0.6903	10.29	0.789	0.0130	2.89	40.8	561.9	2.44E-05	1.160	13824.8	92.0	10327.1
	8.0	729.2	13928.1	20.48	10.4018	0.6353	10.60	0.789	0.0134	2.98	37.3	561.9	2.62E-05	1.153	13765.2	92.7	9795.0
	10.2	633.6	13961.9	21.45	10.4165	0.5520	11.42	0.789	0.0145	3.21	31.5	561.9	3.01E-05	1.143	13662.8	93.6	9169.2
	12.2	552.8	13995.0	22.32	10.4310	0.4817	12.15	0.789	0.0154	3.42	28.0	561.9	3.33E-05	1.137	13613.1	94.4	8507.1
	13.1	547.3	14005.3	22.70	10.4354	0.4769	12.50	0.789	0.0158	3.51	26.8	561.9	3.46E-05	1.136	13600.6	94.5	8664.8
38	7.2	937.9	13875.0	19.80	10.5483	0.8305	9.99	0.681	0.0147	3.26	45.3	508.8	2.46E-05	1.180	14054.6	90.6	13766.0
	8.0	851.0	13896.8	20.14	10.5579	0.7536	10.22	0.681	0.0150	3.33	41.7	508.8	2.63E-05	1.172	13973.4	91.4	12778.1
	10.3	712.2	13945.2	21.05	10.5793	0.6307	10.94	0.681	0.0161	3.57	34.6	508.8	3.05E-05	1.158	13831.7	92.8	11446.9
	12.1	646.4	13963.2	21.75	10.5873	0.5724	11.53	0.681	0.0169	3.76	31.1	508.8	3.34E-05	1.151	13764.5	93.5	10944.1
	13.0	638.4	13985.2	22.09	10.5970	0.5653	11.83	0.681	0.0174	3.86	29.7	508.8	3.47E-05	1.149	13750.2	93.6	11092.7

A.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State of Desalination Plant

A.2.1 Improved State by Connection in Series

Table AI.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (Connect in Series) of Desalination Plant GARO2

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 1063 mg/l																
	Qf m³/h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m³/h	r% r%	Sc m²/s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m².h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
11	7.1	19.0	2157.0	20.15	1.3020	0.0154	18.71	1.513	0.0124	2.75	38.7	942.6	2.25E-05	1.1646	1875.0	98.2	235.0
	8.2	18.4	2183.5	21.78	1.3127	0.0149	20.29	1.513	0.0134	2.98	36.3	942.6	5.89E-04	1.0063	1633.5	98.3	246.8
	10.0	17.2	2204.7	24.21	1.3212	0.0139	22.63	1.513	0.0150	3.32	33.2	942.6	9.28E-04	1.0045	1641.2	98.4	257.3
	12.1	13.9	2231.8	27.08	1.3322	0.0112	25.38	1.513	0.0168	3.73	30.8	942.6	1.26E-03	1.0037	1653.5	98.7	233.2
18	7.2	26.1	2276.4	28.88	1.3502	0.0116	27.10	1.513	0.0179	3.98	30.4	942.6	1.51E-03	1.0033	1675.2	98.7	256.2
	8.1	23.8	2171.0	19.33	1.3279	0.0216	16.74	1.230	0.0136	3.02	42.0	783.9	1.37E-03	1.0028	1607.0	97.5	355.2
	10.2	22.3	2189.7	21.44	1.3476	0.0185	19.86	1.230	0.0161	3.58	35.1	783.9	1.92E-03	1.0023	1630.2	97.9	360.0
	12.1	19.4	2210.3	23.49	1.3561	0.0161	21.81	1.230	0.0177	3.94	32.5	783.9	2.24E-03	1.0022	1640.3	98.2	344.1
24	13.2	15.4	2242.5	24.96	1.3695	0.0128	23.21	1.230	0.0189	4.19	31.7	783.9	2.47E-03	1.0021	1656.3	98.6	290.6
	7.0	30.0	2134.7	16.73	1.3521	0.0254	15.28	1.030	0.0148	3.29	47.1	677.7	1.92E-03	1.0021	1602.3	97.2	445.2
	8.1	25.6	2162.5	17.76	1.3639	0.0216	16.26	1.030	0.0158	3.50	43.3	677.7	2.18E-03	1.0020	1616.0	97.6	404.2
	10.2	24.9	2173.6	19.42	1.3686	0.0211	17.85	1.030	0.0173	3.85	37.7	677.7	2.58E-03	1.0019	1621.3	97.7	431.4
31	12.2	21.1	2192.1	21.10	1.3764	0.0179	19.43	1.030	0.0189	4.19	34.3	677.7	2.96E-03	1.0018	1630.4	98.0	398.7
	13.1	20.1	2219.5	22.13	1.3880	0.0170	20.40	1.030	0.0198	4.40	33.6	677.7	3.17E-03	1.0017	1644.1	98.1	398.2
	7.0	41.5	2130.5	15.65	1.3822	0.0359	14.20	0.837	0.0170	3.76	53.8	583.1	2.36E-03	1.0020	1599.9	96.1	703.5
	8.2	39.6	2152.5	16.59	1.3917	0.0343	15.08	0.837	0.0180	4.00	48.8	583.1	2.67E-03	1.0019	1610.8	96.3	713.3
38	10.1	32.9	2166.4	17.89	1.3977	0.0285	16.31	0.837	0.0195	4.32	42.8	583.1	3.10E-03	1.0017	1617.5	96.9	640.8
	12.1	27.2	2181.1	19.29	1.4041	0.0235	17.63	0.837	0.0210	4.67	38.6	583.1	3.52E-03	1.0017	1624.7	97.4	572.5
	13.3	26.1	2200.8	20.32	1.4126	0.0226	18.60	0.837	0.0222	4.93	37.1	583.1	3.80E-03	1.0016	1634.6	97.5	579.8
	7.1	55.7	2102.4	14.93	1.4016	0.0493	13.47	0.681	0.0198	4.39	61.9	508.8	2.73E-03	1.0020	1585.9	94.8	1101.9
38	8.1	48.7	2111.5	15.64	1.4056	0.0431	14.15	0.681	0.0208	4.61	56.9	508.8	3.03E-03	1.0019	1590.3	95.4	1011.7
	10.2	40.1	2130.6	16.80	1.4140	0.0355	15.23	0.681	0.0224	4.97	48.7	508.8	3.57E-03	1.0017	1599.6	96.2	897.1
	12.0	35.1	2139.1	17.89	1.4178	0.0311	16.25	0.681	0.0239	5.30	44.1	508.8	4.00E-03	1.0017	1603.7	96.7	837.5
	13.1	31.1	2147.3	18.71	1.4214	0.0275	17.02	0.681	0.0250	5.55	42.4	508.8	4.28E-03	1.0016	1607.8	97.1	777.5

Table AI.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (Connect in Series) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 2105 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r [%]	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R [%]	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
12	7.2	57.9	4243.1	20.85	2.5758	0.0470	18.17	1.469	0.0124	2.75	38.2	916.0	3.02E-03	1.0011	3177.7	97.2	716.4
	8.0	49.5	4261.6	22.15	2.5833	0.0402	19.42	1.469	0.0132	2.94	36.7	916.0	3.25E-03	1.0011	3186.9	97.6	654.8
	10.1	42.7	4282.2	24.77	2.5917	0.0347	21.95	1.469	0.0149	3.32	32.8	916.0	3.75E-03	1.0011	3197.1	98.0	638.1
	12.3	38.0	4306.9	27.64	2.6017	0.0308	24.69	1.469	0.0168	3.73	30.3	916.0	4.24E-03	1.0011	3209.5	98.2	638.9
	13.0	34.2	4321.2	29.05	2.6075	0.0278	26.05	1.469	0.0177	3.94	30.3	916.0	4.42E-03	1.0011	3216.7	98.4	606.6
17	7.1	60.3	4226.9	19.11	2.6143	0.0498	16.41	1.267	0.0130	2.88	40.5	804.1	3.33E-03	1.0011	3169.4	97.1	781.2
	8.1	52.4	4243.8	20.31	2.6213	0.0433	17.56	1.267	0.0139	3.08	38.0	804.1	3.63E-03	1.0011	3177.8	97.5	726.4
	10.2	46.7	4255.8	22.41	2.6262	0.0386	19.58	1.267	0.0155	3.43	33.6	804.1	4.19E-03	1.0010	3183.7	97.8	721.7
	12.1	43.7	4269.0	24.45	2.6317	0.0361	21.52	1.267	0.0170	3.77	31.2	804.1	4.66E-03	1.0010	3190.2	97.9	742.4
	13.0	41.4	4287.5	25.73	2.6393	0.0342	22.74	1.267	0.0180	3.99	30.7	804.1	4.89E-03	1.0010	3199.5	98.0	743.2
24	7.1	81.1	4215.6	17.60	2.6726	0.0686	14.88	1.030	0.0144	3.21	45.2	677.7	3.65E-03	1.0011	3163.8	96.1	1171.2
	8.1	77.6	4238.8	18.60	2.6824	0.0656	15.83	1.030	0.0154	3.41	42.1	677.7	3.98E-03	1.0011	3175.3	96.3	1192.4
	10.1	52.8	4246.7	20.23	2.6858	0.0447	17.36	1.030	0.0169	3.74	37.1	677.7	4.57E-03	1.0010	3179.1	97.5	890.2
	12.1	49.1	4262.6	21.93	2.6925	0.0415	18.97	1.030	0.0184	4.09	33.8	677.7	5.11E-03	1.0010	3187.0	97.7	904.5
	13.1	46.6	4273.9	23.05	2.6973	0.0394	20.04	1.030	0.0195	4.32	33.0	677.7	5.38E-03	1.0010	3192.7	97.8	906.6
33	7.1	85.1	4206.0	16.33	2.7494	0.0741	13.54	0.789	0.0172	3.81	53.6	561.9	3.91E-03	1.0012	3159.3	96.0	1460.2
	8.0	80.5	4229.6	17.09	2.7597	0.0701	14.26	0.789	0.0181	4.01	50.1	561.9	4.24E-03	1.0012	3171.0	96.2	1454.6
	10.2	65.7	4239.4	18.47	2.7640	0.0572	15.57	0.789	0.0197	4.38	42.9	561.9	4.96E-03	1.0011	3175.7	96.9	1295.6
	12.2	61.0	4251.1	19.80	2.7691	0.0532	16.81	0.789	0.0213	4.73	38.8	561.9	5.55E-03	1.0011	3181.4	97.1	1299.3
	13.1	55.1	4260.7	20.64	2.7733	0.0480	17.61	0.789	0.0223	4.95	37.8	561.9	5.82E-03	1.0011	3186.2	97.4	1228.9
39	7.0	122.6	4186.8	15.87	2.7948	0.1089	13.08	0.661	0.0198	4.39	62.8	497.0	4.07E-03	1.0014	3150.2	94.2	2426.4
	8.1	95.5	4198.4	16.62	2.8000	0.0848	13.77	0.661	0.0208	4.63	57.1	497.0	4.51E-03	1.0013	3155.7	95.5	1989.6
	10.1	87.3	4220.9	17.74	2.8100	0.0776	14.82	0.661	0.0224	4.98	49.3	497.0	5.22E-03	1.0012	3166.7	95.9	1956.7
	12.1	69.0	4229.0	18.88	2.8136	0.0613	15.87	0.661	0.0240	5.33	44.0	497.0	5.86E-03	1.0011	3170.6	96.7	1656.6
	13.2	63.1	4235.4	19.68	2.8164	0.0561	16.62	0.661	0.0251	5.58	42.3	497.0	6.21E-03	1.0011	3173.8	97.0	1586.7

Table AI.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (Connect in Series) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T) °C	Feed Concentration Cf = 4171 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
10	7.0	111.9	8395.1	22.90	5.0630	0.0902	17.78	1.558	0.0114	2.53	36.2	969.2	4.19E-03	1.0008	6287.8	97.3	1277.0
	8.1	99.0	8427.5	24.66	5.0761	0.0798	19.48	1.558	0.0125	2.78	34.3	969.2	4.58E-03	1.0008	6304.0	97.6	1237.7
	10.1	90.7	8437.5	27.44	5.0801	0.0731	22.16	1.558	0.0142	3.16	31.3	969.2	5.20E-03	1.0008	6309.0	97.8	1290.0
	12.2	84.9	8449.2	30.47	5.0848	0.0684	25.07	1.558	0.0161	3.57	29.3	969.2	5.79E-03	1.0008	6315.0	98.0	1366.4
	13.1	62.7	8462.6	32.25	5.0902	0.0505	26.78	1.558	0.0172	3.82	29.1	969.2	6.05E-03	1.0008	6321.8	98.5	1077.7
17	7.1	135.6	8390.5	20.81	5.1864	0.1120	15.60	1.267	0.0123	2.73	38.5	804.1	4.54E-03	1.0008	6285.5	96.7	1669.9
	8.2	125.4	8400.2	22.16	5.1904	0.1035	16.90	1.267	0.0133	2.96	36.1	804.1	4.95E-03	1.0007	6290.3	97.0	1673.1
	10.2	118.6	8407.1	24.28	5.1932	0.0979	18.93	1.267	0.0149	3.32	32.5	804.1	5.62E-03	1.0007	6293.7	97.2	1772.7
	12.1	103.2	8411.8	26.38	5.1952	0.0852	20.94	1.267	0.0165	3.67	30.3	804.1	6.21E-03	1.0007	6296.1	97.5	1705.7
	13.1	84.3	8419.3	27.79	5.1983	0.0696	22.28	1.267	0.0176	3.90	29.8	804.1	6.52E-03	1.0008	6299.9	98.0	1482.8
23	7.0	158.6	8347.2	19.32	5.2754	0.1337	14.06	1.061	0.0133	2.94	42.0	694.2	4.77E-03	1.0008	6263.9	96.2	2102.6
	8.1	146.7	8385.0	20.46	5.2913	0.1236	15.14	1.061	0.0143	3.17	39.1	694.2	5.21E-03	1.0008	6282.8	96.5	2094.1
	10.2	129.3	8405.1	22.29	5.2998	0.1090	16.88	1.061	0.0159	3.53	34.6	694.2	5.97E-03	1.0007	6292.7	96.9	2056.7
	12.2	118.1	8408.1	24.10	5.3011	0.0995	18.59	1.061	0.0175	3.89	31.9	694.2	6.63E-03	1.0007	6294.1	97.2	2069.5
	13.0	115.1	8414.1	25.19	5.3036	0.0970	19.64	1.061	0.0185	4.11	31.6	694.2	6.89E-03	1.0007	6297.2	97.2	2130.7
30	7.0	200.8	8340.1	18.30	5.3971	0.1732	12.97	0.863	0.0150	3.34	47.7	593.7	5.00E-03	1.0008	6260.8	95.2	3018.7
	8.2	191.8	8366.5	19.30	5.4085	0.1655	13.92	0.863	0.0161	3.58	43.7	593.7	5.52E-03	1.0008	6273.8	95.4	3094.7
	10.0	149.0	8380.2	20.64	5.4144	0.1286	15.16	0.863	0.0176	3.90	39.0	593.7	6.23E-03	1.0008	6280.5	96.4	2618.2
	12.2	135.9	8383.5	22.23	5.4158	0.1173	16.65	0.863	0.0193	4.29	35.1	593.7	7.00E-03	1.0008	6282.1	96.7	2623.2
	13.2	128.7	8402.6	23.24	5.4241	0.1110	17.60	0.863	0.0204	4.53	34.3	593.7	7.35E-03	1.0008	6291.7	96.9	2626.5
38	7.1	271.6	8300.1	17.76	5.5219	0.2405	12.38	0.681	0.0182	4.03	56.8	508.8	5.20E-03	1.0010	6241.6	93.5	4936.5
	8.2	213.5	8333.3	18.57	5.5366	0.1891	13.09	0.681	0.0192	4.27	52.0	508.8	5.72E-03	1.0009	6258.0	94.9	4104.3
	10.1	197.8	8360.9	19.73	5.5488	0.1752	14.17	0.681	0.0208	4.62	45.7	508.8	6.52E-03	1.0009	6271.5	95.3	4115.8
	12.0	171.4	8373.1	20.92	5.5542	0.1518	15.27	0.681	0.0224	4.98	41.5	508.8	7.24E-03	1.0009	6277.4	95.9	3842.4
	13.3	160.5	8387.4	21.87	5.5606	0.1421	16.15	0.681	0.0237	5.27	39.6	508.8	7.71E-03	1.0009	6284.6	96.2	3807.3

Table AI.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (Connect in Series) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 5979 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Op m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
11	7.1	159.9	12071.2	24.23	7.2983	0.1293	16.92	1.513	0.0112	2.48	35.0	942.6	5.22E-03	1.0006	9030.5	97.3	1788.6
	8.0	150.7	12088.3	25.78	7.3052	0.1219	18.42	1.513	0.0122	2.70	33.8	942.6	5.59E-03	1.0006	9039.1	97.5	1835.2
	10.2	146.2	12099.9	28.78	7.3099	0.1182	21.31	1.513	0.0141	3.13	30.7	942.6	6.40E-03	1.0006	9045.0	97.6	2060.0
	12.1	141.5	12113.5	31.56	7.3154	0.1144	23.99	1.513	0.0159	3.52	29.1	942.6	7.04E-03	1.0006	9051.9	97.6	2244.3
	13.0	135.4	12138.7	33.38	7.3256	0.1095	25.75	1.513	0.0170	3.78	29.1	942.6	7.34E-03	1.0006	9064.7	97.7	2304.6
18	7.2	191.5	12009.2	22.15	7.4525	0.1587	14.72	1.230	0.0120	2.66	36.9	783.9	5.56E-03	1.0006	8999.5	96.8	2292.7
	8.2	181.5	12027.1	23.43	7.4600	0.1504	15.95	1.230	0.0130	2.88	35.1	783.9	6.00E-03	1.0006	9008.5	97.0	2353.7
	10.2	176.4	12055.1	25.53	7.4716	0.1462	17.96	1.230	0.0146	3.24	31.8	783.9	6.79E-03	1.0006	9022.4	97.0	2575.8
	12.2	164.3	12060.3	27.70	7.4737	0.1361	20.04	1.230	0.0163	3.62	29.6	783.9	7.51E-03	1.0006	9025.1	97.3	2676.8
	13.1	154.9	12082.4	29.08	7.4829	0.1284	21.35	1.230	0.0174	3.85	29.4	783.9	7.83E-03	1.0006	9036.3	97.4	2688.6
23	7.1	220.7	11962.4	20.79	7.5609	0.1860	13.30	1.061	0.0125	2.78	39.2	694.2	5.77E-03	1.0006	8976.1	96.3	2766.4
	8.1	209.4	11992.1	21.87	7.5734	0.1765	14.32	1.061	0.0135	3.00	37.0	694.2	6.23E-03	1.0006	8991.0	96.5	2827.5
	10.1	202.3	12013.5	23.62	7.5824	0.1705	15.99	1.061	0.0151	3.35	33.1	694.2	7.08E-03	1.0006	9001.6	96.6	3049.7
	12.1	198.7	12050.3	25.43	7.5979	0.1675	17.71	1.061	0.0167	3.71	30.6	694.2	7.84E-03	1.0006	9020.0	96.7	3316.2
	13.0	193.5	12071.8	26.56	7.6070	0.1631	18.77	1.061	0.0177	3.93	30.2	694.2	8.18E-03	1.0006	9030.8	96.8	3424.0
32	7.0	304.2	11940.5	19.53	7.7812	0.2642	11.91	0.813	0.0146	3.25	46.4	572.5	5.95E-03	1.0007	8965.9	94.9	4454.5
	8.3	261.8	11973.7	20.60	7.7957	0.2274	12.89	0.813	0.0159	3.52	42.4	572.5	6.59E-03	1.0007	8982.4	95.6	4150.6
	10.2	238.4	12002.2	21.99	7.8080	0.2070	14.19	0.813	0.0175	3.87	38.0	572.5	7.44E-03	1.0007	8996.5	96.0	4160.5
	12.1	217.5	12018.4	23.42	7.8151	0.1889	15.52	0.813	0.0191	4.24	35.0	572.5	8.22E-03	1.0006	9004.5	96.4	4152.5
	13.0	209.4	12024.9	24.36	7.8179	0.1819	16.42	0.813	0.0202	4.48	34.5	572.5	8.57E-03	1.0007	9007.9	96.5	4229.3
38	7.1	390.5	11889.6	19.15	7.9118	0.3458	11.48	0.681	0.0169	3.74	52.7	508.8	6.15E-03	1.0008	8941.1	93.5	6586.0
	8.0	355.1	11930.2	19.92	7.9298	0.3145	12.18	0.681	0.0179	3.97	49.6	508.8	6.62E-03	1.0008	8961.3	94.1	6351.8
	10.0	269.6	11935.2	21.18	7.9320	0.2387	13.30	0.681	0.0195	4.34	43.4	508.8	7.59E-03	1.0007	8963.5	95.5	5266.9
	12.2	256.6	11991.8	22.54	7.9570	0.2272	14.56	0.681	0.0214	4.75	38.9	508.8	8.54E-03	1.0007	8991.7	95.7	5486.2
	13.1	240.9	12007.1	23.36	7.9638	0.2133	15.32	0.681	0.0225	5.00	38.1	508.8	8.90E-03	1.0007	8999.4	96.0	5420.7

Table AI.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (Connect in Series) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 8217 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
13	7.2	278.1	16522.3	25.73	10.0734	0.2265	15.74	1.426	0.0110	2.45	34.0	892.0	6.14E-03	1.0005	12375.8	96.6	3070.1
	8.2	259.4	16548.2	27.37	10.0840	0.2112	17.32	1.426	0.0121	2.70	32.9	892.0	6.60E-03	1.0005	12388.9	96.8	3150.9
	10.1	245.8	16568.9	29.95	10.0924	0.2002	19.80	1.426	0.0139	3.08	30.5	892.0	7.41E-03	1.0005	12399.4	97.0	3414.0
	12.0	222.3	16588.9	32.66	10.1005	0.1810	22.39	1.426	0.0157	3.49	29.1	892.0	8.14E-03	1.0005	12409.6	97.3	3491.0
	13.3	204.6	16595.4	34.84	10.1032	0.1666	24.48	1.426	0.0172	3.81	28.7	892.0	8.62E-03	1.0006	12413.1	97.5	3512.8
19	7.0	317.4	16487.4	23.64	10.2702	0.2639	13.51	1.194	0.0113	2.51	35.9	763.8	6.33E-03	1.0005	12358.3	96.1	3591.7
	8.2	311.1	16519.1	25.09	10.2834	0.2587	14.91	1.194	0.0125	2.77	33.8	763.8	6.92E-03	1.0005	12374.2	96.2	3883.4
	10.1	294.3	16521.3	27.13	10.2843	0.2447	16.85	1.194	0.0141	3.13	31.0	763.8	7.78E-03	1.0005	12375.4	96.4	4154.0
	12.2	276.2	16561.0	29.39	10.3008	0.2296	18.99	1.194	0.0159	3.53	28.9	763.8	8.63E-03	1.0005	12395.3	96.6	4393.8
	13.2	251.3	16590.3	30.85	10.3130	0.2089	20.37	1.194	0.0171	3.79	28.7	763.8	9.02E-03	1.0005	12410.2	96.9	4287.5
26	7.1	362.2	16434.7	22.20	10.4940	0.3084	11.90	0.971	0.0123	2.72	38.3	647.7	6.66E-03	1.0005	12332.2	95.6	4440.0
	8.0	346.7	16470.5	23.22	10.5092	0.2952	12.87	0.971	0.0133	2.94	36.8	647.7	7.13E-03	1.0005	12350.1	95.8	4594.5
	10.2	309.8	16499.2	25.04	10.5215	0.2638	14.57	0.971	0.0150	3.33	32.7	647.7	8.18E-03	1.0005	12364.4	96.2	4648.0
	12.0	299.8	16520.5	26.66	10.5305	0.2552	16.10	0.971	0.0166	3.68	30.7	647.7	8.96E-03	1.0005	12375.1	96.4	4972.7
	13.1	281.6	16582.8	27.89	10.5571	0.2397	17.24	0.971	0.0178	3.94	30.1	647.7	9.41E-03	1.0005	12406.4	96.6	5001.7
33	7.1	444.1	16273.5	21.22	10.6695	0.3870	10.84	0.789	0.0137	3.05	42.9	561.9	6.87E-03	1.0006	12252.0	94.6	6095.8
	8.1	426.3	16426.9	22.20	10.7363	0.3714	11.70	0.789	0.0148	3.29	40.6	561.9	7.42E-03	1.0006	12328.8	94.8	6319.0
	10.1	349.0	16491.7	23.69	10.7645	0.3041	13.03	0.789	0.0165	3.67	36.3	561.9	8.42E-03	1.0005	12361.1	95.8	5762.8
	12.2	313.5	16508.5	25.25	10.7719	0.2732	14.48	0.789	0.0183	4.07	33.4	561.9	9.37E-03	1.0005	12369.5	96.2	5752.5
	13.2	291.1	16559.6	26.29	10.7941	0.2536	15.44	0.789	0.0196	4.34	32.9	561.9	9.80E-03	1.0006	12395.2	96.5	5693.9
39	7.2	558.3	16101.1	20.67	10.8021	0.4960	10.26	0.661	0.0155	3.45	47.9	497.0	7.10E-03	1.0006	12166.4	93.2	8666.8
	8.0	527.1	16407.4	21.44	10.9381	0.4683	10.85	0.661	0.0164	3.64	45.5	497.0	7.57E-03	1.0006	12319.6	93.6	8646.6
	10.2	447.1	16445.4	22.83	10.9550	0.3972	12.09	0.661	0.0183	4.06	39.8	497.0	8.73E-03	1.0006	12338.4	94.6	8177.0
	12.1	384.8	16470.2	24.15	10.9660	0.3419	13.28	0.661	0.0201	4.46	36.8	497.0	9.63E-03	1.0006	12350.8	95.3	7727.6
	13.1	354.6	16495.9	25.00	10.9775	0.3150	14.06	0.661	0.0213	4.72	36.0	497.0	1.01E-02	1.0006	12363.7	95.7	7540.6

Table AI.2 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (Connect in Series) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 9948 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r°%	Sc m ³ /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R°%	Js mg/m ² .h
					πfc	πp											
12	7.2	375.1	19993.0	27.32	12.1488	0.3044	15.33	1.469	0.0104	2.32	32.2	916.0	6.87E-03	1.0004	14976.8	96.2	3915.4
	8.3	358.7	19993.6	29.15	12.1491	0.2911	17.11	1.469	0.0117	2.59	31.2	916.0	7.42E-03	1.0004	14977.3	96.4	4178.9
	10.0	322.6	20076.8	31.67	12.1828	0.2618	19.49	1.469	0.0133	2.95	29.5	916.0	8.22E-03	1.0004	15019.1	96.8	4281.8
	12.3	309.5	20089.9	34.93	12.1881	0.2512	22.63	1.469	0.0154	3.42	27.8	916.0	9.19E-03	1.0005	15026.0	96.9	4770.4
	13.1	287.6	20020.6	36.69	12.1600	0.2334	24.36	1.469	0.0166	3.68	28.1	916.0	9.50E-03	1.0005	14991.6	97.1	4769.9
17	7.1	436.7	19937.6	25.36	12.3391	0.3606	13.26	1.267	0.0105	2.32	32.7	804.1	7.10E-03	1.0004	14948.9	95.6	4570.2
	8.0	403.6	19947.2	26.69	12.3431	0.3333	14.53	1.267	0.0115	2.55	31.8	804.1	7.58E-03	1.0004	14953.9	95.9	4627.9
	10.1	346.5	20033.1	29.05	12.3785	0.2861	16.72	1.267	0.0132	2.93	29.0	804.1	8.62E-03	1.0004	14996.9	96.5	4573.1
	12.1	339.8	20019.0	31.40	12.3727	0.2806	18.99	1.267	0.0150	3.33	27.5	804.1	9.50E-03	1.0004	14990.1	96.6	5094.8
	13.1	324.5	19846.0	32.97	12.3013	0.2680	20.57	1.267	0.0162	3.60	27.5	804.1	9.92E-03	1.0005	14903.8	96.7	5268.9
27	7.0	511.8	19876.5	23.33	12.7385	0.4372	10.92	0.943	0.0116	2.57	36.7	634.2	7.38E-03	1.0004	14918.8	94.9	5930.3
	8.1	503.4	19918.5	24.50	12.7564	0.4300	12.03	0.943	0.0128	2.83	35.0	634.2	8.01E-03	1.0004	14939.9	94.9	6427.3
	10.3	439.3	19968.8	26.34	12.7779	0.3753	13.73	0.943	0.0146	3.23	31.4	634.2	9.16E-03	1.0004	14965.0	95.6	6398.6
	12.1	388.4	19962.0	27.98	12.7750	0.3318	15.26	0.943	0.0162	3.59	29.7	634.2	1.00E-02	1.0004	14961.7	96.1	6286.1
	13.1	358.6	19807.3	29.17	12.7089	0.3063	16.44	0.943	0.0174	3.87	29.6	634.2	1.04E-02	1.0005	14884.6	96.4	6255.5
33	7.1	598.3	19836.1	22.49	12.9757	0.5213	9.93	0.789	0.0126	2.79	39.3	561.9	7.67E-03	1.0005	14898.8	94.0	7525.9
	8.0	550.5	19861.9	23.45	12.9869	0.4797	10.82	0.789	0.0137	3.04	38.0	561.9	8.19E-03	1.0005	14911.9	94.5	7543.3
	10.2	481.7	19905.0	25.10	13.0057	0.4197	12.32	0.789	0.0156	3.47	34.0	561.9	9.40E-03	1.0005	14933.4	95.2	7519.3
	12.2	437.6	19947.2	26.67	13.0241	0.3813	13.76	0.789	0.0174	3.87	31.7	561.9	1.04E-02	1.0005	14954.6	95.6	7629.8
	13.1	401.5	19735.4	27.70	12.9318	0.3498	14.82	0.789	0.0188	4.17	31.8	561.9	1.08E-02	1.0005	14848.9	96.0	7535.1
38	7.2	715.2	19731.0	21.98	13.1411	0.6333	9.37	0.681	0.0138	3.06	42.4	508.8	7.91E-03	1.0005	14846.7	92.8	9844.7
	8.0	694.8	19844.6	22.80	13.1914	0.6153	10.11	0.681	0.0148	3.29	41.2	508.8	8.39E-03	1.0005	14903.6	93.0	10312.3
	10.3	517.3	19851.8	24.31	13.1946	0.4581	11.39	0.681	0.0167	3.71	36.1	508.8	9.70E-03	1.0005	14907.0	94.8	8656.0
	12.1	488.8	19939.4	25.61	13.2334	0.4329	12.57	0.681	0.0185	4.10	33.9	508.8	1.06E-02	1.0005	14950.9	95.1	9021.4
	13.0	450.5	19692.6	26.51	13.1241	0.3989	13.51	0.681	0.0198	4.41	33.9	508.8	1.10E-02	1.0005	14827.7	95.5	8939.1

A.2.2 Improved State by using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)

Table AI.3 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)) of Desalination Plant GARO2

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 1063 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	J _{wm} m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r°%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R°%	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _{tp}											
11	7.1	16.7	1503.1	15.99	1.0376	0.0135	14.85	1.513	0.0098	2.18	30.7	942.6	2.31E-05	1.1253	1443.8	98.4	164.2
	8.2	14.7	1503.2	16.82	1.0376	0.0119	15.64	1.513	0.0103	2.30	28.0	942.6	6.04E-04	1.0048	1289.2	98.6	151.7
	10.0	12.2	1504.3	18.20	1.0381	0.0099	16.97	1.513	0.0112	2.49	24.9	942.6	9.51E-04	1.0033	1287.9	98.8	137.2
	12.1	10.3	1505.2	19.84	1.0384	0.0083	18.53	1.513	0.0123	2.72	22.5	942.6	1.29E-03	1.0026	1287.5	99.0	125.9
18	13.1	9.6	1505.3	20.63	1.0385	0.0077	19.29	1.513	0.0127	2.83	21.6	942.6	1.55E-03	1.0023	1287.1	99.1	122.0
	7.2	21.9	1500.6	14.90	1.0621	0.0182	13.75	1.230	0.0112	2.48	34.5	783.9	1.40E-03	1.0022	1284.6	97.9	244.9
	8.1	19.6	1501.5	15.43	1.0625	0.0163	14.25	1.230	0.0116	2.57	31.8	783.9	1.62E-03	1.0020	1284.8	98.2	227.6
	10.2	15.9	1503.3	16.68	1.0632	0.0131	15.44	1.230	0.0126	2.79	27.3	783.9	1.97E-03	1.0018	1285.4	98.5	199.1
24	12.1	13.6	1504.4	17.83	1.0637	0.0112	16.52	1.230	0.0134	2.98	24.6	783.9	2.29E-03	1.0016	1285.8	98.7	182.0
	13.2	12.5	1503.9	18.49	1.0635	0.0104	17.14	1.230	0.0139	3.09	23.4	783.9	2.53E-03	1.0015	1285.4	98.8	174.7
	7.0	28.4	1497.7	14.06	1.0828	0.0240	12.90	1.030	0.0125	2.78	39.7	677.7	1.97E-03	1.0018	1282.6	97.3	355.6
	8.1	24.8	1499.2	14.59	1.0834	0.0210	13.40	1.030	0.0130	2.89	35.6	677.7	2.23E-03	1.0016	1283.2	97.7	322.3
31	10.2	20.0	1501.2	15.60	1.0843	0.0169	14.35	1.030	0.0139	3.09	30.3	677.7	2.64E-03	1.0015	1284.0	98.1	278.6
	12.2	16.9	1502.7	16.58	1.0849	0.0143	15.26	1.030	0.0148	3.29	27.0	677.7	3.02E-03	1.0014	1284.6	98.4	251.0
	13.1	15.9	1503.2	17.02	1.0851	0.0134	15.68	1.030	0.0152	3.38	25.8	677.7	3.24E-03	1.0013	1284.7	98.5	241.4
	7.0	36.9	1493.9	13.49	1.1067	0.0319	12.32	0.837	0.0147	3.27	46.7	583.1	2.42E-03	1.0017	1280.6	96.5	542.4
38	8.2	31.8	1496.1	13.97	1.1076	0.0275	12.77	0.837	0.0152	3.38	41.3	583.1	2.74E-03	1.0015	1281.5	97.0	484.9
	10.1	26.2	1498.4	14.72	1.1086	0.0227	13.47	0.837	0.0161	3.57	35.3	583.1	3.17E-03	1.0014	1282.5	97.5	421.3
	12.1	22.1	1500.1	15.52	1.1093	0.0192	14.21	0.837	0.0170	3.77	31.1	583.1	3.61E-03	1.0013	1283.2	97.9	375.6
	13.3	20.3	1500.5	16.00	1.1095	0.0176	14.65	0.837	0.0175	3.88	29.2	583.1	3.89E-03	1.0012	1283.4	98.1	354.9
38	7.1	46.7	1489.1	13.09	1.1300	0.0413	11.91	0.681	0.0175	3.88	54.7	508.8	2.80E-03	1.0017	1278.3	95.6	816.7
	8.1	41.3	1491.9	13.42	1.1312	0.0366	12.22	0.681	0.0179	3.98	49.2	508.8	3.11E-03	1.0016	1279.5	96.1	741.0
	10.2	33.3	1495.2	14.12	1.1327	0.0295	12.86	0.681	0.0189	4.19	41.1	508.8	3.65E-03	1.0014	1280.9	96.9	629.3
	12.0	28.6	1497.2	14.72	1.1336	0.0254	13.41	0.681	0.0197	4.37	36.4	508.8	4.10E-03	1.0013	1281.8	97.3	564.0
13.1	26.4	1498.1	15.09	1.1340	0.0234	13.74	0.681	0.0202	4.48	34.2	508.8	4.39E-03	1.0013	1282.2	97.5	532.8	

Table AI.3 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 2105 mg/l																
	Of m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
12	7.2	37.4	2972.5	16.68	2.0603	0.0304	14.53	1.469	0.0099	2.20	30.5	916.0	3.09E-03	1.0009	2541.0	98.2	370.0
	8.0	33.9	2974.0	17.27	2.0608	0.0275	15.10	1.469	0.0103	2.28	28.5	916.0	3.33E-03	1.0009	2541.7	98.4	348.4
	10.1	27.3	2976.7	18.84	2.0619	0.0221	16.59	1.469	0.0113	2.51	24.8	916.0	3.84E-03	1.0008	2542.9	98.7	308.1
	12.3	22.7	2978.6	20.51	2.0627	0.0184	18.19	1.469	0.0124	2.75	22.4	916.0	4.33E-03	1.0008	2543.8	98.9	281.4
	13.0	21.6	2979.1	21.05	2.0629	0.0175	18.70	1.469	0.0127	2.83	21.7	916.0	4.53E-03	1.0008	2544.0	99.0	274.8
17	7.1	46.4	2968.0	15.79	2.0945	0.0383	13.63	1.267	0.0108	2.39	33.6	804.1	3.40E-03	1.0009	2538.7	97.8	499.4
	8.1	41.0	2970.9	16.41	2.0957	0.0339	14.21	1.267	0.0112	2.49	30.7	804.1	3.71E-03	1.0008	2540.1	98.1	460.2
	10.2	33.1	2974.2	17.72	2.0971	0.0273	15.45	1.267	0.0122	2.71	26.5	804.1	4.28E-03	1.0008	2541.6	98.4	403.4
	12.1	28.2	2976.2	18.92	2.0979	0.0233	16.58	1.267	0.0131	2.91	24.0	804.1	4.75E-03	1.0008	2542.6	98.7	369.2
	13.0	26.4	2977.0	19.49	2.0982	0.0218	17.12	1.267	0.0135	3.00	23.1	804.1	5.00E-03	1.0008	2542.9	98.7	356.6
24	7.1	61.1	2961.6	14.92	2.1424	0.0517	12.72	1.030	0.0124	2.74	38.6	677.7	3.72E-03	1.0009	2535.7	97.1	754.7
	8.1	54.0	2964.6	15.40	2.1437	0.0457	13.18	1.030	0.0128	2.84	35.1	677.7	4.07E-03	1.0009	2537.0	97.4	690.7
	10.1	43.9	2968.9	16.38	2.1455	0.0371	14.09	1.030	0.0137	3.04	30.1	677.7	4.66E-03	1.0008	2539.0	97.9	600.4
	12.1	37.0	2972.4	17.37	2.1470	0.0313	15.01	1.030	0.0146	3.24	26.7	677.7	5.21E-03	1.0008	2540.7	98.2	539.9
	13.1	34.4	2973.5	17.86	2.1474	0.0291	15.47	1.030	0.0150	3.34	25.5	677.7	5.50E-03	1.0008	2541.2	98.4	516.7
33	7.1	85.4	2949.8	14.20	2.2021	0.0744	11.98	0.789	0.0152	3.37	47.4	561.9	3.99E-03	1.0011	2530.0	95.9	1295.9
	8.0	76.4	2954.5	14.54	2.2042	0.0666	12.29	0.789	0.0156	3.46	43.2	561.9	4.34E-03	1.0010	2532.3	96.4	1189.2
	10.2	60.8	2961.5	15.40	2.2072	0.0530	13.07	0.789	0.0166	3.68	36.0	561.9	5.06E-03	1.0009	2535.5	97.1	1007.6
	12.2	51.4	2965.5	16.17	2.2090	0.0448	13.78	0.789	0.0175	3.87	31.8	561.9	5.67E-03	1.0009	2537.4	97.6	897.7
	13.1	48.1	2966.9	16.51	2.2096	0.0419	14.10	0.789	0.0179	3.96	30.3	561.9	5.95E-03	1.0008	2538.1	97.7	859.1
39	7.0	106.9	2941.6	13.80	2.2417	0.0950	11.57	0.661	0.0175	3.88	55.5	497.0	4.18E-03	1.0012	2526.2	94.9	1870.5
	8.1	93.4	2947.4	14.17	2.2443	0.0829	11.90	0.661	0.0180	4.00	49.3	497.0	4.63E-03	1.0011	2528.9	95.6	1680.8
	10.1	76.1	2953.8	14.84	2.2471	0.0676	12.51	0.661	0.0189	4.20	41.6	497.0	5.35E-03	1.0010	2531.9	96.4	1438.9
	12.1	64.2	2959.9	15.51	2.2498	0.0570	13.10	0.661	0.0198	4.40	36.4	497.0	6.00E-03	1.0009	2534.8	97.0	1272.4
	13.2	59.6	2961.9	15.84	2.2507	0.0529	13.40	0.661	0.0203	4.50	34.1	497.0	6.37E-03	1.0009	2535.7	97.2	1208.0

Table AI.3 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 4171 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
					πfc	πp											
10	7.0	78.3	5882.7	18.47	4.0508	0.0631	14.36	1.558	0.0092	2.05	29.2	969.2	4.28E-03	1.0006	5029.9	98.1	721.6
	8.1	68.3	5887.3	19.38	4.0526	0.0550	15.23	1.558	0.0098	2.17	26.8	969.2	4.68E-03	1.0006	5032.1	98.4	667.6
	10.1	55.5	5894.9	21.03	4.0556	0.0447	16.80	1.558	0.0108	2.39	23.7	969.2	5.31E-03	1.0006	5035.8	98.7	598.5
	12.2	46.5	5898.7	22.78	4.0572	0.0375	18.48	1.558	0.0119	2.63	21.6	969.2	5.92E-03	1.0006	5037.6	98.9	551.7
	13.1	43.5	5900.0	23.54	4.0577	0.0351	19.20	1.558	0.0123	2.74	20.9	969.2	6.20E-03	1.0006	5038.3	99.0	536.5
17	7.1	102.9	5874.3	17.34	4.1475	0.0849	13.17	1.267	0.0104	2.31	32.5	804.1	4.62E-03	1.0006	5025.8	97.5	1069.1
	8.2	89.8	5879.8	18.05	4.1498	0.0742	13.84	1.267	0.0109	2.42	29.6	804.1	5.05E-03	1.0006	5028.4	97.8	981.1
	10.2	73.2	5884.9	19.34	4.1518	0.0604	15.06	1.267	0.0119	2.64	25.9	804.1	5.73E-03	1.0006	5030.8	98.2	870.0
	12.1	62.3	5891.8	20.57	4.1547	0.0515	16.21	1.267	0.0128	2.84	23.5	804.1	6.33E-03	1.0006	5034.2	98.5	797.1
	13.1	57.8	5893.7	21.21	4.1555	0.0478	16.82	1.267	0.0133	2.95	22.5	804.1	6.65E-03	1.0006	5035.1	98.6	767.6
23	7.0	132.1	5862.5	16.52	4.2283	0.1113	12.30	1.061	0.0116	2.57	36.8	694.2	4.85E-03	1.0007	5020.1	96.8	1530.8
	8.1	115.1	5869.0	17.09	4.2310	0.0970	12.83	1.061	0.0121	2.68	33.1	694.2	5.31E-03	1.0006	5023.2	97.2	1391.9
	10.2	92.7	5878.5	18.20	4.2351	0.0781	13.86	1.061	0.0131	2.90	28.4	694.2	6.08E-03	1.0006	5027.7	97.8	1210.0
	12.2	78.3	5882.5	19.24	4.2367	0.0660	14.82	1.061	0.0140	3.10	25.4	694.2	6.76E-03	1.0006	5029.6	98.1	1094.1
	13.0	73.8	5884.5	19.68	4.2376	0.0622	15.23	1.061	0.0144	3.19	24.5	694.2	7.04E-03	1.0006	5030.6	98.2	1059.5
30	7.0	172.1	5842.4	15.91	4.3196	0.1485	11.65	0.863	0.0135	3.00	42.8	593.7	5.08E-03	1.0007	5010.4	95.9	2323.9
	8.2	148.4	5852.2	16.43	4.3239	0.1280	12.11	0.863	0.0140	3.12	38.0	593.7	5.62E-03	1.0007	5015.1	96.4	2083.5
	10.0	123.1	5865.6	17.20	4.3296	0.1062	12.81	0.863	0.0149	3.30	33.0	593.7	6.34E-03	1.0007	5021.6	97.0	1827.9
	12.2	102.1	5874.4	18.14	4.3335	0.0880	13.67	0.863	0.0158	3.52	28.8	593.7	7.14E-03	1.0006	5025.8	97.6	1617.3
	13.2	94.7	5877.5	18.59	4.3348	0.0817	14.08	0.863	0.0163	3.62	27.5	593.7	7.50E-03	1.0006	5027.3	97.7	1546.3
38	7.1	226.3	5819.7	15.44	4.4236	0.2004	11.13	0.681	0.0163	3.63	51.1	508.8	5.30E-03	1.0009	4999.6	94.6	3698.2
	8.2	197.9	5831.9	15.84	4.4290	0.1753	11.47	0.681	0.0168	3.74	45.6	508.8	5.84E-03	1.0008	5005.4	95.3	3334.2
	10.1	162.9	5847.4	16.51	4.4359	0.1443	12.06	0.681	0.0177	3.93	38.9	508.8	6.66E-03	1.0007	5012.9	96.1	2885.5
	12.0	138.5	5859.8	17.18	4.4414	0.1227	12.66	0.681	0.0186	4.13	34.4	508.8	7.40E-03	1.0007	5018.9	96.7	2574.5
	13.3	125.8	5865.2	17.64	4.4438	0.1114	13.06	0.681	0.0192	4.26	32.0	508.8	7.89E-03	1.0007	5021.5	97.0	2412.5

Table AI.3 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 5979 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
					π _{fc}	π _p											
11	7.1	122.9	8430.8	19.70	5.8264	0.0994	13.86	1.513	0.0092	2.03	28.6	942.6	5.32E-03	1.0005	7208.3	97.9	1125.9
	8.0	109.8	8436.3	20.42	5.8286	0.0888	14.54	1.513	0.0096	2.13	26.7	942.6	5.71E-03	1.0005	7211.0	98.2	1055.8
	10.2	87.4	8445.7	22.22	5.8324	0.0707	16.25	1.513	0.0107	2.38	23.4	942.6	6.54E-03	1.0005	7215.6	98.5	939.0
	12.1	74.5	8450.6	23.77	5.8344	0.0602	17.72	1.513	0.0117	2.60	21.5	942.6	7.20E-03	1.0005	7218.1	98.8	872.7
	13.0	69.7	8450.3	24.54	5.8343	0.0564	18.46	1.513	0.0122	2.71	20.8	942.6	7.52E-03	1.0005	7217.9	98.8	850.5
18	7.2	161.5	8411.1	18.61	5.9618	0.1338	12.67	1.230	0.0103	2.29	31.8	783.9	5.65E-03	1.0005	7198.7	97.3	1664.2
	8.2	142.9	8418.5	19.24	5.9649	0.1184	13.26	1.230	0.0108	2.39	29.2	783.9	6.11E-03	1.0005	7202.3	97.6	1539.9
	10.2	116.2	8433.5	20.50	5.9711	0.0963	14.43	1.230	0.0117	2.61	25.5	783.9	6.92E-03	1.0005	7209.6	98.1	1363.7
	12.2	98.2	8441.5	21.77	5.9744	0.0813	15.62	1.230	0.0127	2.82	23.1	783.9	7.66E-03	1.0005	7213.6	98.4	1246.6
	13.1	91.8	8443.7	22.36	5.9754	0.0761	16.18	1.230	0.0132	2.92	22.3	783.9	7.99E-03	1.0005	7214.7	98.5	1207.6
23	7.1	199.3	8394.8	17.92	6.0574	0.1680	11.93	1.061	0.0112	2.50	35.2	694.2	5.84E-03	1.0005	7190.8	96.7	2241.0
	8.1	176.0	8404.9	18.46	6.0617	0.1483	12.42	1.061	0.0117	2.60	32.1	694.2	6.33E-03	1.0005	7195.6	97.1	2059.8
	10.1	142.8	8423.7	19.52	6.0696	0.1204	13.39	1.061	0.0126	2.80	27.7	694.2	7.19E-03	1.0005	7204.8	97.6	1802.9
	12.1	120.4	8432.0	20.59	6.0731	0.1015	14.38	1.061	0.0136	3.01	24.9	694.2	7.97E-03	1.0005	7208.9	98.0	1632.5
	13.0	112.6	8435.3	21.07	6.0745	0.0949	14.83	1.061	0.0140	3.10	23.9	694.2	8.33E-03	1.0005	7210.5	98.1	1573.0
32	7.0	283.2	8360.8	17.13	6.2268	0.2459	11.06	0.813	0.0136	3.02	43.1	572.5	6.01E-03	1.0006	7174.4	95.3	3850.3
	8.3	241.5	8378.3	17.68	6.2344	0.2098	11.54	0.813	0.0142	3.15	37.9	572.5	6.68E-03	1.0006	7182.9	96.0	3426.6
	10.2	199.0	8396.6	18.48	6.2424	0.1728	12.24	0.813	0.0151	3.34	32.8	572.5	7.56E-03	1.0006	7191.8	96.7	2996.1
	12.1	169.4	8409.9	19.27	6.2481	0.1471	12.95	0.813	0.0159	3.54	29.2	572.5	8.36E-03	1.0005	7198.3	97.2	2698.4
	13.0	158.3	8414.0	19.65	6.2499	0.1375	13.29	0.813	0.0163	3.63	27.9	572.5	8.74E-03	1.0005	7200.2	97.4	2587.7
38	7.1	345.8	8336.9	16.80	6.3387	0.3062	10.68	0.681	0.0157	3.48	49.0	508.8	6.22E-03	1.0007	7163.0	94.2	5422.2
	8.0	309.8	8351.1	17.14	6.3450	0.2743	10.96	0.681	0.0161	3.57	44.7	508.8	6.73E-03	1.0007	7169.8	94.8	4984.6
	10.0	251.7	8375.7	17.87	6.3559	0.2229	11.58	0.681	0.0170	3.78	37.8	508.8	7.72E-03	1.0006	7181.8	95.8	4281.4
	12.2	208.9	8394.1	18.67	6.3641	0.1850	12.28	0.681	0.0180	4.00	32.8	508.8	8.70E-03	1.0006	7190.7	96.5	3766.2
	13.1	195.4	8400.2	18.99	6.3668	0.1730	12.56	0.681	0.0185	4.10	31.3	508.8	9.09E-03	1.0006	7193.6	96.7	3604.3

Table A.I.3 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 8217 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r°%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R°%	Js mg/m ² .h
					πfc	πp											
13	7.2	192.1	11571.9	21.09	8.0577	0.1564	13.07	1.426	0.0092	2.04	28.3	892.0	6.24E-03	1.0004	9898.5	97.7	1760.6
	8.2	169.9	11581.6	21.85	8.0616	0.1383	13.78	1.426	0.0097	2.15	26.2	892.0	6.73E-03	1.0004	9903.2	97.9	1642.3
	10.1	139.6	11594.3	23.31	8.0668	0.1137	15.15	1.426	0.0106	2.36	23.4	892.0	7.56E-03	1.0004	9909.5	98.3	1483.3
	12.0	118.6	11607.9	24.79	8.0724	0.0966	16.55	1.426	0.0116	2.58	21.5	892.0	8.32E-03	1.0004	9916.3	98.6	1376.3
	13.3	107.7	11612.5	25.80	8.0742	0.0877	17.50	1.426	0.0123	2.73	20.5	892.0	8.82E-03	1.0004	9918.6	98.7	1322.0
19	7.0	251.5	11549.2	20.03	8.2173	0.2091	11.92	1.194	0.0100	2.22	31.7	763.8	6.41E-03	1.0004	9887.4	96.9	2511.3
	8.2	216.7	11562.3	20.78	8.2228	0.1802	12.60	1.194	0.0106	2.34	28.6	763.8	7.03E-03	1.0004	9893.8	97.4	2287.1
	10.1	178.0	11579.2	21.96	8.2298	0.1480	13.69	1.194	0.0115	2.55	25.2	763.8	7.91E-03	1.0004	9902.1	97.8	2040.8
	12.2	148.9	11591.2	23.27	8.2348	0.1238	14.91	1.194	0.0125	2.77	22.7	763.8	8.79E-03	1.0004	9908.0	98.2	1859.3
	13.2	138.1	11601.0	23.91	8.2388	0.1149	15.50	1.194	0.0130	2.88	21.8	763.8	9.20E-03	1.0004	9912.9	98.3	1793.2
26	7.1	326.0	11518.7	19.30	8.4013	0.2775	11.08	0.971	0.0114	2.53	35.7	647.7	6.71E-03	1.0005	9872.5	96.0	3720.6
	8.0	291.4	11533.9	19.76	8.4078	0.2481	11.48	0.971	0.0118	2.63	32.8	647.7	7.21E-03	1.0005	9879.9	96.5	3446.4
	10.2	231.8	11558.0	20.86	8.4180	0.1974	12.46	0.971	0.0128	2.85	27.9	647.7	8.29E-03	1.0004	9891.7	97.2	2976.4
	12.0	198.8	11572.4	21.76	8.4242	0.1693	13.28	0.971	0.0137	3.04	25.3	647.7	9.10E-03	1.0004	9898.8	97.6	2719.3
	13.1	183.0	11579.1	22.31	8.4270	0.1558	13.78	0.971	0.0142	3.15	24.0	647.7	9.57E-03	1.0004	9902.1	97.8	2597.0
33	7.1	422.3	11479.2	18.78	8.5808	0.3680	10.47	0.789	0.0133	2.95	41.5	561.9	6.90E-03	1.0005	9853.3	94.9	5603.5
	8.1	373.6	11500.8	19.22	8.5902	0.3255	10.84	0.789	0.0137	3.05	37.6	561.9	7.49E-03	1.0005	9863.9	95.5	5129.6
	10.1	303.9	11531.2	20.07	8.6035	0.2648	11.57	0.789	0.0147	3.25	32.2	561.9	8.53E-03	1.0005	9878.8	96.3	4454.2
	12.2	254.5	11550.7	20.95	8.6119	0.2217	12.34	0.789	0.0156	3.47	28.4	561.9	9.51E-03	1.0005	9888.4	96.9	3978.4
	13.2	236.3	11558.7	21.37	8.6154	0.2058	12.71	0.789	0.0161	3.57	27.1	561.9	9.97E-03	1.0004	9892.3	97.1	3804.4
39	7.2	192.1	11571.9	21.09	8.0577	0.1564	13.07	1.426	0.0092	2.04	28.3	892.0	6.24E-03	1.0004	9898.5	97.7	1760.6
	8.2	169.9	11581.6	21.85	8.0616	0.1383	13.78	1.426	0.0097	2.15	26.2	892.0	6.73E-03	1.0004	9903.2	97.9	1642.3
	10.1	139.6	11594.3	23.31	8.0668	0.1137	15.15	1.426	0.0106	2.36	23.4	892.0	7.56E-03	1.0004	9909.5	98.3	1483.3
	12.0	118.6	11607.9	24.79	8.0724	0.0966	16.55	1.426	0.0116	2.58	21.5	892.0	8.32E-03	1.0004	9916.3	98.6	1376.3
	13.3	107.7	11612.5	25.80	8.0742	0.0877	17.50	1.426	0.0123	2.73	20.5	892.0	8.82E-03	1.0004	9918.6	98.7	1322.0

Table AI.3 Results of Operation Conditions in Improved State (using Stripper (Winflows 4.04 Programming Application)) of Desalination Plant GARO2 (Continues)

Temp. (T)° C	Feed Concentration Cf = 9948 mg/l																
	Qf m ³ /h	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	TCF	Jw,m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r°%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R%	Js mg/m ² .h
					πfc	πp											
12	7.2	514.5	11446.8	18.45	8.7346	0.4571	10.09	0.661	0.0153	3.39	47.0	497.0	7.12E-03	1.0006	9837.8	93.7	7850.2
	8.0	467.2	11464.3	18.76	8.7424	0.4150	10.33	0.661	0.0156	3.47	43.4	497.0	7.62E-03	1.0006	9846.2	94.3	7298.3
	10.2	373.0	11503.9	19.60	8.7600	0.3314	11.01	0.661	0.0167	3.70	36.3	497.0	8.83E-03	1.0005	9865.6	95.5	6213.3
	12.1	318.0	11528.0	20.30	8.7707	0.2825	11.60	0.661	0.0176	3.90	32.2	497.0	9.76E-03	1.0005	9877.4	96.1	5581.2
	13.1	295.2	11537.9	20.66	8.7751	0.2622	11.92	0.661	0.0180	4.00	30.5	497.0	1.02E-02	1.0005	9882.3	96.4	5320.4
17	7.2	231.4	14011.3	22.57	9.7217	0.1877	12.92	1.469	0.0088	1.95	27.1	916.0	6.97E-03	1.0004	11983.9	97.7	2035.6
	8.3	202.3	14023.3	23.46	9.7266	0.1642	13.75	1.469	0.0094	2.08	25.0	916.0	7.56E-03	1.0003	11989.8	98.0	1893.9
	10.0	169.7	14037.9	24.83	9.7325	0.1377	15.04	1.469	0.0102	2.27	22.7	916.0	8.38E-03	1.0003	11997.0	98.3	1737.7
	12.3	139.5	14058.4	26.72	9.7408	0.1132	16.81	1.469	0.0114	2.54	20.7	916.0	9.38E-03	1.0003	12007.3	98.6	1597.4
	13.1	131.5	14059.7	27.38	9.7413	0.1067	17.44	1.469	0.0119	2.64	20.1	916.0	9.72E-03	1.0003	12007.9	98.7	1562.0
27	7.1	287.7	13990.7	21.68	9.8837	0.2376	11.92	1.267	0.0094	2.09	29.4	804.1	7.17E-03	1.0004	11973.7	97.1	2707.4
	8.0	257.0	14004.1	22.29	9.8893	0.2122	12.48	1.267	0.0099	2.19	27.3	804.1	7.68E-03	1.0004	11980.3	97.4	2532.1
	10.1	206.3	14023.1	23.71	9.8971	0.1703	13.79	1.267	0.0109	2.42	23.9	804.1	8.74E-03	1.0003	11989.7	97.9	2245.5
	12.1	173.9	14037.5	25.07	9.9031	0.1436	15.06	1.267	0.0119	2.64	21.8	804.1	9.66E-03	1.0003	11996.9	98.3	2067.0
	13.1	161.3	14043.3	25.76	9.9055	0.1332	15.70	1.267	0.0124	2.75	21.0	804.1	1.01E-02	1.0003	11999.8	98.4	1999.1
33	7.0	430.8	13931.9	20.47	10.1995	0.3680	10.54	0.943	0.0112	2.48	35.5	634.2	7.41E-03	1.0004	11945.0	95.7	4817.0
	8.1	375.8	13956.1	21.03	10.2098	0.3210	11.02	0.943	0.0117	2.60	32.0	634.2	8.08E-03	1.0004	11956.8	96.2	4393.6
	10.3	299.7	13989.4	22.13	10.2240	0.2560	11.99	0.943	0.0127	2.82	27.4	634.2	9.27E-03	1.0004	11973.3	97.0	3812.1
	12.1	257.5	14005.1	23.02	10.2307	0.2199	12.78	0.943	0.0136	3.01	24.9	634.2	1.01E-02	1.0004	11981.0	97.4	3492.3
	13.1	238.9	14012.9	23.52	10.2341	0.2040	13.23	0.943	0.0140	3.12	23.8	634.2	1.06E-02	1.0004	11984.9	97.6	3352.8
38	7.1	530.1	13892.1	20.08	10.3861	0.4619	10.06	0.789	0.0127	2.83	39.8	561.9	7.65E-03	1.0005	11925.6	94.7	6755.9
	8.0	474.5	13916.1	20.48	10.3965	0.4134	10.39	0.789	0.0132	2.92	36.5	561.9	8.23E-03	1.0004	11937.3	95.2	6243.0
	10.2	378.1	13958.2	21.45	10.4149	0.3295	11.20	0.789	0.0142	3.15	30.9	561.9	9.48E-03	1.0004	11958.1	96.2	5366.1
	12.2	319.5	13983.8	22.31	10.4260	0.2784	11.95	0.789	0.0151	3.36	27.5	561.9	1.05E-02	1.0004	11970.7	96.8	4836.4
	13.1	298.8	13992.8	22.70	10.4300	0.2603	12.29	0.789	0.0156	3.45	26.4	561.9	1.10E-02	1.0004	11975.1	97.0	4650.2

A.3 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO1

Table AI.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO1

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 19 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	J _{wm} m/s	Q _p m ³ /h	r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R%	J _s mg/m ² .h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
2	2/1	12	3222	70.6	6243.2	52.57	3.8406	0.0573	48.45	0.0330	7.32	38.6	916.0	3.71E-05	1.2805	6059.9	97.8	2.331
3	3/1	13	2576	73.9	4983.0	49.46	3.0779	0.0602	46.11	0.0323	7.18	37.8	892.0	3.73E-05	1.2721	4808.1	97.1	2.390
4	4/1	12	2521	39.8	4867.7	50.26	2.9980	0.0323	46.96	0.0320	7.10	37.4	916.0	3.72E-05	1.2696	4690.3	98.4	1.272
5	5/1	12	2725	53.8	5327.1	50.20	3.2672	0.0436	46.65	0.0318	7.05	37.1	916.0	3.72E-05	1.2674	5102.5	98.0	1.708
8	8/1	14	2054	44.0	3948.8	46.12	2.4528	0.0359	43.38	0.0313	6.96	36.6	868.1	3.76E-05	1.2603	3782.5	97.9	1.378
9	9/1	15	1739	36.9	3331.9	45.81	2.0792	0.0303	43.44	0.0323	7.18	37.8	844.5	3.77E-05	1.2692	3217.9	97.9	1.192
10	10/1	15	1626	49.5	3109.9	43.60	1.9419	0.0406	41.38	0.0308	6.84	36.0	844.5	3.79E-05	1.2533	2967.8	97.0	1.523
11	11/1	12	1563	18.2	2987.0	46.40	1.8462	0.0147	44.23	0.0301	6.69	35.2	916.0	3.75E-05	1.2503	2844.4	98.8	0.547
12	12/1	13	1421	31.8	2709.5	46.27	1.6819	0.0259	44.29	0.0311	6.90	36.3	892.0	3.75E-05	1.2587	2599.6	97.8	0.986
13	13/1	13	1279	26.8	2429.9	46.09	1.5102	0.0218	44.27	0.0311	6.89	36.3	892.0	3.75E-05	1.2586	2334.1	97.9	0.833
15	15/1	11	1491	38.9	2856.4	45.37	1.7578	0.0315	43.31	0.0286	6.36	33.5	942.6	3.75E-05	1.2364	2687.6	97.4	1.114
16	16/1	15	1437	18.6	2753.4	45.78	1.7182	0.0152	43.76	0.0326	7.23	38.0	844.5	3.76E-05	1.2717	2664.4	98.7	0.605
17	17/1	12	1592	28.8	3058.6	45.96	1.8870	0.0234	43.77	0.0298	6.62	34.8	916.0	3.75E-05	1.2470	2899.7	98.2	0.860
18	18/1	13	1568	23.7	3013.1	46.12	1.8653	0.0193	43.94	0.0308	6.84	36.0	892.0	3.75E-05	1.2562	2877.4	98.5	0.729
20	20/1	15	1398	21.9	2684.5	45.47	1.6740	0.0180	43.50	0.0324	7.19	37.8	844.5	3.77E-05	1.2696	2591.6	98.4	0.710
22	22/1	13	1062	10.9	2039.4	45.68	1.2628	0.0089	44.10	0.0309	6.87	36.1	892.0	3.75E-05	1.2574	1949.8	99.0	0.336
23	23/1	13	1115	18.1	2142.3	46.40	1.3263	0.0147	44.76	0.0314	6.97	36.7	892.0	3.75E-05	1.2622	2055.6	98.4	0.568
24	24/1	16	1243	26.1	2393.6	43.26	1.4963	0.0215	41.47	0.0318	7.06	37.1	824.3	3.79E-05	1.2624	2295.4	97.9	0.831
26	26/1	18	1129	20.9	2175.0	42.96	1.3688	0.0173	41.30	0.0336	7.45	39.2	783.9	3.80E-05	1.2785	2112.0	98.1	0.703
27	27/1	16	1198	26.2	2311.8	44.04	1.4441	0.0216	42.30	0.0324	7.20	37.9	824.3	3.78E-05	1.2689	2226.8	97.8	0.850
29	29/1	17	1190	18.6	2299.9	46.07	1.4409	0.0153	44.33	0.0350	7.77	40.9	804.1	3.76E-05	1.2949	2259.6	98.4	0.650
30	30/1	16	1200	28.5	2321.0	45.06	1.4487	0.0235	43.32	0.0332	7.37	38.8	824.3	3.77E-05	1.2772	2248.4	97.6	0.948
31	31/1	15	1216	23.4	2354.3	44.83	1.4639	0.0192	43.07	0.0320	7.11	37.4	844.5	3.77E-05	1.2663	2260.5	98.1	0.749
32	1/2	15	1172	23.4	2271.8	43.86	1.4121	0.0192	42.14	0.0314	6.96	36.6	844.5	3.78E-05	1.2591	2168.1	98.0	0.735
33	2/2	14	1326	19.4	2574.3	43.55	1.5937	0.0158	41.64	0.0301	6.68	35.2	868.1	3.78E-05	1.2474	2432.7	98.5	0.582

Table AI.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GAROI (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 19 m ³ /h																	
	Date	Temp. (T)°C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% %	Js mg/m ² .h
	2022						π _{fc}	π _p										
34	3/2	17	1214	29.6	2358.4	47.71	1.4750	0.0244	45.95	0.0363	8.05	42.4	804.1	3.74E-05	1.3089	2337.9	97.6	1.073
36	5/2	15	1264	31.5	2439.0	47.12	1.5183	0.0258	45.31	0.0337	7.48	39.4	844.5	3.75E-05	1.2838	2377.0	97.5	1.062
37	6/2	14	1207	21.8	2329.1	44.76	1.4449	0.0178	43.00	0.0311	6.90	36.3	868.1	3.77E-05	1.2575	2223.2	98.2	0.678
38	7/2	15	1103	19.5	2125.6	44.63	1.3238	0.0160	43.00	0.0320	7.10	37.4	844.5	3.77E-05	1.2657	2043.3	98.2	0.623
40	9/2	17	1003	16.1	1923.6	40.80	1.2083	0.0133	39.29	0.0310	6.89	36.2	804.1	3.82E-05	1.2533	1833.9	98.4	0.500
41	10/2	17	1079	21.3	2079.4	46.12	1.3040	0.0176	44.52	0.0351	7.80	41.1	804.1	3.76E-05	1.2965	2047.5	98.0	0.749
44	13/2	19	1181	27.6	2270.6	46.43	1.4349	0.0229	44.71	0.0374	8.31	43.8	763.8	3.76E-05	1.3188	2275.9	97.7	1.033
45	14/2	19	1100	21.5	2112.9	43.44	1.3357	0.0179	41.83	0.0350	7.78	40.9	763.8	3.79E-05	1.2924	2076.2	98.0	0.754
46	15/2	20	1179	22.7	2262.5	41.05	1.4356	0.0189	39.34	0.0339	7.53	39.7	743.6	3.83E-05	1.2794	2201.6	98.1	0.770
47	16/2	20	1291	25.5	2478.5	43.26	1.5724	0.0213	41.42	0.0357	7.93	41.7	743.6	3.80E-05	1.2984	2447.1	98.0	0.913
48	17/2	17	1301	21.5	2499.0	44.45	1.5689	0.0177	42.59	0.0336	7.46	39.3	804.1	3.78E-05	1.2802	2432.4	98.3	0.722
50	19/2	18	1287	25.2	2465.3	44.32	1.5546	0.0209	42.48	0.0345	7.67	40.4	783.9	3.78E-05	1.2886	2417.7	98.0	0.871
51	20/2	19	1608	38.6	3088.9	44.55	1.9526	0.0321	42.33	0.0354	7.87	41.4	763.8	3.79E-05	1.2969	3045.8	97.6	1.367
52	21/2	19	1479	40.4	2941.3	45.73	1.8376	0.0336	43.63	0.0365	8.11	42.7	763.8	3.77E-05	1.3087	2892.5	97.3	1.475
53	22/2	20	1394	27.5	2691.2	41.54	1.7041	0.0230	39.56	0.0341	7.58	39.9	743.6	3.82E-05	1.2814	2617.5	98.0	0.939
54	23/2	21	1249	24.9	2383.0	42.26	1.5203	0.0208	40.47	0.0360	7.98	42.0	727.1	3.81E-05	1.2996	2360.1	98.0	0.895
57	26/2	22	1258	24.4	2394.7	41.34	1.5341	0.0205	39.53	0.0362	8.03	42.3	710.7	3.82E-05	1.3007	2375.5	98.1	0.884
59	28/2	20	1236	28.1	2348.1	40.85	1.4951	0.0235	39.08	0.0337	7.48	39.4	743.6	3.83E-05	1.2771	2288.6	97.7	0.949
60	1/3	19	1211	23.5	2348.8	45.09	1.4799	0.0195	43.33	0.0363	8.06	42.4	763.8	3.78E-05	1.3060	2324.6	98.1	0.853
61	2/3	20	1307	33.6	2520.8	40.82	1.5967	0.0280	38.96	0.0336	7.46	39.3	743.6	3.83E-05	1.2760	2442.2	97.4	1.129
62	3/3	20	1442	35.1	2844.3	45.12	1.7880	0.0293	43.06	0.0371	8.25	43.4	743.6	3.78E-05	1.3138	2815.6	97.6	1.304
64	5/3	21	1623	34.8	3130.2	41.05	1.9896	0.0291	38.80	0.0345	7.65	40.3	727.1	3.83E-05	1.2839	3051.4	97.9	1.200
66	7/3	20	1409	26.7	2733.0	42.06	1.7278	0.0223	40.06	0.0346	7.67	40.4	743.6	3.82E-05	1.2859	2663.1	98.1	0.923
67	8/3	22	1571	24.6	3095.4	42.18	1.9599	0.0207	39.96	0.0366	8.12	42.7	710.7	3.82E-05	1.3048	3044.5	98.4	0.900
69	10/3	19	1501	32.9	2947.4	42.93	1.8493	0.0274	40.82	0.0342	7.59	39.9	763.8	3.80E-05	1.2834	2854.6	97.8	1.125

Table AI.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GAROI (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 19 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R %	Js mg/m ² . h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
71	12/3	19	1389	30.9	2686.4	47.89	1.6942	0.0257	45.93	0.0385	8.54	44.9	763.8	3.75E-05	1.3301	2710.4	97.8	1.188
73	14/3	20	1265	23.9	2397.6	43.01	1.5279	0.0199	41.21	0.0355	7.89	41.5	743.6	3.80E-05	1.2965	2374.3	98.1	0.850
74	15/3	21	1346	24.0	2669.3	43.11	1.6807	0.0201	41.16	0.0366	8.12	42.7	727.1	3.80E-05	1.3062	2622.4	98.2	0.878
76	17/3	21	949	20.1	1838.4	38.79	1.1667	0.0168	37.36	0.0332	7.37	38.8	727.1	3.85E-05	1.2706	1770.8	97.9	0.667
78	19/3	20	1052	19.8	2119.1	41.36	1.3228	0.0165	39.77	0.0343	7.62	40.1	743.6	3.82E-05	1.2833	2034.7	98.1	0.679
81	22/3	21	1111	26.9	2214.3	42.44	1.3919	0.0225	40.78	0.0362	8.04	42.3	727.1	3.81E-05	1.3026	2165.8	97.6	0.975
82	23/3	21	1193	25.7	2310.5	38.79	1.4665	0.0215	37.05	0.0329	7.31	38.5	727.1	3.85E-05	1.2678	2220.8	97.8	0.846
85	26/3	21	1028	23.4	2060.8	41.36	1.2929	0.0196	39.80	0.0354	7.85	41.3	727.1	3.82E-05	1.2932	1997.2	97.7	0.827
86	27/3	21	1095	23.5	2148.5	42.44	1.3577	0.0197	40.81	0.0363	8.05	42.4	727.1	3.81E-05	1.3029	2112.9	97.9	0.852
88	29/3	22	989	18.3	1946.2	38.89	1.2328	0.0154	37.39	0.0342	7.60	40.0	710.7	3.85E-05	1.2800	1878.5	98.1	0.626
89	30/3	20	922	18.9	1871.5	38.82	1.1653	0.0158	37.37	0.0322	7.16	37.7	743.6	3.85E-05	1.2620	1762.7	98.0	0.609
90	31/3	20	971	19.7	1922.2	40.33	1.2069	0.0164	38.85	0.0335	7.44	39.2	743.6	3.83E-05	1.2750	1844.4	98.0	0.660
92	2/4	21	999	20.7	1971.1	38.69	1.2432	0.0173	37.17	0.0330	7.33	38.6	727.1	3.85E-05	1.2689	1884.4	97.9	0.684
95	5/4	22	1063	23.5	2054.0	40.90	1.3091	0.0197	39.32	0.0360	7.99	42.0	710.7	3.83E-05	1.2986	2023.9	97.8	0.846
96	6/4	20	1061	23.4	2064.8	41.13	1.3039	0.0195	39.55	0.0341	7.57	39.9	743.6	3.82E-05	1.2814	2002.6	97.8	0.798
97	7/4	20	1092	23.6	2121.1	42.21	1.3403	0.0197	40.60	0.0350	7.77	40.9	743.6	3.81E-05	1.2909	2073.8	97.8	0.827
101	11/4	21	1138	27.9	2238.0	42.96	1.4131	0.0234	41.28	0.0367	8.14	42.9	727.1	3.80E-05	1.3073	2206.8	97.5	1.023
102	12/4	21	1208	30.4	2343.0	42.06	1.4864	0.0254	40.31	0.0358	7.95	41.8	727.1	3.81E-05	1.2980	2304.7	97.5	1.089
103	13/4	20	1227	29.8	2421.4	42.65	1.5219	0.0249	40.86	0.0352	7.82	41.2	743.6	3.81E-05	1.2932	2359.1	97.6	1.050
104	14/4	23	1279	28.9	2469.0	40.69	1.5795	0.0244	38.85	0.0366	8.13	42.8	694.2	3.83E-05	1.3041	2443.9	97.7	1.058
107	17/4	22	1298	24.4	2537.5	40.62	1.6109	0.0205	38.74	0.0355	7.87	41.4	710.7	3.83E-05	1.2930	2479.6	98.1	0.865
108	18/4	22	1271	22.1	2508.5	41.10	1.5874	0.0186	39.25	0.0359	7.97	42.0	710.7	3.83E-05	1.2979	2452.8	98.3	0.794
109	19/4	22	1305	31.0	2536.1	42.83	1.6132	0.0260	40.95	0.0375	8.32	43.8	710.7	3.80E-05	1.3147	2525.0	97.6	1.162
110	20/4	23	1300	29.4	2515.9	42.06	1.6081	0.0248	40.20	0.0379	8.41	44.3	694.2	3.81E-05	1.3178	2514.3	97.7	1.114
113	23/4	23	1364	33.9	2617.4	41.98	1.6778	0.0286	40.05	0.0377	8.38	44.1	694.2	3.82E-05	1.3163	2620.4	97.5	1.280

Table AI.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO1 (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 19 m ³ /h																	
	Date	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% _o	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% _o	Js mg/m ² .h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
114	24/4	23	1308	35.6	2537.7	42.78	1.6207	0.0300	40.90	0.0386	8.56	45.0	694.2	3.80E-05	1.3252	2548.1	97.3	1.372
115	25/4	22	1289	24.4	2529.7	41.10	1.6038	0.0205	39.24	0.0359	7.97	42.0	710.7	3.83E-05	1.2978	2478.0	98.1	0.876
117	27/4	24	1353	28.9	2601.4	41.54	1.6721	0.0244	39.62	0.0385	8.54	44.9	677.7	3.82E-05	1.3227	2615.2	97.9	1.112
118	28/4	22	1390	30.0	2691.7	40.64	1.7143	0.0252	38.67	0.0354	7.86	41.3	710.7	3.83E-05	1.2923	2637.3	97.8	1.062
120	30/4	22	1326	28.7	2586.2	41.62	1.6431	0.0241	39.72	0.0363	8.07	42.5	710.7	3.82E-05	1.3025	2547.8	97.8	1.043
121	1/5	24	1399	33.4	2717.8	41.49	1.7408	0.0282	39.50	0.0384	8.51	44.8	677.7	3.82E-05	1.3214	2720.1	97.6	1.281
122	2/5	23	1372	31.5	2636.7	42.06	1.6893	0.0265	40.12	0.0378	8.39	44.2	694.2	3.81E-05	1.3170	2639.7	97.7	1.191
124	4/5	22	1251	24.0	2344.8	43.39	1.5102	0.0202	41.62	0.0381	8.46	44.5	710.7	3.80E-05	1.3214	2375.9	98.1	0.914
125	5/5	25	1555	37.9	2977.1	40.72	1.9228	0.0322	38.56	0.0386	8.56	45.0	661.2	3.83E-05	1.3222	2996.1	97.6	1.461
127	7/5	24	1432	38.4	2862.4	43.52	1.8158	0.0325	41.46	0.0403	8.94	47.0	677.7	3.79E-05	1.3427	2883.0	97.3	1.546
128	8/5	23	1683	40.6	3303.6	42.31	2.1015	0.0342	39.97	0.0377	8.36	44.0	694.2	3.82E-05	1.3155	3280.0	97.6	1.530
130	10/5	25	1403	35.9	2792.1	40.18	1.7798	0.0305	38.16	0.0382	8.47	44.6	661.2	3.84E-05	1.3178	2764.2	97.4	1.370
131	11/5	25	1396	32.6	2751.0	41.10	1.7594	0.0277	39.10	0.0391	8.68	45.7	661.2	3.83E-05	1.3282	2754.1	97.7	1.275
132	12/5	24	1273	28.1	2531.5	42.08	1.6087	0.0238	40.22	0.0390	8.67	45.6	677.7	3.81E-05	1.3292	2528.4	97.8	1.097
135	15/5	26	1101	24.2	2163.1	41.41	1.3895	0.0206	39.77	0.0410	9.09	47.9	647.7	3.81E-05	1.3477	2199.6	97.8	0.991
137	17/5	22	1352	25.5	2640.8	41.26	1.6770	0.0214	39.32	0.0360	7.99	42.0	710.7	3.83E-05	1.2986	2592.5	98.1	0.918
138	18/5	24	1217	27.3	2612.5	40.72	1.6193	0.0231	38.85	0.0377	8.37	44.1	677.7	3.83E-05	1.3145	2516.9	97.8	1.030
139	19/5	26	1242	24.5	2392.7	41.26	1.5473	0.0209	39.46	0.0406	9.02	47.5	647.7	3.82E-05	1.3441	2442.7	98.0	0.996
141	21/5	25	1203	24.6	2458.9	40.98	1.5536	0.0209	39.17	0.0392	8.70	45.8	661.2	3.83E-05	1.3290	2433.3	98.0	0.964
143	23/5	26	1101	24.2	2202.1	39.36	1.4061	0.0206	37.70	0.0388	8.62	45.4	647.7	3.84E-05	1.3239	2186.5	97.8	0.940
144	24/5	26	1069	21.0	2148.1	40.41	1.3695	0.0179	38.79	0.0400	8.87	46.7	647.7	3.83E-05	1.3364	2149.6	98.0	0.839
145	25/5	25	963	17.9	1799.1	42.96	1.1719	0.0152	41.52	0.0415	9.22	48.5	661.2	3.79E-05	1.3555	1872.1	98.1	0.743
148	28/5	26	999	20.7	1931.5	36.91	1.2475	0.0176	35.42	0.0365	8.10	42.6	647.7	3.88E-05	1.2986	1902.8	97.9	0.755
149	29/5	27	981	19.9	1911.3	38.23	1.2353	0.0170	36.74	0.0390	8.65	45.5	634.2	3.86E-05	1.3242	1915.0	98.0	0.776
150	30/5	27	1015	21.6	1964.3	37.56	1.2725	0.0185	36.04	0.0382	8.49	44.7	634.2	3.87E-05	1.3161	1960.6	97.9	0.826

Table AI.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO1 (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 19 m ³ /h																	
	Date	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% h	Js mg/m ² . h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
151	31/5	28	1090	24.5	2108.4	40.26	1.3707	0.0210	38.64	0.0422	9.37	49.3	620.7	3.82E-05	1.3592	2173.7	97.8	1.034
152	1/6	29	1158	24.7	2209.5	40.21	1.4479	0.0212	38.52	0.0433	9.62	50.7	607.2	3.82E-05	1.3707	2307.9	97.9	1.071
153	2/6	29	1199	27.9	2324.8	41.77	1.5151	0.0240	40.02	0.0450	10.00	52.6	607.2	3.79E-05	1.3907	2450.3	97.7	1.257
155	4/6	27	1212	32.6	2356.3	41.44	1.5241	0.0278	39.68	0.0421	9.35	49.2	634.2	3.81E-05	1.3593	2425.2	97.3	1.372
157	6/6	29	1491	37.2	2908.1	40.72	1.8915	0.0320	38.60	0.0434	9.64	50.8	607.2	3.82E-05	1.3718	3017.3	97.5	1.616
158	7/6	29	1533	40.9	2967.4	38.53	1.9350	0.0352	36.38	0.0409	9.09	47.8	607.2	3.85E-05	1.3432	3022.5	97.3	1.675
159	8/6	31	1609	41.1	3124.7	39.74	2.0488	0.0356	37.47	0.0447	9.93	52.3	583.1	3.82E-05	1.3841	3275.9	97.4	1.839
160	9/6	33	1753	46.9	3452.1	39.10	2.2676	0.0409	36.62	0.0464	10.30	54.2	561.9	3.82E-05	1.4010	3646.1	97.3	2.176
163	12/6	30	1465	45.6	2774.0	40.26	1.8287	0.0393	38.22	0.0443	9.84	51.8	593.7	3.82E-05	1.3803	2925.5	96.9	2.020
164	13/6	30	1484	40.2	2847.6	39.97	1.8686	0.0347	37.88	0.0439	9.75	51.3	593.7	3.82E-05	1.3757	2979.4	97.3	1.765
165	14/6	30	1843	48.9	3577.3	41.39	2.3382	0.0422	38.84	0.0450	9.99	52.6	593.7	3.81E-05	1.3888	3763.8	97.3	2.202
166	15/6	31	1700	43.9	3308.3	39.56	2.1676	0.0380	37.17	0.0444	9.85	51.9	583.1	3.83E-05	1.3799	3455.5	97.4	1.949
167	16/6	32	1756	45.6	3386.2	40.39	2.2329	0.0396	37.94	0.0467	10.36	54.5	572.5	3.81E-05	1.4057	3614.2	97.4	2.128
169	18/6	30	1694	39.4	3316.1	37.66	2.1613	0.0340	35.29	0.0409	9.08	47.8	593.7	3.87E-05	1.3413	3360.1	97.7	1.612
171	20/6	31	1622	34.2	3193.4	38.12	2.0841	0.0296	35.82	0.0428	9.49	50.0	583.1	3.85E-05	1.3611	3277.1	97.9	1.463
172	21/6	31	1768	36.8	3443.1	41.70	2.2554	0.0319	39.22	0.0468	10.40	54.7	583.1	3.79E-05	1.4093	3672.0	97.9	1.723
173	22/6	29	1771	39.6	2486.6	38.25	1.8306	0.0341	36.20	0.0407	9.05	47.6	607.2	3.86E-05	1.3410	2854.7	97.8	1.614
174	23/6	29	1463	27.0	3417.6	39.87	2.0985	0.0232	37.54	0.0423	9.38	49.4	607.2	3.84E-05	1.3580	3314.0	98.2	1.141
176	25/6	32	2198	56.3	4311.4	39.85	2.8266	0.0489	36.82	0.0453	10.05	52.9	572.5	3.83E-05	1.3891	4521.1	97.4	2.549
177	26/6	31	2002	49.7	3937.6	36.79	2.5707	0.0430	34.00	0.0406	9.01	47.4	583.1	3.89E-05	1.3367	3969.9	97.5	2.018
178	27/6	30	1927	49.2	3783.1	38.28	2.4633	0.0424	35.60	0.0413	9.16	48.2	593.7	3.86E-05	1.3454	3841.3	97.4	2.031
180	29/6	33	1762	42.2	3460.5	37.69	2.2752	0.0368	35.19	0.0446	9.90	52.1	561.9	3.85E-05	1.3795	3602.2	97.6	1.881
181	30/6	34	1841	45.7	3581.1	38.79	2.3699	0.0399	36.21	0.0473	10.49	55.2	551.3	3.82E-05	1.4099	3822.3	97.5	2.159

A.4 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2

Table AI.5 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T) °C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jwm m/s	Op m ³ /h	r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% mg/m ² .h	Js mg/m ² .h
							πfc	πp										
2	2/1	12	6287.5	128.4	9137.0	20.45	6.2586	0.1042	14.16	0.0096	2.14	26.7	916.0	2.49E-05	1.1134	8587.1	98.0	1.238
3	3/1	14	5017.0	112.3	7854.3	19.24	5.2593	0.0918	13.93	0.0101	2.23	27.9	868.1	2.51E-05	1.1180	7195.3	97.8	1.130
4	4/1	12	4900.8	86.5	6325.9	19.55	4.5554	0.0702	14.92	0.0102	2.26	28.2	916.0	2.48E-05	1.1205	6289.7	98.2	0.880
5	5/1	13	5363.3	100.2	6855.1	19.53	4.9751	0.0816	14.50	0.0102	2.26	28.2	892.0	2.49E-05	1.1200	6842.2	98.1	1.019
8	8/1	14	3975.5	80.0	5936.2	17.94	4.0500	0.0654	13.82	0.0100	2.22	27.7	868.1	2.51E-05	1.1169	5535.2	98.0	0.798
9	9/1	15	3354.5	68.4	4581.9	17.82	3.2541	0.0561	14.48	0.0108	2.39	29.9	844.5	2.50E-05	1.1270	4472.3	98.0	0.737
10	10/1	16	3130.9	70.3	4876.9	16.96	3.2948	0.0579	13.59	0.0104	2.31	28.9	824.3	2.52E-05	1.1217	4491.1	97.8	0.733
11	11/1	13	3007.7	51.1	4109.5	18.05	2.8980	0.0416	15.04	0.0106	2.34	29.3	892.0	2.48E-05	1.1252	4004.1	98.3	0.539
12	12/1	14	2727.5	53.2	4077.2	18.00	2.7804	0.0435	15.12	0.0109	2.43	30.3	868.1	2.49E-05	1.1297	3843.6	98.0	0.582
13	13/1	14	2446.0	48.8	3752.7	17.93	2.5328	0.0399	15.30	0.0111	2.45	30.7	868.1	2.49E-05	1.1314	3506.7	98.0	0.539
15	15/1	12	2875.9	54.8	4398.0	17.65	2.9514	0.0445	14.59	0.0099	2.21	27.6	916.0	2.49E-05	1.1174	4064.0	98.1	0.545
16	16/1	15	2771.9	51.6	3596.6	17.81	2.6113	0.0423	15.09	0.0112	2.49	31.2	844.5	2.49E-05	1.1332	3608.5	98.1	0.580
17	17/1	13	3079.2	62.8	4719.5	17.88	3.1755	0.0511	14.61	0.0102	2.27	28.4	892.0	2.49E-05	1.1210	4371.3	98.0	0.643
18	18/1	13	3033.2	52.6	3961.5	17.94	2.8481	0.0428	14.99	0.0105	2.33	29.2	892.0	2.49E-05	1.1247	3933.6	98.3	0.553
20	20/1	15	2703.1	48.7	3543.2	17.69	2.5612	0.0400	15.03	0.0112	2.48	31.0	844.5	2.49E-05	1.1326	3537.3	98.2	0.545
22	22/1	13	2052.8	33.1	2673.2	17.77	1.9243	0.0269	15.72	0.0110	2.45	30.6	892.0	2.48E-05	1.1317	2674.3	98.4	0.365
23	23/1	13	2156.6	40.2	3375.5	18.05	2.2526	0.0327	15.69	0.0110	2.44	30.5	892.0	2.48E-05	1.1314	3129.6	98.1	0.443
24	24/1	17	2409.8	54.9	3664.3	16.83	2.5079	0.0454	14.23	0.0112	2.49	31.2	804.1	2.51E-05	1.1321	3438.3	97.7	0.617
26	26/1	19	2189.5	46.5	2867.1	16.71	2.1021	0.0387	14.52	0.0122	2.70	33.7	763.8	2.52E-05	1.1436	2891.4	97.9	0.565
27	27/1	16	2326.8	50.8	3642.4	17.13	2.4560	0.0418	14.59	0.0112	2.48	31.0	824.3	2.50E-05	1.1320	3378.5	97.8	0.568
29	29/1	18	2315.4	48.9	3074.3	17.92	2.2330	0.0405	15.59	0.0127	2.81	35.2	783.9	2.49E-05	1.1516	3103.3	97.9	0.620
30	30/1	17	2336.7	52.8	3307.6	17.53	2.3304	0.0436	15.10	0.0119	2.65	33.1	804.1	2.50E-05	1.1417	3221.9	97.7	0.630
31	31/1	16	2370.2	43.3	3159.8	17.44	2.2753	0.0356	15.06	0.0115	2.56	32.0	824.3	2.50E-05	1.1370	3143.8	98.2	0.500
32	1/2	16	2287.4	43.4	3176.7	17.06	2.2482	0.0357	14.72	0.0113	2.50	31.3	824.3	2.50E-05	1.1334	3096.4	98.1	0.489
33	2/2	14	2592.0	44.8	3391.1	16.94	2.4447	0.0366	14.40	0.0104	2.31	28.9	868.1	2.50E-05	1.1226	3358.3	98.3	0.466

Table AI.5 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2 (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r°	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R%	Js mg/m ² .h
							πfc	πp										
34	3/2	17	2374.3	54.8	3519.5	18.56	2.4334	0.0452	16.03	0.0127	2.81	35.1	804.1	2.48E-05	1.1520	3394.8	97.7	0.693
36	5/2	15	2455.8	50.9	3812.9	18.33	2.5704	0.0417	15.66	0.0117	2.59	32.3	844.5	2.48E-05	1.1391	3570.4	97.9	0.593
37	6/2	15	2344.9	40.4	3222.6	17.41	2.2828	0.0331	15.02	0.0112	2.48	31.0	844.5	2.49E-05	1.1325	3152.6	98.3	0.452
38	7/2	16	2140.0	39.3	2846.1	17.36	2.0516	0.0323	15.21	0.0117	2.59	32.4	824.3	2.49E-05	1.1386	2838.6	98.2	0.458
40	9/2	17	1936.0	35.1	2510.5	15.87	1.8359	0.0290	13.93	0.0110	2.44	30.5	804.1	2.52E-05	1.1290	2510.0	98.2	0.386
41	10/2	18	2093.1	46.4	3152.2	17.94	2.1732	0.0384	15.68	0.0127	2.83	35.4	783.9	2.49E-05	1.1526	3022.8	97.8	0.591
44	13/2	20	2285.7	58.0	3434.6	18.06	2.3862	0.0484	15.59	0.0134	2.99	37.3	743.6	2.50E-05	1.1612	3321.1	97.5	0.780
45	14/2	20	2126.8	46.8	2808.3	16.90	2.0587	0.0390	14.74	0.0127	2.82	35.3	743.6	2.52E-05	1.1507	2839.5	97.8	0.595
46	15/2	21	2277.6	49.3	2984.2	15.97	2.2024	0.0413	13.69	0.0122	2.70	33.8	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1424	3005.7	97.8	0.600
47	16/2	20	2495.3	55.5	3356.4	16.83	2.4410	0.0463	14.31	0.0123	2.74	34.2	743.6	2.52E-05	1.1455	3351.5	97.8	0.685
48	17/2	18	2515.9	49.2	3318.5	17.29	2.4172	0.0408	14.78	0.0120	2.67	33.4	783.9	2.51E-05	1.1424	3332.5	98.0	0.592
50	19/2	18	2482.0	54.8	3769.5	17.24	2.5900	0.0454	14.56	0.0118	2.63	32.8	783.9	2.51E-05	1.1398	3562.8	97.8	0.649
51	20/2	20	3109.9	83.8	4812.6	17.33	3.3049	0.0699	13.96	0.0120	2.67	33.4	743.6	2.53E-05	1.1413	4520.9	97.3	1.009
52	21/2	20	2961.0	72.0	4394.2	17.79	3.0682	0.0601	14.65	0.0126	2.81	35.1	743.6	2.52E-05	1.1497	4227.9	97.6	0.910
53	22/2	21	2709.3	59.8	3522.9	16.16	2.6086	0.0501	13.48	0.0120	2.66	33.2	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1399	3552.1	97.8	0.717
54	23/2	21	2399.1	54.1	3080.2	16.44	2.2935	0.0453	14.07	0.0125	2.78	34.7	727.1	2.53E-05	1.1472	3142.8	97.7	0.677
57	26/2	23	2410.7	57.2	3305.9	16.08	2.4091	0.0482	13.60	0.0128	2.85	35.6	694.2	2.54E-05	1.1503	3288.0	97.6	0.733
59	28/2	21	2363.9	61.2	3598.0	15.89	2.4955	0.0512	13.33	0.0118	2.63	32.9	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1380	3392.4	97.4	0.724
60	1/3	20	2348.8	57.9	3447.6	17.54	2.4180	0.0483	15.04	0.0130	2.88	36.0	743.6	2.51E-05	1.1544	3345.6	97.5	0.752
61	2/3	21	2520.8	64.6	3703.3	15.88	2.6052	0.0541	13.21	0.0117	2.61	32.6	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1366	3537.1	97.4	0.759
62	3/3	20	2844.3	71.0	4170.7	17.55	2.9263	0.0592	14.55	0.0126	2.79	34.8	743.6	2.52E-05	1.1485	4028.2	97.5	0.891
64	5/3	22	3130.2	78.2	4546.4	15.97	3.2242	0.0657	12.69	0.0116	2.58	32.2	710.7	2.56E-05	1.1344	4354.2	97.5	0.908
66	7/3	21	2733.0	73.8	3978.9	16.36	2.8094	0.0618	13.49	0.0120	2.66	33.3	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1400	3825.9	97.3	0.885
67	8/3	22	3095.4	84.1	4445.2	16.41	3.1670	0.0706	13.19	0.0121	2.68	33.5	710.7	2.55E-05	1.1407	4300.6	97.3	1.015
69	10/3	21	2947.4	70.8	4383.6	16.70	3.0685	0.0593	13.56	0.0120	2.67	33.4	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1409	4181.8	97.6	0.853

Table AI.5 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2 (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)°C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m ² . h
							πfc	πp										
71	12/3	20	2686.4	60.0	3988.0	18.63	2.7842	0.0501	15.76	0.0136	3.02	37.7	710.7	2.52E-05	1.1619	3877.4	97.8	0.815
73	14/3	22	2397.6	56.3	3637.8	16.73	2.5349	0.0473	14.11	0.0129	2.87	35.8	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1523	3477.3	97.7	0.728
74	15/3	21	2669.3	66.7	4012.8	16.77	2.7969	0.0559	13.90	0.0123	2.74	34.3	727.1	2.53E-05	1.1450	3825.6	97.5	0.824
76	17/3	23	1838.4	60.3	2785.9	15.09	1.9488	0.0508	13.06	0.0123	2.73	34.2	694.2	2.55E-05	1.1433	2643.5	96.7	0.743
78	19/3	22	2119.1	55.5	2941.1	16.09	2.1253	0.0467	13.89	0.0127	2.82	35.3	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1495	2908.3	97.4	0.706
81	22/3	22	2214.3	59.7	2951.2	16.51	2.1695	0.0502	14.27	0.0131	2.90	36.2	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1543	2981.3	97.3	0.780
82	23/3	20	2310.5	51.4	3420.2	15.09	2.3906	0.0429	12.61	0.0109	2.42	30.2	743.6	2.55E-05	1.1256	3225.2	97.8	0.559
85	26/3	21	2060.8	45.2	2857.6	16.09	2.0587	0.0378	13.95	0.0124	2.75	34.4	727.1	2.53E-05	1.1456	2817.4	97.8	0.560
86	27/3	21	2148.5	50.6	2868.9	16.51	2.1001	0.0424	14.33	0.0127	2.83	35.3	727.1	2.52E-05	1.1504	2886.0	97.6	0.645
88	29/3	22	1946.2	52.4	2560.4	15.13	1.8928	0.0440	13.16	0.0120	2.67	33.4	710.7	2.55E-05	1.1402	2569.3	97.3	0.631
89	30/3	21	1871.5	47.0	2600.3	15.10	1.8718	0.0393	13.15	0.0117	2.59	32.4	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1359	2539.7	97.5	0.549
90	31/3	20	1922.2	46.1	2917.9	15.69	2.0190	0.0384	13.57	0.0117	2.60	32.5	743.6	2.54E-05	1.1367	2750.9	97.6	0.539
92	2/4	22	1971.1	51.6	2534.6	15.05	1.8924	0.0433	13.07	0.0120	2.66	33.2	710.7	2.55E-05	1.1391	2566.3	97.4	0.617
95	5/4	23	2054.0	48.5	3068.3	15.91	2.1586	0.0409	13.66	0.0129	2.86	35.7	694.2	2.54E-05	1.1512	2948.3	97.6	0.625
96	6/4	21	2064.8	46.0	3094.2	16.00	2.1594	0.0385	13.75	0.0122	2.71	33.9	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1432	2948.8	97.8	0.562
97	7/4	22	2121.1	53.4	3205.1	16.42	2.2370	0.0449	14.10	0.0129	2.86	35.8	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1521	3068.2	97.5	0.689
101	11/4	22	2238.0	58.9	3381.8	16.71	2.3603	0.0495	14.27	0.0131	2.90	36.2	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1543	3243.5	97.4	0.770
102	12/4	22	2343.0	57.4	3064.5	16.36	2.2711	0.0482	14.02	0.0128	2.85	35.6	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1511	3112.3	97.6	0.736
103	13/4	21	2421.4	61.7	3325.5	16.59	2.4055	0.0517	14.12	0.0125	2.78	34.8	727.1	2.53E-05	1.1477	3297.8	97.5	0.774
104	14/4	23	2469.0	68.4	3659.2	15.83	2.5826	0.0577	13.19	0.0124	2.76	34.5	694.2	2.55E-05	1.1449	3508.2	97.2	0.850
107	17/4	24	2537.5	73.4	3311.8	15.80	2.4734	0.0621	13.26	0.0129	2.86	35.7	677.7	2.55E-05	1.1504	3364.6	97.1	0.945
108	18/4	23	2508.5	69.0	3706.0	15.99	2.6189	0.0581	13.30	0.0125	2.78	34.8	694.2	2.55E-05	1.1464	3562.2	97.3	0.864
109	19/4	22	2536.1	67.5	3472.9	16.66	2.5238	0.0567	14.06	0.0129	2.86	35.7	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1517	3460.2	97.3	0.869
110	20/4	25	2515.9	75.1	3275.7	16.36	2.4572	0.0637	13.84	0.0138	3.07	38.4	661.2	2.54E-05	1.1633	3368.6	97.0	1.039
113	23/4	24	2617.4	71.1	3607.5	16.33	2.6322	0.0602	13.64	0.0132	2.94	36.7	677.7	2.54E-05	1.1556	3596.7	97.3	0.942

Table AI.5 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2 (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m ² , h
							πfc	πp										
114	24/4	23	2537.7	66.1	3518.2	16.64	2.5521	0.0557	14.01	0.0132	2.93	36.7	694.2	2.53E-05	1.1558	3499.7	97.4	0.872
115	25/4	24	2529.7	67.8	3780.5	15.99	2.6682	0.0574	13.26	0.0129	2.86	35.7	677.7	2.55E-05	1.1504	3629.7	97.3	0.873
117	27/4	25	2601.4	79.7	3842.5	16.16	2.7339	0.0677	13.36	0.0134	2.97	37.1	661.2	2.55E-05	1.1566	3726.5	96.9	1.066
118	28/4	23	2691.7	74.0	4013.7	15.81	2.8258	0.0624	12.92	0.0122	2.70	33.8	694.2	2.56E-05	1.1414	3826.9	97.3	0.901
120	30/4	24	2586.2	73.9	3874.4	16.19	2.7318	0.0625	13.39	0.0130	2.89	36.1	677.7	2.55E-05	1.1522	3722.0	97.1	0.960
121	1/5	25	2717.8	81.1	4025.2	16.14	2.8608	0.0688	13.22	0.0132	2.93	36.7	661.2	2.55E-05	1.1546	3892.6	97.0	1.072
122	2/5	25	2636.7	78.8	4052.4	16.36	2.8380	0.0668	13.46	0.0135	2.99	37.3	661.2	2.55E-05	1.1579	3872.8	97.0	1.060
124	4/5	23	2344.8	65.4	3390.1	16.88	2.4168	0.0552	14.39	0.0136	3.01	37.6	694.2	2.53E-05	1.1608	3328.6	97.2	0.888
125	5/5	26	2977.1	94.3	4383.9	15.84	3.1335	0.0803	12.67	0.0130	2.90	36.2	647.7	2.57E-05	1.1516	4238.5	96.8	1.230
127	7/5	25	2862.4	89.3	3821.4	16.93	2.8357	0.0758	14.05	0.0141	3.12	39.0	661.2	2.54E-05	1.1663	3897.8	96.9	1.255
128	8/5	25	3303.6	102.1	4362.0	16.46	3.2523	0.0867	13.17	0.0132	2.92	36.6	661.2	2.56E-05	1.1540	4422.9	96.9	1.345
130	10/5	26	2792.1	86.1	4218.8	15.63	2.9845	0.0733	12.60	0.0130	2.88	36.0	647.7	2.57E-05	1.1507	4033.5	96.9	1.117
131	11/5	27	2751.0	84.6	4147.3	15.99	2.9464	0.0723	13.00	0.0138	3.06	38.3	634.2	2.56E-05	1.1614	4005.8	96.9	1.166
132	12/5	25	2531.5	73.2	3707.8	16.37	2.6471	0.0621	13.66	0.0137	3.03	37.9	661.2	2.54E-05	1.1609	3621.4	97.1	1.000
135	15/5	26	2163.1	59.5	3331.5	16.11	2.3390	0.0506	13.70	0.0141	3.13	39.2	647.7	2.54E-05	1.1666	3205.0	97.3	0.839
137	17/5	24	2640.8	77.5	3765.5	16.05	2.7089	0.0656	13.28	0.0129	2.86	35.8	677.7	2.55E-05	1.1507	3685.8	97.1	0.999
138	18/5	25	2612.5	70.7	3656.3	15.84	2.6597	0.0600	13.11	0.0131	2.91	36.4	661.2	2.56E-05	1.1531	3614.2	97.3	0.927
139	19/5	26	2392.7	73.1	3151.5	16.05	2.3601	0.0622	13.63	0.0140	3.12	39.0	647.7	2.55E-05	1.1656	3231.1	96.9	1.026
141	21/5	26	2458.9	75.5	3194.1	15.94	2.4064	0.0643	13.48	0.0139	3.08	38.5	647.7	2.55E-05	1.1633	3288.1	96.9	1.048
143	23/5	26	2202.1	67.6	3330.0	15.31	2.3550	0.0575	12.89	0.0133	2.95	36.9	647.7	2.56E-05	1.1549	3194.4	96.9	0.897
144	24/5	27	2148.1	71.0	3214.6	15.72	2.2905	0.0606	13.37	0.0142	3.15	39.4	634.2	2.55E-05	1.1670	3129.1	96.7	1.007
145	25/5	25	1799.1	53.9	2705.8	16.71	1.9113	0.0458	14.71	0.0147	3.27	40.8	661.2	2.52E-05	1.1759	2648.7	97.0	0.794
148	28/5	28	1931.5	61.1	2933.5	14.36	2.0848	0.0524	12.21	0.0133	2.96	37.0	620.7	2.58E-05	1.1545	2808.3	96.8	0.815
149	29/5	29	1911.3	62.4	2886.0	14.87	2.0626	0.0537	12.74	0.0143	3.18	39.8	607.2	2.57E-05	1.1679	2801.4	96.7	0.895
150	30/5	28	1964.3	63.7	2913.8	14.61	2.0905	0.0546	12.45	0.0136	3.02	37.8	620.7	2.57E-05	1.1583	2825.1	96.8	0.867

Table AI.5 Results of Long-Term Operation of GARO2 (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r ^o %	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% h	Js mg/m ² ·h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
151	31/5	29	2108.4	71.4	2751.6	15.66	2.0896	0.0614	13.51	0.0152	3.38	42.2	607.2	2.55E-05	1.1804	2868.4	96.6	1.086
152	1/6	29	2209.5	75.8	3458.2	15.64	2.4369	0.0652	13.15	0.0148	3.29	41.1	607.2	2.56E-05	1.1745	3328.3	96.6	1.121
153	2/6	30	2324.8	77.3	3122.8	16.25	2.3500	0.0667	13.85	0.0161	3.56	44.5	593.7	2.54E-05	1.1921	3247.1	96.7	1.241
155	4/6	29	2356.3	79.6	2771.3	16.12	2.2047	0.0684	13.86	0.0156	3.46	43.3	607.2	2.54E-05	1.1862	3041.3	96.6	1.242
157	6/6	30	2908.1	108.4	4475.4	15.84	3.1851	0.0935	12.63	0.0146	3.25	40.6	593.7	2.57E-05	1.1715	4324.8	96.3	1.587
158	7/6	31	2967.4	113.7	4592.4	14.99	3.2720	0.0985	11.70	0.0140	3.10	38.8	583.1	2.59E-05	1.1614	4390.2	96.2	1.589
159	8/6	33	3124.7	121.3	4095.6	15.46	3.1456	0.1057	12.31	0.0156	3.46	43.3	561.9	2.57E-05	1.1835	4272.6	96.1	1.891
160	9/6	33	3452.1	143.4	4962.4	15.21	3.6658	0.1250	11.56	0.0146	3.25	40.6	561.9	2.59E-05	1.1698	4921.8	95.8	2.100
163	12/6	30	2774.0	99.1	3710.0	15.66	2.7971	0.0855	12.83	0.0149	3.30	41.3	593.7	2.56E-05	1.1748	3808.8	96.4	1.474
164	13/6	30	2847.6	104.5	4301.9	15.55	3.0842	0.0902	12.44	0.0144	3.20	40.0	593.7	2.57E-05	1.1683	4176.4	96.3	1.507
165	14/6	31	3577.3	141.1	5379.5	16.10	3.8766	0.1222	12.24	0.0146	3.24	40.5	583.1	2.58E-05	1.1705	5242.0	96.1	2.062
166	15/6	32	3308.3	135.9	5078.2	15.39	3.6417	0.1180	11.76	0.0145	3.21	40.1	572.5	2.59E-05	1.1678	4896.9	95.9	1.965
167	16/6	34	3386.2	149.5	5306.5	15.71	3.7994	0.1307	11.93	0.0156	3.46	43.2	551.3	2.58E-05	1.1825	5139.4	95.6	2.327
169	18/6	32	3316.1	134.8	4324.3	14.65	3.3177	0.1171	11.34	0.0139	3.10	38.7	572.5	2.60E-05	1.1606	4433.9	95.9	1.880
171	20/6	32	3193.4	129.1	4942.3	14.83	3.5328	0.1121	11.30	0.0139	3.09	38.6	572.5	2.60E-05	1.1600	4718.5	96.0	1.794
172	21/6	33	3443.1	144.7	5247.8	16.22	3.7863	0.1260	12.44	0.0158	3.50	43.7	561.9	2.57E-05	1.1859	5153.2	95.8	2.280
173	22/6	31	2486.6	93.2	3714.3	14.88	2.6838	0.0806	12.16	0.0145	3.22	40.3	583.1	2.58E-05	1.1692	3624.9	96.3	1.352
174	23/6	31	3417.6	134.2	4426.4	15.51	3.3949	0.1161	12.11	0.0145	3.21	40.1	583.1	2.58E-05	1.1684	4582.5	96.1	1.940
176	25/6	33	4311.4	177.3	5858.5	15.50	4.4306	0.1545	11.10	0.0141	3.12	39.0	561.9	2.61E-05	1.1618	5907.5	95.9	2.494
177	26/6	32	3937.6	162.8	6088.2	14.31	4.3535	0.1414	9.99	0.0123	2.73	34.1	572.5	2.64E-05	1.1381	5705.2	95.9	2.000
178	27/6	32	3783.1	153.8	5778.1	14.89	4.1518	0.1336	10.76	0.0132	2.94	36.7	572.5	2.62E-05	1.1509	5501.9	95.9	2.036
180	29/6	34	3460.5	146.8	5650.5	14.66	3.9822	0.1283	10.70	0.0140	3.10	38.7	551.3	2.62E-05	1.1597	5282.9	95.8	2.048
181	30/6	34	3581.1	158.9	5503.1	15.09	3.9705	0.1389	11.14	0.0145	3.23	40.3	551.3	2.60E-05	1.1677	5303.8	95.6	2.310

A.5 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing

Table AI.6 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	J _{Wm} ml/s	Q _p m ³ /h	r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R%	J _s mg/m ² .h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
2	2/1	12	6287.5	123.4	8867.0	19.69	6.1491	0.1002	13.50	0.0092	2.04	25.5	916.0	2.50E-05	1.1075	8391.9	98.0	1.135
3	3/1	14	5017.0	102.9	7075.4	18.48	4.9410	0.0841	13.48	0.0097	2.16	27.0	868.1	2.51E-05	1.1137	6733.7	97.9	1.002
4	4/1	12	4900.8	92.3	6915.0	18.79	4.7944	0.0749	13.93	0.0095	2.11	26.3	916.0	2.50E-05	1.1114	6566.0	98.1	0.876
5	5/1	13	5363.3	106.8	7565.2	18.77	5.2642	0.0870	13.45	0.0094	2.09	26.2	892.0	2.51E-05	1.1102	7176.6	98.0	1.008
8	8/1	14	3975.5	78.5	5606.2	17.18	3.9151	0.0641	13.19	0.0095	2.12	26.4	868.1	2.52E-05	1.1109	5322.1	98.0	0.748
9	9/1	15	3354.5	67.1	4731.9	17.06	3.3157	0.0550	13.66	0.0102	2.26	28.2	844.5	2.52E-05	1.1188	4523.4	98.0	0.682
10	10/1	16	3130.9	64.5	4415.8	16.20	3.1051	0.0530	13.02	0.0100	2.21	27.7	824.3	2.53E-05	1.1158	4210.3	97.9	0.643
11	11/1	13	3007.7	54.5	4244.5	17.29	2.9530	0.0444	14.23	0.0100	2.22	27.7	892.0	2.50E-05	1.1175	4052.1	98.2	0.544
12	12/1	14	2727.5	50.7	3849.6	17.24	2.6874	0.0415	14.45	0.0104	2.32	29.0	868.1	2.50E-05	1.1231	3693.4	98.1	0.530
13	13/1	14	2446.0	44.8	3452.7	17.17	2.4103	0.0366	14.66	0.0106	2.35	29.4	868.1	2.50E-05	1.1251	3318.3	98.2	0.474
15	15/1	12	2875.9	49.7	4059.8	16.89	2.8142	0.0404	13.97	0.0095	2.11	26.4	916.0	2.49E-05	1.1117	3855.2	98.3	0.473
16	16/1	15	2771.9	53.8	3911.1	17.05	2.7402	0.0441	14.20	0.0106	2.35	29.3	844.5	2.51E-05	1.1242	3756.6	98.1	0.569
17	17/1	13	3079.2	56.1	4346.0	17.12	3.0234	0.0457	13.99	0.0098	2.18	27.2	892.0	2.50E-05	1.1152	4140.4	98.2	0.550
18	18/1	13	3033.2	55.1	4281.5	17.18	2.9784	0.0449	14.11	0.0099	2.20	27.5	892.0	2.50E-05	1.1163	4082.7	98.2	0.545
20	20/1	15	2703.1	52.2	3813.2	16.93	2.6719	0.0428	14.16	0.0105	2.34	29.2	844.5	2.51E-05	1.1238	3661.5	98.1	0.550
22	22/1	13	2052.8	35.2	2899.3	17.01	2.0164	0.0286	14.87	0.0104	2.32	28.9	892.0	2.49E-05	1.1236	2782.0	98.3	0.367
23	23/1	13	2156.6	37.2	3045.5	17.29	2.1182	0.0303	15.06	0.0106	2.35	29.3	892.0	2.48E-05	1.1254	2927.2	98.3	0.393
24	24/1	17	2409.8	49.6	3398.8	16.07	2.3982	0.0409	13.57	0.0107	2.38	29.7	804.1	2.52E-05	1.1251	3267.6	97.9	0.531
26	26/1	19	2189.5	48.0	3087.1	15.95	2.1936	0.0399	13.67	0.0114	2.54	31.8	763.8	2.53E-05	1.1338	2991.4	97.8	0.549
27	27/1	16	2326.8	45.8	3283.4	16.37	2.3083	0.0377	13.97	0.0107	2.38	29.7	824.3	2.51E-05	1.1256	3157.3	98.0	0.490
29	29/1	18	2315.4	49.3	3265.1	17.16	2.3120	0.0408	14.75	0.0120	2.66	33.3	783.9	2.51E-05	1.1420	3186.4	97.9	0.591
30	30/1	17	2336.7	47.8	3295.8	16.77	2.3255	0.0395	14.34	0.0113	2.51	31.4	804.1	2.51E-05	1.1334	3191.9	98.0	0.542
31	31/1	16	2370.2	46.8	3343.8	16.68	2.3510	0.0385	14.23	0.0109	2.42	30.3	824.3	2.51E-05	1.1282	3223.4	98.0	0.510
32	1/2	16	2287.4	44.9	3226.7	16.30	2.2688	0.0369	13.94	0.0107	2.37	29.6	824.3	2.51E-05	1.1252	3102.3	98.0	0.480
33	2/2	14	2592.0	47.8	3657.7	16.18	2.5537	0.0391	13.54	0.0098	2.17	27.1	868.1	2.51E-05	1.1142	3481.7	98.2	0.468

Table AI.6 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R%	Js mg/m ² .h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
34	3/2	17	2374.3	48.8	3348.8	17.80	2.3629	0.0403	15.34	0.0121	2.69	33.6	804.1	2.50E-05	1.1442	3274.3	97.9	0.591
36	5/2	15	2455.8	46.8	3464.8	17.57	2.4276	0.0384	15.04	0.0112	2.48	31.1	844.5	2.49E-05	1.1327	3353.2	98.1	0.524
37	6/2	15	2344.9	44.4	3308.7	16.65	2.3182	0.0364	14.23	0.0106	2.35	29.4	844.5	2.51E-05	1.1245	3178.7	98.1	0.470
38	7/2	16	2140.0	41.6	3019.9	16.60	2.1230	0.0342	14.38	0.0110	2.45	30.6	824.3	2.51E-05	1.1298	2914.9	98.1	0.458
40	9/2	17	1936.0	38.6	2732.4	15.11	1.9275	0.0318	13.08	0.0103	2.29	28.7	804.1	2.53E-05	1.1200	2614.2	98.0	0.398
41	10/2	18	2093.1	43.9	2952.2	17.18	2.0903	0.0363	15.00	0.0122	2.71	33.8	783.9	2.50E-05	1.1448	2887.9	97.9	0.535
44	13/2	20	2285.7	52.5	3221.7	17.30	2.2974	0.0438	14.92	0.0129	2.86	35.7	743.6	2.51E-05	1.1529	3174.6	97.7	0.675
45	14/2	20	2126.8	48.3	2998.3	16.14	2.1379	0.0403	13.90	0.0120	2.66	33.3	743.6	2.53E-05	1.1407	2923.0	97.7	0.579
46	15/2	21	2277.6	54.3	3209.4	15.21	2.2967	0.0455	12.84	0.0114	2.53	31.7	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1322	3106.1	97.6	0.620
47	16/2	20	2495.3	58.0	3516.4	16.07	2.5078	0.0484	13.48	0.0116	2.58	32.3	743.6	2.54E-05	1.1357	3413.7	97.7	0.675
48	17/2	18	2515.9	54.2	3547.3	16.53	2.5120	0.0449	13.93	0.0113	2.51	31.4	783.9	2.52E-05	1.1329	3434.4	97.8	0.614
50	19/2	18	2482.0	53.3	3499.5	16.48	2.4782	0.0442	13.91	0.0113	2.51	31.4	783.9	2.52E-05	1.1326	3387.2	97.9	0.603
51	20/2	20	3109.9	74.8	4380.9	16.57	3.1248	0.0624	13.37	0.0115	2.56	32.0	743.6	2.54E-05	1.1344	4248.6	97.6	0.863
52	21/2	20	2961.0	70.8	4170.8	17.03	2.9750	0.0590	13.98	0.0121	2.68	33.5	743.6	2.53E-05	1.1416	4071.0	97.6	0.853
53	22/2	21	2709.3	66.3	3816.8	15.40	2.7317	0.0555	12.60	0.0112	2.49	31.1	727.1	2.56E-05	1.1293	3685.1	97.6	0.743
54	23/2	21	2399.1	57.6	3380.2	15.68	2.4190	0.0483	13.19	0.0117	2.60	32.5	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1364	3283.7	97.6	0.675
57	26/2	23	2410.7	62.6	3394.8	15.32	2.4466	0.0528	12.81	0.0121	2.68	33.5	694.2	2.56E-05	1.1400	3309.2	97.4	0.756
59	28/2	21	2363.9	56.7	3330.7	15.13	2.3836	0.0474	12.67	0.0113	2.50	31.2	727.1	2.56E-05	1.1302	3218.0	97.6	0.638
60	1/3	20	2348.8	54.7	3332.6	16.78	2.3700	0.0456	14.33	0.0124	2.74	34.3	743.6	2.52E-05	1.1457	3254.7	97.7	0.676
61	2/3	21	2520.8	61.6	3575.3	15.12	2.5516	0.0516	12.50	0.0111	2.47	30.8	727.1	2.56E-05	1.1281	3438.5	97.6	0.684
62	3/3	20	2844.3	68.2	4034.7	16.79	2.8695	0.0569	13.85	0.0119	2.65	33.1	743.6	2.53E-05	1.1400	3921.0	97.6	0.814
64	5/3	22	3130.2	82.3	4435.4	15.21	3.1775	0.0691	11.98	0.0110	2.43	30.4	710.7	2.57E-05	1.1257	4258.4	97.4	0.902
66	7/3	21	2733.0	67.7	3875.9	15.60	2.7663	0.0566	12.77	0.0113	2.52	31.5	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1313	3738.4	97.5	0.768
67	8/3	22	3095.4	81.2	4386.2	15.65	3.1423	0.0682	12.46	0.0114	2.53	31.6	710.7	2.56E-05	1.1315	4232.8	97.4	0.926
69	10/3	21	2947.4	73.8	4179.6	15.94	2.9831	0.0618	12.89	0.0115	2.54	31.8	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1327	4036.5	97.5	0.845

Table AI.6 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jwm m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R%	Js mg/m ² .h
							πfc	πp										
71	12/3	20	2686.4	63.8	3811.0	17.87	2.7104	0.0532	15.07	0.0130	2.89	36.1	710.7	2.53E-05	1.1535	3747.5	97.6	0.830
73	14/3	22	2397.6	60.5	3399.8	15.97	2.4349	0.0508	13.46	0.0123	2.73	34.2	710.7	2.54E-05	1.1439	3316.0	97.5	0.744
74	15/3	21	2669.3	65.8	3785.8	16.01	2.7019	0.0551	13.23	0.0118	2.61	32.6	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1369	3669.4	97.5	0.774
76	17/3	23	1838.4	46.3	2606.9	14.33	1.8733	0.0390	12.37	0.0117	2.59	32.3	694.2	2.57E-05	1.1344	2521.4	97.5	0.540
78	19/3	22	2119.1	52.5	3005.4	15.33	2.1523	0.0441	13.10	0.0120	2.66	33.3	710.7	2.55E-05	1.1395	2919.7	97.5	0.629
81	22/3	22	2214.3	55.2	3140.2	15.75	2.2489	0.0463	13.43	0.0123	2.73	34.1	710.7	2.54E-05	1.1436	3061.7	97.5	0.678
82	23/3	20	2310.5	53.6	3278.2	14.33	2.3313	0.0448	11.91	0.0103	2.28	28.5	743.6	2.57E-05	1.1176	3123.0	97.7	0.551
85	26/3	21	2060.8	48.9	2923.6	15.33	2.0863	0.0409	13.16	0.0117	2.60	32.5	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1361	2831.3	97.6	0.572
86	27/3	21	2148.5	51.3	3047.9	15.75	2.1751	0.0429	13.50	0.0120	2.66	33.3	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1401	2962.2	97.6	0.615
88	29/3	22	1946.2	47.6	2760.4	14.37	1.9768	0.0400	12.31	0.0113	2.50	31.3	710.7	2.57E-05	1.1298	2658.7	97.6	0.536
89	30/3	21	1871.5	43.8	2655.3	14.34	1.8948	0.0367	12.36	0.0110	2.44	30.5	727.1	2.56E-05	1.1265	2549.7	97.7	0.481
90	31/3	20	1922.2	43.5	2727.9	14.93	1.9398	0.0363	12.89	0.0111	2.47	30.8	743.6	2.55E-05	1.1288	2624.4	97.7	0.483
92	2/4	22	1971.1	48.3	2795.6	14.29	2.0020	0.0406	12.20	0.0112	2.48	31.0	710.7	2.57E-05	1.1284	2689.3	97.6	0.539
95	5/4	23	2054.0	52.6	2912.3	15.15	2.0929	0.0443	12.97	0.0122	2.71	33.9	694.2	2.56E-05	1.1422	2836.1	97.4	0.643
96	6/4	21	2064.8	49.0	2929.2	15.24	2.0903	0.0410	13.06	0.0116	2.58	32.2	727.1	2.55E-05	1.1348	2833.6	97.6	0.569
97	7/4	22	2121.1	52.5	3008.1	15.66	2.1542	0.0441	13.42	0.0123	2.73	34.1	710.7	2.54E-05	1.1435	2932.6	97.5	0.645
101	11/4	22	2238.0	55.8	3173.8	15.95	2.2729	0.0469	13.59	0.0124	2.76	34.5	710.7	2.54E-05	1.1457	3100.1	97.5	0.695
102	12/4	22	2343.0	58.9	3322.5	15.60	2.3795	0.0495	13.15	0.0120	2.67	33.4	710.7	2.55E-05	1.1401	3229.7	97.5	0.708
103	13/4	21	2421.4	58.8	3434.5	15.83	2.4511	0.0493	13.31	0.0118	2.62	32.8	727.1	2.54E-05	1.1378	3331.4	97.6	0.696
104	14/4	23	2469.0	65.0	3500.0	15.07	2.5155	0.0548	12.49	0.0118	2.61	32.7	694.2	2.56E-05	1.1360	3390.3	97.4	0.765
107	17/4	24	2537.5	69.7	3594.5	15.04	2.5929	0.0589	12.38	0.0120	2.67	33.3	677.7	2.57E-05	1.1387	3491.2	97.3	0.837
108	18/4	23	2508.5	66.2	3555.9	15.23	2.5557	0.0558	12.60	0.0119	2.64	33.0	694.2	2.56E-05	1.1374	3448.8	97.4	0.786
109	19/4	22	2536.1	64.5	3595.9	15.90	2.5754	0.0542	13.25	0.0121	2.69	33.6	710.7	2.55E-05	1.1413	3499.4	97.5	0.782
110	20/4	25	2515.9	71.6	3562.7	15.60	2.5790	0.0608	12.95	0.0130	2.88	35.9	661.2	2.56E-05	1.1509	3497.8	97.2	0.928
113	23/4	24	2617.4	72.2	3707.5	15.57	2.6745	0.0611	12.84	0.0125	2.77	34.6	677.7	2.56E-05	1.1448	3620.3	97.2	0.900

Table AI.6 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Qp m ³ /h	r% r°	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R°	Js mg/m ² .h
							π _{fc}	π _p										
114	24/4	23	2537.7	67.1	3597.2	15.88	2.5854	0.0565	13.22	0.0125	2.77	34.6	694.2	2.55E-05	1.1454	3513.4	97.4	0.836
115	25/4	24	2529.7	69.4	3583.5	15.23	2.5849	0.0587	12.58	0.0122	2.71	33.9	677.7	2.57E-05	1.1414	3488.8	97.3	0.848
117	27/4	25	2601.4	74.4	3684.5	15.40	2.6669	0.0631	12.67	0.0127	2.81	35.1	661.2	2.57E-05	1.1469	3604.7	97.1	0.942
118	28/4	23	2691.7	71.8	3813.7	15.05	2.7415	0.0605	12.24	0.0115	2.56	32.0	694.2	2.57E-05	1.1328	3684.7	97.3	0.828
120	30/4	24	2586.2	71.2	3663.4	15.43	2.6426	0.0602	12.72	0.0123	2.74	34.3	677.7	2.56E-05	1.1432	3572.2	97.2	0.879
121	1/5	25	2717.8	78.3	3848.2	15.38	2.7857	0.0664	12.53	0.0125	2.78	34.8	661.2	2.57E-05	1.1451	3759.3	97.1	0.981
122	2/5	25	2636.7	75.6	3734.4	15.60	2.7030	0.0641	12.83	0.0128	2.85	35.6	661.2	2.56E-05	1.1492	3660.8	97.1	0.970
124	4/5	23	2344.8	61.2	3324.1	16.12	2.3890	0.0516	13.65	0.0129	2.86	35.7	694.2	2.54E-05	1.1510	3262.5	97.4	0.788
125	5/5	26	2977.1	90.3	4214.9	15.08	3.0615	0.0769	11.98	0.0123	2.74	34.2	647.7	2.58E-05	1.1419	4106.1	97.0	1.114
127	7/5	25	2862.4	83.1	4052.4	16.17	2.9337	0.0705	13.19	0.0132	2.93	36.6	661.2	2.56E-05	1.1541	3990.3	97.1	1.096
128	8/5	25	3303.6	98.1	4678.0	15.70	3.3864	0.0832	12.28	0.0123	2.73	34.1	661.2	2.57E-05	1.1416	4556.0	97.0	1.204
130	10/5	26	2792.1	83.9	3951.8	14.87	2.8708	0.0714	11.95	0.0123	2.73	34.2	647.7	2.58E-05	1.1415	3849.1	97.0	1.032
131	11/5	27	2751.0	85.6	3892.3	15.23	2.8375	0.0731	12.35	0.0131	2.91	36.3	634.2	2.58E-05	1.1518	3825.8	96.9	1.121
132	12/5	25	2531.5	72.2	3584.8	15.61	2.5949	0.0612	12.96	0.0130	2.88	36.0	661.2	2.56E-05	1.1509	3519.7	97.1	0.935
135	15/5	26	2163.1	62.5	3063.9	15.35	2.2251	0.0532	13.06	0.0134	2.99	37.3	647.7	2.56E-05	1.1572	3024.4	97.1	0.840
137	17/5	24	2640.8	73.0	3740.5	15.29	2.6983	0.0617	12.52	0.0122	2.70	33.7	677.7	2.57E-05	1.1406	3639.3	97.2	0.887
138	18/5	25	2612.5	74.8	3700.3	15.08	2.6783	0.0635	12.34	0.0123	2.74	34.2	661.2	2.57E-05	1.1424	3605.9	97.1	0.922
139	19/5	26	2392.7	70.2	3387.5	15.29	2.4606	0.0598	12.77	0.0132	2.92	36.5	647.7	2.56E-05	1.1531	3332.5	97.1	0.923
141	21/5	26	2458.9	72.4	3481.1	15.18	2.5286	0.0617	12.59	0.0130	2.88	36.0	647.7	2.57E-05	1.1506	3417.2	97.1	0.940
143	23/5	26	2202.1	63.8	3119.0	14.55	2.2651	0.0543	12.22	0.0126	2.79	34.9	647.7	2.58E-05	1.1453	3047.1	97.1	0.802
144	24/5	27	2148.1	64.3	3041.6	14.96	2.2166	0.0549	12.68	0.0135	2.99	37.3	634.2	2.57E-05	1.1567	3001.3	97.0	0.865
145	25/5	25	1799.1	48.7	2549.8	15.95	1.8451	0.0413	14.02	0.0140	3.11	38.9	661.2	2.54E-05	1.1659	2535.1	97.3	0.683
148	28/5	28	1931.5	59.1	2734.5	13.60	1.9996	0.0506	11.53	0.0126	2.80	35.0	620.7	2.60E-05	1.1444	2669.8	96.9	0.744
149	29/5	29	1911.3	60.5	2705.0	14.11	1.9848	0.0521	12.06	0.0136	3.01	37.7	607.2	2.58E-05	1.1571	2670.7	96.8	0.822
150	30/5	28	1964.3	60.2	2780.8	13.85	2.0335	0.0516	11.75	0.0128	2.85	35.6	620.7	2.59E-05	1.1476	2722.8	96.9	0.773

Table AI.6 Results of Long-Term Operate Simulation of GARO2 by Application of Winflows 4.04 Programing (Continues)

Time (days)	Feed Flow Rate Qf = 8 m ³ /h																	
	Date 2022	Temp. (T)° C	Cf mg/l	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Pf bar	Osmotic Pressure bar		NDP bar	Jw _m m/s	Op m ³ /h	r% r%	Sc m ² /s	Kcp	β	Cm mg/l	R% R%	Js mg/m ² .h
							π _{ic}	π _p										
151	31/5	29	2108.4	67.8	2983.6	14.90	2.1894	0.0583	12.65	0.0142	3.16	39.5	607.2	2.57E-05	1.1664	2969.8	96.8	0.965
152	1/6	29	2209.5	71.6	3125.2	14.88	2.2937	0.0615	12.53	0.0141	3.13	39.1	607.2	2.57E-05	1.1645	3106.2	96.8	1.009
153	2/6	30	2324.8	78.7	3286.8	15.49	2.4208	0.0679	13.02	0.0151	3.35	41.9	593.7	2.56E-05	1.1780	3305.2	96.6	1.187
155	4/6	29	2356.3	77.0	3333.3	15.36	2.4463	0.0662	12.86	0.0145	3.21	40.2	607.2	2.56E-05	1.1698	3327.9	96.7	1.115
157	6/6	30	2908.1	101.9	4111.4	15.08	3.0281	0.0879	12.02	0.0139	3.09	38.7	593.7	2.59E-05	1.1615	4076.7	96.5	1.419
158	7/6	31	2967.4	108.1	4193.4	14.23	3.0993	0.0936	11.10	0.0133	2.94	36.8	583.1	2.61E-05	1.1517	4123.5	96.4	1.434
159	8/6	33	3124.7	123.4	4411.6	14.70	3.2833	0.1075	11.41	0.0145	3.21	40.1	561.9	2.60E-05	1.1673	4398.4	96.1	1.784
160	9/6	33	3452.1	138.5	4873.4	14.45	3.6271	0.1207	10.83	0.0137	3.05	38.1	561.9	2.61E-05	1.1570	4816.4	96.0	1.901
163	12/6	30	2774.0	96.4	3922.1	14.90	2.8886	0.0832	11.97	0.0139	3.08	38.5	593.7	2.59E-05	1.1608	3886.4	96.5	1.339
164	13/6	30	2847.6	99.4	4025.9	14.79	2.9651	0.0858	11.79	0.0137	3.03	37.9	593.7	2.59E-05	1.1578	3979.1	96.5	1.359
165	14/6	31	3577.3	134.4	5053.5	15.34	3.7355	0.1163	11.61	0.0139	3.08	38.5	583.1	2.59E-05	1.1600	5006.0	96.2	1.863
166	15/6	32	3308.3	127.2	4672.2	14.63	3.4654	0.1105	11.17	0.0137	3.05	38.1	572.5	2.61E-05	1.1577	4619.4	96.2	1.747
167	16/6	34	3386.2	140.4	4778.5	14.95	3.5687	0.1227	11.39	0.0149	3.30	41.3	551.3	2.60E-05	1.1724	4786.3	95.9	2.087
169	18/6	32	3316.1	127.6	4683.3	13.89	3.4736	0.1108	10.42	0.0128	2.84	35.6	572.5	2.63E-05	1.1452	4580.3	96.2	1.634
171	20/6	32	3193.4	122.1	4510.3	14.07	3.3452	0.1060	10.72	0.0132	2.93	36.6	572.5	2.62E-05	1.1502	4430.3	96.2	1.610
172	21/6	33	3443.1	138.1	4860.8	15.46	3.6177	0.1203	11.84	0.0150	3.33	41.6	561.9	2.58E-05	1.1749	4878.3	96.0	2.072
173	22/6	31	2486.6	88.2	3513.5	14.12	2.5969	0.0763	11.48	0.0137	3.04	38.0	583.1	2.60E-05	1.1578	3473.6	96.5	1.209
174	23/6	31	3417.6	127.4	4828.4	14.75	3.5689	0.1103	11.17	0.0133	2.96	37.0	583.1	2.61E-05	1.1528	4752.9	96.3	1.700
176	25/6	33	4311.4	179.7	6080.5	14.74	4.5273	0.1565	10.25	0.0130	2.88	36.0	561.9	2.63E-05	1.1470	5959.6	95.8	2.333
177	26/6	32	3937.6	155.9	5557.2	13.55	4.1229	0.1354	9.45	0.0116	2.58	32.3	572.5	2.65E-05	1.1295	5362.1	96.0	1.812
178	27/6	32	3783.1	148.8	5339.1	14.13	3.9612	0.1292	10.19	0.0125	2.78	34.8	572.5	2.63E-05	1.1414	5206.0	96.1	1.864
180	29/6	34	3460.5	144.1	4880.3	13.90	3.6456	0.1260	10.27	0.0134	2.97	37.2	551.3	2.63E-05	1.1521	4804.7	95.8	1.931
181	30/6	34	3581.1	149.9	5050.1	14.33	3.7725	0.1311	10.57	0.0138	3.06	38.3	551.3	2.62E-05	1.1574	4994.8	95.8	2.068

Appendix I

A.6 Deviation Percentage %

Table AI.7 The Deviation Percentage % of Results between Experimental and Winflows 4.04 Application.

Deviation Percentage %												
Time (days)	Date 2022	Qp m ³ /h	Js mg/m ² .h	Jw _m m/s	NDP bar	Pf bar	β	K _{cp}	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Cm mg/l	R%
2	2/1	4.62	8.34	4.62	4.62	3.72	0.53	-0.36	3.89	2.96	2.27	-0.08
3	3/1	3.23	11.37	3.23	3.23	3.95	0.39	-0.26	8.41	9.92	6.42	-0.19
4	4/1	6.66	0.42	6.66	6.66	3.89	0.81	-0.55	-6.69	-9.31	-4.39	0.12
5	5/1	7.20	1.15	7.20	7.20	3.89	0.87	-0.59	-6.52	-10.36	-4.89	0.12
8	8/1	4.53	6.32	4.53	4.53	4.24	0.54	-0.36	1.88	5.56	3.85	-0.04
9	9/1	5.68	7.53	5.68	5.68	4.26	0.73	-0.50	1.96	-3.27	-1.14	-0.04
10	10/1	4.23	12.22	4.23	4.23	4.48	0.52	-0.36	8.35	9.46	6.25	-0.19
11	11/1	5.40	-0.91	5.40	5.40	4.21	0.69	-0.46	-6.67	-3.29	-1.20	0.12
12	12/1	4.42	8.93	4.42	4.42	4.22	0.58	-0.39	4.71	5.58	3.91	-0.09
13	13/1	4.19	12.05	4.19	4.19	4.24	0.56	-0.38	8.20	7.99	5.37	-0.17
15	15/1	4.30	13.20	4.30	4.30	4.31	0.51	-0.34	9.30	7.69	5.14	-0.18
16	16/1	5.88	1.94	5.88	5.88	4.27	0.80	-0.54	-4.18	-8.75	-4.10	0.08
17	17/1	4.20	14.37	4.20	4.20	4.25	0.52	-0.35	10.61	7.91	5.28	-0.22
18	18/1	5.92	1.45	5.92	5.92	4.24	0.75	-0.50	-4.75	-8.08	-3.79	0.08
20	20/1	5.77	-0.99	5.77	5.77	4.30	0.78	-0.53	-7.18	-7.62	-3.51	0.13
22	22/1	5.41	-0.57	5.41	5.41	4.28	0.72	-0.49	-6.32	-8.46	-4.03	0.10
23	23/1	4.00	11.17	4.00	4.00	4.21	0.54	-0.36	7.46	9.78	6.47	-0.14
24	24/1	4.60	13.90	4.60	4.60	4.52	0.62	-0.42	9.74	7.25	4.96	-0.23
26	26/1	5.86	2.82	5.86	5.86	4.55	0.86	-0.59	-3.23	-7.67	-3.46	0.07
27	27/1	4.23	13.66	4.23	4.23	4.44	0.57	-0.39	9.85	9.86	6.55	-0.22
29	29/1	5.38	4.76	5.38	5.38	4.24	0.83	-0.57	-0.65	-6.20	-2.68	0.01
30	30/1	5.03	14.01	5.03	5.03	4.34	0.73	-0.50	9.46	0.36	0.93	-0.22
31	31/1	5.53	-2.11	5.53	5.53	4.36	0.77	-0.53	-8.09	-5.82	-2.53	0.15
32	1/2	5.30	2.02	5.30	5.30	4.45	0.72	-0.49	-3.46	-1.57	-0.19	0.07
33	2/2	6.02	-0.43	6.02	6.02	4.49	0.75	-0.51	-6.86	-7.86	-3.68	0.12
34	3/2	4.33	14.81	4.33	4.33	4.09	0.67	-0.46	10.95	4.85	3.55	-0.26
36	5/2	3.96	11.68	3.96	3.96	4.15	0.56	-0.38	8.04	9.13	6.08	-0.17
37	6/2	5.27	-4.11	5.27	5.27	4.37	0.71	-0.48	-9.90	-2.67	-0.83	0.17
38	7/2	5.45	-0.08	5.45	5.45	4.38	0.77	-0.52	-5.86	-6.10	-2.69	0.11
40	9/2	6.09	-3.28	6.09	6.09	4.79	0.80	-0.55	-9.98	-8.84	-4.15	0.18
41	10/2	4.33	9.49	4.33	4.33	4.24	0.68	-0.46	5.39	6.34	4.46	-0.12
44	13/2	4.33	13.49	4.33	4.33	4.21	0.72	-0.50	9.57	6.20	4.41	-0.25
45	14/2	5.69	2.66	5.69	5.69	4.50	0.87	-0.61	-3.21	-6.77	-2.94	0.07
46	15/2	6.21	-3.30	6.21	6.21	4.76	0.90	-0.63	-10.14	-7.55	-3.34	0.22
47	16/2	5.76	1.52	5.76	5.76	4.52	0.85	-0.59	-4.50	-4.77	-1.86	0.10
48	17/2	5.75	-3.78	5.75	5.75	4.40	0.83	-0.57	-10.12	-6.90	-3.06	0.20
50	19/2	4.46	7.07	4.46	4.46	4.41	0.64	-0.44	2.74	7.16	4.93	-0.06
51	20/2	4.21	14.49	4.21	4.21	4.39	0.61	-0.42	10.74	8.97	6.02	-0.30
52	21/2	4.56	6.19	4.56	4.56	4.27	0.70	-0.48	1.71	5.08	3.71	-0.04
53	22/2	6.51	-3.65	6.51	6.51	4.70	0.93	-0.65	-10.86	-8.34	-3.75	0.25
54	23/2	6.27	0.21	6.27	6.27	4.62	0.94	-0.66	-6.46	-9.74	-4.48	0.15

Appendix I

Table AI.7 The Deviation Percentage % of Results between Experimental and Winflows 4.04 Application (Continues).

Deviation Percentage %												
Time (days)	Date 2022	Qp m ³ /h	Js mg/m ² .h	Jwm m/s	NDP bar	Pf bar	β	Kcp	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Cm mg/l	R%
57	26/2	5.83	-3.02	5.83	5.83	4.73	0.89	-0.63	-9.40	-2.69	-0.65	0.23
59	28/2	4.89	11.89	4.89	4.89	4.78	0.69	-0.48	7.36	7.43	5.14	-0.20
60	1/3	4.75	10.14	4.75	4.75	4.33	0.75	-0.52	5.66	3.34	2.72	-0.14
61	2/3	5.37	9.77	5.37	5.37	4.79	0.75	-0.52	4.66	3.46	2.79	-0.12
62	3/3	4.85	8.60	4.85	4.85	4.33	0.74	-0.51	3.95	3.26	2.66	-0.10
64	5/3	5.59	0.67	5.59	5.59	4.76	0.77	-0.54	-5.22	2.44	2.20	0.13
66	7/3	5.35	13.25	5.35	5.35	4.65	0.76	-0.53	8.35	2.59	2.29	-0.23
67	8/3	5.59	8.84	5.59	5.59	4.63	0.80	-0.56	3.44	1.33	1.58	-0.10
69	10/3	4.96	0.94	4.96	4.96	4.55	0.71	-0.50	-4.22	4.65	3.48	0.10
71	12/3	4.33	-1.74	4.33	4.33	4.08	0.72	-0.50	-6.35	4.44	3.35	0.15
73	14/3	4.65	-2.30	4.65	4.65	4.54	0.73	-0.51	-7.29	6.54	4.64	0.18
74	15/3	4.79	6.06	4.79	4.79	4.53	0.71	-0.49	1.33	5.66	4.08	-0.03
76	17/3	5.33	27.33	5.33	5.33	5.04	0.78	-0.55	23.24	6.42	4.62	-0.79
78	19/3	5.68	10.91	5.68	5.68	4.72	0.87	-0.61	5.55	-2.19	-0.39	-0.15
81	22/3	5.91	13.11	5.91	5.91	4.60	0.93	-0.65	7.65	-6.40	-2.69	-0.21
82	23/3	5.54	1.46	5.54	5.54	5.04	0.71	-0.49	-4.32	4.15	3.17	0.10
85	26/3	5.62	-2.19	5.62	5.62	4.72	0.84	-0.58	-8.28	-2.31	-0.50	0.19
86	27/3	5.82	4.59	5.82	5.82	4.60	0.89	-0.62	-1.30	-6.24	-2.64	0.03
88	29/3	6.44	15.03	6.44	6.44	5.02	0.92	-0.64	9.18	-7.81	-3.48	-0.25
89	30/3	5.98	12.34	5.98	5.98	5.03	0.83	-0.58	6.77	-2.12	-0.39	-0.17
90	31/3	5.03	10.41	5.03	5.03	4.84	0.70	-0.49	5.67	6.51	4.60	-0.14
92	2/4	6.67	12.61	6.67	6.67	5.05	0.94	-0.66	6.36	-10.30	-4.79	-0.17
95	5/4	5.06	-2.93	5.06	5.06	4.78	0.78	-0.55	-8.41	5.08	3.80	0.20
96	6/4	5.01	-1.17	5.01	5.01	4.75	0.73	-0.51	-6.50	5.33	3.91	0.15
97	7/4	4.81	6.40	4.81	4.81	4.63	0.75	-0.52	1.67	6.15	4.42	-0.04
101	11/4	4.73	9.71	4.73	4.73	4.55	0.75	-0.52	5.23	6.15	4.42	-0.14
102	12/4	6.19	3.75	6.19	6.19	4.65	0.95	-0.67	-2.60	-8.42	-3.77	0.07
103	13/4	5.72	10.14	5.72	5.72	4.58	0.86	-0.60	4.68	-3.28	-1.02	-0.12
104	14/4	5.28	10.05	5.28	5.28	4.80	0.78	-0.55	5.04	4.35	3.36	-0.14
107	17/4	6.66	11.38	6.66	6.66	4.81	1.02	-0.72	5.06	-8.54	-3.76	-0.15
108	18/4	5.26	9.10	5.26	5.26	4.75	0.79	-0.55	4.06	4.05	3.18	-0.11
109	19/4	5.79	10.06	5.79	5.79	4.56	0.90	-0.63	4.53	-3.54	-1.13	-0.12
110	20/4	6.39	10.68	6.39	6.39	4.65	1.07	-0.76	4.58	-8.76	-3.83	-0.14
113	23/4	5.88	4.45	5.88	5.88	4.65	0.93	-0.66	-1.52	-2.77	-0.66	0.04
114	24/4	5.65	4.23	5.65	5.65	4.57	0.90	-0.63	-1.51	-2.25	-0.39	0.04
115	25/4	5.09	2.88	5.09	5.09	4.75	0.78	-0.55	-2.33	5.21	3.88	0.06
117	27/4	5.22	11.55	5.22	5.22	4.70	0.84	-0.59	6.68	4.11	3.27	-0.21
118	28/4	5.25	8.09	5.25	5.25	4.81	0.76	-0.53	3.00	4.98	3.72	-0.08
120	30/4	5.03	8.42	5.03	5.03	4.69	0.78	-0.55	3.57	5.45	4.02	-0.11
121	1/5	5.20	8.44	5.20	5.20	4.71	0.82	-0.58	3.42	4.40	3.43	-0.11
122	2/5	4.66	8.53	4.66	4.66	4.65	0.76	-0.53	4.05	7.85	5.47	-0.12

Appendix I

Table AI.7 The Deviation Percentage % of Results between Experimental and Winflows 4.04 Application (Continues).

Deviation Percentage %												
Time (days)	Date 2022	Qp m ³ /h	Js mg/m ² .h	Jwm m/s	NDP bar	Pf bar	β	Kcp	Cp mg/l	Cc mg/l	Cm mg/l	R%
124	4/5	5.11	11.23	5.11	5.11	4.50	0.84	-0.59	6.45	1.95	1.98	-0.19
125	5/5	5.46	9.48	5.46	5.46	4.80	0.85	-0.60	4.25	3.86	3.12	-0.14
127	7/5	6.14	12.66	6.14	6.14	4.49	1.05	-0.74	6.94	-6.04	-2.37	-0.22
128	8/5	6.81	10.47	6.81	6.81	4.62	1.07	-0.76	3.93	-7.24	-3.01	-0.13
130	10/5	5.15	7.59	5.15	5.15	4.86	0.79	-0.56	2.58	6.33	4.57	-0.08
131	11/5	5.00	3.89	5.00	5.00	4.75	0.83	-0.59	-1.17	6.15	4.49	0.04
132	12/5	5.19	6.48	5.19	5.19	4.64	0.85	-0.60	1.37	3.32	2.81	-0.04
135	15/5	4.70	-0.09	4.70	4.70	4.72	0.80	-0.57	-5.03	8.03	5.64	0.14
137	17/5	5.67	11.23	5.67	5.67	4.74	0.87	-0.62	5.89	0.66	1.26	-0.18
138	18/5	5.91	0.48	5.91	5.91	4.80	0.93	-0.66	-5.77	-1.20	0.23	0.16
139	19/5	6.33	10.03	6.33	6.33	4.74	1.07	-0.76	3.95	-7.49	-3.14	-0.12
141	21/5	6.56	10.35	6.56	6.56	4.77	1.10	-0.78	4.05	-8.99	-3.92	-0.13
143	23/5	5.22	10.57	5.22	5.22	4.96	0.83	-0.59	5.64	6.34	4.61	-0.18
144	24/5	5.17	14.07	5.17	5.17	4.83	0.89	-0.63	9.38	5.38	4.08	-0.32
145	25/5	4.75	13.95	4.75	4.75	4.55	0.86	-0.61	9.66	5.77	4.29	-0.30
148	28/5	5.54	8.72	5.54	5.54	5.29	0.88	-0.63	3.37	6.78	4.93	-0.11
149	29/5	5.37	8.23	5.37	5.37	5.11	0.93	-0.66	3.03	6.27	4.66	-0.10
150	30/5	5.67	10.81	5.67	5.67	5.20	0.92	-0.66	5.45	4.56	3.62	-0.18
151	31/5	6.39	11.20	6.39	6.39	4.85	1.18	-0.85	5.14	-8.43	-3.53	-0.18
152	1/6	4.72	10.03	4.72	4.72	4.86	0.85	-0.61	5.57	9.63	6.67	-0.20
153	2/6	5.99	4.37	5.99	5.99	4.68	1.19	-0.85	-1.72	-5.25	-1.79	0.06
155	4/6	7.24	10.24	7.24	7.24	4.71	1.38	-1.00	3.23	-20.28	-9.43	-0.11
157	6/6	4.82	10.57	4.82	4.82	4.80	0.85	-0.61	6.04	8.13	5.74	-0.23
158	7/6	5.06	9.75	5.06	5.06	5.07	0.84	-0.61	4.93	8.69	6.07	-0.20
159	8/6	7.28	5.67	7.28	7.28	4.92	1.37	-1.00	-1.73	-7.72	-2.95	0.07
160	9/6	6.28	9.47	6.28	6.28	5.00	1.09	-0.80	3.41	1.79	2.14	-0.15
163	12/6	6.66	9.16	6.66	6.66	4.85	1.19	-0.86	2.68	-5.72	-2.04	-0.10
164	13/6	5.19	9.82	5.19	5.19	4.89	0.90	-0.65	4.89	6.42	4.72	-0.19
165	14/6	5.11	9.66	5.11	5.11	4.72	0.90	-0.65	4.80	6.06	4.50	-0.20
166	15/6	5.03	11.09	5.03	5.03	4.94	0.87	-0.63	6.38	7.99	5.67	-0.27
167	16/6	4.50	10.32	4.50	4.50	4.84	0.85	-0.62	6.09	9.95	6.87	-0.28
169	18/6	8.13	13.06	8.13	8.13	5.19	1.33	-0.97	5.36	-8.30	-3.30	-0.23
171	20/6	5.12	10.29	5.12	5.12	5.12	0.84	-0.61	5.44	8.74	6.11	-0.23
172	21/6	4.80	9.11	4.80	4.80	4.69	0.92	-0.67	4.53	7.37	5.33	-0.20
173	22/6	5.57	10.63	5.57	5.57	5.11	0.97	-0.70	5.36	5.41	4.18	-0.21
174	23/6	7.76	12.39	7.76	7.76	4.90	1.34	-0.97	5.02	-9.08	-3.72	-0.21
176	25/6	7.70	6.48	7.70	7.70	4.90	1.27	-0.93	-1.31	-3.79	-0.88	0.06
177	26/6	5.36	9.39	5.36	5.36	5.31	0.76	-0.55	4.26	8.72	6.01	-0.18
178	27/6	5.33	8.44	5.33	5.33	5.10	0.82	-0.60	3.28	7.60	5.38	-0.14
180	29/6	3.98	5.74	3.98	3.98	5.18	0.66	-0.48	1.83	13.63	9.05	-0.08
181	30/6	5.12	10.48	5.12	5.12	5.04	0.88	-0.64	5.66	8.23	5.83	-0.26

APPENDIX

AII

*Behavior and
Guidelines of Winflows
4.04 Programming*

Appendix II

Behavior and Guidelines of Winflows 4.04 Programming

AII.1 The main interface of the program

Fig 3.1 GARO1 desalination plant diagram

Fig 3.1 GARO1 desalination plant diagram

Appendix II

Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram

Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram

Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram

Appendix II

Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram **Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram**
AII.2 Help Lists

Winflows RO Element Design Guidelines															
Water Source			RO Permeate	Brackish Well Water	Brackish Surface Water		Seawater Well	Surface Seawater		Tertiary Treated Wastewater		MBR Permeate	High pH RO		
Pre-Treatment			RO		MF/UF	Conventional		MF/UF	Conventional	MF/UF	Conventional	MBR	City/Well	Waste Water	2nd Pass
Parameters	Condition	Unit													
SDI15	Max		1	3	3	5	3	3	5	3	5	2			
Permeate Flux	Max Avg	m/hr	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.06
	Typical Range	m/hr	0.03 - 0.04	0.02 - 0.03	0.02 - 0.03	0.02 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.02	0.02 - 0.02			
Lead Element Flux	Max	m/hr	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.07
Element Recovery	Max(flux >18 ...	%	35	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	40	33	50
	Max(flux <12 ...	%	35	22	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	40	33	50
Flux, % annual de	Default Value	%	2	3	3	5	4	5	7	10	15	5	3	5	2
Salt Passage, % ar	Default Value	%	2	5	5	7	5	5	7	10	15	5			
Max Feed Flow	16" elem	m3/day	1635.3	1635.3	1417.3	1308.2	1635.3	1417.3	1308.2	1199.2	1090.2	1417.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
	8" elem	m3/day	408.8	408.8	354.3	327.1	408.8	354.3	327.1	299.8	272.5	354.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
	4" elem	m3/day	87.2	87.2	76.3	70.9	87.2	76.3	70.9	65.4	60.0	76.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
	2.5" elem	m3/day	32.7	32.7	27.3	21.8	32.7	27.3	21.8	21.8	21.8	27.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Min Conc. Flow	16" elem	m3/day	174.4	174.4	218.0	218.0	218.0	218.0	218.0	218.0	218.0	218.0	305.3	436.1	218.0
	8" elem	m3/day	43.6	43.6	54.5	54.5	54.5	54.5	54.5	54.5	54.5	54.5	76.3	109.0	54.5
	4" elem	m3/day	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	21.8	27.3	10.9
	2.5" elem	m3/day	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0

Note: Click on Unit cell to change into another Unit

Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram

Tips on Designing RO Units Operating on Natural Waters with Below 5000 mg/L TDS

The below instructions are a guide how to design simple RO units where the flow rates are big enough so 18 or more elements are required, and the osmotic pressure of the feed small enough to make it possible to operate above 65 percent permeate recovery. In this case, the task is to design an RO unit that at 80 percent permeate recovery will produce 1.5×10^6 gpd permeate with below 200 mg/L TDS from deep well water with 2000 mg/L TDS.

1. **Determine which RO elements to use.**
 - a. 8" diameter elements are chosen. Those are typically available in 365, 400 and 430 ft² active membrane area versions. Typically, the more active membrane area, the thinner is the feed channel spacer, and the higher is the fouling tendency of the element. In this case, the feed is deep well water with low fouling tendency, so a 400-ft²-element model is chosen.
2. **Determine approximate number of RO elements**
 - a. Select the average permeate flux, for example from Design Guidelines. In this example, the feed water is deep well water with a very low fouling tendency, so 15 gfd average permeate flux is chosen.
 - b. Calculate the number of elements required (N) from the permeate flow rate (Fp), average permeate flux (Jw), and the active membrane area per element (AA).
 $F_p = N \cdot AA \cdot J_w$, which in this case gives $N = 250$ elements.
3. **Determine number of element housings.**
 - a. There are typically 6 or 7 elements per housing. In this case, 7 elements per housing is chosen, which gives 36 element housings.
4. **Determine array.**
 - a. The below table is used to determine how to approximately arrange the housings.

Permeate Recovery, %	Typical array* Housings in 1 st stage	
i. 65-80	2-1	2/3 of total
ii. 80-90	4-2-1	4/7 of total

* or multiple of it

At 80 percent permeate recovery, a two-stage array will probably work fine, which means that about 2/3 of the housings will be in the first stage. Thus, try a 24-12 array.
5. **Run Winflows with the 24-12 array and look for**
 - a. Warnings
 - b. Element permeate recovery (shown in Winflows Explorer) not too high <15-20%. The lower the permeate flux, the higher element recovery is acceptable
 - c. The permeate flux (shown in Winflows Explorer) profile not too skewed (preferably, the flux of the last element should be at least half the flux of the leading element). It is possible that an interstage booster pump or permeate backpressure in the first stage is needed to balance the permeate flux between the stages.
 - d. The pressure drop over the elements
 - e. The predicted permeate TDS should be below the maximum allowed.

Fig 3.1 GAROI desalination plant diagram

Appendix II

Application	Element Subgroup	Model	GPD	Rejection %	Test Conditions *		FCS**
					Feed TDS mg/L	Pressure psig	Feed spacer T, mil
Seawater RO	High Rejection	AC-400,34	5800	99.85	32000	800	34
Seawater RO	High Rejection	AC-440	6400	99.85	32000	800	28
Seawater RO	High Rejection	AD-90	1400	99.8	32000	800	28
Seawater RO	High Rejection	AD-365	6500	99.8	32000	800	34
Seawater RO	High Rejection	AD-400,34	7000	99.8	32000	800	34
Seawater RO	High Rejection	AD-440	7700	99.8	32000	800	28
Seawater RO	Low Energy	AE-90	2000	99.8	32000	800	28
Seawater RO	Low Energy	AE-400,34	9000	99.8	32000	800	34
Seawater RO	Low Energy	AE-440	9900	99.8	32000	800	28
BW RO PA	Standard	AG2540TM	750	99.5	2000	225	28
BW RO PA	Standard	AG4040C	2400	99.5	2000	225	28
BW RO PA	Standard	AG4040FM	2400	99.5	2000	225	27
BW RO PA	Standard	AG4040FM,34	2200	99.5	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	Standard	AG8040C	10000	99.5	2000	225	28
BW RO PA	Standard	AG8040F	10000	99.5	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	Standard	AG8040F 400	11000	99.5	2000	225	27
BW RO PA	Standard	AG8040N	9600	99.2	2000	225	31
BW RO PA	Standard	AG8040N 400	10500	99.2	2000	225	27
BW RO Low Foul.	Standard	AG4040F LF	2300	99.5	2000	225	27
BW RO Low Foul.	Standard	AG8040F 365 LF	9500	99.5	2000	225	31
BW RO Low Foul.	Standard	AG8040F 400 LF	11000	99.5	2000	225	27
BW RO FR	Standard	AG8040F400FR,34	11000	99.5	2000	225	34
BW RO Low Foul.	Duraslick RO	DSL RO2540	750	99.5	2000	225	31
BW RO Low Foul.	Duraslick RO	DSL RO4040	2300	99.5	2000	225	31
BW RO Low Foul.	Duraslick RO	DSL RO8040	10000	99.5	2000	225	31
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-90	2400	99.8	2000	225	28
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-365	10000	99.8	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-400	11000	99.8	2000	225	31
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-400,34	11000	99.8	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-440	12000	99.8	2000	225	28
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-400 H	11000	99.8	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	High Rejection	AG-440 H	12000	99.8	2000	225	28
BW RO FR	High Rejection	AG-400 FR H	11000	99.8	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	Mid Energy	AG8040F-400 LE	9590	99	2000	150	34
BW RO PA	Mid Energy	AG-400 LE H	10000	99.5	2000	150	34
BW RO PA	Mid Energy	AG-440 LE H	11000	99.5	2000	150	28
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO3 4040F35	2280	99	2000	425	35
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO3 8040F35	9370	99	2000	425	35
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO5 4040F35	2640	99.5	2000	225	35
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO5 8040F35	11050	99.5	2000	225	35
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO7 4040F35	2640	92	500	75	35
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO7 8040F35	12610	92	500	75	35

Appendix II

BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO5 HP4040F35	2200	99.5	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO5 HP8040F35	9200	99.5	2000	225	34
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO7 HP4040F35	2200	92	500	75	35
BW RO PA	Ind High Press.	RO7 HP8040F35	9200	92	500	75	35
BW RO PA	Low Energy, Std	AK2540TM	750	99	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Low Energy, Std	AK4040C	2300	99	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Low Energy, Std	AK4040FM	2200	99	500	115	27
BW RO PA	Low Energy, Std	AK8040C	10000	99	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Low Energy, Std	AK8040F	10000	99	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Low Energy, Std	AK8040F 400	11000	99	500	115	27
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-90	2300	99.5	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-365	10000	99.5	500	115	34
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-400	11000	99.5	500	115	31
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-440	12000	99.5	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-400,34	11000	99.5	500	115	34
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-400 H	11000	99.65	500	115	34
BW RO PA	Low Energy, HR	AK-440 H	12000	99.65	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Lower Energy, HR	AK-90 LE	2900	99.3	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Lower Energy, HR	AK-400 LE,34	12900	99.3	500	115	31
BW RO PA	Lower Energy, HR	AK-440 LE	14000	99.3	500	115	28
BW RO PA	Ultra Low Energy	AP-90	2300	95	500	75	34
BW RO PA	Ultra Low Energy	AP-365	10000	95	500	75	34
BW RO PA	Ultra Low Energy	AP-400	11000	95	500	75	31
NF PA	On Shore	HL2540FM	840	99.5	2000	110	28
NF PA	On Shore	HL4040FM	2700	99.5	2000	110	27
NF PA	On Shore	HL8040F 400	13000	99.5	2000	110	27
NF PA	Duraslick NF	DSL NF2540	600	98	2000	110	31
NF PA	Duraslick NF	DSL NF4040	2400	98	2000	110	31
NF PA	Duraslick NF	DSL NF8040	8600	98	2000	110	31
NF PA	Process NF	DK-400	9500	99.6	2000	110	34
NF PA	Process NF	DK-440	10500	99.6	2000	110	28
NF PA	Process NF	DK4040F30	1900	98	2000	110	31
NF PA	Process NF	DK8040F30	8100	98	2000	110	31
NF PA	Process NF	DL8040F30	10200	96	2000	110	31
NF PA	Process NF	IND NF1 4040F35	1600	99	2000	110	35
NF PA	Process NF	IND NF1 8040F35	6610	99	2000	110	35
Municipal	High Rejection	MUNI-RO-400-HR	11000	99.8	2000	225	31
Municipal	High Rejection	MUNI-RO-430-HR	12000	99.8	2000	225	28
Municipal	Low Energy	MUN-RO-400-LEFF	11000	98.5	500	115	31
Municipal	Low Energy, HR	MUN-RO-400HR-LE	11000	99.5	500	115	31
Municipal	Low Energy, HR	MUN-RO-430HR-LE	12000	99.5	500	115	28
Municipal	Ultra Low Energy	MUNI-RO-400-ULE	11000	95	500	75	31
Municipal	NF PA	MUNI-NF-400	13000	99.5	2000	110	27
Food & Bev RO	Standard RO	BEV-RO-CG	10000	99	2000	225	34
Food & Bev RO	Standard RO	BEV-RO-FF	10000	99	2000	225	34
Food & Bev RO	Standard RO	BEV-RO-400-CG	11000	99	2000	225	31
Food & Bev RO	Standard RO	BEV-RO-400-FF	11000	99	2000	225	31

Appendix II

Food & Bev RO	Standard RO	BEV-RO-440-CG	12000	99	2000	225	28
Food & Bev RO	Standard RO	BEV-RO-440-FF	12000	99	2000	225	28
Food & Bev RO	Low Energy RO	BEV-RO-LE-FF	10000	98.5	500	115	34
Food & Bev RO	Low Energy RO	BEV-RO-LE-400FF	11000	98.5	500	115	31
Food & Bev RO	Low Energy RO	BEV-RO-LE-440FF	12000	98.5	500	115	28
Food & Bev RO	Ultra Low Ener. RO	OSMO-BEV-ULE-CG	10000	95	500	75	31
Pharma	USPG	416-USPG	2400	99	2000	225	31
Pharma	USPG	813-USPG	10000	99	2000	225	31
Pharma	USPG	817-USPG	10000	99	2000	225	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS NF	HWS NF4040	2100	96	2000	110	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS NF	HWS NF8040	9000	96	2000	110	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS RO	HWS RO 2540	400	99	500	115	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS RO	HWS RO 4040	1100	99	500	115	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS RO	HWS RO 8040	4600	99	500	115	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS RO	HWS RO 2540 HR	450	99.5	2000	225	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS RO	HWS RO 4040 HR	1800	99.5	2000	225	31
High Temp Disin.	Dtherm HWS RO	HWS RO 8040 HR	7500	99.5	2000	225	31
High Temp Oper.	Duratherm RO	DTh STD RO 4040	1800	99.5	2000	225	31
High Temp Oper.	Duratherm RO	DTh STD RO 8040	7500	99.5	2000	225	31
CA Elements	High Rejection	CE8040F	6700	97.5	2000	425	28
CA Elements	NF CA	BEV-NF-400-FF	9400	97	2000	225	31
OSMO Legacy	RO PA	411-HR(PA)	1600	99.5	2000	225	34
OSMO Legacy	RO PA	416-HR(PA)	2200	99	2000	225	31
OSMO Legacy	RO PA	813-HR(PA)	10200	99	2000	225	31
OSMO Legacy	RO PA	815-HR(PA)	9000	99.5	2000	225	31
OSMO Legacy	RO PA	817-HR(PA)	9600	99	2000	225	31

* The stated data are the nominal ones listed on the Fact Sheet of the respective element.

** FCS means Feed Channel Spacer, and T is its thickness

Most NSF/ANSI 61 certified SUEZ membrane elements are listed at

<http://info.nsf.org/Certified/PwsComponents/Listings.asp?Company=56220&Standard=061&>

Other NSF/ANSI 61 certified SUEZ membrane elements are listed at

<https://www.csagroup.org/testing-certification/product-listing/certificate/?cert=265930-6861-08>

RO element cross reference list

Notes:

- Reverse Osmosis (RO) elements on the same row have approximately the same performance characteristic.
- **Red type** means: Permeate End Adaptors may need to be replaced because of different permeate tube or ATD.
- Values within parentheses are options; for example- SWC4(,B) MAX means SWC4 MAX and SWC4B MAX
- Any trademarks or brands in this document are the property of and may be registered by their respective owner.
- In SUEZ made membrane elements FR refers to Fouling Resistant construction and LF to Low Fouling coating on TFM membrane. Please consult our Engineering staff for further details.

Table 1 – Low Energy RO

	Filmtec	Hydranautics	Toray	CSM	KMS	SUEZ
Low Energy RO	NF90-4040			NE4040-90		AP-90
		ESNA1-LF (-LD)				AP-365
	NF90-400			NE8040-90		AP-400
	XLE-4040, LC LE-4040	ESPA4 (-LD) -4040	TMH10A	RE4040-BLF		AK-90 LE
		ESPA4,ESPA4-LD	TMH20A-(370, 400, 400C)	RE-8040-BLF		AK-400 LE
	XLE-440	ESPA4 MAX	TMH20A-(430, 440, 400C)	RE8040-BLF440		AK-440 LE
	LP-4040					AK4040FM
		ESPA3				AK8040F-400
	LE-4040	ESPA1(-LD)-4040	TMG10	RE4040-BLN		--
			TMG20-(370, 370C)			AK-400 H
		ESPA1	TMG20-(400, 400C)	RE8040-BLN		AK-400 H
	BW30 (ECO, ECO PRO)-440i	ESPA2 (+, MAX)	TMG20-(430, 440, 440C)	RE8040-BLN440		AK-440 H

Appendix II

	Filmtec	Hydranautics	Toray	CSM	KMS	SUEZ
Standard RO	LE-400		TMGD-400			AG-400 LE H
	BW30 (LE, HRLE)-440		TMGD-440			AG-440 LE H
	BW30-4040	CPA2-4040		RE4040-CE	4040-(FR, HR), 4820HR	AG4040FM
	BW30-365	CPA2			8040-HR-375	AG8040F
	BW30-400			RE8040-CE	8040-HR-400	AG-8040F-400
	BW30FR-(365, 400)				8040-FR-(375,400)	AG8040F-400 LF
		CPA (2, 5-LD) -4040	TM710 (D,)	RE4040-(BE,BN)		
		CPA (2, 3)	TM720-370	RE8040-(BE, BN)		AG-400 H
	(BW30, SG30)-400/34i	CPA(5,7)-LD,	TM720(D,N)-400	RE8040-B34	8040-HR-400-34	AG-400 H
	BW30-440i, BW30HR-440i	CPA(5,7) MAX	TM720-430, TM720(D)-440	RE8040-BE440	8040-HR-440-28	AG-440 H
		LFC3-LD-4040	TML10 (D,F)	RE4040-FE ⁿ		AG-90 LF
			TML20(DA)-400	RE8040-(FE ⁿ , FN)		AG-400 LF
	BW30(,X)FR-400/34i	LFC3-LD	TML20(D,N)-400, TML20(D)-370	RE8040-(FN,FE ⁿ 34,FD ⁿ)	8040-FR-400-34	AG-400 LF, 34, AG-400 FR H ¹
			TML20-430	RE8040-FE ⁿ 440	8040-FR-440-28	AG-440 LF
		CPA4				AE-400
Seawater RO	SW30-4040	SWC5-LD-4040		RE4040-SHF		AE-90
	SW30 (U, X) LE-400i	SWC5(-LD)	TM820(F,R,S,V)-400	RE8040-SHF400		AE-400, 34
	SW30 (U, X) LE-400i	SWC5 MAX	TM820(R,S,V)-440	RE8040-SHF440	8040-HF-400	AE-440
	SW30HR LE-4040		TM810C	RE4040-(SHA, SHN)	4040-(SW,HF)	AD-90
	SW30HR-380, SW30HRLE-370/34i		TM820(A,C)-370	RE8040-(SHA,SHN)	8040-SW-335, 2822 SS-3(00,60)	AD-365
	SW30HRLE-(400,400i)	SWC4(+, LD)	TM820(A,C,E,M)-400	RE8040-(SHA, SHN) 400	8040-SW-400(,34)	AD-400, 34
	SW30HRLE-440i	SWC4 MAX	TM820M-440	RE8040-(SHA, SHN) 440	8040-SW-440-28	AD-440
	SW30XHR-(400,400i)	SWC4B(-, LD)	TM820K-400			AC-400, 34
	SW30XHR-440i	SWC4B MAX	TM820K-440			AC-440

المستخلص

تعتمد معظم الدراسات السابقة المتعلقة بظروف التشغيل وأداء محطات التحلية التي تعمل بنظام التناضح العكسي على دراسات قصيرة الأمد للمتغيرات المستخدمة، مثل درجة الحرارة، التركيز، ومعدل تدفق المياه المغذية. في هذه الأطروحة، تم توسيع حدود هذه المتغيرات لتصل إلى مستويات حرجة من التركيزات ودرجات الحرارة، والتي يمكن أن تؤثر بشكل كبير على أداء محطة التحلية. وقد بلغت عدد المحاولات التجريبية أكثر من 120 محاولة باستخدام مياه صناعية بتركيزات ودرجات حرارة وتصريف تراوحت بين 1063 إلى 9948 ملغم/لتر، و10 إلى 39 درجة مئوية، و7.0 إلى 13.3 م³/ساعة على التوالي.

اعتمدت هذه المتغيرات لتحديد ظروف التشغيل لمحطة تحلية المياه بالتناضح العكسي الثانية في كرامة علي (GAR02)، الواقعة شمال محافظة البصرة. من ناحية أخرى، تم اعتماد تشغيل طويل الأمد للمحطة على مدى ستة أشهر، ابتداءً من 2022/1/1 وحتى 2022/6/30، تم خلالها مراقبة أداء المحطة باستخدام مياه مغذية من نهر شط العرب. وقد أظهرت محطة GAR02 أداءً متسقاً وقابلاً للتكيف تحت ظروف مختلفة للمياه المغذية، وعلى الرغم من التحديات المرتبطة بالملوحة العالية والعكورة، فقد حافظ النظام على كفاءة جيدة في إزالة الأملاح واستقرار معدل الاسترداد، حيث كانت مواعمة معلمات التشغيل الموسمية عاملاً رئيسياً في الحفاظ على الاستقرار طويل الأمد.

تم تفصيل خطة العمل في الفصل الثالث، حيث تم في هذه الدراسة إنشاء نموذج محاكاة لمحطة GAR02 باستخدام برنامج Winflows 4.04، واستخدمت مخرجات البرنامج للمقارنة مع النتائج التجريبية، ولتمثيل نفس ظروف التشغيل من حيث التركيز، درجة الحرارة، وتصريف المياه المغذية. وقد تبين وجود تطابق كبير في النتائج، حيث لم تتجاوز نسبة الانحراف 10%.

تم تطبيق ثلاث سيناريوهات لتحسين أداء محطة التحلية. أظهرت طريقة توصيل الوعائين على التوالي داخل نظام GAR02 تحسناً ملحوظاً في الأداء عبر عدة مؤشرات رئيسية، إذ انخفض تركيز المياه المنتجة، وارتفعت معدلات الاسترداد ورفض الأملاح، حيث تراوحت نسب التحسين من 0.7% إلى 40.8%. وتشير هذه التحسينات إلى أثر إيجابي قوي لتوصيل التسلسل، مما يجعله تعديلاً تشغيلياً ذا قيمة لتحسين كفاءة النظام.

أما إضافة وحدة نزع الغازات (Air Stripper) فقد أظهرت تحسينات محددة، تمثلت بشكل رئيسي في تقليل تركيز المياه المنتجة وزيادة نسبة رفض الأملاح، إلا أن الفوائد اقتصرت على هذين الجانبين دون حدوث تغييرات ملحوظة في مؤشرات الأداء الأخرى. وقد ثبت أن وحدة نزع الغازات تكون أكثر فاعلية

في ظروف الملوحة العالية ومعدلات التدفق المتوسطة إلى العالية، ما يشير إلى إمكانية استخدامها كوحدة مساندة، وليست حلاً شاملاً بحد ذاتها.

فيما أدى تطبيق استراتيجية إعادة التدوير والخلط إلى تحسين كبير في معدلات الاسترداد، إذ تراوحت الزيادة بين 28% و77%، مع تحقيق مكاسب إضافية مقارنة بالحالة الأساسية بلغت حتى 34%. ومع ذلك، أدى هذا النهج أيضاً إلى ارتفاع في تركيز المياه المنتجة بنسبة تراوحت بين 1.1% و69.4%. وعلى الرغم من فعاليته في تعظيم استرداد المياه، إلا أن هذه الطريقة قد تتطلب خطوات معالجة إضافية للحفاظ على جودة المياه المطلوبة.

تم تطوير أربعة نماذج رياضية تمثل دوال هدف مختلفة باستخدام تقنية البرمجة الجينية التعبيرية (Gene Expression Programming -GEP) في هذه الدوال، استُخدمت المتغيرات الأكثر تأثيراً على أداء محطة التحلية، وذلك بعد استخراج معاملات الارتباط بين المتغيرات باستخدام برنامج IBM SPSS Statistics، وتم اختيار المتغيرات ذات معامل ارتباط قريب من 1. ومن خلال هذه الدوال الهدف، تم تحديد القيم المثلى للمتغيرات التي تحقق أفضل تدفق للمياه المنتجة باستخدام GEP كأداة تحسين. وقد كانت القيم المثلى للمتغيرات T ، r% ، Sc ، و Kcp هي 20.519 درجة مئوية، 45.01%، 572.6، و $10 \times 2.456 \times 10^{-5}$ على التوالي، من أجل الحصول على أفضل معدل لتدفق المياه المنتجة كدالة هدف.

توفر هذه الدراسة رؤى أساسية لتحسين أنظمة التحلية بالتناضح العكسي لمعالجة المياه عالية الملوحة من نهر شط العرب. وتُسهم النماذج المطورة في دعم التصميم منخفض التكلفة وتحسين الأداء، مما يوفر حلاً مستداماً لأزمة شح المياه في جنوب العراق، كما تسهم النتائج في وضع سياسات عملية واقتصادية لإدارة المياه محلياً.

تحسينات الكفاءة والنمذجة الرياضية لمحطة تحلية المياه

بالتناضح العكسي

رسالة مقدمة الى

كلية الهندسة - جامعة البصرة

كجزء من متطلبات نيل شهادة الدكتوراه

في علوم الهندسة المدنية

تقدم بها

حيدر عبد الرضا خنفر

(ماجستير في الهندسة المدنية)

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